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TEACHING FOREIGN LANGUAGES

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TASHKENT STATE UNIVERSITY OF LAW

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(TSUL ICON - FLT)**

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TEACHING FOREIGN LANGUAGES
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In accordance with “Plan of Scientists in the Law sphere, Specialists and Scientific-Practical Activities for 2019-2020 study years”, Resolution No. 56-R of February in 2020 of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan “On additional measures to prevent the spread of coronavirus infection”, Foreign languages department organized an international scientific and practical online conference on the topic “TSUL International Conference on Teaching Foreign Languages” (TSUL iCON - FLT) on April 30, 2021.

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FOREWORD

One of the most important aspects of the Presidential Resolution in Uzbekistan, dated April 20, 2017, “On measures to further development the system of higher education”, focuses on training highly qualified specialists in accordance with international standards, preparation of young professionals with up to date knowledge and skills and enabling them to demonstrate high level professionalism in their field of study.

In line with this goal, the Foreign languages department of Tashkent State University of Law organized a an international scientific and practical online conference on the topic “TSUL International Conference on Teaching Foreign Languages” (TSUL iCON - FLT).

This special publication presents the articles submitted to the conference by young researchers, Bachelor and Master’s course students.

Foreign languages department, TSUL

СЎЗ БОШИ

Ўзбекистон Республикаси Президенти Ш.М.Мирзиёевнинг 2017 йил 20 апрелдаги “Олий таълим тизимини янада ривожлантириш чора-тадбирлари тўғрисида”ги Қарорининг енг муҳум жиҳатларидан бири, унда олий малакали мутахасислар тайёрлашда халқаро стандартлар меъзонига риоя қилиш, унинг даражасида шарт-шароит яратиш, руҳи ва талабига мос замонавий билим ва кўникмаларга эга ёш кадрларни тайёрлашга алоҳида эътибор қаратилганлигидан келиб чиқиб, илмий изланишдаги талабалар, ёш-тадқиқотчилар, магистр ва бакалавр талабалари учун Тошкент давлат юридик университети Хорижий тиллар кафедраси томонидан “TSUL International Conference on Teaching Foreign Languages” (TSUL iCON - FLT) мавзусида масофавий илмий-методик конференция ўтказилди.

Ушбу тўпламда, анжуман учун бакалаврият ва магистратура босқичи талабалари ҳамда ёш изланувчилар томонидан тақдим этилган маърузалар матни ва мақолалар кенг оммага тақдим этилмоқда.

ТДЮУ, Хорижий тиллар кафедраси

Modern theoretical and practical aspects of linguistics

SADIAN LIE PRINCIPLE IN LINGUISTICS

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Abstract

This paper explores how “lie” in our daily life is expressed and the purpose of using lie in our language so that we can provide the solution in the conflicts where “lie” could be involved, in order to make a conclusion based on scientific evidence, rather based on personal feelings and emotion. Everybody considers “lie” as a negative reaction while we all lie in one way or another, deliberately or non-deliberately in order to avoid some troubles or harassment. The science demonstrates that they are people who lie without even they can realize it by themselves. Sometimes, “lie” could take demagogic tendencies, often observed in politics. The study states that the conflict where “lie” is involved could be avoided if the linguists and psychologists are called upon as experts while in the daily life people accuse one another of not telling the truth on some matters, and especially at the court during the trial. For these reasons, the discussion tries to provide answers to the following research questions: (a) Can a linguist or psychologist provides relevant evidence in the conflicts where people do their best not to tell the truth? (b) Through which mechanism an expert in Linguistics or Psychology could use to come with a conclusion based on scientific evidence? (c) Is it possible to distinguish “lie” to the truth? In order to answer these research questions, the authors based their analysis on introspection and relative studies rather than a datum.

Keywords: Philosophy, Forensic Linguistics, Pragmatics, Forensic Psychology, lie, truth

1. Introduction

Linguistics and Philosophy of Language are the essential fields in order to understand this topic on lie. These two disciplines, Linguistics and Philosophy of Language are subdivided into many different branches; Linguistics, for example,

includes work undertaken in semantics, pragmatics, phonology, syntax, sociolinguistics and many other fields (Chapman & Routledge, 2009, p. vii).

The conception of lying as a threat to language, as it is formulated in the literature, is based on a series of unrealistic assumptions. Most importantly, the cognitive, emotional and social capacities required for lying, lie-detection and moral enforcement are never equally spread within communities: they are highly variable. Lying and language came to be entangled in a never-ending co-evolutionary spiral, which changed the map of communicative relationships within communities, and participated in shaping our languages, societies, cognition and emotion. We evolved for lying, and because of lying, just as much as we evolved for and because of honest communication.

2. Literature Review

The subjective psyche of the human being is not an object for natural-scientific analysis, as would be any item or process in the natural world; the subjective psyche is an object for Ideological understanding and socioideological interpretation via understanding, and once understood and interpreted, a psychic phenomenon becomes explainable solely in terms of the social factors that shape the concrete life of the individual in the conditions of his social environment (Leningrad, 1927; quoted in Volosinov, 1973, p. 25-26).

Every demonstration produces knowledge of the truth of its conclusion for every person who comprehends it as a demonstration, and strictly speaking, there is no way for me to demonstrate a conclusion to or for another person (Corcoran, 1989; quoted in Corcoran, 2008, p. 3).

According to Corcoran (2016, p. 5), before Boole, logic was focused on two central problems of logic as formal epistemology: how to show that a given conclusion follows from given premises that formally imply it, and how to show that a given conclusion doesn't follow from given premises that don't formally imply it.

3. Aim of the research

This study aims to provide the solution in the conflicts where lie could be involved, in order to make a conclusion based on scientific evidence, rather based on personal feelings and emotion.

4. Research Methodology

This study is based on introspection rather than data.

5. Analysis and Discussion

Sadian Lie Principle in Philosophy of Language recognizes lie as a defense mechanism for protecting one's self against the extern pressure and it is considered as a wrong and irresponsible reaction of ignoring the truth.

According to Devitt and Sterelny (1999, p. 20), the sentence is true if a certain situation in the world obtains and not true if the situation does not.

Speaking about the lie, Huff (1993, p. 9) says that the crooks already know these tricks; honest men must learn them in self-defense.

The notion about truth and linguistic meaning must be taken into account as the truth-conditional approach is not the only approach to linguistic meaning, but it is clearly the currently dominant paradigm in philosophical semantics. For that reason alone, it deserves our fullest attention (Taylor, 1998, p. 113).

According to Taylor, the old notion of which Tarski aims to capture the actual meaning is the classical conception of truth as correspondence with reality. That conception of truth dates back at least to Aristotle, who says, "To say of what is that it is not, or of what is not that it is, is false, while to say of what is that it is, or of what is not that it is not, is true" (1998, p. 115).

When we are talking about the lie, we should not forget to mention the "Intentionality" which is according Searle a general term for all the various forms by which the mind can be directed at, or be about, or of, objects and states of affairs in the world (1998, p. 85).

This term intentionality is one of the key points in this research as lie could be sometimes or often intentional, and when it is not the case it is difficult to be accepted in our society unless if it can be demonstrated black and white by using scientific evidence.

Telling a lie in the way that you can be coherent from the beginning of a conversation to the end, and being able to retell it under other circumstances with the same logic, coherence and verbal fluidity could be a sign of intelligence or malignity. In many courtrooms, the experimented counterfeiters are difficult to be demystified because they know how to answer the questions ask by the opponent side while those who supposed to be non-guilty could look to be guilty because the attorneys of the opponent side try to push them to accept or confess the fact that they even do not know.

Woolridge (2019) notifies that lying is physiologically arousing, and Lie-tellers tend to pause for longer than truth-tellers, if someone is lying, he will give fewer details, fewer first-person pronouns, fewer differentiation such as but, without, hasn't, else, and also fewer admissions of a lack of memory and shorter responses, but he will have more negative emotions, more equivocation or uncertainty, and more discrepancies or contradictions, hesitations could be also a sign of lie but not always because beginner and intermediate speakers could pause for longer than native speakers.

6. Concluding remarks

In this study based on “lie” in language, the author considered more elements from his introspection rather than basing the study upon the data. This study answered the research questions and showed the importance of Linguist experts in such cases and insisted more on a multidisciplinary approach as lie could have some aspects with language and society. The author comes with scientific evidence in which lie could be considered as pathological behavior and at the same time as a defense mechanism to an external risks, while some parents could decide to lie to their children for the sake of avoiding to talk about what is considered as taboo in their culture and this could be often observed in many of African cultures where sexuality cannot be taught by parents to their own children, but they could decide to leave the school teacher who teaches the life Education to be in charge of it or just leave children in the mercy of society when the consequences could be fatal such as being pregnant because of curiosity.

Further Research and Outlook

This research recognizes the importance of associating Linguist experts in the conflicts which deal with “the lie” for better analysis in order to come up with the conclusions based upon scientific evidence. Therefore the multidisciplinary approach is recommended as “lie” could have some aspects with language and society which could be studied in Sociolinguistics. The author further recommends more aspects to take into consideration in the study of “lie” in Linguistics such lie due to a pathological reason where someone lies without even knowing that he is lying and also children at their very young age when they are telling a story and so forth.

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Biographical notes

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BUGUNGI KUNDAGI TIL, TIL DOIMIY HARAKATDA*Avazova Zebuniso Salayevna**Magistrant, O'zDJTU*

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqola bugungi kunda til va uning ijtimoiy mavqeyi, tilning boyishi – til doim harakatda ekanligi haqida soʻz yuritadi. Jumladan, tilning jamiyatdagi oʻrni, tilning boyib borishi, boshqa tillardan oʻzlashgan soʻzlar va ulardan nutq jarayonida foydalanish maqolada keng yoritib berilgan. Bundan tashqari shevaga xos soʻzlar, bugungi kunda ishlatilmay qolgan soʻzlar va tilni qanday kelajak avlodga saqlab qolish maqolaning asosiy gʻoyasi sifatida yoritilgan.

Kalit soʻzlar: inson resurslari, ijtimoiy hodisa, oʻzlashgan soʻzlar, neologizmlar, sheva xos soʻzlar, til muhandisligi

Til - odamlarning tabiiy muloqot vositasi va oʻzaro fikrimizni ifoda etishning eng samarali usulidir. Biz tildan turli xil maqsadlarda foydalanamiz: murakkab gʻoyalar va tushunchalarni tushuntirishda, inson resurslarini boshqarishda, muzokara qilishda, ishontirishda, ehtiyojlarimizni ifodalashda, his-tuygʻularimizni ifoda etishda, hikoyalar aytib berishda, madaniyatimizni kelajak avlodlar uchun yozib qoldirishda, sheʼriyat va nasrda nafis goʻzallik yaratishda. Koʻpchiligimiz uchun til hayotimizning barcha jabhalarida asos boʻlib xizmat qiladi. Hozirgi kunda tildan foydalanish cheklangandir. Asosan, til faqat odamlar oʻrtasidagi toʻgʻridan-toʻgʻri munosabatlarda qoʻllanilib, hayotimizda har kuni foydalaniladigan tizimlar, xizmatlar va jihozlar bilan oʻzaro munosabatlarimizda til kam qoʻllanilmoqda. Hatto insonlar oʻrtasida bir birini tushunish bir tilni biluvchilar oʻrtasida odatda cheklanib qolgan. Shu nuqtai nazardan, tilni baʼzan muloqotga yordam sifatida emas, balki toʻsiq sifatida koʻrish mumkin. Oʻzgarishlar yuz bermoqda, va bu oʻzgarishlar bizning tildan foydalanishimizni tubdan oʻzgartiradi va muloqotning barcha jihatlarida tilning qadr-qimmatini sezilarli darajada oshiradi. Ushbu oʻzgarish til muhandisligi rivojlanishining natijasidir. Til muhandisligi tilni yanada samarali vosita qilish uchun uni kengaytirish va takomillashtirish usullarini taqdim etadi. Bu yoʻnalish tadqiqotlar natijasida toʻplangan til va uning ishlash uslubi haqidagi juda

katta bilimlarga asoslanadi. Bunda vaqt o'tishi bilan ishlab chiqilgan elektron lug'atlar va grammatikalar, terminologik zaxiralari va korporatsiyalar kabi til resurslaridan foydalaniladi. Biz tadqiqot orqali til haqida bilishimiz kerak bo'lgan narsalarni tushunib yetamiz va uni tushunish va boshqarish uchun zarur bo'lgan texnikani ishlab chiqamiz. Resurslar kompyuterlarning kuchidan foydalangan holda tilni aniqlash, tasdiqlash, tushunish va boshqarish uchun zarur bo'lgan bilimlar bazasini aks ettiradi. Ushbu til haqidagi bilimlarni qo'llash orqali biz siyosiy, ijtimoiy va iqtisodiy spektrdagi muammolarni hal qilishda yordam beradigan yangi dasturlarni ishlab chiqa olamiz. Rivojlanayotgan til haqidagi bilimlarimizdan foydalanib, ko'p narsalarni qilish uslubimizni o'zgartirish, ularni oson va samarali qilish uchun yangi imkoniyatlar mavjud bo'lib bormoqda. Matnyozishni qabul qilishdan tashqari, turli xil tillarda yozma tabiiy til va nutqni taniiy olganda, biz hammamiz keng ko'lamli axborot-kommunikatsiya xizmatlarining afzalliklaridan, shuningdek, qulayliklardan foydalanish va biznes operatsiyalarini masofadan turib, telefon orqali yoki boshqa telematik xizmatlar orqali amalga oshirish imkoniyatlariga ega bo'lamiz. Agar mashina inson tilini tushunsa, turli xil tillarda tarjima qilsa va nutqni chiqarsa hamda chop etsa, biz hayotimizning ko'p sohalarida yordam beradigan juda kuchli vositaga ega bo'lamiz. Mashina bir-birimizni yaxshiroq tushunishimizga tezda yordam bersa, bu biznesda ham, hukumatda ham samarali hamkorlik qilishimizga kattab imkon yaratadi. Til muhandisligining muvaffaqiyati bu barcha imkoniyatlarning yutug'i bo'ladi. Bu narsalarning ba'zilari allaqachon amalga oshirilishi mumkin, ammo ularni yanada rivojlantirish kerak. Oldinga siljish jadallashmoqda va kelgusi bir necha yil ichida ko'plab yutuqlarni ko'rishimiz mumkin bo'ladi. Til - samarali muloqot vositasi hisoblanadi. Shuningdek, til ma'lumotni yozib olish va o'zlashtirish vositasi; amalda biz kerakli ma'lumotlarning aksariyatini namoyish etishning eng qulay usulidir. Til bizning biznes faoliyatimiz uchun ham, ma'muriyatimiz uchun ham muhimdir. Til hayotimizning ko'plab ijtimoiy, madaniy va siyosiy jihatlarida katta rol o'ynaydi. Til madaniyatimizning ajralmas qismidir. Til har birimizga o'zimizni anglashga yordam beradi. Bizning har birimiz uchun o'z tilimiz milliy va madaniy

o‘ziga xosligimiz uchun asos bo‘lib, urf-odatlarimiz bilan bog‘lanishni, shuningdek, ta‘lim va ko‘ngil ochishning asosi bo‘lib xizmat qiladi. Evropada turli xil tillar va madaniyatlarning mavjudligi bizga bir- birimizning madaniyatimiz va turmush tarzimiz haqida ko‘p narsalarni o‘rganish imkoniyatiga ega ekanligimizni anglatadi. Bunday holat yaxlit Evropa jamiyatining asoslaridan biri bo‘lib qolmoqda. Agar ko‘p tilli jamiyatning afzalliklari Evropa turmush tarzining o‘ziga xos xususiyati bo‘lib qoladigan bo‘lsa, unda biz aloqa va tushunish uchun to‘siqlarni engib o‘tish usullarini o‘rganishimiz kerak bo‘ladi. Ba‘zan biznes, ma‘muriyat va siyosatdagi xalqaro faoliyat uchun faqat bitta yoki ikkita tildan foydalanish mumkin, deyishadi. Ma‘lum darajada bu to‘g‘ri. Biroq, bu to‘liq qamrovli bo‘lmaydi. Bir nechta tillarning ustunligi kuchlarning nomaqbul nomutanosibliigi va resurslardan yomon foydalanilishiligini keltirib chiqargan bo‘lardi. Eng muhimi, bu har qanday faoliyatda samarali ishtirok eta oladigan odamlarning sonini sezilarli darajada kamaytiradi va bu qimmatli hissalarini kamaytirishi va norozilikka olib kelishi mumkin. Vaqt o‘tishi bilan, bunday yondashuv keng qo‘llanilmaydigan tillarni chetga surib qo‘yadi, ularning qo‘llanilish doirasini qisqartiradi va madaniyatimizning boyligi va xilma-xilligini kamayishiga olib keladi. Bu holat nafaqat bizning milliy, mintaqaviy va madaniy o‘ziga xosliklarni his qilishimizga, balki ozligimizga toqat qilmasdan, balki ularning qadr-qimmatini anglab, qo‘llab-quvvatlab, haqiqiy Evropa jamiyatiga mansubligimizga salbiy ta‘sir ko‘rsatishi mumkin. Tildan foydalanishga nisbatan bunday cheklovli yondashuv ko‘plab odamlarning onatillarida kompyuter tizimlariga kirishini taqiqlash orqali juda muhim yangi xizmatlar va imkoniyatlarning mavjudligini cheklab qo‘ymoqda. Ko‘p tilli dunyoda Evropaning tabiiy ravishda ko‘p tilli hamjamiyat sifatida tutgan mavqei bizning tijorat manfaatlarimiz uchun ishlatilishi mumkin. O‘zimizning ichki bozorimizni yagona bozor sifatida rivojlantirish uchun yaqindan hamkorlik qilsak, biz ko‘p tilli bozorning muammolariga yechimlarni ishlab chiqa olamiz. Tilga bo‘lgan ehtiyojlarimizni, ayniqsa biznes, ma‘muriyat va ta‘lim sohalarida muvaffaqiyatli qo‘llab-quvvatlashda til muhandisligi bizni jahon bozorida raqobatlashishga yordam beradi. Bir tomondan,

bizning biznesimiz ko‘p tilli bozor ehtiyojlariga xizmat ko‘rsatish uchun texnologiyadan foydalanish tajribasi orqali raqobatbardoshlikka ega bo‘ladi. Boshqa tomondan, bizda dunyoga sotiladigan til mahsulotlari ham mavjud bo‘ladi. Axborot jamiyatining muhim xususiyatlaridan biri umrbod o‘qitish uslubi bo‘lishi kutilmoqda. Bundan tashqari, kelajakdagi menejerlar bir nechta tillarni bilishlari kerakligi tan olinmoqda. Til muhandisligi nafaqat tilni o‘rganish uchun, balki talaba ehtiyojlariga yanada mos keladigan samarali tizimlarni ishlab chiqish uchun shaxsiy o‘qitish tizimlarini rivojlantirishga muhim hissa qo‘shadi. Tilga asoslangan mahsulotlar biznes va ma‘muriyat hamda jismoniy shaxslarning ish faoliyatini yaxshilaydi. Til texnologiyasidan foydalangan holda ishlab chiqarilgan mahsulotlar bizning tizimimizdagi inqilobni o‘zgartiradi va umuman biznes, hukumat va jamoat uchun mavjud bo‘lgan xizmat turlarini kengaytiradi. Nutqni tanib olish, tushunish va kompyuter orqali hosil qilish insonning kompyuter bilan o‘zaro ta‘sirini yanada samaraliroq qiladi. Tabiiy tilni mashinalar yordamida tushunish bizning ma‘lumotlarga bo‘lgan ehtiyojimizni yanada aniqroq vasezgirlik bilan etkazib beradi, bu esa juda ko‘p ma‘lumotlarga ega bo‘lish muammosini engishga yordam beradi. Kompyuter yordamida tarjima qilish xizmatlari va chet el tilidagi hujjatlarni yaratish nafaqat Evropa doirasidagi aloqalarimizni yaxshilaydi, balki tashqi bozorlarga keng kirish imkoniyatini beradi. Til muhandisligi - bu inson tilini har qanday shaklda taniy oladigan, tushunadigan, talqin qiladigan va yaratadigan kompyuter tizimlarini ishlab chiqishda til haqidagi bilimlarni qo‘llash hisoblanadi. Amalda til muhandisligi texnikalar va til resurslari to‘plamini o‘z ichiga oladi. Birinchisi kompyuter dasturida, ikkinchisi esa kompyuter dasturiy ta‘minotidan foydalanish mumkin bo‘lgan bilimlar omboridir.

Tilni tabiiy tushunish. Tilni tushunish ko‘plab dasturlar uchun juda muhimdir. Biroq, mukammal tushunish har doim ham talab qilinmaydi. Darhaqiqat, qisman tushunchaga ega bo‘lish ko‘pincha bu jarayonning juda foydali dastlabki bosqichi hisoblanadi, chunki bu tushuncha chuqurligini keyingi darajalarga ko‘tarish uchun oqilona tanlab olishga imkon beradi. Matnlarni sayoz yoki qisman tahlil qilish,

cheklanmagan matnlarning samarali dastlabki tasnifini samarali olish uchun ishlatiladi. Ushbu dastlabki tahlildan, masalan, cheklangan maydon doirasidagi matn tarkibini belgilaydigan chuqurroq semantik tahlil qilish uchun matnning "qiziqarli" qismlariga e'tibor qaratish uchun foydalanish mumkin. Bundan tashqari, u statistik va lingvistik bilimlar bilan birgalikda noma'lum so'zlarning lingvistik xususiyatlarini avtomatikravishda aniqlash uchun ishlatilishi mumkin, keyinchalik tizim bilimlariga qo'shilishi mumkin. Semantik modellar, tushunchalar va ular o'rtasidagi munosabatlar nuqtai nazaridan tilning ma'nosini ifodalash uchun ishlatiladi. Semantik model, masalan, so'rov bildirilgan haqiqiy terminologiya yoki tilga bog'liq bo'lmagan ma'lumotni, so'rovni asosiy ma'noga solish uchun ishlatilishi mumkin. Bu ma'lumotni indekslash uchun ishlatiladigan haqiqiy ibora yoki tuzilma bilan tanishishga hojat qolmasdan ma'lumotlarga ko'p tilli kirishni qo'llab-quvvatlaydi. Semantik model bilan tahlil va avlodning kombinatsiyasi matnlarni tarjima qilishga imkon beradi. Rivojlanishning hozirgi bosqichida yetarli darajada til muhandisligi resurslaridan foydalanish uchun bunga erishish mumkin bo'lgan dasturlar, lug'at va tushunchalar bilan cheklangan bo'lishi kerak. Hujjat tuzilishi uchun shablonlar, shuningdek, o'zgaruvchan qismlarga ega keng tarqalgan iboralar yuqori sifatli matn yaratishda yordam berish mumkin.

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THE IMPORTANCE OF THE COMMUNICATIVE SPEECH CULTURE IN INTERACTION

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Abstract: This article is devoted to the description of speech communication and its culture from the perspective of linguistics and other related areas. Indeed, the culture of speech communication is of utmost importance to interact with others in both native and target languages. Hence, one must always try to follow the norms and standards of speech culture for the successful interaction. Once we learn L2 we are bound to be confronted by its culture which may arise some misunderstandings and difficulties and, thus, the culture of speech communication is a must to be perceived as a key factor of any language.

Key words: *speech communication, culture, cultural norms, linguistic study, interaction, pragmatic focus, ethic communication*

Indeed, the transition in linguistic study paradigms and ideologies in the second half of the twentieth century drew scientists' attention to procedural, activity-oriented linguistics with a strong pragmatic focus. It is evident that the function of the language, not its structure, was the focus of scientific research in linguistics. Linguistic pragmatists have concluded that language could only be studied by looking at how it is applied by a particular language user (listening, writing, reading) in specific contexts, and that the functions of language can only be determined if the meaning of the participant's presence in the communicative act, as well as the whole collection of situational variables, are taken into account. Therefore, not only the means of speech communication, but also the actual actors, the circumstances of communication, objectives, outcomes, implications of communication, etc., falls into the realm of scientific research interests of linguists [1, 159].

It is worth noting that our speech isn't just a reflection of our level of language proficiency; it's also a representation of our society in general. Considering this, it is of importance to define culture in the first place.

It's particularly difficult to communicate effectively with people from other cultures. Cultures offer people new possibilities about the world, new ways of seeing, hearing, and understanding it. As a result, even though people use the "same" language, the same words will mean different things to them from various cultures.

In fact, the observance of some, essentially artificial, created and "allowed" by society traditions and norms is culture in the narrow sense. These traditions and conventions are aimed at making the assimilation of people as comfortable as possible. It is critical that an individual creates inconvenience to himself by following the rules of conduct and communication in order to make others' lives easier. Meanwhile, it is assumed that other members of society would behave similarly "by nature."

However, *speech culture* encompasses more than just etiquette. Our language and speech do not occur in isolation. This is a kind of projection on all societal structures. More specifically, this is a dialectical relationship: language represents the socio-political processes that occur in society while also shaping our worldview in certain ways [2, 8]. The attitude toward the national language determines speech culture of a society, and the degree and state of the national language, in turn, determines the nation's level of growth. It only takes a few well-known statistics to see how much weight is placed on speech culture issues in a variety of countries. For instance, the representatives of the postwar Germany that had been destroyed were concerned about the sharp decline in German language culture during the Hitler years, whereas many people refer to the French's dogmatic attitude toward their language as "linguistic chauvinism." To say it mildly, English-language signs, advertising, and other materials are not welcomed in France. The French are battling the invasion of Americanisms in various ways, including by legislation. Besides, linguists in Portugal meet almost every year to address the standards of the

Portuguese language. *The Complete Plain Words* can be found on the desk of every English official. The modern speech situation in Russia is characterized by a lack of interest (indifference) in the Russian language in general and speech culture in particular.

It is apparent that when a person conveys the native language, he/she progressively becomes more aware of the richness and variety of the world, from concrete objects to basic social norms to abstract principles and laws of the universe. Only by entering the community and participating in social activities and language development can shape him/her as a person. “Language is the place of being,” as stated by German philosopher Martin Heidegger. A person lives in the language's dwelling” [3, 192]. Language, which is one of the forms of human behavior and does not exist in theory outside of culture, turns out to be an essential part of culture (as a set of results of human activity in different spheres of life - industrial, social, spiritual). However, as a form of existence of thinking and as a means of communication, it is on a par with culture.

It is recommended that when teaching the culture of verbal communication, careful attention must be paid to the language norms that are needed for successful and "ethnic" communication:

- Orthoepic- a word that refers to a language's pronunciation system.
- Grammatical-the formation of word forms, phrase and sentence construction;
- Stylistic- the proper use of linguistic units for stylistic coloring;
- Syntactic-the adherence to sentence combinations and word order.

As one might be aware, the issue of speech culture encompasses three major aspects: normative, communicative, and ethical, the latter of which is no less significant than the first two. The key ethical concept of verbal communication is to preserve balance, which demonstrates itself in greetings, addressing, choosing a full or abbreviated name, hello and goodbye styles, using counter remarks, maintaining a cultural communication environment, and so on.

Moreover, the concept of "communicative culture" or "culture of communication" of a linguistic personality is based on the culture of speech. As for Sokolova communicative culture is as a collection of information, skills, and relationships that allow for the free creation of a speech utterance for the optimal solution of communication problems [4, 192]. The culture of thought, which exists in the form of particular types of cognitive activity aimed at the interpretation and generation of texts that conform to the purpose and reliably represent truth; and emotional culture, or culture of feelings, which is an appropriate response to the surrounding reality. Galskova, on the other hand, claims that it represents the dynamic nature of the procedural and successful characteristics of the practice of teaching foreign languages, which also involves education, the development of the student's personality through the appropriate educational discipline [5, 287]. Foreign language education, which consists of a collection of fundamental knowledge, concepts, skills, competencies, and abilities, is therefore essential to the development of a foreign language community.

There are four fundamental skills of integrative mastery of a foreign language society, according to Passov and Kuzovleva [6, 11]:

- the ability to influence appropriated foreign culture in close proximity to natives (a cognitive aspect);
- the ability to apply different kinds of abilities in communication (an evolving aspect);
- applied capacity for the realization of moral potential (an educational aspect);
- the ability to communicate through the types of speech activity (the result of the educational aspect).

According to Koykova, there are a number of crucial cultural criteria of speech communication [7, 7]:

- *Don't be concerned about how others would respond if you speak your opinion.* Know that you own the right to convey whatever you want. You have the right to free expression, and no one can take that away from you.
- *Maintain your confidence.* It is essential not to let the emotions control completely. Remember that this is just a discussion, and speaking calmly and slowly can make people think more highly of you. Being confident makes you appear composed and in command, particularly when others are panicking around you.
- *Do not shout.* People cannot hear you any better if you shout. In reality, it will cause them to lose interest in you.
- *Speak clearly.* Only be loud enough for people to hear your speech and your point of view.

In sum, the culture of speech is a topic that any civilized person should be familiar with. We should pay attention to what we say as modern people. Our primary form of communication was and continues to be speech. In order to communicate successfully with others in different aspects of our lives, we must always consider that not only what we say, but also how we say is important and, thus, every modern person should have a clear understanding of speech culture.

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THE ANALYSIS OF PHRASEOLOGICAL UNITS REPRESENTING THE ETHICAL CONCEPT OF “FIDELITY” IN ENGLISH LANGUAGE

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Abstract: In this article it is given the analysis of phraseological units representing the ethical concept of “fidelity” in English language. Phraseological units representing the ethical concept of “fidelity” objectify conceptual signs of fidelity, its relationship with other phenomena of the moral and sensory sphere.

Key words: *phraseological units, linguacultural, phraseologism, faithfulness, culture, mentality, national identity*

The phraseological fund of the language is figuratively compared with a mirror in which “the linguocultural community identifies its national identity” (Telia 1996: 9, 83), it is a valuable source of information about the culture and mentality of the people (Maslova 2004: 43). The phraseological units, the figuratively motivated base of which is correlated in one way or another with the subject area of culture, contain semiotically different natural language components, the semantic content of which is “scooped out of the conceptual sphere of culture” (Telia 2004: 675).

Phraseological units representing the ethical concept of “fidelity” objectify conceptual signs of fidelity, its relationship with other phenomena of the moral and sensory sphere. The analyzed empirical material seems to be expedient to distribute into the following groups.

1. Phraseological units with the meaning of “persistence in beliefs, views”:

- *hold to* - to remain fixed to a belief, or in adherence to a principle, etc. (TBEI 1961: 106);

- *dyed in the wool* - unchanging in a particular belief (with allusion to the fact that yarn was dyed when raw, producing a more even and permanent color) (COED 2002: 446); thoroughly committed; inveterate; unchanging: He is a dyed-in-the-wool Conservative Republican (SAI 1997: 104);

- *stick at* - to be persistent in an activity (TBEI 1961: 171);

- *stick to* - to be persistent in continuing an activity; to remain fixed in an argument or to principle, opinion, etc. (TBEI 1961: 172);

- *keep faith with* - to continue to support or believe in a person, organization, or idea (LDCE 2001: 494);

- *carry a / the torch* - 1) to show great and unchanging loyalty to a cause or a person: Although the others gave up fighting for their rights, John continued to carry the torch; 2) to be in love, usually without success or return: He is carrying a torch for Anna, even though she is in love with someone else (SAI 1997: 57). The second interpretation of this phraseological unit implies the relationship between loyalty and love.

2. Phraseological unit with the meaning “deep interest”:

- *put one’s heart into* - to put one’s zealous interest into, to devote oneself keenly to (work, a hobby, etc.) (TBEI 1961: 101).

3. Phraseologism, actualizing the manifestation of a sense of patriotism in relation to their country. Excessive, extreme displays of patriotism are usually assessed negatively:

- *wrap oneself in the flag* - (chiefly N. Amer.) To make an excessive show of one’s patriotism (COED 2002: 537).

4. Phraseologisms with the meaning “reliability”:

- *tried and tested (or true)* - having proved effective or reliable before (COED 2002: 1541);

- *girl Friday* - a very dependable and helpful female office worker; especially a secretary: Miss Johnson is the manager's girl Friday (SAI 1997: 146).

5. Phraseological units with the meaning “readiness to intercede for someone, help someone, defend something”:

- *take up the cudgels for* - to defend vigorously a person's character, conduct, etc. The word “cudgel”, which is now obsolete except in this idiom, was the name of a short thick stick used as a weapon (TBEI 1961: 58); to come to the defense of; to support or fight for: He was the first to take up the cudgels for his friend (SAI 1997: 405);

- *at one's beck and call / at the beck and call of*- ready and willing to do whatever someone asks; ready to serve at a moment's notice (SAI 1997: 17);

- *stand by* - to serve as a support and help (TBEI 1961: 167); to be loyal to; support; help: When three big boys attacked Bill, Ed stood by him (SAI 1997:381)

- *stand (or stick) up for* - to give one's support, help, influence, to a person, party, cause, principle, etc. The allusion is to planting one's feet firmly beside or in front of a person or thing where he or it can be defended from attack (TBEI 1961: 169);
- *stick by one* - to support; remain loyal to: All of Peter's friends stuck by him faithfully, in spite of what has been said about him in the press (SAI 1997: 385);

- *at someone's back* - in pursuit or support of someone (COED 2002: 96);

- *take sides* - to support one person or cause against another or others (COED 2002: 1332);

- *back up* - to help or be ready to help; stay behind to help; agree with or speak in support of: Jim has joined the Boy Scouts and his father is backing him up. The principal backs up the faculty (CAM 1997: 22);

- *back of / in back of* - in support or encouragement of helping: Jones will be elected because many powerful men are back of him. Get in back of your team by cheering them at the game (SAI 1997: 21);

- *bear up* - to hold up; carry; support; encourage: He was borne up by love of country (SAI 1997: 26).

5. Phraseologisms with the meaning “to appreciate someone, something”:

- *make much of* - to attach much value or importance to; to treat (a person) with affectionate or respectful attention (TBEI 1961: 126);

- *apple of one's eyes* - something or someone that is adored; a cherished person or object: Charles is the apple of his mother's eye. John's first car was the apple of his eye. He was always polishing it (SAI 1997: 11).

7. Phraseological units that objectify the conjugation of fidelity with other phenomena that represent undoubted human values: - fidelity with truthfulness, sincerity

- *as good as one's word (or good as one's word / promise)* - trustworthy; sure to keep your promise: The coach said he would give the players a day off if they won, and he was as good as his word. We knew she was always good as her word, so we trusted her (SAI 1997: 13-14);

- *on the up and up* - honest; trustworthy; sincere: We felt that he was honest and could be trusted. This information is on the up and up (SAI 1997: 293);

- *make good* - to do what one promised to do; make something come true: Mr. Smith borrowed some money. He promised to pay it back on payday. He made good his promise (CAM 1997: 257);

- *man of his word* - a man who keeps his promises and does the things he agrees to do; a man who can be trusted: My uncle is a man of his word (CAM 1997: 262)

- *open and aboveboard* - honest: Jacob felt that the firm was doing business that wasn't entirely open and aboveboard (CAM 1997: 294);

- *good faith* - honest and sincere intentions: He proposed a second meeting as a sign of his good faith (LDCE 2001: 494);

- *fair and square* - open, honest: without cheating; honestly: He won the game fair and square (SAI 1997: 113);

- *play fair* - to do what is right to others; act in a fair and truthful way: Mary would not date any other boys while Jim, her favorite boyfriend, was away; she said that would not be playing fair (CAM 1997: 315). - fidelity with friendship:

- *a bosom friend* - a close friend with whom there is mutual intimacy about in innermost thoughts and feelings (TBEI 1961: 33); a close buddy with whom one has a confidential relationship: Sue and Jane have been bosom friends since their college days (CAM 1997: 40); fidelity with love:

- *all in all* - the person or thing that you love most: She was all in all to him. Music was his all in all. (CAM 1997: 6); - fidelity with trust:

- *eat out of one's hand* - to trust someone fully; believe or obey without question: The governor has the reporters eating out of his hand. Helen is so pretty and popular that all the boys eat out of her hand (CAM 1997: 107);

- *in someone's confidence* - in a position of trust with someone (COED 2002: 299);

- *swear by* - to have complete confidence in; be sure of; trust completely: We can be sure that Fred will come on time, since his friend Tom swears by him (CAM 1997: 393).

The analyzed idiomatic expressions indicate, on the whole, a positive assessment of fidelity, which is reflected in the emotional attitude towards behavior of this kind - towards its approval. However, the excessive manifestation of loyalty to one's country, is evaluated negatively and causes an emotive-evaluative reaction of condemnation.

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CHANGING INTERNET COMMUNICATION FROM VERBAL INTO GRAPHICAL

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Abstract: Article discusses transformation of verbal language into graphical communication in the internet. Several forms of current verbal communication, clarification of graphics and their semantic features are analyzed in this research. Modern types of graphic information are claimed as a prior means of communication.

Key words: *graphics, symbol, sign, verbal communication, internet language, diagram, table, electronic literacy.*

People have been communicating with each other since their early evolution. They exchange information not only with verbal language but also early groups cooperated by using graphical language. During several centuries symbols and signs have been equally used with alphabetical system of languages. In this modern life

communication moved to the internet, at the same time individuals are using graphic signs in the virtual world as well.

Even graphics could be understandable for every nation and user, we cannot explain detailed information with them. However, it has been observed non-linguistic data, while people are speaking. In fact, facial definition, “body language”, appearance and environment inform to the listener about speaker’s attitude. At the time of expressing ideas with non-linguistic factors, graphics are not often characterized alone. They usually comes as a system of signs.

As we paid attention graphic representations utilized in the transformation of meaning. It could be interesting that language users observe differences and similarities between graphical communication and verbal language. Graphics are expressed by different sorts of shapes, curved patterns of the objects, textures and colorful symbols to inform clues. For example, google maps, financial graphs, several sorts of tables and diagrams transfer data as a form. In fact, pictures and images are also covered as a graphics. In contrast, a particular sign is presented as a member of united symbols in systematic graphics.

Computer Mediated Communication expressed by hybrid forms of information with its perspective information on electronic literacy. There was a historical movement of using graphic information and the theory named “from book to screen” which has the meaning of text versus images. A visual type of cooperation which is expressed by the virtual image is replacing the print type of verbal communication and it also form visibility of words to illustrate latest tendencies in internet media to change text with graphics. Additionally, it is also considered as a main readjustment of graphics in common collaboration. (Richards, 2000)

As we can see Graphic Communications are used more than other means for the reason of technological advancement. Unparalleled situation of users is not only appeared in the internet but also it may be observed in printing media. Youth usually use high technology a a means of conservation in social network services such as

TikTok, YouTube, Facebook, Instagram or Telegram. As a result, digital world changed personal communication and cultural attitude as well. (Brain, 2020)

According to the historical facts, pictorial images was syntactical and semantic base of writing, symbols are representation of interpretation. Symbols are often used when people communicate with each other at a different time. For instance, a member of a family wants to transfer their thoughts by leaving messages to others. At the same time, they may decide the usage of types of graphics and transformation design as well.

Actually, there are numerous kinds of graphics in our daily communication and they are presented by different purposes. For example, tables show absolute figures, trends of progressive quantities are expressed by line graphs, histograms illustrate rates or pie charts demonstrate the analysis of data with round forms. Obviously, individuals express information by various signs. If we discuss about line graphs, horizontal axis shows the period, vertical axis often presents amount of products, lines inform about types and categories, inscription define the relations or caption supports needed data to exchange the message into clauses.

While analyzing graphical semantics of tables, language user might observe a relation between texts and forms, one cell can be turned into texts, there is also the relation between columns and caption, content of the cell presents value, every type of table could generated several sentences by different orders of columns and rows. However, not all sentences inform table incompleteness, empty cell organizations or specialized language.

Graphic information may not contain a lot of senses inside the sign, while verbal language often claims much data with given words of the sentence. If we convert graphs into clauses, they do not express the same meaning. Sentence is based on string structure of syntax and this form is interpreted semantically. However, intervening syntax is not appeared in graphics and signs are directly interpreted. As a result, symbols only illustrate a limited series of connection, such as saturation and

icons. Many dimensions are represented indefinitely in texts, through them several syntactic connections are clarified between words.

Several types of graphics appear as language and they may be transformed concretely or interpreted abstractly. For example, circuit diagram or maps can be interpreted directly and languages of visual programming interpreted indirectly. Every note in circuit diagram stands for one component, various nodes express different components. Therefore, if there is no connection between two terms, it means that there is no chain between them. If the link is abstractly interpreted, nodes clarify similarity and link absence does not express the absence of coherence.

As we have discussed, internet binary is appeared in the formation of texts and illustration of graphics. Consequently, this is not the analysis of signs by the meaning of information, but it is the observation of communication. Implementation of internet communication demand the analysis of graphic literacy in virtual world. As a result, novel ways of electronic literacy and utilization of informational technologies changed according to the interaction of internet users. According to the analysis that the process of communication in the internet is not only technological action, but also it is considered as hybrid reaction of people to each other with verbal and graphic interaction.

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ARAB TILIDA AFFIKSLAR (ZOIDA HARFLAR) NING SO'Z TARKIBIDA JOYLASHISH XUSUSIYATLARI

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Annotatsiya: Maqolada arab tilida affikslar hamda ularning so'z tarkibida joylashish xususiyatlarini haqida ma'lumot berilgan bo'lib, har bir tahlil etilgan ma'lumot misollar orqali izohlangan.

Kalit so'zlar: zoida harf, affiks, prefiks, suffiks, fe'l, sifat, sifatdosh, so'z vaznlari, harakatlar.

Arab tilida ism va fe'l so'z turkumlariga oid yangi so'zlarning yasashida zoida harflar muhim ahamiyat kasb etadi. Tilshunoslikda "zavaid" deb ham yuritiladigan ushbu harflar, so'zning boshi, o'rtasi yoki oxiriga qo'yiladi. Hamda ular yoki so'z o'zgartiruvchi, yoki so'z yasovchi, yo bo'lmasa shakl yasovchi qo'shimchalar vazifasini bajarib keladi. Shu o'rinda bir savol tug'iladi, xo'sh, "zavaid" yoki "zoida harflar" o'zi nima?

Somiy tillar oilasiga mansub tillarda qo'shimchalar orqali so'z yasalishi – affiksatsiya muhim ahamiyat kasb etib, arab tilida ham uning ahamiyati katta ekanligini ko'rish mumkin. Arab tilidagi "zāida" so'zi lug'aviy jihatdan "keragidan ortiqcha narsa", degan ma'noni bildirib, tilshunoslikda ushbu atama "affiks" tushunchasini ifodalaydi. Arab tilshunosi Ibn Ya'iysh affikslarni shunday ta'riflaydi:

"Ziyoda harf (affiks) so'zga ergashib keluvchi qism bo'lib, u orqali man'no kengayib boradi. Zoidaning asl mohiyati uning o'zakka qo'shilib, ba'zi holatlarda esa tushib qolishi, fa, 'ayn va lam harflari o'rnida kelayotgan hech bir o'zak harfining o'rnini bosa olmasligida namoyon bo'ladi. Zoida yo so'zning bir qismining

takrorlanishi, yoki o'zak tarkibiga kirmaydigan boshqa bir harfning qo'shilishi bilan xarakterlanadi"¹.

Arab tilidagi so'zlar tarkibida affikslar ikki xil ko'rinishda namoyon bo'ladi. Birinchisi, so'z tarkibida harf affiks vazifasida kela oladi, masalan, “k,t,b” (“kataba” fe'lining o'zbek tilidagi ma'nosi “yozmoq”) o'zagining birinchi harfidan so'ng alif qo'shish bilan “kātibun” (“yozuvchi”/“yozayotgan”) so'zi yasaladi, bu yerda alif sifatdash yasovchi “-ayotgan”, yoki ot yasovchi “-uvchi” qo'shimchalari ma'nosini bildiradi. Ikkinchidan, so'z tarkibida harakat qo'shimcha bo'lib keladi, masalan, “nahrūn” (“daryo”) va “naharūn” (“kenglik”, “daryo”)².

Arab tilida yangi so'zlarning yasalişida quyidagi harflar affikslar vazifasini bajaradi:

Alif ا	Hamza ء
Waaw و	Nun ن
Yay ي	Ha ه
Miym م	Sin س
Ta ت	Lam ل

Ushbu harflarni arab tilida “alyawma tansāhu” (tarj. Sen bugun uni unutasan) va “sa'altumūniyhaa” (tarj. Sizlar mendan uni so'radingiz) iboralari ko'rinishida yod olinadi. Arab tili o'rganuvchilari so'zlarni o'zak va affiksial morfemalarga ajratayotganlarida bu iboralarga murojaat qiladilar, ya'ni, so'z tarkibidagi ushbu ibora ichida mavjud bo'lgan harflarni chiqarib tashlash orqali, ular so'zlarni ma'noli qismlarga bo'ladilar. Arab tilida affikslarga bag'ishlangan ko'pchilik tadqiqot ishlarida ularni umumiy “zavāid” deya, ba'zi holatlarda esa bunday harflarning so'z tarkibida kelish o'rniga ko'ra, “savābiq” (“prefikslar”), “lavāḥiq” (“sufikslar”) hamda “dawāxil” (“infikslar”) nomlari tilga olinadi. Bundan tashqari ularning muḥīṭa

¹ المنصف، شرح الإمام أبي الفتح عثمان بن جني النحوي لكتاب التصريف لإمام أبي عثمان المازني النحوي البصري، تحقيق: إبراهيم مصطفى عبد هلال أمين، إدارة إحياء التراث القديم وزارة المعارف (القاهرة)، الطبعة الأولى 1393- هـ 1943م. ج 1، ص 11

² ياسر محمد البدوي محمد. الزيادة و دلالتها الصرفية و النحوية. السودان، -2012.ص.22

(“sirkumfiks”), muq̣hama (“interfiks”), muḍo‘afa (“duplifiks”) kabi turlari ham mavjud.

Arab tilida soʻz, unga zoida harflarning qoʻshilishi natijasida toʻrt, besh, olti va hatto, yeti oʻzakli hosila soʻzga ham oʻzgarishi mumkin. Ushbu harflar soʻz tarkibida, albatta, arab tilidagi unli tovushlarni bildiruvchi kasa (“i”), ḍomma (“u”) hamda fatḥa (“a”) harakatlaridan biri bilan keladi. Soʻzni oʻzak va morfemalarga ajratishda, ushbu harflarning joylashish oʻrniga ham eʼtibor berish lozim, aynan shu jihat orqali soʻzlarni maʼnoli qismlarga oson ajratish mumkin. Buni quyidagi bandlar orqali muxtasar izohlab beramiz:

1. Soʻz tarkibidagi uch undosh harflardan oldin kelayotgan har bir hamza, yay, nun va ta harflari affiks sanaladi, masalan:

ʻAktubu: Men yozayapman. Ushbu soʻzning birinchi hamzali alif harfi hozirgi zamon feʼlining birinchi shaxs, birlik shaklini yasovchi “-yapman” qoʻshimchasi sanaladi.

ʻAhmadu: 1. Ahmad; 2. Eng maq̣tovli. Ushbu soʻzda ham birinchi hamzali alif harfi sifatning qiyosiy-orttirma darajasini yasovchi qoʻshimcha hisoblanib, bu yerda u “eng” yuklamasi maʼnosini bildiradi.

Yaḍribu: U urayapti (muzakkar jinsi). Bu soʻzning birinchi ya harfi feʼlining hozirgi zamon shaklini yasovchi uchinchi shaxs birlik “-yapti” qoʻshimchasidir.

Najmaʻu: Biz yigʻayapmiz. Ushbu feʼl tarkibidagi dastlabki nun (n) harfi feʼlining hozirgi zamon shakli, birinchi shaxs, koʻplik sonini yasovchi “-yapmiz” qoʻshimchasidir.

Tasmaʻu: 1. Sen eshitayapsan (muzakkar jinsi). 2. U eshitayapti (muannas jinsi). Ushbu feʼldagi ta harfi feʼlining hozirgi zamon shakli, ikkinchi shaxs, birlik sonini yasovchi “-yapsan” (kontekstga qarab, “-yapti” deb ham tarjima qilish mumkin) qoʻshimchasidir. Uch va undan ortiq undosh harflardan oldin kelayotgan har bir mim affiks vazifasida keladi, masalan:

Maṣnaʻun: zavod. Bu soʻzning mim harfi oʻrin-joy nomini yasovchi qoʻshimcha sanaladi.

Mahmuudun: maqtalgan. Bu soʻzda esa mim, choʻziq “u” unli tovushini bildirayotgan waw bilan birgalikda majhul daraja sifatdosh yasovchi “-l” qoʻshimchasi vazifasini bajarib kelmoqda.

Musmiʻun: majburlab eshittiruvchi, ijrochi. ʻAsmaʻa (majburlab eshittirmoq; ijro etmoq) toʻrtinchi bob vazni shaklida turgan feʻldan, uning boshiga “mu-” prefiksini qoʻyish orqali aniq daraja sifatdosh shakli yasaldi. Bu soʻz tarkibida mim zoida harf sanaladi. U oʻzbek tilida ot yasovchi “-chi” yoki “-yotgan” qoʻshimchalariga toʻgʻri keladi.

Munʼoliqun:yoʻlga chiqayotgan odam. Bu yerda ham ajratib koʻrsatilgan zoida harf orqali aniq daraja sifatdosh shakli yasaladi.

Uchta undosh harflardan oldin kelayotgan har bir alif va nun, yay va nun, ta va nun, nun harfining oʻzi, nun va mim harflari affiksdir, masalan:

Inqasama: boʻlinmoq. Bu yerda ajratib koʻrsatilgan zoida harf oʻzbek tilidagi majhullikni anglatuvchi “-il” qoʻshimchasi maʼnosini beradi.

yandahiru: u yengilayapti. Bu soʻzda ajratib koʻrsatilgan zoida harflar feʻlning hozirgi zamon shakli, muzakkar jinsidagi uchinchi shaxs, birlik soni shaklini yasovchi “-yapti” hamda oʻzlik nisbatini yasovchi “-il” qoʻshimchasi maʼnolarini beradi.

Tanhaniy: sen burilayapsan/u burilayapti. Bu soʻzda ajratib koʻrsatilgan zoida harflar feʻlning hozirgi zamon shakli, muannas jinsidagi uchinchi shaxs, birlik soni shaklini yasovchi “-yapti” (kontekstga qarab, muzakkar jinsida, “-yapsan” deb ham tarjima qilish mumkin) hamda oʻzlik nisbatini yasovchi “-il” qoʻshimchasi maʼnolarini beradi.

Tansa: sen eshitayapsan/u eshitayapti. Bu soʻzda ajratib koʻrsatilgan ta zoida harfi feʻlning hozirgi zamon shakli, muannas jinsidagi uchinchi shaxs, birlik soni shaklini yasovchi “-yapti” (kontekstga qarab, muzakkar jinsida, “-yapsan” deb ham tarjima qilish mumkin) qoʻshimchasi maʼnosini beradi.

munfaʻilun; hayajonlanuvchi, hayajonlanayotgan/hayajonlanayapti. Bu yerda ajratib koʻrsatilgan zoida harf feʻlning hozirgi zamon shaklini yasovchi “-yotgan” hamda

aniq daraja sifatdosh shaklini yasovchi “-uvchi”, “-yotgan” qo’shimchalari ma’nosini beradi.

Sin va ta harflaridan oldin kelayotgan har bir alif, yay, ta va nunlar, o’zidan keyin turgan sin va ta bilan birgalikda, zoida harflar (affikslar) sanaladi. Misol uchun:

Istafhama: so’ramoq.

Yastajmi‘u: yig’ayapti, yig’ilyapti. Bu so’z tarkibidagi yay hozirgi zamon fe’lini yasovchi “-yap” hamda “-ti” shaxs-son qo’shimchasi ma’nolarini beradi.

Nastaxriju: qazib chiqarayapmiz. Bu yerda nun hozirgi zamon fe’lini yasovchi “-yap” hamda “-miz” shaxs-son qo’shimchasi ma’nolarini beradi. **Tastashiyru:** sen maslahat so’rayapsan/u maslahat so’rayapti. Bu so’z tarkibidagi ta hozirgi zamon fe’lini yasovchi “-yap” hamda “-san” va “-ti” shaxs-son qo’shimchasi ma’nolarini beradi.

Yuqorida affikslar sifatida qayd etib ko’rsatilgan alif, sin hamda ta harflari arab tilida fe’l yasovchi prefikslar sanalib, ular uch o’zakli fe’llarga qo’shilib, o’ninchi bob fe’li shaklini hosil qiladilar. Keltirilgan misollarda o’ninchi bob fe’lini yasovchi affikslardan oldin kelayotgan ay, ta va nun harflari esa bu yerda fe’lning hozirgi zamon shakli va shaxs-son qo’shimchalari ma’nolarini anglatayapti.

To’rt, besh va olti harfli so’zlarning tarkibidagi, oxirgi undoshdan oldin kelayotgan har bir alif, yay, waw harflari affiks vazifasida kelib, shuningdek, ular, bunday holatlarda, cho’ziq “ā”, “ū” va “ī” unililarni ham ifodalaydi.

Masalan:

Ṭobībun: davolovchi, shifokor. Bu so’z aslida, “ṭobba” (“davolamoq”) fe’lidan yasalgan bo’lib, bu yerda yay (“ī”) harfi fe’ldan ot yasovchi “-lovchi” qo’shimchasi vazifasini bajarmoqda.

Rihānun: garovlar. Bu so’z arab tilidagi “rahnun” (“garov”) so’zining ko’plik shakli bo’lib, alif (“ā”) bu yerda ko’plik shaklini yasovchi “-lar” qo’shimchasi vazifasida kelayapti.

G'ofūrun: kechirimli. Ushbu soʻz arab tilidagi “kechirmoq” maʼnosini bildiruvchi “gʻafara” feʼlidan yasalgan boʻlib, bu yerda waw (“ū”) sifat yasovchi “-li” qoʻshimchasi vazifasida kelayapti.

1. Toʻrt harfli soʻzning ikkinchi harfi boʻlib kelayotgan har bir alif affiks sanaladi, bu holatda ham alif choʻziq “ā” unlisini ifodalaydi, masalan:

Kātibun: yozuvchi/yoʻzayapti.

Jālisun: oʻtirayotgan/oʻtirayapti.

Ṭālibun: izlovchi/izlayapti.

Arab tilida yuqorida keltirilgan misollardagi kabi tuzilgan soʻzlar aslida uch oʻzakli feʼllarga alif (“ā”) zoida harfini qoʻshish orqali yasalib, bu yerda alif kontekstga qarab bir necha, “-uvchi”, “-lovchi” va “-yotgan” sifatdosh yasovchi hamda hozirgi zamon feʼlining uchinchi shaxs shaklini yasovchi “-ayapti” qoʻshimchalari vazifasini bajarib keladi.

2. Besh harfli soʻzning uchinchi harfi boʻlib kelayotgan har bir ta affiks sanaladi, masalan:

ʻirtada: kiyinmoq.

ʻibtasama: tabassum qilmoq.

ʻiktasaba: topmoq, izlab qoʻlga kiritmoq.

Ushbu misollarda keltirilgan soʻzlar tarkibidan joy olgan dastlabki alif, buyerda u “i” tovushi orqali ifodalanmoqda, hamda ta harflarining uch oʻzakli feʼllarga qoʻshilishi natijasida oʻzlik nisbati maʼnosini beruvchi sakkizinchi bob feʼl shakli yasaladi. Shunga koʻra, bunday tuzilishli feʼllardagi ushbu zoida harfni oʻzlik nisbati yasovchi “-in”, “-an”, “-it”, “-il” qoʻshimchalariga muqobil variant sifatida koʻrsatish mumkin. Yana qoʻshimcha sifatida, agarda besh oʻzakli soʻzlarning dastlabki harfi ham ta boʻlsa, bunday holatlarda ham ushbu harf affiks sanaladi va u beshinchi va oltinchi bob feʼllari tarkibida kuzatiladi.

Shu oʻrinda, chalkashlik kelib chiqmasligi uchun yana bir jihatga eʼtibor qaratish lozim. Besh harfli soʻzlar tarkibidagi hamzali alif va nun, yoki hozirgi zamon shaklini yasovchi qoʻshimchalar (yay, nun, ta) hamda nundan soʻng kelayotgan ta harfi ham

zoida (affiks) sanalib, bunday tarkibli soʻzlarda nun oʻzak harf, undan avval kelayotgan barcha harflar qoʻshimcha hisoblanadi, ushbu holatda ham ta harfi oʻzlik nisbat yasovchi “-t” qoʻshimchasi maʼnosini anglatadi:

ʼint**ab**aha: eʼtiboqqaratmoq.

ʼint**a**ha: tugatmoq.

1. Soʻzning oxirida turgan tamarbuta belgisi (“-atun” tovushini bildiradi) ham affiks vazifasini bajaradi. Ushbu belgi arab tilida muannas jinsini bildiradi, misol uchun:

Mazraʼ**atun**: poliz.

Ṭolib**atun**: talaba qiz.

2. Uch harfli soʻzning oxirida turgan alif va hamza ikkisi affikslar vazifasini bajarib keladi. Ular ikkisi soʻz oxirida birgalikda kelganda, oʻsha soʻzning muannas jinsida turganligiga ham ishora qiladi. Misollar:

Samraʼ**u**: bugʻdoy rang (muannas jinsida).

Najlaʼ**u**: shahlokoʻzli (muannas jinsida).

Ḥamraʼ**u**: qizil rang (muannas jinsida).

Ṣaḥraʼ**u**: sahro (muannas jinsida).

Ushbu keltirilgan misollarni tahlilidan shu narsa maʼlum boʻladiki, soʻz tarkibidan joy olgan alif va hamza soʻzlarning muannas jinsida ekanligini bildirish bilan birga, “ot+sifat+li”, “ot+rang” tuzilishli qoʻshma va birikmali sifatlarni ham yasaydi.

1. Arabcha soʻzning oxirida turgan alif va nun harflari ham affiks hisoblanadi.

Masalan:

Ṣofvā**nu**: begʻubor, musaffo.

Ṣinvā**nu**: tugʻishgan aka-ukalar.

Kaslā**nu**: dangasa, behafsala.

ʼaṭshā**nu**: chanqagan.

Demak, keltirilgan misollar, soʻzga qoʻshilgan alif va nun zoida harflari sifatdosh hamda sifat soʻz turkumiga mansub soʻzlarni yasab, ular anglatgan maʼnosiga koʻra, oʻzbek tilidagi sifat yasovchi “be-”, “-agan” qoʻshimchalariga

to'g'ri keladi. Shuningdek, ushbu zoida harflar “-lar” ko'plik yasovchi qo'shimchasi vazifasini ham bajaradi.

Xulosa qilib aytganda, arab tilida zoida harflar (affikslar) deyilganda, odatda, “alyawma tansāhu” iborasi tarkibiga kiruvchi harflar tushunilib, ular o'zak so'zga qo'shilib, ism va fe'l turkumlariga oid so'zlarni yasashga xizmat qiladi. Shuningdek, ular so'z yasovchilik vazifasi bilan birga so'z o'zgartiruvchi va shakl yasovchi affikslar vazifasini ham bajarib keladi. Arab tilida hosila so'z tarkibidagi zoida harflar (affikslar) ni ajratishda ularning so'z tarkibida joylashgan o'rniga ham ahamiyat berish lozim. Odatda, arab tilida shakl o'zgartiruvchi qo'shimchalar so'z oxiriga qo'shilsa, so'z yasovchi va so'z o'zgartiruvchi qo'shimchalar so'zning boshi yoki o'rtasiga qo'shilib kelar ekan. Yana, arab tilshunosligida uch o'zakli so'z tarkibidagi birinchi, ikkinchi va uchinchi undosh harflarning yolg'iz o'zi yoki yonidagi o'zak undosh bilan birga takrorlanishi natijasida ham so'zlar yasalib, bunda ushbu takrorlangan harflar ham zoida harflar, deya sanalar ekan.

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COMMUNICATION IN CUSTOMS AND TRADITIONS

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Abstract: The appeal is a linguistic phenomenon that is in the focus of attention of different areas of linguistics. Scientists describe appeal as an important

component of speech etiquette. In the twentieth century in connection with the growing interest in the pragmatics of human speech, appeals began to be studied as special language units in the aspect of their functioning in the act of communication. Even though the sound interest in the study of treatment in linguistics, a number of specialists note the insufficient knowledge of this linguistic phenomenon.

Key words: *linguistic phenomenon, appeal, speech, linguistic phenomenon, syntactic function, interdependence, concept, communication method, communication environment, communicative situation, nominative, vocative, emotional expressive, discursive, deictic, mean.*

Conventionally, appeal is understood as “a grammatically independent and intonationally separate component of a sentence or a more complex syntactic whole, indicating the person or subject to which speech is addressed” [9, p. 304].

The concepts of vocative and appeal in the scientific literature are often used as synonymous. Sometimes the syntactic difference between these terms is emphasized.

In the dictionary of linguistic terms, a vocative is defined as “a word or phrase formally not included in the sentence that refers to who the speaker is talking to, i.e. used to attract the attention of the person to whom the speaker is speaking” [2]. Unlike vocative appeal is defined as “the use of nouns, pronouns, substantive adjectives or equivalent phrases for naming persons or objects to which speech is addressed; syntactically appeals are usually executed in super-segmented (prosodic) means” [2].

V.I. Karasik, in contrast to the aforementioned scientists, does not differentiate between the concepts of vocative and appeal. By the term vocative, it means “both speech acts and language units, through which the corresponding language units are expressed. Words used as an address express not only the speaker’s attitude to the addressee, but also carry information about the speaker himself, his upbringing, and his ability to behave in a social position. Vocatives exist in all languages, specifically reflect the national-cultural features of languages, are heterogeneous in their composition and have a complex content structure” [8, p. 202]. Thus, vocatives carry

a significant communicative load and perform a number of speech functions in the process of direct speech contact.

Most often, the appeal is expressed: in your own name, for example: Salima, where are you going so late?; Hamdamov, you'll come with your parents tomorrow!; What do you think about this, Shukurov?; A negative noun: Girl, pass the ticket, please!; Friends, I'm glad to see you!; Adjective or participle: Take me on the road, dear; Dear, how to get to the metro station? When contacting, there may be explanatory words – definitions or applications, for example: My friend, we will devote wonderful impulses to our motherland!

Appeal is an important component, because depending on the situation it can determine its success, or it can be the cause of communicative failure. According to N.I. Formanovskaya, “in communicative processes, circulation is one of the frequency units of communication, namely addressing, which carries the most important contact-setting function” [14, p. 83].

The choice of lexical means of registration of an appeal from a number of so-called characteristics of a communicative situation: relations between the addressee and the addressee: gender, age, family, social, official, etc.; communication environment: official, unofficial; communication method: contact, distant; purpose of communication: attracting attention, maintaining verbal contact, expressing an attitude towards the interlocutor, the intention to continue to request, apologize, etc.; tonality of communication: respectful, courteous, asking, patronizing, etc. [4, 7].

A pragmatic approach to the study of appeal reveals its multi-functionality. The number of functions, as well as their names, varies among different researchers. These are: nominative; vocative; socio-regulatory, or etiquette; emotional expressive (expression of emotions); assessment and characterization; discursive; deictic (clarification, indication of the addressee).

If, however, L.V. Kozhukhova points out, the appeal at the same time expresses the addressee's assessment and gives him a characteristic, then this is a manifestation of the emotional-evaluative function built on it [8, p. 80]. The

addressee qualification function is also defined as characterizing [6]. Characterization can be carried out according to a number of parameters: social status: Ah, master, master, you are very young; age: Ah, is that you, grandfather? Acquaintance or kinship: Ah, no, Mommy, don't talk!; professions and occupation: Hussar, you are cheerful and careless ...

T.V. Nesterova believes that it is necessary to distinguish between vocatives with a minimum degree of pragmatism and expressive vocatives, which are addressed expressions of emotions. The former are characteristic for establishing contact in a neutral situation that does not have additional emotionally expressive coloring. The second ones are marked with additional emotionally expressive components [10, p. 15-16]. Among them, one can single out the emotional content of which is directly related to the positive or negative attitude to the addressee, since emotionality is a state that occurs in the decision-making process of evaluating perceived phenomena of reality and their connection, “the relation reflected and fixed in the semantics of the word, the speaker's feeling for the object of speech” [14, p. 64].

Among the evaluative nature vocations can be attributed calls characterizing the addressee by personal qualities and properties that become the object of evaluation, for example: Let go of your hands, shameless, otherwise the Count God knows what he will think!; Angel of my soul, carbuncle of my heart, lend money ...

In the above examples, the address denotes both the addressee of the utterance and the relation of the speaker to it.

The desire of speakers to save language means leads to the fact that over time the significance of a purely vocative function decreases, as evidenced by such a historical process as the loss of a vocative case form. And in the first place is the expression of the value attitude to the addressee.

So, when considering the most common type of vocabulary calls expressed by anthroponyms, it is revealed that the age status of communicants, the official sphere of communication, the roles of “boss-subordinate” in the language are realized primarily through the use of first and middle names. Full forms of personal names

and their brief options convey emotions and assessments, indicating the informal nature of communication and specifying the speaker's emotional attitude to the interlocutor.

A large group of evaluating characterizers are metaphorized nominations, that is, the names of animals, objects, and phenomena of reality used as a vocative: swallow, gold, treasure, angel; snake, scarecrow, club. For example: Oh you, my little light, my victorious little head; Where are you, my friend, my apple tree?; Look, you devil, what you thought up. Nothing will come of you.

The appeal, therefore, belongs to the group of language tools that necessarily express any logical, semantic or expressive-stylistic shades, can be considered as a special expressive tool [12].

Obviously, the appeal is always purposeful and correlated with a specific communication situation. The choice of the form of a vocative is determined by the combination of pragmatic parameters of the situation of verbal communication, namely: status-role relations of communicants, their personal relationships, their emotional and mental state.

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**THE ANALYSIS OF FIGURES OF SPEECH IN UZBEK AND ENGLISH
LANGUAGES THROUGH THE BOOK “THE ADVENTURES OF
SHERLOCK HOLMES”**

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Abstract: In this article the translation of the sentences in the translation work based on the bilingual versions of “The Adventures of Sherlock Holmes and provided examples of figures of speech in both English and Uzbek languages. In translation, migration is mainly based on metaphor, metonymy and synecdoche, from English to Uzbek, and there analyzed how the sentences in translation process changed.

Key words: figures of speech, expressive, metaphor, metonymy, synecdoche, comparison, analyze

Expressive means of a language, expressive and stylistic devices, tropes, speech figures are widely used in linguistics. In different styles sometimes these terms are considered synonymic, sometimes they differ. The main peculiarity of literary style is image. “Despite the fact that image is considered a main peculiarity of literary style, it can make any text stylistically colorful. Emotions (or expressiveness), first, is connected with image and emerges from it. Emotional or expressive speech is also considered image. Therefore, in different styles (texts) the indicators of image or expressiveness are realized in three layers of a language, thus phonetic, lexical and grammatical”

Almost all the figures of speech that appear in everyday speech may also be found in literature. In serious poetry and prose, however, their use is more fully conscious, more artistic, and much more subtle; it thus has a stronger intellectual and emotional impact, is more memorable, and sometimes contributes a range and depth of association and suggestion far beyond the scope of the casual colloquial use of imagery. In this article, we tried to analyse the book “Stories” by Jack London from the metaphorical and synecdoche point.

Metaphor. A metaphor makes a comparison between two unlike things or ideas. *Examples include:*

- ✓ Heart of stone
- ✓ Time is money
- ✓ The world is a stage
- ✓ She's a night owl
- ✓ He's an ogre

Synecdoche. Synecdoche occurs when a part is represented by the whole or, conversely, the whole is represented by the part. *Examples include:*

- ✓ Wheels - a car
- ✓ The police - one policeman

- ✓ Plastic - credit cards
- ✓ Coke - any cola drink
- ✓ Hired hands – workers

PERSONIFICATION

Personification gives human qualities to non-living things or ideas.

Examples include:

- ✓ The flowers nodded.
- ✓ The snowflakes danced.
- ✓ The thunder grumbled.
- ✓ The fog crept in.
- ✓ The wind howled

English version of the book

Kitobning o`zbekcha varianti

She was bringing in some money by typing page 10

U harf terish orqasidan kun kechirar edi

Sir, but I've already caught him (page 34)

Biroq men uni allaqachon qo'lga olib bolganman, janob On page 90

But his face is still as black as a chimney-sweep's, On page 39

Lekin yuzlari xuddi mo'ridan chiqqan qora tutunday qop-qora

At this point Ryder turned rather pale and simply stood shaking in the corner of On page 34

Rider qizarib ketdi, o'midan turdi-da burchakka borib On page 90

She then raised her veil revealing a face showing such fear that she looked as if she were a small animal

Voajab uning yuzidagi dahshat xuddi ovdan zo'rga qutulib qochgan kichkina jonivornikiga o'xshardi

being hunted down On page 36

On page 92

I froze when I saw the fear and panic on his face

On page 39

Uning yuzlaridagi qoʻrquv iskanjasi va vahima koʻrib, oʻzim ham muzlab qoldim On page 96

Hellen stopped speaking for a moment as the memory of tragedy brought tears to her eyes

On page 48

Bu ayanchli hikoya koʻzlariga achhiq yosh olib kelganligi sababli Yelena ozgina muddat sukut saqladi On page 106

With one of his hands bleeding heavily

Chuqur kesib tashlangan tinmasdan qon oqardi

After look the address of the lady, the King left, and Sherlock and arranged to meet the next day On page 51

Sherlok qiroidan honimning manzilini olganidan keyin Qirol uni tark etdi. Ertasi kuni biz Sherlock bilan oʻsha xonim bilan uchrashishni reja qildik On page 4

Not along after, with Sherlock disguised as a priest, we made our way to Irane Adler's house and waited for her carriage to appear On page 53

Birozdan soʻng Sherlock bilan ruhoniylar qiyofasida Ayrin Edlarning uyi tomon yoʻlga otlandik On page 70

I'm involved in it On page 21

Sabab unda men borligim boʻlgan On page 74

Turner him self didn't suffer any

Charlzning sirli olimidan qisqa muddat

- imprisonment as he died shortly after the mysterious murder of Charlies McCarthy was solved by Sherlock Holmes** On page 36
- Imagine how terrified I was yesterday when I heard the sound of a whistle ,the very same sound I heard on the night of her death** On page 40
- But I had a very serious accident during the night** On page 46
- The three criminals escaped without a trace and it was the last we heard of them since all evidence of them and their business disappeared up in smoke** On page 49
- But McCarthy who were nervous when he saw his friend and shouted him** On page 16
- McCarthy blackmailedTurner ,threatening him that he would reveal the whole turth to the police if he did not get financial support for** On page 17
- o'tib bu olamdan ko'z yumdi
On page 74
- Opamning joni uzilgan tundagi kabi hushtak ovozini eshitib qanchalar dahshatga tushganimni tasavur ham qilolmaysiz On page 96
- Jiddiy halokat yuz berdi On page 101
- Osha jinoyatchilar izziz goyib bolgan. Bir izziz qop-qora tutumday goyib bolgandek endi yoq On page 108
- Ammo o'glini korib g'azab otiga mingan janob Karti unga baqirib ketgan On page 68
- Karti Turnrga agar o'g'li va ozi uchun moddiy yordam korsatmasa uning kirdikorlarini poolitsiyaga fosh qilishini aytb popisa qildi On page 69

- Who had got addicted to the terrible habit of smoking opium On page 21** U chekishga juda ham mukkasidan ketganlardan edi On page 73
- I decided to visit my old friend Sherlock Holmes and found him sitting on the sofa with a big old hat lying on the chair next to him On page 22** Ne koz bilan qarayki, Sherlock uyida yolgiz, divanda suyanib xayollariga chomgancha otirardi On page 75
- But Baker only laughed at the idea of taking away an eaten goose and simply took his belongings On page 29** Aytilgan gaplarda opkasi boshashgan Beyker toyib toyib kulardi On page 84
- Mrs Roylott died, leaving the Doctor so heart broken that he abandoned all his work. As time passed he became very bitter disappointed even aggressive He had no friends other than the wanderning gypsises they ha no-one else to look after them and the only money they had was the money left by their mother which the Doctor kept form them On page 29** Lekin taqdirni qarangki Roylot xonimning baxti uzoq uzoqqa chozilmadi. Rafiqasining kitilmagan olimi Doktorni yurak xastaligiga duchor qildi Shundan keyin Doktor uchun butun dunyo zulmatga aylandi Uning hamma narsadan kongli soviy boshladi Ishini esa butunlayga tashalab yuborgandi Vaqt otgani sari uni kuchi gam gussa bosar hamma narsadan kongli qolgan edi On page 84
- Please tell me every detail of this mattaer On page 32** Iltimos, menga ushbu masalaning har bir tafsilotini aytib bering On page 87
- I rushed into my sisiter's room and** Uning yuzlaridagi qorquv iskanjasi va

saw her there her face filled with fear and terror On page 37 vahimani korib ozim ham muzlab qoldm On page 93

But I had a very serious accident during the night On page 44 Dahshatdan dod deb yuborgim keldi On page 102

They were welcomed by a frightened woman who said something in German to the Colonel In page 45 Qorquvdan yuragi ichiga tushib ketgan bir ayol ketib oldi On page 103

He managed to escape just before the machine squeezed him to a pulp On page 46 Ezgilab sharbatga aylantirmasidan avval tezroq bu yerdan On page 105

I cant believe you tricked me into coming all this way I know exactly what you are using this machine for On page 48 Aqlimga sigmayapti siz meni shu yol bilan bur burda qilib tashlamoqchimisiz On page 107

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THE STUDY OF DISCOURSE AND DISCOURSE ANALYSIS IN LINGUISTICS

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Abstract: This very article aims to discuss the study of discourse and discourse analysis in linguistics as well as some other related fields. Indeed, this very term has been a controversial discussion among many linguistics due to its abstractness. Therefore, several definitions have been provided prior to its emergence and usage in linguistics. In fact, the oppositions “discourse-text” and “discourse-speech” are of great significance in order to illustrate the essence of discourse itself. Based on the various perceptions of the scholars, the author also indicates her own views on these terms accordingly. All in all, in our view more in-depth study of discourse and discourse analysis is still needed for further research.

Key words: *discourse, discourse analysis, concept, approaches, disciplines, speech, text, linguistics, communication*

For a start, being a very broad concept, discourse is currently used in a number of scientific disciplines and interdisciplinary research. Depending on the object of study, each area of knowledge puts different shades of meaning into the concept of discourse. Prior to its usage in linguistics, this very term has owned various definitions in terms of philosophy, sociology, political sciences and etc. As Demyankov stated the Latin lexeme “discursus” in the meaning of "conversation, interaction" was recorded in the 5th century [1, 35]. Various variations of the word "discursive" are found in the sphere of scientific usage in the late 19th and early 20th centuries: "discursive thought," "discursive activity," "discursive cognition," and so on. However, it is only in the 1970s that the word "discourse" started to gain a terminological status [2, 244].

Despite the large amount of research in this field, discourse still lacks a consistent and widely accepted definition since it is basically an interdisciplinary term. Its polysemy is noted in many dictionaries; for example, discourse is defined in the Philosophical Encyclopedia as "one of the complex and difficult to define concepts of modern linguistics, semiotics, and philosophy, which has spread widely in Anglo- and especially French-speaking cultures." "Discourse" is described as "an undefined term-concept used in linguistic, literary, philosophical, psychological, and historical study" in the stylistic encyclopedic dictionary of the Russian language.

For linguistics, the meaning of this term is of utmost importance. There are two major approaches of the description of discourse in this field. It is often associated with the concept of text in the first approach, and with the concept of speech in the second. In his work "Discourse Analysis," published in 1952, American scientist Z. Harris (1952) coined the idea of "discourse" in the theory of linguistics of the text and he then characterized "discourse" as a series of sentences spoken (or written) by one (or more) people in a specific situation ("the sentences spoken or written in succession by one or more people in a single situation"). The researcher further points out that language is realized in a coherent discourse, not in jumbled words and sentences - from a single word to a broad book, from a monologue to a speech [3, 3]. Moreover, he noted that discourse analysis helps to create a specific form of discourse by providing an understanding of the text, its type, and the significance of each factor in its construction. Two issues with discourse analysis are found by the linguist. The first suggests that descriptive linguistics is restricted to the sentence as a basic unit, while in the course of expression, the speaking person actually connects sentences. The second is linguistic and cultural, with the following mandatory elements: an individual, speech, and scenario.

Furthermore, discourse was defined as a coherent text combined with extralinguistic factors in the 1990s of the previous century. "Discourse is a coherent text in conjunction with extralinguistic - pragmatic, sociocultural, psychological, and other influences, a text taken in the event aspect," according to the Linguistic

Encyclopedic Dictionary. The relationship between the terms of "discourse" and "text" is, however, a moot question. The text is thought to be a result of human interaction, the perception process, and discourse is the interaction, the process itself, with the text being a part of it. In a bid to provide a clear definition, Kaplunenko emphasizes that "Discourse is a more general linguistic object that encompasses not only the linguistic framework of a speech work, but also the usual parameters of a communicative process, communicant features, and communication strategy, whereas the text is a more limited phenomenon that does not extend beyond the structural and semantic boundaries of a speech work" [4, 100].

According to the second approach, the correlation between "discourse" and "speech" can be traced back to F. de Saussure. In European and Russian science schools, categorical features like "language in live contact" and link with "speaking individual" established the foundation for understanding discourse. The sense of a specific form of utterance, characteristic of a separate socio-historical class, was added to the understanding of "discourse" within the context of this approach.

D. Shiffrin, a well-known American scientist, defines "discourse" as the presence of two scientific paradigms: formal and functional. For those who believe in the first, discourse is a degree of linguistic structure that extends beyond the sentence, i.e. discourse is linked to the text in this case. Discourse, for functionalists, is expression that enables them to perform specific tasks, or in other words, discourse is social contact. The linguist argues that in order to understand the discourse, these concepts must be integrated into the formal-functional framework. As a result, discourse is seen as a set of functionally ordered, contextualized language use units. The utterance is the basic unit of discourse. Hence, discourse is associated with speech, or speech behavior, which focuses emphasis on two aspects of discourse: first, the property of processuality, and second, the relationship with the social world [5,17]. As a result, it could be concluded that social study, rather than linguistic research, is more prevalent in this school. Linguistics, in collaboration with sociology

and psychology, has as its primary goal the recognition of the addressee's communicative intentions and the message's address.

Of the many approaches to the definition of discourse, one stands out, which differs in the depth of comprehension. This is the approach of the French school of discourse analysis, which took shape in the 70s of the 20th century. Linguists K. Arosh, P. Henri, and M. Pesche did not completely agree with Z. Harris's definition of discourse and critically analyzed F. de Saussure's main concepts. As a consequence, discourse is described in the French tradition as "an intentionally decided heterogeneous unity, realized either in the form of oral speech as a result of communicants' interaction in a specific socio-cultural setting, or in the form of a written text in its various aspects." [6, 28].

Considering the abovementioned approaches, from our perspective, the concepts (text/speech/discourse) are not interchangeable despite their close relationship and interdependence. We opine that the definition of "discourse" is much broader than the concepts of "text" and "speech communication" or "speech," since it encompasses a variety of extralinguistic variables, has several dimensions, and is not constrained by any temporal or spatial context, as the concepts of "text" and "speech communication" or "speech". Besides, these components serve as discourse fragments, an essential and indispensable aspect of entire communication in a particular scenario.

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ЎЗБЕК ВА ИНГЛИЗ ХАЛҚ МАҚОЛЛАРИДА МАКРОГРАДУОНИМИЯ

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Аннотация: Мазкур мақолада лексик-семантик парадигма – градуонимиянинг бир тури бўлган макроградуонимия ҳамда унинг инглиз ва ўзбек халқ мақоллари таркибида учраши ўрганилган бўлиб, унинг мазкур икки тилдаги мақоллар таркибидаги турлари таҳлил қилинган.

Калит сўзлар: мақол, паремология, градуонимия, макроградуонимия.

Мақол таркибидаги даражаланиш муносабати бевосита унинг компонентлари орасидаги луғавий градуонимияга асосланади. Луғавий градуонимиянинг бир нечта турлари ўзбек тилшунослари томонидан ўрганилган. Хусусан, луғавий даражаланишнинг мазмуний кўламларида бир томонлама (*чақалоқ – гўдак – бола – ўсмир – йигит*), айланувчан (*ёз – куз – қиш – баҳор*), марказдан қарама-қарши томонларга боровчи (*совуқ – илиқ – иссиқ*) [2, 83-85] каби йўналишлар мавжудлиги О.Бозоров томонидан айтиб ўтилган эди. Кейинроқ Ж.Ш.Джумабаева томонидан лексик градуонимиянинг мазкур хусусиятларини янада чуқур тадқиқ қилиб, бир томонлама даражаланишнинг ўсувчи ёки камаювчи турлари аниқлаб берилди ва бундай даражаланиш қатори «микроградуонимик қатор» деб аталди; марказдан қарама-қарши томонларга йўналувчи икки қутбли ўзаро антонимик муносабатларга эга градуонимлари мавжуд қаторлар «макроградуонимик қатор» деб аталди [3, 26]. Агар

макроградуонимик қатор аъзолари учта бўлса, ушбу макроградуонимик муносабат «йиғиқ макроградуонимия» дейилади, агар бундай қатор аъзолари учтадан ортса, ушбу макроградуонимик муносабат «ёйиқ макроградуонимия» дейилади. Макроградуонимиянинг мазкур ички турлари яна ўз ўрнида лексема маъносидаги белгининг ошиб ёки камайиб боришини ифодалашига кўра ўсувчи ва камаювчи турларга ажралади.

Градуонимиянинг юқорида санаб ўтилган барча турлари ҳам инглиз тилидаги, ҳам ўзбек тилидаги мақолларнинг таркибида кўзга ташланади. Буни қуйидаги мисоллар билан исботлаш мумкин. Баъзи градуонимик қатор аъзолари фақат битта мақолнинг таркибида мавжуд бўлса, баъзилари эса бир нечта мақол таркибида қатнашади. Масалан, *little* → *average* → *much* ўсувчи йиғиқ макроградуонимик қатори бир қанча инглиз халқ мақоллари таркибида учрайди: *A little too late, is much too late; He is not poor that has little, but he that desires much; He that desires but little has no need of much; He that eats least eats most; Less is more; Politeness costs little, but yields much; Promise little, but do much.* Қуйидаги ўзбек халқ мақоллари ҳам биргина *тор* → *лойиқ/ўртача* → *кенг* ўсувчи йиғиқ макроградуонимик қатори градуонимларини ўз таркибида сақлайди: *Тор тортишиб йиқилар, Кенг – кенгашиб; Торга – тор дунё, Кенга – кенг дунё; Оёқда этигинг тор бўлса, Дунё кенглигидан не фойда; Уйимиз тор бўлса ҳам, Кўнглимиз кенг.* Инглиз тилидаги *difficult/hard* → *normal* → *easy* камаювчи йиғиқ макроградуонимик қатори градуонимлари шу тилдаги фақат *All things are difficult before they are easy* мақолида учрайди. Шу каби ўзбек тилидаги *қийин* → *ўртача* → *осон* камаювчи йиғиқ макроградуонимик қатори аъзолари *Қуда бўлмоқ – қийин, Жудо бўлмоқ – осон* мақоли таркибида мавжуддир. Ҳар икки тилда ҳам градуонимик қаторнинг ҳар бир турига хос бўлган градуонимларнинг бир нечта мақоллар таркибидаги иштирокини кузатишимиз мумкин [1].

Инглиз тилида ҳам, ўзбек тилида ҳам бир нечта мақоллар мавжудки, уларнинг таркибидаги градуонимлар уларнинг ўсувчи ёки камаювчи градуонимик қатордаги тартибига мос келмаган ҳолда жойлашади. Масалан:

➤ *England is the paradise of* ➤ *Бор товоғим, кел*
women, the hell of horses, and the товоғим,
purgatory of servants. *Бормасанг, келмасанг,*
Ўртада син товоғим.

Инглизча мақолда *hell* → *purgatory* → *heaven/paradise* йиғиқ макроградуонимик қаторининг учта аъзоси ҳам қатнашган бўлиб, лекин уларнинг мақолдаги тартиби градуонимик қатордаги тартибидан фарқ қилади. Ўзбек тилидаги мақолда эса *кетмоқ/бормоқ/тарк этмоқ* → *қолмоқ* → *келмоқ* йиғиқ макроградуонимик қаторининг фақат икки аъзоси қатнашган бўлиб, ушбу мақолда ҳам уларнинг жойлашув тартиби градуонимик қатордагидек эмас. Яна шундай мақоллар борки, уларнинг таркибида бир эмас, иккита йиғиқ макроградуонимик қатор аъзолари жой эгаллаган. Бу каби мақоллар фақат инглиз тилидаги мақоллар орасидан топилди, ўзбек тилининг паремиологик фондидан эса топилмади. Масалан, қуйидаги мақолда *be born* → *live* → *die* ва *poor* → *normal* → *rich* йиғиқ макроградуонимик қаторлар аъзолари мавжуд: *Fools live poor to die rich.*

Таркибида мақоллардаги жойлашув тартиби уларнинг градуонимик қатор тартибидан фарқ қиладиган градуонимлар ва бир мақолда бир турдаги бир нечта градуонимик қатор аъзолари қатнашган мақолларни «таркибида мазкур турга мансуб аралаш градуонимик қатор аъзолари қатнашган мақоллар» деб аташ тавсия этилади. Чунки бу каби мақоллар таркибида бир турга мансуб ўсувчи ёки камаювчи градуонимик қатор аъзолари қатнашган мақоллар қаторига қўшишнинг мантиқан иложи йўқ. Таркибида бир турга мансуб аралаш градуонимик қатор аъзолари қатнашган мақолларни градуонимларнинг кейинги турларига эга мақоллар орасида ҳам топиш мумкин бўлиб, уларнинг ҳар бирини ўз турининг ичида кўриб чиқамиз.

Ўз таркибида тўртта ёки ундан ортиқ градуонимларга эга ёйиқ макроградуонимик қатор аъзолари ҳам мақоллар таркибида ўсувчи, камаювчи ва аралаш шаклларда учрайди.

А) Таркибида ўсувчи ёйиқ макроградуонимик қатор аъзолари қатнашган мақоллар:

➤ *Never cast dirt into that fountain of which you have sometimes drunk.* (never → rarely → seldom → sometimes → frequently/often → usually → always) ➤ *Асли душман дўст Қайнаб қони қўшилмас.* (душман → ёв/ганим → рақиб → таниш/бетараф → ўртоқ → дўст)

В) Таркибида камаювчи ёйиқ макроградуонимик қатор аъзолари қатнашган мақоллар:

➤ *If you try to please all you will please none.* (all → every/each → some → any → a/an/one → no/none) ➤ *Ақлидан эл рози, Аҳмоқдан дил норози.* (доно → оқил → зеҳнли → ақлли → гўсхўр → тентак → аҳмоқ/ақлсиз → нодон → телба/жинни)

С) Таркибида аралаш ёйиқ макроградуонимик қатор аъзолари қатнашган мақоллар:

➤ *Hear all, see all, say nowt, tak' all, keep all, gie nowt, and if tha ever does owt for nowt do it for thysen.* (Hear all, see all, say nothing, take all, keep all, give nothing, and if you ever do anything for nothing do it for yourself.) (all → every/each → some → any → a/an/one → no/none) ➤ *Аҳмоқдан – чақмоқ, Донодан – аҳмоқ.* (телба/жинни → нодон → аҳмоқ/ақлсиз → тентак → гўсхўр → ақлли → зеҳнли → оқил → доно)

➤ *A wise enemy is better than a foolish friend.* (brilliant → душмани доно яхши. (дўст → wise → canny/sensible → clever → ўртоқ → таниш/бетараф → рақиб crazy → fool → absurd → stupid → → ёв/ганим → душман, asinine → insane/mad/idiot, телба/жинни → нодон → enemy/foe → acquaintance/neutral → аҳмоқ/ақлсиз → тентак → гўсхўр friend) → ақлли → зеҳли → оқил → доно)

Юқорида таркибида аралаш ёйиқ макроградуонимик қатор аъзолари қатнашган мақолларга мисол сифатида келтирилган инглиз тилидаги биринчи мисолда сўзларнинг тарихий вариантлари қатнашган бўлиб, инглиз халқининг мулоқотида ҳозиргача унинг ушбу кўриниши қўлланилади.

Инглиз ва ўзбек тилларининг иккисида ҳам таркибида ҳам йиғиқ, ҳам ёйиқ макроградуонимик қатор аъзолари қатнашган мақоллар учрайди, масалан:

➤ *A good word for a bad one is worth much and costs little.* дароздан яхши. (доно → оқил → (excellent → good → normal → bad / зеҳли → ақлли → гўсхўр → тентак ill → evil, much/many → average → → аҳмоқ/ақлсиз → нодон → little / few) телба/жинни, пакана → ўртача → дароз)

Хулоса қилиб айтганда, лексик градуонимиянинг бир тури бўлган макроградуонимия турли тил оилаларига мансуб инглиз ва ўзбек тилларининг паремиологик таркибида кўп учрайди. Хусусан, ҳар икки тилда ҳам макроградуонимиянинг ўсувчи ва камаювчи турларидан ташқари аралаш тартибда жойлашувини ҳамда бир нечта макроградуонимик қаторнинг аъзоларини ўз таркибида сақлаган мақоллар ҳам мавжуд.

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ЛОГИСТИКА СОҲАСИ ТЕРМИНОЛОГИК МАЙДОНИ

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Аввалдан қўлланилиб келинган «термин» ва «терминология» масалалари юзасидан кўплаб тадқиқот ишлари олиб борилган бўлиб, турли таърифлар берилган. Термин (лотинча terminus – чегара, ҳад) – билим ёки фаолиятнинг махсус соҳасига оид доир тушунчани ифодаловчи сўз ёки сўз бирикмасидир [<https://qomus.info/oz>]. Термин ва умумистеъмолдаги сўзлар бир-бирини тўлдирадиган лексик бирликлардир. Систем характерга эгалик, ўз терминологик майдонида бир маъноликка мойиллик, ҳис туйғуни ифодаламаслик, услубий бетаърафлик кабилар терминга хос хусусиятлардир. П.Нишоновнинг таъкидлашича, «Термин – тузилишига кўра сўз ёки сўз бирикмаси бўлиб, семантикаси жихатидан махсус соҳа доираси билан чегараланган ва шу соҳага оид тушунчани ифодаловчи лексик бирликдир»[Нишонов П. Француз ва ўзбек тиллари юридик терминологиясининг қиёсий-типологик тадқиқи: Филол. фан. ном. ... дисс. автореф. –Тошкент, 2009. – 26 б.]

Терминологияни тушунишдаги хилма-хиллик (рус тилшунослигида) ўзбек тилшунослигида бўлгани каби, хорижий тил илмида ҳам мавжуд. Терминологиянинг моҳияти хусусидаги нуқтаи назарлар тафовути ҳақида Д.Сагедер шундай ёзади: Терминологияни илмий фан сифатида қарашга доир нуқтаи назарлар анча тарқоқ. Ҳозирги вақтда ушбу соҳа ва унга ёндош бўлган бир қатор мунозарали масалалар бўйича турли талқинлар мавжуд.

Терминология фанми ёки фақат методми? Терминология ўз хусусий назариясига эга бўлган алоҳида гуманитар фан мақомига эгами ёки у ўзининг назарий имкониятлари учун нисбатан консолидацияланган фанлардан миннатдор бўлиши керакми, назарий жиҳатдан нисбатан барқарор бирор фан таркибими? <...>. Терминология фанининг аҳамиятини камситиб бўлмайди. Уни ўз эволюцияси ва замонавий технологияларнинг тез ўзгарувчан оламида олдинга томон ҳаракатланиши туфайли тарихан муҳим куч сифатида кўриб чиқиш лозим [227; -Б.124].

Термининг ўзига хос хусусиятларидан бири термининг махсус соҳада ва профессионал соҳада қўлланилишидир. Бундай терминологиянинг луғат қатлами маълум бир билим соҳаси билан чегараланган бўлади.

Б.Н. Головин таъкидлашича “касб-ҳунар нуқтаи назаридан қаралганида термин ўзида муайян касбий тушунчаларни ифода этади”[Головин Б.Н. Лингвистические основы учения о терминах. М.: 87. - 135б].

А.А. Реформатскийнинг фикрича: “Термин – бу сўз бўлиб, ўзининг алоҳида ва махсус белгилари билан чегараланади, фан, техника, иқтисодиёт, сиёсат ва дипломатия соҳаларида бир маъноли, аниқ сўздир. У экспрессивликдан холи, муайян предмет ёхуд тушунчани ифода этувчи, ўзининг қатъий ва аниқ мазмуний чегарасига ҳамда изоҳига эга бўлади”. [Реформатский А.А. Термин как член лексической системы языка//Проблемы структурной лингвистики. -М.: Наука.1968. - 210 с.].

Н.П.Кузькинни фикрича, “ умумий адабий лексика билан махсус соҳадаги термин ўртасидаги ёхуд сўз бирикмаси билан шакл ва таркибий жиҳатдан ҳеч қандай фаркли жиҳатлари бўлмаган тақдирда ҳам умумадабиётда кенг қўлланиладиган лексема ҳаммага таниш бўлган объектга хос бўлиб, терминологик соҳадаги термин эса фақатгина тор доирадаги мутахассисларгагина оид бўлади”[Кузькин Н.П. К вопросу о сущности термина // Вестник ЛГУ. – №20. – Вып. 4. – Л., 1962. – С. 132.]

“ Ҳар қандай термин” деб қайд этади Р.Ф. Пронин , - атрофидаги сўзлар ва контекстга боғлиқ бўлмаган сўзлар алоҳида семантик бирлик сифатида эмас, балки маълум бир соҳадаги техник маънога эга, қўлланилганлик даражасига, соҳасига кўра таркибини ўзгартириш мумкин бўлган сўз сифатида қаралиши керак”[Пронина Р.Ф. Перевод английской научно-технической литературы. – М.: Высшая школа, 1996. –145 с.]

Аммо баъзи тилшунослар ушбу фикрга қарама қарши фикрни яъни терминнинг контекстга ҳеч қандай алоқаси йўқ деган ғояни илгари суришади. “Агарда терминологиянинг қайсидир туркумга хослиги аниқ бўлса, у ҳолда терминлар контекст ташқарисида ҳам ишлаши мумкин” [Реформатский А.А. Термин как член лексической системы языка // Проблемы структурной лингвистики. – М., 1968. – 536 с.]

Фикримизча мазкур хилма хиллик, олимларнинг контекст тушунчасини турлича тушунишидадир. Контекстни сўз айланиши, нутқдаги вазият, баёнот жанрини қамраб олади, айнан шунинг учун ҳам нутқнинг контексти, вазят мазмунини ажратиб туради. контекст оғзаки ёки ёзма нутқ (матн)нинг нисбатан тугал қисми бўлиб, ўз таркибидаги сўзлар ёки ибораларнинг маъноларини аниқлашга имкон беради.

Логистика соҳаси мутахасислари томонидан олиб борилган тадқиқотлар таҳлиллар натижасида ушбу соҳа билан кесишган 12 та фан жабҳалари, жумладан, менеджмент, савдо-сотиқ фаолияти, маркетинг, нарх бўйича таълим, халқаро муносабатлар, транспорт, информатика, технология, машинасозлик кабилар аниқланган³. Ушбу далил логистика терминологияси тизими В.М. Лейчик тавсифлаган унификация тамойили асосида шаклланганлигини тасдиқлайди. В.М. Лейчикнинг тавсифлашича, “бир нечта соҳага оид бўлган билимларни комплекс тарзда эгаллаш терминлар мажмуининг бирлашувига

олиб келади” яна шуни таъкидлайдики, “маълум бир соҳага оид терминологиянинг ясалиш жиҳатларини таҳлил қилганда аниқ бўлдики, ушбу усуллар лексемаларнинг табиий равишда тилда ясалиши йўллари билан мос келади” [Лейчик В.М. Терминоведение: предмет, методы, структура. М., 2006. - С. 96.]

А.И. Смирницкийнинг тадқиқотларида юритган назариясига мувофиқ терминологик майдонларга ажратиш тамойиллари ишлаб чиқилган [Смирницкий А.И. Лексикология английского языка. М.: МГУ, 1998. - С. 17.] бўлиб, ҳар бир махсус соҳа ўзи хос терминлар билан тўлдирилган.

Шу тариқа, 9 та терминологик майдон:

- *purchasing management* / харидни тизимини бошқариш;
- *logistics of production* / ишлаб чиқаришни логистик қўллаб қувватлаш;
- *order management* / буюртма тизими бошқаруви;
- *transportation* / транспорт воситасида юкларни ташиш;
- *warehousing and material handling* / омборда сақлаш ва маҳсулотни қайта ишлаш;
- *inventory management* / замланган маҳсулот бошқаруви;
- *information technologies* / ахборот технологиялари;
- *logistics management* / логистика тизими бошқаруви;
- *supply chain management* / таъминот тизими бошқаруви.

Ушбу термино-майдон логистика тизимининг таркибий қисми билан мос келиб, инглиз тили логистикасининг тизимлилигинидан далолат беради.

Логистика соҳасининг асосий тадқиқ объектларидан бири оқим бўлиб, асосий терминлари – моддий оқим, ахборот оқими, молиявий оқим ва бошқалар. Ушбу тушунчанинг логистика соҳасидаги маъносига ойдинлик киритиш мақсадида келтирилган турли изоҳларга мурожаат қиламиз: “ҳаракатланувчи масса эмас балки [Ожегов С.И. Словарь русского языка. М., 1990. - С. 57.], бир бутун саналадиган объектлар мажмуи...” [Аникин Б.А. Логистика. М., 2002. - С. 17.] ёки “ишлаб чиқариш манбасидан белгиланган

жойга ўзгартиладиган бир хил иқтисодий элементлар тўплами” [Стаханов В.Н., Украинцев В.Б. Теоретические основы логистики. - Ростов-на-Дону, 2001. - С. 57].

Оқим терминининг изоҳини логистик манбалардан топиш мушкул масала бўлиб, ташкилот бошқаруви бўйича энг йирик энциклопедик нашрда мавжуд эмас [Управление организацией: Энциклопедический словарь. М., 2001. - С. 142.]. Негаки, оқимлар фақат иқтисодий тавсифга эга.

Логистика соҳасининг муҳим шартлари қуйидагилардан иборат:

- *логистик операция/иш;* *логистика хизмати;*
- *логистиканинг вазифаси;* *логистика технологияси;*
- *логистика жараёни;* *логистик цикл/давр;*

Логистика оқимлар билан боғлиқ жараёнларнинг ўзига хос хусусиятларини ўрганиш билан бирга операцион/ишга оид шартлар тўғридан-тўғри оқим терминлари гуруҳига асосланади.

Асосий тушунча сифатида эътироф этилган логистик тушунчаси оқимлар устида олиб борилган тадқиқотлар жараёнида янги пайдо бўлган термин маъноси қабул қилинсагина, уни инкор этиш мумкин бўлади.

Операцион гуруҳга оид барча терминлар аслида логистикага оид бўлиб, шунингдек, терминларни оқимлар, вазифалар, жараёнлар, цикллар/даврларга бўлиб татбиқ этиш уларнинг мазмуни ҳамда истиқболли тадқиқот натижаларига янгича қарашни талаб этади.

Логистиканинг таркибини ташкил этувчи терминларга қуйидагиларни мисол қилиш мумкин:

- *логистик таркибий қисм;* *логистика тизими;*
- *микро-логистика тизими;* *логистик занжир;*
- *макрологистик тизим;* *логистика тармоғи;*
- *мезологистик тизим;* *логистика воситаси;*
- *логистика тизимининг бирлиги.*

Операцион, оқим гуруҳлари ва шакллантирувчи терминлар логистиканинг асосий терминологияси ҳисобланиб, соҳада қўлланиладиган қолган терминлар уларга асосланади. Шунингдек, бу гуруҳлар терминларни умумлаштириб, амалда тадбиқ этади. Логистика ва занжир таъминотини бошқариш мустақил объектлар ва тадқиқот предметига эга бўлган турли йўналишлар занжир таъминотини бошқаришга оид бўлган терминлар – таъминот занжири, занжир таъминоти бошқаруви, ташкилотлараро логистикани мувофиқлаштириш кабилар А.Г.Купцова томонидан фанга киритилган [Анализ терминосистемы новой области знаний (логистики). Статья. М., 2007. - С. 56-57.С.] бўлиб, бошқарув йўналишлари бир-бири билан узвий боғланган.

Айрим тадқиқотчиларнинг фикрича, логистика соҳасининг терминологияси тўлиқ шакллантирилмаган. Шу ўринда, А.Н. Стерлигованинг инглиз тили логистика термино-тизими кўп сўзларнинг бошқа тиллардан ўзлашганига қарамасдан логистика соҳасини асосий шаклланган соҳалар қаторига қўшса бўлади, - деган фикрни илгари суради. Рус тили логистик терминологияси эса бугунги куннинг долзарб соҳаларидан бири ҳисобланади [Купцова А.Г. Современные проблемы перевода терминов. М., 2006.- С.13-14.]. Тилшуносларнинг эътирофига биноан, бугунги кунда рус ва ўзбек тилларига ўзлашган кўплаб янги терминлар стандартизация ва унификациялашни тақозо этади. Л.Л.Кутинанинг фикрига кўра, “кераксиз дублетларнинг кириб келиши ва ўзлашишини бартараф этиш керак”.

Таъкидлаш жоизки, логистиканинг инглиз тили термин-тизими нисбатан ёш ва доимий равишда ўсиб боровчи лексик бирликлар мажмуидир. Логистика мунтазам бошқа махсус соҳалар, жумладан, транспорт, менежмент, молияга оид терминология билан ўзаро алоқада бўлиб, уларга хос терминларни ўзлаштириб ёки ўзининг доирасини доимий кенгайтириб боради. Бундан англаш мумкинки, термин-тизими тўлиқ шаклланмаган, балки, шаклланиш босқичида эканлигини кўрсатади. Демак, логистика термин-тизими бир-бирига боғлиқ бўлган фан соҳаларининг терминлари воситасида доимо ўзининг терминологиясини

тўлдириб боради. Бундан ташқари, ушбу соҳа термин-тизимида қўлланила бошланган терминлар ўзига хос маъно касб этади. Шунга қарамай, ушбу соҳа термин-тизими ўзига хос хусусиятларга эга бўлиб, айниқса таркибий қисмида бу ҳолат яққол кўзга ташланади.

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КОННОТАТИВ КОМПОНЕНТЛАРНИНГ КЎЧИМ АСОСЛИ МЕТАФОРЛАРДА ИФОДАЛАНИШИ

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Аннотация: Мақолада коннотатив маъно кўчимлар асосида очиб берилади. Айниқса, метафора коннотатив компонент учун энг муҳим аҳамият касб этиши ва бу воқелик асосида субъектив баҳонинг даражаланиш имконияти кенглиги яққол мисоллар асосида тушунтирилади.

Калим сўзлар: *эмоционал-баҳолаш, метафора, лисоний коллектив, коннотатив компонент, антонимик характер.*

Метафоралар эмоционал-баҳоловчи номинациялар ташкил қилишда универсал лисоний восита сифатида жуда кўпчилик тадқиқотчиларнинг диққат-эътиборини тортган қизиқарли мавзудир (Вольф Е.М.(1979,1985), Лукянова Н.А.(1976,1979), Ретунская М.С.(1987). Стернин И.А (1979,1985), Телия В.Н. (1981,1986,1991) ва б).

Метафораларда нафақат баҳолаш, балки ҳис-ҳаяжон, қаҳр-ғазаб, нафрат, жирканиш, бепарқлик, назар-писанд қилмаслик сингари салбий ва аксинча хурмат-иззат, ҳайрат, қувонч каби ижобий коннотатив компонентлар, шунингдек эмоционал бўёқдорлик иштирок этиб, улар мулоқот жараёнида фикрни экспрессив ифодалаш воситаси сифатида ҳам қўлланилади. (Вольф,1985:170).

Метафорадаги баҳоловчи коннотация лисоний коллектив тасаввурида объектни «яхши-ямон» диапозонида идрок қилинишига ёрдам беради. Умуман «яхши» ва «ёмон» критериясига кирувчи баҳоловчи метафоралар ёрдамида гапирувчининг (муаллифнинг), лисоний коллективнинг, ёки умуминсониятнинг у ёки бу даражадаги мулоқот эҳтиёжлари қондирилади. Бу эҳтиёжлар эстетик, ахлоқий-этик, ижтимоий характерда бўлиб, инсоният онгида шаклланган

эстетик ва ахлоқий нормаларга мос келувчи ёки зид келувчи камчиликлар, нуқсонлар, тушунчаларни ифодаланади.(Салеев: 1995: 12). Баҳолашнинг антонимик характерда бўлишлиги идрок қилинаётган лисоний birlikларнинг интуитив равишда ижобий ва салбий муносабат билдиришга асосланишига боғлиқ.

Метафорик коннотациядаги баҳоловчи белгилар лисоний муҳитда шаклланган лисоний меъёрлар билан белгиланади ва баҳоловчи муносабат мулоқот жараёнида ёшга, касбга, диний этиқодга доир тушунчаларни ҳам қамраб олади. Шу нуқтаи назардан уларни метафоранинг коммуникатив вазиятга кўра аниқланадиган кўчирма маънода ифодаланадиган коннотатив компонентлари дея талқин қилиш мумкин (Телия,1991:121). Бундай ҳолда эмоционал баҳолаш лексик birlikнинг семантик белгилари образлари орқали идрок қилинади.

Айрим ҳолларда денотатив маъно ифодаладиган номинатив birlikлар бошқа сўзлар билан бирикиб, коннотатив баҳоловчи компонентларга эга бўладилар. Масалан, «сут», «қор», «қоғоз» каби лексик birlikлар денотатив маъносидан ташқари рангни ифодаловчи «оқ» маъносига ҳам эга ва улар бошқа лексик birlikлар билан бирикиб, «оқ» маъносини йўқотганлари ҳолда қўшимча, образли ижобий ёки салбий баҳоловчи маъноларга ҳам эга бўлади. Масалан:

Crabby man- жиззаки одам,

Negro – негр, ҳабаш, қора одам.

Elder journalist – кекса журналист.

Бундай ҳолатни айнан «оқ» сифатининг феъллар билан бирикиви орқали ясалган салбий маъноли метафораларда ҳам кўришимиз мумкин:

Thirst- ташналикдан қийналмоқ;

Hesitate– иккиланмоқ, бирор қарорга келолмаслик;

Forget something suddenly –тўсатдан ниманидир унутиб қуймоқ.

Бундай коннотацияларни умуминсоний, миллий, ижтимоий, касбий соҳаларга кўра классификация қилиш мумкин. (Лукьянова 1979: 37).

Ассоциатив кўчирма маънодаги метафоралар миллий характерга эга бўлишлари мумкин.. Масалан, ўзбек тилида «қўл» нейтрал маъноли номинатив бирлик билан бирикиб ясалган, турли мулоқот вазиятларида қўлланиладиган метафоралардаги ижобий, салбий ва нейтрал баҳоловчи коннотацияларга эътибор берайлик:

Ижобий баҳоловчи коннотацияли метафоралар:

қўли узун - бирор ишни бажаришда қурби етмоқ, маблаги кўп(оз) бўлмоқ;

қўлини сўрамоқ- келинликка розилик сўрамоқ

қўли ширин - маҳоратли ошпаз

Салбий баҳоловчи коннотацияли метафоралар

қўли калта- бирор ишни уддасидан чиқаолмаслик, муҳтожлик;

қўли эгри - ўғри, ноинсоф

қўлнинг кири - тез сарфланадиган маблағ

қўли оғир –уқувсиз,

қўлини совуқ сувга урмаслик – ишёқмаслик, дангасалик

Нейтрал баҳоловчи коннотацияли метафоралар:

қўл етмас – қуби етмаслик, иложсиз;

қўл олмоқ- қўл бериб кўришмоқ, шогирд(мурид) бўлмоқ, келишмоқ;

қўли қичимоқ- бирор ишни бажаришга чанқоқлик, эҳтиёж

Метафораларда асос сўз функциясини бажарувчи компонентлар турли тилларда турлича баҳоловчи компонентларга эга бўлиши мумкин. Масалан, рус ва ўзбек тилларида «**айиқ**» сўзи асосида «бесунақайлик» коннотатив баҳоловчи маъноси ётса, француз тилида бу сўз билан ясалган метафораларда кўполлик, тарбиясизлик коннотатив маънолари ифодаланади: **rude man**– кўпол, тарбиясиз одам, - **as rude a bear** айиқдек кўпол.

Ассоциатив метафоралар ҳайвон ва жониворлар номи билан ясалганида умуминсоний салбий баҳоловчи характерда бўлишлиги билан қизиқарлидир.

Масалан, одатда **ит** ҳақида гапирилганида, барча тилларда «қопоғонлик», **товук** – «хафсаласиз», **бўри** – «оч, ёвуз», **эшак** - «қайсар», «овсар» сингари коннотатив маънолар англанади. Бундай умуминсоний характердаги метафораларни ижобий баҳоловчи номинацияларда ҳам кўришимиз мумкин. Масалан, барча тилларда «**олтин**» сўзининг- «қимматбаҳо», «**океан**» сўзининг – «бепаён» сингари коннотатив компонентлари мавжуд (Стернин, 1985: 170).

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ОСОБЕННОСТИ РАБОТЫ НАД ПОНЯТИЕМ «СТИЛЬ РЕЧИ»

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Аннотация. В статье освещается вопрос об особенностях работы над стилями речи при обучении русскому языку. Выделены особенности каждого

вида стиля при работе над навыками правильного и целесообразного употребления языковых средств. Определены стилистические навыки, которые основываются на понимании стилистической дифференциации речи. Проанализированы три ступени изучения стиля речи в экономическом вузе.

Ключевые слова: *стили речи, профессиональная компетенция, стилистические особенности, языковые средства, стилистика, коммуникативный метод.*

Возросшие профессиональные требования к личности специалиста усилили потребность в формировании творческой индивидуальности, реализации творческих способностей, развитии индивидуального стиля деятельности. Профессионально-важными качествами личности экономиста является способность умело сочетать в своем мышлении и поведении образное и логическое. Экономисту как творческой личности необходимо овладеть логикой, развивать педагогическую интуицию, способность к импровизации, овладеть разносторонними знаниями, в том числе умением общаться на русском языке.

Коммуникативный метод предполагает освоение неродного языка в процессе живого непринужденного общения. Он способствует разрушению психологического барьера между преподавателем и студентом при использовании многочисленных приемов с использованием ситуативных заданий, деловых и ролевых игр. Благодаря коммуникативному методу мы формируем профессиональную компетенцию-готовность и умение общаться в профессиональной сфере коммуникации.

Говоря о достоинствах коммуникативного метода, В.Г. Костомаров и О.Д. Митрофанова метко характеризуют его: «Только коммуникативность способна сделать процесс овладения русским языком привлекательным для тех, кого интересует функция, но не структура, кто готов изучать структуру ради функции, но никак не хочет изучать структуру ради структуры». Из этого следует, что студенты будут активно, с интересом изучать русский язык, если

поймут, что он поможет им глубже овладеть специальностью и, очевидно, в дальнейшем профессиональной деятельностью. Формирование навыков профессионального общения, осуществляемого с помощью разных видов и форм речи, проходит в процессе обучения речевой деятельности (чтению, аудированию, устной и письменной речи). Обучение языку – сложный многосторонний процесс, и одну из важнейших сторон этого процесса составляет развитие речи студентов. Язык неразрывно связан с мышлением. Следовательно, и развитие речи связано с развитием мышления. Осваивая в вузе основы наук и тем самым, развивая свое мышление, студент в то же время совершенствует свою речь. Но овладение языком, развитие речи являются не только результатом, но и важнейшим условием успешного усвоения основ наук.

Для развития речи необходимо соблюдать в построении предложений логичность (точность, обоснованность, четкость и ясность, последовательность), образность, эмоциональную выразительность, соответствие нормам литературного языка.

Развитие речи должно обогатить студентов необходимым (и доступным им) запасом слов и синтаксических конструкций, сформировать у студентов навыки правильного употребления слов, словосочетаний, предложений. Этими неразрывно связанными компонентами развития речи определяется содержание работы преподавателя по развитию речи в процессе преподавания русского языка. Язык должен быть изучен с двух точек зрения: с точки зрения строя языка, его системы и с точки зрения употребления языковых единиц в речи, т.е. определяются две основные части: «учение о строе языка и учение о его употреблении».

К дисциплинам, изучающим строй языка, относятся: фонетика, грамматика, лексика, а дисциплина, изучающая употребление языка – стилистика.

В один ряд со стилистикой следует поставить культуру речи, которая вычленилась в самостоятельный раздел языкознания. Взаимодействуя, оба эти раздела языкознания регулируют вопросы употребления, функционирования языковых средств.

«Особенности работы над понятием «стиль речи» определяются спецификой самого речевого понятия. Чтобы раскрыть речевое понятие, надо выйти за пределы языка и проанализировать речевую ситуацию. «Стиль – это явление, которое может быть понято только при учете целей, задач, ситуаций и сферы общения и самого содержания высказывания».

Следует иметь в виду, что вопросы употребления языковых средств – важнейшая задача курса русского языка, цель которого: научить студентов свободно пользоваться устной и письменной речью в различных сферах – общественно-экономической, научной, бытовой, производственной.

Осуществление этой задачи предполагает «усвоение учащимися (студентами) дифференцированного со стилистической точки зрения использования лексики, фразеологии, грамматических средств русского языка.

Работа над навыками правильного и целесообразного употребления языковых средств требует систематического проведения. Это должно найти отражение в новом поколении вузовских программ, учебных пособий, учебников. Это важно учитывать и при обучении русскому языку будущих экономистов (финансистов, менеджеров, аудиторов, банкиров). Для правильной организации работы по развитию речи важно помнить о том, что при «параллельном», «аспектном» изучении культуры речи в практическом учебном курсе необходимо установить точную взаимосвязь с другими разделами и аспектами курса русского языка и стилистики. В современном русском литературном языке наиболее последовательно выделяются следующие функциональные стили речи: разговорно-обиходный, научный (научно-технический, естественнонаучный, научно-гуманитарный, научно-популярный), газетно - публицистический, официально-деловой и

художественный. Выделяемые стили речи нельзя понимать, как замкнутые, изолированные системы. Они взаимосвязаны, и отдельные элементы их часто переходят из одного стиля в другой, влияют друг на друга. Каждый из функциональных стилей речи соответствует определенной, довольно широкой сфере общения, которая связана с определенным родом общественной деятельности людей. Они имеют свои, особые нормы отбора и сочетания языковых единиц, отвечающие специфическим задачам общения в данной коммуникативной сфере. Стилистическая дифференциация речи создает условия и базу для максимальной выразительности речи, для выражения конкретной речевой ситуации, ее целевого назначения.

На этом основании у студентов-экономистов должны быть выработаны определенные стилистические навыки, которые основываются на понимании стилистической дифференциации речи. Для этого преподавателю следует определить количество стилистически окрашенного материала, вводимого на каждом этапе обучения. На конкретном речевом материале целесообразно продемонстрировать различия устной и письменной форм речи. Работу над формированием стилистических навыков необходимо связать с иллюстрацией специфических особенностей функционирования языка в профессиональных сферах общения.

Работа над основными понятиями стиля речи начинается уже на первом курсе, однако полное представление о стиле речи как системе языковых средств может быть сформировано лишь к концу вузовского курса русского языка. На начальном этапе понятие стиля может быть раскрыто главным образом через признаки внеязыковые – особенности языковой ситуации и содержания. Языковые же примеры стиля вырисовываются постепенно, по мере изучения уровней русского языка.

Представляется целесообразным выделить три ступени изучения стиля речи в экономическом вузе:

- на первом этапе – первоначальное знакомство с понятиями всех функциональных стилей речи. Задача этого этапа – закрепить в сознании студентов связь каждого стиля речи с типовой речевой ситуацией, познакомить с основными стилевыми чертами и научить соотносить с ними содержание и языковую форму высказывания (на материале лексики, словообразования, морфологии и тех синтаксических сведений, которыми располагают студенты этого этапа обучения русскому языку);
- на второй ступени представление о языковой структуре стилей речи расширяется за счет синтаксических сведений;
- и, наконец, на третьей ступени, сведения о функциональных стилях речи обобщаются, систематизируются и приобретают практическую направленность: определение видов речи, составление речей по образцу, анализ образцов, произнесение речей.

Стиль – понятие речевое, и определить его можно, учитывая такие внеязыковые обстоятельства как задачи речи, сфера общения.

Учет экстралингвистических факторов позволяет сделать описание стиля многомерным, «объемным». При таком подходе разрозненные лингвистические приметы стиля (окраска, частотность языковых единиц) объединяются в цельную речевую структуру, отражающую условия и цели общения.

Для стиля важен отбор значений лексико-грамматической единицы. Употребляясь в речи, «языковая единица как бы расщепляется» и выступает в разных стилях, в разных своих функциональных значениях. Так, при близкой частотности форм настоящего времени глаголов в научном и разговорном стилях речи они резко отличаются по значению: в разговорном стиле они обозначают конкретное действие, происходящее в данный момент – Пишу письмо. Что читаешь? и т.д., в научном стиле, наоборот, преобладает значение объективного процесса, протекающего безотносительно ко времени. – Аудиторы ведут проверку соответствия баланса предприятия. Банкир работает с клиентами. Менеджер управляет людьми и бизнесом и т.д.

В современной лингвистике выделяют два вида стилистически окрашенных языковых средств – экспрессивные и функциональные.

Экспрессивная и функциональная окраски взаимодействуют в языке и часто (хотя и не всегда) проявляются в слове (или другой языковой единице) одновременно. Одни виды эмоциональной экспрессии закрепляются за разговорными единицами, другие – за книжными. Изысканность, поэтическая приподнятость, торжественность, официальность присущи книжным словам, фамильярность, шутливость, непринужденность, непритязательность – разговорным. Поэтому представляется возможным соединить экспрессию и нормативность.

Стилистическая окраска пронизывает всю языковую систему, но распределена она по уровням языка неравномерно.

Имеются также стилистически окрашенные структуры в словообразовании и синтаксисе. Например, суффиксальные модели существительных со значением собирательности: мужичье, офицерье (разг.) – солдатня, шоферня (разг.) – интеллигенция (нейтр.) – профессура, клиентура (кн.).

В качестве примера стилистически окрашенных синтаксических конструкций могут быть использованы предложения с причастными оборотами (кн.) в сопоставлении с придаточными определительными (нейтр.) или конструкции побудительных предложений: Не читай! (нейтр.) – Я тебе почитаю! (разг.) и др.

В пределах стиля используются как стилистически окрашенные, так и нейтральные средства, однако и те, и другие сочетаются между собой на основе выполнения единого коммуникативного задания и потому образуют речевую систему.

Вследствие этого в сознании студентов формируются принципы отбора языковых средств в соответствии с условиями и задачами общения, внутренние установки на использование определенных единиц языка.

Ознакомление студентов со стилевым расслоением речи начинается с разграничения наиболее контрастных типов речи. Такими, несомненно, являются разговорный тип, ядро которого – разговорный стиль, и противостоящий ему книжный тип, объединяющий все остальные стили (научный, официально-деловой, публицистический, художественный). В основе этого разграничения несколько факторов, важнейший из которых – сфера общения.

Существенно и различие в коммуникативной функции языка. Для разговорного стиля характерна бытовая тематика, невысокая содержательность речи, оперирование не столько понятиями, сколько представлениями.

В книжных стилях наблюдается противоположное стремление к точности называния: преобладают термины, однозначные слова, прямые значения слов.

Это главное разделение внутри функциональных стилей (разговорный стиль – книжные стили) поддерживается существующей стилистической дифференциацией слов на книжные и разговорные.

Различия между разговорной и книжной речью в значительной мере определяются формой речи, устной или письменной, хотя все функциональные стили могут реализоваться и в той, и в другой форме речи, однако вероятность этих реализаций в разных стилях различна. Форма речи накладывает отпечаток на структуру функционального стиля. При непосредственном (устном) общении большую роль играет интонация, мимика, жесты и другие дополнительные способы передачи информации. Вступает в силу закон экономии языковых средств – отсюда обилие неполных предложений в разговорном стиле. И наоборот, отсутствие непосредственного контакта при общении (письменная форма речи) и как следствие этого отсутствие дополнительных каналов информации обязывают прибегать к полным структурам в книжных стилях.

Разговорный стиль от книжных отличает также еще и то, что в основе разговорного стиля лежит диалог, основу же книжных стилей составляет монологическая речь.

Коммуникативный принцип, господствующий в современной методике преподавания русского языка студентам-нефилологам, требует обучения их главным образом научному стилю, т.е. языку будущей специальности, предполагая, что в средней школе им привили навыки общения в разговорной, национально культурной сфере.

Обучать устной монологической и диалогической речи студентов-экономистов – задача чрезвычайно актуальная. Нерусским студентам надо привить навыки монологической речи как устной, так и письменной с использованием различных функциональных стилей, особенно стилей книжных, которыми до вуза, как правило, студенты не владеют.

Среди книжных стилей резко других противопоставлены художественный, с одной стороны, научный и официально-деловой с другой. Различия между ними сводятся, в основном, к различию в функциях языка.

Язык науки и делопроизводства выполняет функцию сообщения. Язык художественного произведения выступает не только (и, быть может, не столько) средством коммуникации, но и средством воздействия на людей.

Ученый сообщает свои наблюдения при помощи понятий, абстракций, художник – через конкретный образ, путем умелого отбора выразительных деталей. Первый сообщает сведения о предмете речи, второй показывает, рисует, изображает этот предмет.

Для разграничения художественного и научного стилей существенны следующие противопоставления: 1) конкретность - абстрактность; 2) образность – отсутствие образности; 3) субъективность – объективность; 4) эмоциональность – отсутствие эмоциональности.

Следующий этап расчленения речи связан с выделением на фоне научно-деловой речи официально-делового стиля.

Речь научная и официально-деловая похожи, так как основываются на общей языковой функции – функции сообщения. Различия между ними обусловлены сферами общения, близкими, но не идентичными: научный стиль связан с научной деятельностью человека, официально-деловой – с общественной. Существенные стилевые различия между ними проходят главным образом по линии «абстрактность – конкретность». Ср., например, деловое описание какого-либо определенного человека (так называемую производственную характеристику) и научное описание человека как биологической особи.

Последним на этапе знакомства с функциональными стилями изучаются элементы публицистического стиля. Это сложное, многоаспектное речевое единство; в нем органически сливаются черты разных функциональных стилей: научного, официально-делового, художественного, разговорного.

Специфика публицистики объясняется многофункциональной природой стиля. Для нее, как и для художественного стиля, характерна не только функция сообщения, но и функция воздействия, причем в двух ее проявлениях – воздействие на чувство и воздействие на волю. Адресатом воздействия являются массы, объединенные общими социально-политическими интересами (сфера общественного сознания, обслуживаемая публицистическим стилем, как известно, общественная жизнь, политика). На оси «абстрактное – конкретное» публицистический стиль располагается рядом с научным.

С другой стороны, функция воздействия на волю и обращенность к массам сближают его с официально-деловым стилем, с языком приказов, инструкцией. Отсюда тенденция к штампу, языковому шаблону, клише, общая для публицистического и официально-делового стилей.

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ЖАҲОН ТИЛШУНОСЛИГИДА ТЕРМИНЛАР ТАСНИФИГА ОИД АЙРИМ МУЛОҲАЗАЛАР

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Аннотация: Мақолада жаҳон тилшунослигида термин ва терминология тушунчаларига бўлган муносабатлар, қарашлар, нуқтаи назарлар баён этилди. Шунингдек, терминларнинг тилшуносликда тутган ўрни, махсус лексик бирлик сифатида луғат қатлаидан муҳим ўрин эгаллаши ўрганилди. Термин тушунчасига муаллифнинг муносабати билдирилди.

Калит сўзлар: терминология, ўзлашган сўзлар, тилшунослик, лексик бирлик, луғат қатлами

Немис тилшунослигида терминларни тадқиқ этишининг муҳим нуқтаи назарлари мавжуд бўлиб, бу янги назарияларни аниқлаш учун 1970 йиллардан бери немис тилшунослигида муайян ёндошувларга мурожаат қилиниб, тадқиқотлар олиб борилмоқда. Немис тилшунослигида терминология „Fachsprache“ сифатида кўплаб тилшунослик адабиётларида берилди. Л. Ҳоффман, „Fachsprache“ барча тил воситаларининг йиғиндиси сифатида махсус чегараланган мулоқот доирасида фақат ўша маълум соҳада фаолият юритадиган инсонлар тушуниши учун ишлатилади” – деб қайд этади [2. 53]. Ҳ. Флук терминлар нафақат мутахассислар ўртасида алоқа воситаси сифатида намоён бўлиши акс эттирилган, балки билиш воситаси, яъни касбий билимларга эга бўлиш усулларини билишга ҳам хизмат қилади, деган фикрни билдиради [1. 34]. Бундан кўринадики, бу таърифлар ҳатто тизимли йўналтирилган бўлишига қарамай, терминларнинг функционал ва мулоқот вазифалари борлигини кўрсатади. Терминлар бошқа томондан мутахассислар ўртасида ўзаро мулоқотни самарали ёритиб бериш имконини беради.

80-йилларнинг бошига келиб, прагматингвистик матн моделига бурилиш юз бериши билан терминлар махсус мулоқот воситаси сифатида қабул қилишини учун илмий матнларда ишлатила бошлади. Р. Бульманн ва А. Фернзнинг таъкидлашича, Л. Ҳоффманн ўз лингвистик қарашларида терминологик фаразларга ва терминологияда термин тизимли бўлишга эга, деган фаразларга қарши ўлароқ, у терминга шунчаки умумтилнинг стилистик варианты, деб ёндашди [7. 224]. Д. Моен ва П. Роналд томонидан билдирилган, термин (махсус сўз бирикмаси ва тилда махсус ифодаланадиган сўзлар) у аниқ бир фан соҳаси ҳисобланиб, (терминологик аниқлик асосида) ушбу соҳани аниқ тушуниш, аниқ тасвирлаш имконини беради, деган фикр термин тушунчасига берилган таърифларни янада тўлдиради [5. 27]. Бизнингча, термин махсус лексика, у ҳар доим мутахассис билан боғланган бўлади, чунки термин тўла аниқликни талаб қилади. Термин мутахассис бўлмаганлар томонидан

ишлатилганда, термин ўзининг касбий тушунча, фикр билан бевосита боғлиқ бўлган жиҳатини йўқотади.

Фақатгина терминологияда терминларнинг аниқлашда чекланишга йўл кўйилиши махсус лексикалар ва умумтил қоидаларига тўғри келмайди. Бироқ жамиятда фан ва техниканинг ривожланиши туфайли, айрим терминлар эскириши мумкин. В. Клуते терминни ўтказувчанлик хусусиятига эга ва бошқа тил бўлимларига тез тарқалиши мумкин, шунингдек махсус лексика ва умумтил ўртасида тобора ортиб бораётган алмашув мавжудлигини айтади [4. 85]. Гарчи, умумтилда махсус лексика элементлари бўлмаса-да, лексика, синтаксис ва индивидуал фикрлаш шаклини исботлаш учун терминлар таъсирига қараганда кўпроқ тахмин бўлиши мумкин.

Термин юзасидан олиб борилган тадқиқотларда икки хил фикр бири-бирига зид келади. “Редукцион фараз” тарафдорлари терминологияни умумтил деб ҳисоблашади, чунки соҳа мутахассислари умумтилнинг баъзи имкониятларидан кўпроқ фойдаланадилар. Бу ўринда, Р. Штолц шундай фикр билдиради: “Бошқа томондан, терминнинг ўзига хос хусусияти шундаки, улар луғат таркибида мавжуд бўлади ва тегишли фаннинг эҳтиёжларига мослаштирилади ва умумтилга ўтиши равон кечади, шунингдек умуман тушунарли бўлган сўзларни ўз ичига олади. Бошқа томондан эса уларнинг ўзига хос хусусияти маълум (умумтилда) грамматик (морфологик, синтактик) воситалардан фойдаланиш частотасини белгилайди” [8. 98]. Олимларнинг тадқиқотларига кўра, терминология фақат терминлар тўпламини ўз ичига олади, уларнинг умумийлиги терминология деб номланади. И. Хонхолд терминологик луғатларни кузатар экан, қайси сўз туркумлари айнан термин ясаши мумкинлиги борасида фикр билдиради. От ва от-сўз бирикмалар терминологик луғатларнинг кўп қисмини ташкил қилиб, феъллар, сифатлар, атрибутив ишлатиладиган сифатдошлар, равишдошлар термин бўлиши мумкинлигини айтиб ўтади [3. 32]. Шунини алоҳида қайд этиш жоизки, “термин”нинг аниқ таърифи фақат лексик, морфологик, синтактик ва

функционал-стилистик даражадаги мураккаб тилшунослик тадқиқотларини олиб боришга имкон беради.

Терминлар ва терминологиянинг ўзига хос хусусиятларини узоқ вақт ўрганиш мобайнида каттагина миқдорда “термин” тушунчаси таърифлари тўпланиб қолди. Рус тилшунослари Л. Рахманова ва В. Суздалцева ўзларининг тадқиқотларида терминнинг шундай изоҳлайдилар: “Термин бу фан, технология ва бошқа тушунчаларнинг стандартлашган тасвири, расмий равишда тан олинган сўз ёки сўз бирикмаси. Унинг терминологияси фонида, термин аниқ ва стилистик жиҳатдан нейтрал бўлиб қолмоқда. Бу соҳа термини ва одатда ишлатиладиган терминларни бир-биридан ажратиб туради, бунда улар нафақат мутахассислар томонидан тушунилади ва ишлатилади” [6. 224].

Хулоса шуки, биз ўрмончилик терминлари устида олиб бораётган тадқиқотимиздан келиб чиқиб, “термин – бу сўз, аммо оддий сўз эмас, шунингдек сўз бирикмаси, ўз семантик доирасига эга бўлган махсус соҳаларда ишлатилиш кўлами билан чегараланган ҳамда шу соҳага оид тушунчани ифодаловчи лексик бирлик” деб таъриф бердик.

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**ЗАМОНАВИЙ ТИЛШУНОСЛИК: СОЦИОЛИНГВИСТИКА ТИЛ
БИРЛИКЛАРИНИ ИЖТИМОЙ ШАРОИТДА ЎРГАНУВЧИ ФАН
СИФАТИДА.**

Маматова Феруза Махаммадовна

Ўзбекистон Миллий Университети мустақил изланувчиси

Охириги йилларда замонавий тилшуносликда лисоний ходисаларни тилшунослик ва бошқа илмий соҳа билан биргаликда тадқиқ қилиниши долзарб бўлиб бормоқда. Зеро, бу каби ёндашувлар тил бирликларини бир сатҳда эмас, балки етарли даражада чуқурроқ ўрганишга, илмий билимлар ва янги фактлар билан бойитиш орқали турли жиҳатларини очиб бериш имконини беради. Тадқиқотларга мана шу каби ёндашувлар натижасида психолингвистика, этнопсихолингвистика, социолингвистика ва бошқа илмий соҳалар вужудга келди. Социолингвистика ва психолингвистика туташган жойида юқорида тилга олинган анъанани давом эттирувчи социопсихолингвистика яралди.

Тилни унинг ижтимоий шароитида ўрганиш анъанаси натижасида XX-асрнинг ўрталарида пайдо бўлган социолингвистика фан сифатида, социолингвист олимларнинг тилнинг ички тузилиши эмас, балки уни жинси, ёши, ижтимоий мавқеи каби ҳолатларидан келиб чиққан ҳолда муайян жамият вакиллари фойдаланиши қизиқтириб қолди. А.А. Леонтьев тил жараёнларини

фаолият категориялари (сабаб, мақсад, восита ва ҳ.к.) асосида тадқиқ қилиш кераклигини таъкидлаб ўтган [2, 12-13].

Замонавий социолингвистиканинг муҳим ғоялари И.А.Бодуэн де Куртенэ, Е.Д.Поливанов, Л.П.Якубинский, В.М.Жирмунский, Б.А.Ларин, А.М.Селищев, В.В.Виноградов, Г.О.Винокур, Ф.Брюно, А.Мейе, П.Лафарг, М.Коэн, Ш.Балли и А.Сеше, Ж.Вандриес в Бельгии, Б.Гавранек, А.Матезиус, У.Лабов, А.Д.Швейцер, Л.Б. Никольский, В. И. Беликов, Л. П. Крысин ва бошқаларга тегишли. Масалан, тилнинг воситалари мулоқот йўналишлари бўйича бўлинган, мулоқотнинг соҳалар бўйича тақсимланиши эса маълум даражада ижтимоий шарт-шароитлар билан белгиланади деган фикр Ш. Баллига тегишлидир.

Социолингвистиканинг таснифлаш бўйича фикрлар бир-биридан фарқли бўлса-да, тил ва жамият бу соҳанинг асосий ўрганиш объекти эканлиги рад этилмайди. Масалан социолингвистик терминлар йиғиндиси жамланган луғатда у қуйидагича таърифланади: “тилнинг ижтимоий табиати, вазифалари, тилга турли социал омиллар (ижтимоий муносабатларнинг турли белгилари) таъсири ва тилнинг жамиятдаги ўрни билан боғлиқ муаммоларнинг катта ҳажмини ўрганувчи тилшуносликнинг бўлиmidир”[3]. Кенг маънода, социолингвистиканинг тадқиқот предмети сифатида “тил ва жамият” тушунилади деб ёзади А.Д. Швейцер [4, 15-16]. У. Лабов тилнинг кундалик фойдаланилишидаги изланишлардан олинган маълумотлар асосида тил тизими ва нутқий ўзгаришларни ўрганувчи билмилар соҳаси дейди [1, 96]. Р.Хадсон эса шундай фикр билдиради: “Социолингвистика – тилни жамиятга нисбатан ўрганишдир. Тилнинг социологияси бу жамиятни унинг тилга бўлган муносабатида ўрганиш. Агар биринчи берилган таърифда социолингвистиканинг вазифаси айрим лисоний, универсал ёки ўзига хос фактларга ойдинлик киритиш бўлса, иккинчисининг мақсади, аксинча, жамият ҳақида тил маълумотларидан фойдаланган ҳолда янгиликларни билиб олишдир” [6].

Социолингвистиканинг мустақил фан сифатида шаклланиши унинг бўлимлари, методлари, объектларини янада аниқ ажратиб олишга имкон яратди. Социолингвистиканинг бир қатор бўлимлари мавжуд. М.Халлидей куйидагиларни аниқлаб берган [5]:

- Тилнинг макросоциологияси ва лисоний демография, диглоссия, кўп тиллилик, кўп шевалик, лисоний қурулиш ва стардатлаштириш.
- Пиджинизация ва креолизация ҳодисалари
- Ижимоий шевалик ва ностандарт муқобилларнинг тасвири
- Социолингвистика ва таълим
- Нутқнинг этнографияси
- Лисоний регистрлар ва репертуарлар, кодларнинг алмашинуви
- Грамматик ва фонологик ўзгаришларнинг социологик омиллари
- Тил, маданиятнинг жамиятдаги вазифалари
- Болаларда лисоний ривожланишига социолингвистик ёндашув
- Лингвистик нисбийлик
- Лингвистик тизимларнинг функционал назарияси
- Этнометодологик лингвистика
- Матн назарияси

У. Лаббов социолингвистик тадқиқотларга яқин аммо ўзгача бўлган бир нечта мавзулар мажмуини беради [1, 96-81] :

- Тилни стандартлаштириш ва лисоний режалаштириш
- Икки тиллик ва кўп тиллик ҳатти-ҳаракат
- Пиджинизация ва креолизация
- Мулоқотнинг этнографияси
- Нутқ анализи
- Тилнинг ижтимоий қатламлашиши
- Тилга муносабат
- Стилистика
- Лисоний вариантлик

- Ривожланувчи лисоний ўзгаришлар
- Коммуникатив тизимлар

М.Халлидей ва У.Лабовлар ёритиб берган социолингвистиканинг муаммоларидан келиб чиқган ҳолда ўрганилиши зарур бўлган муаммоларнинг мавжудлиги ҳақидаги фикрларга қўшиламыз.

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ПАРАФРАЗЛАР ТАДҚИҚОТ ОБЪЕКТИ СИФАТИДА

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Аннотация: Ушбу мақолада тилнинг тасвирий воситаларидан бири парафразларнинг номланиши ҳақида бўлиб, уларнинг жаҳон тилшунослигидаги мавқеи ҳақидадир. Шунингдек, парафразларнинг рус ва ўзбек тилларидаги ўрганилганлик даражаси ҳам мумкин қадар аниқланди.

Парафразалар асосан предметларга нисбатан қўлланилиб, уларнинг белги-хусусиятларини белгилашда энг муҳим омил эканлиги аниқланди.

Калим сўзлар: *парафраза, айланма (тасвирий) нутқ, перифраза, стилистик приём.*

Ўзбек тили давлат тили мақомини олгач, унинг ўқитилиши ва илмий тадқиқ этилишига жуда катта эътибор берилди. Чунки Ўзбекистоннинг биринчи Президенти И.А. Каримов айтганидек; “Она тилининг буйук аҳамияти шундаки, у маънавият белгиси сифатида кишиларни яқин қилиб жипслаштиради”⁴. Бинобарин, маънавиятимиз белгиси бўлган она тилимиздан – унинг турли-туман ифода воситаларидан кўп ва хўб фойдаланиш, шу воситаларнинг ҳали маълум бўлмаган томонларини, ўзига хосликларини очиб бериш ҳам илмий, ҳам амалий жихатдан муҳим аҳамиятга эгадир, бу давр талаби ҳамдир.

Тилимизнинг бойлигини яққол кўрсатиб турувчи, унинг ифода воситаларидан бири бўлган парафраза муаммоси на шу кунгача алоҳида тадқиқот объекти бўлмаган. Аммо парафраза ҳақида, унинг тил ва нутқдаги ўрни ҳақида оз бўлса-да, муайян фикрлар учраб туради. Парафраза термини тилшуносликда турлича талқин қилинади. Шунга кўра кўйида айни терминнинг луғатларда берилши ва изоҳи билан танишиб чиқамиз:

Профессор О.С. Ахманова лингвистик терминлар луғатида ушбу терминни парафраза тарзида (шаклида) қўллайди ва изоҳлайди: “1. Описательное выражение. 2. Троп, состоящий в замене обычного слова (простого обозначения некоторого предмета одним словом) описательным выражением⁵.” Демак, ишда парафразаларга отатдаги сўзни тасвирий ифода билан алмаштирувчи кўчим сифатида қаралади.

⁴ Каримов И.А. Ўзбекистоннинг ўз истиқлол ва тараққиёт йўли, -Тошкент, 1992. -71-бет.

⁵ Ахманова О.С. Словарь лингвистических терминов. М, 1969 С.312. Выражение являющееся описательной передачей смысла другого

Д.Э. Розенталь ва М.А.Теленковаларнинг луғатида эса ушбу термини “парафраз ва парафраза” тарзида берилади ва шундай изоҳланади: “выражения или слова. Пишущий эти строки (вместо “я” в речи автора) 2. Троп, состоящий в замене названия лица, предмета или явления описанием их характерные черты. Царь зверей (вместо “лев”)”⁶. Демак, парафраза муайян предметининг номи ўрнида қўлланиб, унинг муҳим жиҳатларини, жумладан: белгисини, характерини ва хусусиятини ўзида акс эттирувчи кўчимдир.

“Школьный словарь иностранных слов” луғатида бу термини перифраза тарзида берилади. Ушбу термин грекча periphrasis сўзидан олиниб, “Околная речь”, яъни “айланма (тасвирий) нутқ” деган маънони билдириши айтилади⁷ Демак. Парафраза фикрни тўғридан-тўғри, бевосита эмас, балки бавосита-тасвирий ифодалаш эканлиги қайд этилади.

Хуллас рус тилшунослигида – ўзбек тилига оид тадқиқотларда, жумладан, “Ўзбек тили стилистикаси” дарслигида қайд этилган термин перифраз тарзида ишлатилади ва қўйидагича изоҳ берилади.

“Русча-ўзбекча луғат” да эса, бу термин парафраза берилиб, шундай изоҳланади: “парафраза 1. Лит.бирор асар мундарижасини, маъносини бошқа сўзлар билан айтиб бериш; 2. Муз. бошқа мусикий асардан ёки халқ куйларидан олиб ишланган енгил, шўх асар ёки пьеса”⁸. Кўринадики, парафраза муҳим, фаол қўлланадиган тушунчалардан қатъий ўрин олган.

“Кишиларнинг отларини ёки бошқа предметларнинг номини тўғридан-тўғри гапирмасдан, уларни турли хил сўз ёки тасвирий иборалар воситасида баён қилиш перифраз дейилади. Бу термин перифраза, парафраза, парафраз деб ҳам юритилади”⁹.

⁶ Розенталь Д.Э., Теленкова М.А, Словарь-справочник лингвистических терминов. М., 1976, -С. 270

⁷ . Одинцов В.В., Смолицкая Г.А. Школный словарь иностранных слов. М., 1983.-С. 128-129.

⁸ Розенталь Д.Э., Теленкова М.А, Словарь-справочник лингвистических терминов. М., 1976, -С. 270.

⁹ Одинцов В.В., Смолицкая Г.А. Школный словарь иностранных слов. М., 1983.- С. 128-129.

Профессор А.Ҳожиёвнинг “Лингвистик терминларнинг изоҳли луғати”да эса ушбу термин парафраза шаклини олади ва “Нарса”, ҳодисани ўз номи билан эмас, тасвирий усул билан маълум контекст, ситуациядаги характерли белги-хусусияти орқали ифодаланадиган стилистик приём. Мас. дала маликаси (маккажўхори), революция бешиги (Ленинград) каби”¹⁰ деб изоҳланади.

Хуллас, умумтилшунослик нуктаи назарида айни термин парафраза, парафраз, перифраз каби вариантларда қўлланади ва нутқнинг таъсирчан ифода воситаларидан бири эканлиги қайд этилади.

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ПАРОНИМИЯ ВА У БИЛАН ЧЕГАРАДОШ ҲОДИСАЛАР

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Аннотация: Мақола замонавий тилшуносликда паронимия ва у билан туташ ҳодисаларнинг ўрганилишига бағишланган. Паронимларнинг муҳим белгилари сифатида сўзларнинг формал ўхшашлиги, паронимик

¹⁰ Русча-ўзбекча луғатча (Русско-узбекский словарь), 11 том. П-Я-Т.1984, -16-бет.

жуфтликларнинг семантик фарқланиши, нутқда янглиш ёки аниқ бир мақсадга қаратилган ўзаро алмаштириш (парономазия) каби омиллар билан белгиланади.

Калим сўзлар: паронимия, омонимия, синонимия, парономазия, фонетик ўхшашлик, семантик фарқланиш.

Паронимия – ўзаклари жуда қадимийликка борадиган мураккаб ва кўп жиҳатли ҳодисадир. Агар лингвистик тафаккур тарихини йўлларнинг тармоқланган тўри сифатида тасаввур қилинса, тадқиқотчилар томонидан паронимия муаммоси бўйича босиб ўтилган йўлни ингичка, бироқ катта йирик магистраллар ва уларнинг сон-саноксиз шахобчалари билан кесишадиган чизик билан белгилаш мумкин. Шу йўл билан силжишда давом этиб, аввало бу соҳадаги тадқиқот тафаккури ривожланишини билдирувчи асосий даврларни аниқлаш лозим.

Паронимик аралаштириш тил нормасини маълум бузилиши сифатида тилнинг паталогияси деб баҳоланиши мумкин ва тилшуносликнинг маданий-нутқ жиҳатига киради. Рус тилшунослигида “салбий” тил материални ўрганиш зарурияти ҳақида Л. В. Щерба, Г. С. Винокур, А. М. Пешковский, В. В. Виноградов ва бошқалар кўп марталаб ёзишган. Паронимик жараёнларнинг моҳиятига берилмай, В. В. Виноградов паронимия (“сўзларнинг ўхшаш садоланиши”) ва омонимияни чегаралашга эътибор қаратади: “Омофония – омонимияга қараганда анча кенг тушунча. У бир хил товушликнинг ёки оҳангдошликнинг барча кўринишларини ҳам ҳамма конструкторларда, ҳам сўз уланишларида ва уларнинг бўлақларида, нутқнинг алоҳида бўлақларида, алоҳида морфемаларда, ҳатто бир-бирига яқин товуш бирикмаларида ўз ичига олади. Шундай қилиб, омонимия билан бу сўзнинг асл маъносидан нутқда пайдо бўладиган ёки ҳатто тил тизимида учрайдиган омофониянинг хилма-хил типларини, оҳангдошликни ва ўхшаш садоланишни аралаштириш ва ҳатто яқинлаштириш мумкин эмас”¹¹. Шунингдек олим оҳангдош сўзларнинг шаклан

¹¹ Виноградов В.В. Об омонимии и смежных явлениях // Вопросы языкознания. - 1960. - № 5. - С.4- 6.

ўхшашлиги уларнинг маъновий “ўзига тортишини” шарт қилиб қўяди, бу “уларнинг семантик муносабатларида акс этади”¹², деб фикр билдиради.

Ш. Балли тил патологияларини ўрганиш зарурлиги ҳақида шундай ёзади: “Тил аномалиялари экспериментал тарзда ишлатилишга лойиқ, улар жонли тилга тегишлидир ва бавосита унинг табиатини ва ишлашини, шунингдек у бошидан ўтказадиган ўзгаришларнинг йўналишини ёритади”, тилшуносни “тилнинг тўғрилиги камомадини тўлдиришга яширин интилиш сабабли” нутқда юз берадиган камчиликлар қизиқтириши керак”¹³. Ушбу олим паронимларни, улар ўртасида бўлиши мумкин бўлган семантик муносабатларига эътибор қаратмай фақат шаклан ўхшашлик жиҳатдан кўриб чиқади. Қизиғи шундаки, И. Н. Кузнецованинг таъкидлашича, Ш.Балли намуна сифатида иккала компонентнинг сезиларли семантик фарқланиши билан характерланадиган француз тилидаги паронимик бирликни (французча *allocation: allocution*; “ажратилган: нутқ”) келтиради. Бироқ, бу муаммо тадқиқотчиларининг яқдил фикрига кўра, бундай, семантик боғланмаган паронимлар уларнинг энг кам типик кўринишини ифодалайди. Аксарият кўпчилик ҳолларда паронимлар ўзаро семантик корреляцияларни намоён қиладилар.

Паронимларнинг бошқа таърифлари ҳам шаклий (формал) (фонетик-орфографик) ўхшашлик принципига асосланган:

О.С.Ахманова “садоланишининг ўхшашлиги ёки морфема таркибининг қисман тўғри келиши оқибатида нутқда ёки янглиш, ёки каламбур тарзда ишлатилиши мумкин бўлган сўзлар” дея таърифлайди¹⁴. Охирги таърифда паронимларнинг фақат фонетик яқинлиги факти, балки бундай яқинликнинг натижаси – паронимларни нутқда аралаштириб юборилиши ҳам кўрсатилади.

О.В.Вишнякованинг концепцияси бўйича паронимия “битта лексик-грамматик разрядга тегишли бўлган оҳангдош бир негизли турли маъноли

¹² Ўша жойда.

¹³ Балли Ш. Общая лингвистика и вопросы французского языка. - М., 1959. С. 35-36.

¹⁴ Ахманова О.С. Словарь лингвистических терминов. - М.,1969. – С.313.

сўзларнинг” соҳаси билан чекланади¹⁵. Бу таъриф ҳам функционал ҳам семантик белгиларни эътиборга олади. Муаллиф томонидан лексик паронимлар, *par excellence* паронимлар – “лексик-семантик яқинликка эга бўлган ва битта семантик майдонга тегишли бўлган бир негизли сўзлар” алоҳида ажратиб кўрсатилган¹⁶.

Кейинги тадқиқотларда, паронимиянинг умумназарий жиҳатларини ишлаб чиқиш давом эттирилди, шу муносабат билан конкрет тилнинг идиоматикасига катта эътибор қаратилди ва секин-аста этимологик мезоннинг тор доирасидан чиқилди. Л. Г. Яркованинг немис тили материали асосида қилган иши катта қизиқиш касб этади. Паронимия деганда “лексик бирликларнинг ўхшаш (аммо омонимиядаги каби айнан бир хил бўлмаган) садоланиши ва нутқда кутилмаган семантик муносабатга киришувчи, ёки янглиш ўзаро алмаштиришга, ёки каламбурга олиб борувчи семантик фарқланишлар” тушунилади¹⁷. Паронимик муносабатлар муаллиф томонидан тилнинг лексикасида омонимия, синонимия, антонимия, вариантлик билан бир қаторда парадигматик муносабатларнинг бир тури деб баҳоланади.

И.Н.Кузнецова паронимия муаммоси бўйича олиб борган тадқиқотида “паронимларнинг фонетик фарқлари мумкин бўлган миқдорни априор тарзда (хилма-хил фонемалар сонини ихтиёрий чеклаш билан) эмас, балки паронимик материалнинг ўзида берилган тил реалликларини таҳлил қилиш йўли билан белгилаш лозим деб таъкидлайди¹⁸. Паронимия ушбу концепция доирасида битта формал белги билан эмас, балки формал, семантик ва биринчи навбатда, функционал (нутқда паронимик жуфтликнинг диагностик хусусияти сифатида янглиш алмаштириш имконияти) белгиларининг бирикмаси билан аниқланади.

¹⁵ Вишнякова О.В. Паронимия в русском языке. - М., 1984.- С.5.

¹⁶ Вишнякова О.В. Паронимия в русском языке. - М., 1984.- С.7.

¹⁷ Яркова Л.Г. Паронимия в современном немецком языке: Автореф. дис. ... канд. филол. наук. -Л., 1979. – С.16.

¹⁸ Кузнецова И.Н. Пособие по французской лексикологии.-М.,1991.-С.29.

Шу нуқтаи назар паронимик соҳага товуш яқинлигини кўрсатадиган маълум синонимик сўзларни киритадиган семантик мезонни эътиборга олувчи бошқа таърифлардан ажралиб туради. У билан паронимия ва синонимия соҳалари айрим бўлақларда бир-биридан ажратилмаган бўладилар, балки, аксинча, кесишадилар. Шундай қилиб, паронимик жараён лексик интерференциянинг бир кўриниши сифатида гавдаланади. Лексик интерференцияни И. Н. Кузнецова икки томонлама (ифода планида ва мазмун планида) битта ёки турли тилларнинг лексик birlikларини дастлаб шаклан, шунингдек семантик ўхшашлиги билан боғлиқ ва тил нормасининг ғайриихтиёрий (янглиш) ёки ихтиёрий (стилистик) бузилишига олиб келадиган икки томонлама тортилиши¹⁹, деб таърифлайди.

Л.К.Федотова паронимия ҳодисасини структур-функционал мезонлар нуқтаи назаридан таҳлил қилади. Бу эса, иккита асосий жиҳатни назарда тутади: биринчи навбатда, паронимия нутқ ҳодисаси деб тан олинади; иккинчиси, муаллиф томонидан паронимларнинг шаклий ва мазмуний яқинлик даражасини аниқлаш учун бир қатор асослар таклиф қилинади. Тилшунос паронимиянинг қаторига анча мураккаб парасинтагматик муносабатларни киритиб, унинг тил мавқеини аниқлаштиради: “Ушбу муносабатлар парадигматиканинг ва синтагматиканинг синтезидан иборат бўлиб, битта синтагматик қатор доирасида бир вақтнинг ўзида турли парадигматик синфларнинг элементлари амалга ошганда юз беради”²⁰. Паронимларни бир маънода аниқлаш ва бу билан бошқа лексик гуруҳлардан уларни нутқ мавқеи ҳақида далолат берувчи вазифаси орқали чегаралаш таклиф қилинади.

Л.Н.Федотова пароним сўзларнинг мазмун планини таҳлил қилиб, “интеграл белги” (ИБ) тушунчасидан фойдаланади. Муаллиф умумлаштириш

¹⁹ Кузнецова И.Н. Пособие по французской лексикологии.-М.,1991.-С.27.

²⁰ Федотова Л.Н. Паронимия в современном английском языке: структура и функции: Автореф. дис.... канд. филол. наук. - Минск, 1989. – С.11.

даражаси бўйича интеграл белгиларнинг 4 та категориясини ажратиб кўрсатади: масалан, категория 3: *metronomic/metonimic* (ИБ - *of quality*), *nitigate/militate* (ИБ - *action*); камроқ умумий категория 2 - *day/date* (ИБ - *time*); хусусий интеграл белгилар (мос равишда белгининг кам умумлаштирилган даражаси); *abyssal/abysmal* (ИБ - *deep*)/ *amiable/amicable* (ИБ - *friendly*).

Ғарбий Европа филологик анъанасида паронимияни тушуниш анча торифодаланган. Паронимларни белгилаш учун “confusable” атамасидан фойдаланишда ёки уларни анча умумий тушунча “malaprop”, яъни янглиш, нотўғри сўз қўллаш тушунчасига киритишади: инглизча: *absence - abstinence; costume - custom*.

А.Рум “confusable” тушунчасининг нолингвистиклигини тан олиб, уни аслини олганда, биз паронимлар деб атайдиган таърифга тенглаштиради: “бу сўз бошқаси билан фақат ёзилишда, талаффуздагина эмас, балки у билан умумий ёки ассоциатив боғланган маънога эга бўлган сўздир”²¹ дея таърифлайди. Шундай қилиб, асосий мезонлар бу - садоланишдаги, ёзилишдаги ўхшашлик, контекстуал маъновий яқинликдир. А.Рум анъанавий рўйхатга яна сўзлардаги бўғинлар сонининг тахминий тенглиги, битта функционал услубга тегишлилик ва бошқа бир каторларини кўшиб, уларни битта умумий шиор: “*sight - sound – sense criterion*” остида бирлаштиради.

А.Рум бошқа “suggestible” тушунчасидан фойдаланади. “Suggestible” тушунчаси мазмунига кўра ўта жўяли ва шу сабабли жуда ранг-баранг ҳолатларни масалан, паронимияни (*jubilee/jubilant*); омофонияни (*whet/wet*), солецизмларни, яъни тасодифий нутқий хатоларни, янглиш айтилган сўзларни (*calvary/cavalry*), сохта этимологияни (*taper - tapir: animal with tapering nose*) ўз ичига олиб, терминологик кучга эга эмас. А. Рум “confusable” ва “suggestible” тушунчалари қўлланилишининг такрорланиш даражаси ва функционал-услуб нуқтаи назаридан бўлиши мумкин бўлган табақаланиш ҳақида шундай тахмин

²¹ Room A. Room’s dictionary of confusibles.-L., 1980.- 15p.

билдиради: “suggestible” атамаси “анча ноёб сўз билан ассоциация орқали пайдо бўлган жуда кенг қўлланиладиган сўз”; “confusable” ёки тор ихтисослаштирилган маънога (“specialist”) ёки ҳамма ерда қўлланиладиган маънога эга бўлиши мумкин бўлган сўз”²² деб белгилайди.

У.Коутс “Near-homonymy as a factor in a language change” ишида пароним атамасини, унинг мазмунини омонимия ва унга туташадиган ҳодисалар билан боғлаб, инкор қилади. Паронимларни (near-homonyms) “иккита ёки ундан ортик фонетик яқин, қоидага кўра, турли маъноларга эга бўлган сўзлар (шунга қарамай, шундай ҳоллар бўладики, паронимлар синонимлар ҳисобланадилар; бу бўлиши мумкин бўлган паронимлар тўқнашуви натижаларининг биттасидир (“clash of near-homonyms)”²³ деб таърифлайди. Бироқ, ушбу тадқиқотчининг, омонимлар ва унга туташадиган ҳодисалар тил коммуникацияси асосларига путур етказадилар, деган эътирози билан қўшилишиш қийин: “The tidiness of the system is disturbed by both neutralization and near-homonyms”²⁴. Агар тил тизимини ўзига етарли, фақат ўзига йўналтирилган, сўзловчи кишининг фаолиятига бефарқ, дея тасаввур қилинса, бу таъкид тўғри бўлиши мумкин эди. Маълумки, паронимия ва стилистик мақсадларда қўлланиладиган товуш ўхшашликларининг бошқа турлари (парономазия), адабий тил бойиши манбаларидан бирига, нутқ экспрессиясининг воситаларидан бирига айланади. Паронимлардан моҳирона фойдаланиш, қоидага кўра тилни юқори даражада (маданий-нутқ жиҳатдан) билишдан далолат беради ҳамда муаллифга фикрни аниқ ва экспрессив тарзда ифодалаш – стилистик жиҳатдан нозик маъновий тус ва ассоциациялар киритишга ёрдам беради²⁵.

²² Room A. Room’s dictionary of confusibles.-L., 1980.- 3p.

²³ Coates W.A. Near-homonymy as a factor in language change // Language. - 1968. - p. 468.

²⁴ Coates W.A. Near-homonymy as a factor in language change // Language. - 1968. - p. 477.

²⁵ Антипина О.П. Сопоставительный анализ паронимов русского и английского языков: Дисс....канд. филол. наук.-Уфа 2012. С.25.

Шундай қилиб, “пароним” атамасининг умумий мазмуни таҳлилидан келиб чиқиб, қуйидаги муҳим жиҳатларни ажратиб кўрсатиш мумкин:

Қуйидагилар паронимлар ҳисобланади:

- 1) битта лексик-грамматик синфга кирувчи, одатда, этимологик яқин бўлган фақат бир хил ўзакли сўзлар;
- 2) нутқда паронимик силжишга дучор қилинадиган ҳар хил ўзакли сўзлар;
- 3) ҳар қандай оҳангдош, ўзининг мазмуний структурасида битта бўлса ҳам интеграл белгига эга бўлган сўзлар;
- 4) нутқда атайлаб /каламбур ёки тасодифий /паронимик хато/ ўзаро алмаштиришга лойиқ бўлган фонетик яқин сўзлар.

Хулоса қилиб айтганда, паронимия ва у билан туташ ҳодисалар етарли даражада тўла тадқиқ қилинмаган. Лингвистик адабиётларда паронимларнинг моҳиятини ҳар томонлама ёритиш мавжуд эмас, оҳангдош сўзларнинг гуруҳларидаги лексик-семантик контактлар ҳар хил талқин қилинади. “Пароним” атамасини қатъий терминологик парадигмага киритишнинг қийинчиликлари паронимия ҳодисаси ўзининг мураккаб онтологик мавқеи, ушбу ҳодисанинг айрим умумназарий жиҳатларининг ишлаб чиқилмаганлиги оқибати сифатида изоҳланади.

Паронимия сўзларнинг янглиш ўзаро алмаштирилишига, ёки каламбурга олиб боровчи товуш яқинлашуви билан боғлиқ ҳодисаларнинг барча комплексини ўз ичига олади. Шаклларнинг яқинлиги оҳангдош сўзларнинг семантик контаминациясини келтириб чиқаради. Мос равишда қуйидагиларни паронимларнинг муҳим белгилари деб ҳисоблаш керак:

- а) сўзларнинг формал (фонетик-орфографик) ўхшашлиги;
- б) паронимик жуфтлик (қатор) компонентларининг семантик фарқланиши;
- в) нутқда янглиш ёки аниқ бир мақсадга қаратилган ўзаро алмаштириш паронимазия натижаси сифатида;

г) иккита сабабнинг ўзаро муносабати ҳисобига сўзларнинг ихтиёрий ва ғайриихтиёрий семантик контаминациялари: формал яқинлик ёки бир хил моделда позицион бир хиллик ва маъновий контаминация учун семантик асосларнинг мавжудлиги.

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БИПОЛЯРНОСТЬ ОЦЕНКИ ЧЕЛОВЕКА В АНТРОПОЦЕНТРИЧЕСКИХ ПОСЛОВИЦАХ

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Аннотация: В антропоцентрических пословицах узбекского и русского языков заложен огромный оценочный потенциал, раскрытие которого позволит определить систему ценностей узбекского и русского народов как различных лингвокультурных общностей. Оценочный потенциал не только антропоцентрических пословиц узбекского и русского языков, но и пословичных изречений всех существующих языков мира предопределяется тем, что пословица как особая паремиологическая единица в отличие от слова выполняет функцию не только номинации предметов и явлений действительности, а прежде всего жизненной ситуации.

Ключевые слова: *оценка, антропоцентрические пословицы, биполярность, ценность, антиценность, паремиологическая единица.*

Оценочный потенциал не только антропоцентрических пословиц узбекского и русского языков, но и пословичных изречений всех существующих языков мира предопределяется тем, что пословица как особая паремиологическая единица в отличие от слова выполняет функцию не только номинации предметов и явлений действительности, а прежде всего жизненной ситуации, при этом номинация ситуации также выражает оценочное отношение данной ситуации и конкретные предписания действовать согласно общепринятым нормам. Отсюда следует, что пословицы, как и все паремии, есть «особые номинативные единицы, существующие в языке для выражения ценностного отношения, которое реализуется через категории «нужное», «должное», «хорошее», «плохое». Народные изречения являются частью той системы, которая целиком и полностью зависит от человека, от его выбора, ценностных предпочтений, от того, что человек считает нормой» [3, 180].

Естественно, что только ценностное отношение человека к жизненным ситуациям и объективной действительности в целом формируется под воздействием системы ценностей общества.

Оценка как познавательная деятельность человека осуществляется путем соотнесения характеристик объекта изучения или описания с его эталонным шаблоном, зафиксированном в сознании индивида и социума в целом. В основе оценки всегда лежит сравнение объекта с эталоном. Сравнение характеристик объекта с эталоном производится посредством оценочных категорий, которые представлены инвариантными оппозициями *хорошо* и *плохо*.

Аксиологические категории *хорошо* или *плохо* выделяются на фоне категории *нейтрально* и служат в антропоцентрических пословицах для соотнесения характеристики человека с системой ценностей национально-этнической культуры народа. Аксиологическую категорию нейтральности А.В. Белобородова называет категорией *безразлично* и определяет как альтернативу хорошему и плохому. По мнению автора, любой объект может быть признан хорошим, безразличным или плохим. Исключения составляют объекты, находящиеся вне сферы оценок [1, 264]. Иначе говоря, вне сферы оценок находятся такие объекты реальной или воображаемой действительности, которые не побуждают говорящего или слушающего к выражению оценочного значения.

В связи с тем, что антропоцентрические пословицы изначально носят назидательный характер, воздействующая сила которого базируется на оценочности поведения человека, с одной стороны, и что, с другой стороны, «безразличие имеет нечеткие границы. Оценочной шкале свойственна асимметрия и нестабильность. Проявление безразличия в большинстве случаев как норма не рассматривается, а так как мы определили, что норма занимает положительную часть шкалы, следовательно, безразличие не закрепляется за зоной «+» [2, 48]. Оценочные значения пословицы целесообразно рассматривать в аспекте аксиологической оппозиции *хорошо/плохо*.

Объектом оценки в антропоцентрических пословицах узбекского и русского языков выступает человек, его характеристики по различным параметрам, поведение и деятельность в целом. Положительная/отрицательная оценка человека формирует его аксиологический статус.

Абсолютный аксиологический статус какого-либо объекта – это такой статус объекта, который выражается категориями «хорошо», «плохо» и «безразлично», а относительный – сравнительными категориями «лучше», «хуже» и «равноценно». Антропоцентрические пословицы узбекского и русского языков обладают как абсолютным, так и относительным аксиологическим статусом. Например, абсолютный аксиологический статус присущ пословицам узбекского языка типа *Урса ҳам, эл яхши, Сўкса ҳам, эл яхши. Бахши бор жойда яхши бор*; русского языка типа *Вместе хорошо и недруга бить. Плохой зевает, резвый на ходу хватает*. В антропоцентрических же пословицах узбекского языка типа *Қолоқдан чўлоқ яхши. Ғараз мараздан ёмон* и в пословицах русского языка типа *Сердце матери лучше солнца греет* проявляется их относительный аксиологический статус.

Антропоцентрические пословицы узбекского и русского языков с точки зрения представленных в них оценок человека по критерию положительности/отрицательности оценки описываемого объекта можно классифицировать в три большие группы:

1) антропоцентрические пословицы с положительной оценкой человека. Например, в узбекском языке: *Одам одамнинг дардини олар. Интилганга толе ер*; в русском языке: *Пока и мы человеки – счастье не пропало*;

2) антропоцентрические пословицы с отрицательной оценкой человека. Например, в узбекском языке: *Безоридан ҳамма безор. Бекорчидан безиб қоч, чақимчидан – кўчиб*; в русском языке: *Плохая арба – дороге беда, плохой человек – семье горе. Грех сладок, человек падок. Человек сам себе убийца*;

3) антропоцентрические пословицы с противопоставлением положительной и отрицательной оценок человека. Например, в узбекском языке: *Ёмон – ўз*

гамида, яхши – эл гамида; в русском языке: *Старый друг лучше новых двух.*

Как видим из представленной классификации, оценочные значения узбекских и русских антропоцентрических пословиц являются биполярными по признаку положительности/отрицательности. В пословице может содержаться или положительная оценка человеку, его характеру, поведению и действиям, или отрицательная оценка, или же противопоставляться.

Следовательно, положительность/отрицательность оценки человека в антропоцентрических пословицах узбекского и русского языков, которая производится по аксиологическим категориям *хорошо* или *плохо*, образуют биполярность оценочных значений пословиц.

Существует немало антропоцентрических пословиц в узбекском и русском языках, в которых положительная или отрицательная оценка представлена особыми маркерными лексемами типа: в узбекском языке *яхши, ёмон, зарур, ҳожат йўқ, фойда, зарар, фойдали, бефойда, афзал, гуноҳ, савоб, ҳалол, ҳаром* и др., в русском языке: *хорошо, плохо, лучше, хуже, можно, нельзя, надо, нужно, не надо, полезно, вредно, ладно, неладно* и др. Эти маркеры способствуют более явному выражению положительности или отрицательности оценки, придавая пословице более категоричный, предписывающий характер. Сравним:

В узбекском языке: *яхши – ёмон: Яхши йигит юрт тузар, ёмон йигит юрт бузар. Яхши раҳбар элни ўйлар, ёмон раҳбар ҳовли бўйлар. Ёмон аталиб тирик юргунча, Яхши аталиб ўлган яхши. Ёмон ёмон билан. Яхши замон билан; фойда – зарар: Ёлгон айтиб фойда кўрсанг, охири зарар топарсан. Рост айтиб зарар кўрсанг, охири фойда топарсан. Юзи юпқалик ризққа зарар. Ёмоннинг зарари тегар кенг йўлда, яхшининг фойдаси тегар тор йўлда.*

В русском языке: *хорошо – плохо: Хорошо там, где нас нет. У хорошего хозяина и работники хорошие. Хороших людей больше. Промеж худых и хорошему плохо. За плохим пойдешь, плохое и найдешь; можно – нельзя: Горе – деньги нажить, а с деньгами и дураку можно жить. Если народу служить, и*

на полюсе можно прожить. В своем деле самому судьей быть нельзя. Без солнышка нельзя пробыть, без милого нельзя прожить.

Вышеизложенные маркеры оценочного значения антропоцентрических пословиц узбекского и русского языков служат прямыми показателями положительности или отрицательности оценки человека и прямо предписывают адресату определенную модель поведения, мышления или отношения к чему-либо или кому-либо в рамках оценочных категорий *хорошо* или *плохо*.

Таким образом, в антропоцентрических пословицах узбекского и русского языков реализуются этическая, эстетическая, интеллектуальная, прагматическая, валеологическая, эмоциональная, нормативная виды оценки человека, которые выделяются по критерию качеств человека и образа его жизнедеятельности. Характерной особенностью содержащихся в антропоцентрических пословицах различных видов оценки человека является их биполярность, которая обусловлена тем, что в основе оценочной деятельности лежат универсальные аксиологические категории *хорошо* и *плохо*.

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ИНГЛИЗ ВА ЎЗБЕК ПАРЕМИЯЛАРИДА ФИТОНИМЛАРНИНГ АКСЕОЛОГИК ФУНКЦИЯЛАРИ

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Аннотация: Такдим этилган тезисда ўзбек ва инглиз халқ оғзаки ижодидаги фитопаремияларнинг аксеологик функциялари тўғрисида умумлаштирилган хулосалар чиқарилиб, уларга тегишли тамойилар аниқланган. Шунингдек, фитопаремиялар умумбашарий маънавий қадриятларни акс этишда муҳим ўрин тутиши ва уларнинг аксеологик функциялари аниқланган.

Калит сўзлар: фитопаремия, фольклор, аксиологик тушунчалар, паремиялар

Ўзбек ва инглиз фольклори ўзига хос миллий қадриятларнинг акс этилиши ва шу билан бирга умум башарий жиҳатлари билан ажралиб туради. Ҳар икки халқнинг оғзаки ижоди тизимида мақол ва маталлар ҳаётни ангалаш, ундаги донноликни акс этиш ва бу аксиологик ҳолатларни халққа етказиш билан ажралиб туради. Асралар давомида бу ҳолат халқнинг бадий тафаккури асосида ривожланиб, миллий манавият ривожланишига катта ҳисса қўшиб келмоқда. Шундай экан ўзбек ва инглиз халқ оғзаки ижод анъаналари бадий жиҳатдан бой ўзига хос мақол ва маталларнинг юзага келишига асос бўлиб келган.

Икки халқ мақол ва маталларнинг компротивистик таҳлили шуни кўрсатмоқдаки, уларнинг бадий структурасида ўхшаш ва фарқликлар мавжудлиги ва уларда ҳар бир халққа хос бўлган аксиологик (аксиология – грекча *axia* қадрият, *logos* таълимот) тушунчалар акс этганлиги кўзга ташланади. Шундан келиб чиқиб қайд этиш мумкинки, бугунги кунда

Ўзбек ва инглиз паремиялардаги мазмунан ўхшаш ва фарқ аксиологизмлар кенг ўрин олган.

Бизнинг фикримизча, паремияларнинг мазмунидан келиб чиқиб, уларнинг қурилишида иштирок этувчи унсурлар, яъни фитонимлар, оронимлар, стратонимлар ва бошқа бир қатор онимларнинг бадий-стилистик ва семантик функцияларидан келиб чиқиб, фитопаремия, стратопаремия космопаремия ва бошқа шу каби тушунчаларни қўллаш терминларнинг янада деверсификациялашга ёрдам беради

Ўзбек ва инглиз фитопаремияларнинг таҳлилидан келиб чиқсак, уларда бир неча микро мотивлар асосида яхлит маъно ифода этилади. Фитопаремияларда акс этилган бош маъно унда иштирок этувчи фитонимлар мазмунидан келиб чиқиб яхлитланади. Аксарият фитопаремияларда кўчим етакчилик қилиши ҳалқнинг бадий таффақўри нақадар теран эканлигидан далолат беради. Фитопаремияларнинг сифатий кўрсаткичлари асосида умумий аксеологик мазмун шаклланади. Натижада фитопаремиологик аксеологизмларнинг таснифлаш тамойилларини яратиш имконияти туғилади. Фитонимлар иштирок этган ўзбек ва инглиз паремиялардаги аксеологик мазмун ўз семантик майдонларига эга бўлиб, уларнинг чегаралари бир вақтнинг ўзида мос келиши ва фарқланиб туриши мумкин.

Таркибида фитонимлар иштирок этган ўзбек ва инглиз паремияларида қуйидаги аксеологик мазмун мавжуд эканлигини кузатиш мумкин:

1. Ҳаёт фаровонлиги меҳнатга боғлиқ эканлигини тасдиқлаш.

He that would eat the fruit must climb the tree (Сўзма-сўз таржимаси: Ким мева егиси келса, дарахтга чиқиши лозим).

Ўзбекча версияси: Жон куйдирмасанг, жонона қайда, тоққа чиқмасанг, дўлона қайда.

2. Ўхшатиш. Кишига таъриф бериш.

As the tree, so the fruit. (Сўзма-сўз таржимаси: Дарахт қандай бўлса меваси ҳам шунга ухшаш).

Ўзбекча версиялари: Буғдойдан – буғдой, арпадан – арпа.

Олма олмадан ранг олар.

3. Ижтимоий-маиший муносабатларнинг боғлиқлиги.

Just as the twig is bent, the tree is inclined (Сўзма-сўз таржимаси: Шох каерга эгилса, дарахт ҳам уша томон букилади).

Ўзбекча версияси: Теракка қараб, тол ўсар. онага қараб, қиз ўсар.

4. Тарбия жараёнининг қайд этилиши.

Tall oaks from little acorns grow / every oak has been an acorn

(Сўзма-сўз таржимаси: Катта нарса кичик нарсдан ўсади / эман дарахти ҳам бир пайти уруғ бўлган).

Ўзбекча версиялари: Дарахтдан мева оламан десанг, ниҳоллигидан парвариш қил. Эгри бутокни ниҳолида тобини ол.

5. Ижтимоий ҳаёт билан боғлиқ этикет чегара меъёрларининг акс этилиши.

Put not your hand between the bark and the tree (Сўзма-сўз таржимаси: Дарахтнинг пустлоғи ва танасининг ўртасига қўлингни тикма. Маъноси: Бировнинг оилавий ишига аралашма).

Ўзбекча версияси: Ҳар меванинг пўчоғи бор, ҳар сўзнинг ўлчови бор.

6. Ҳаёт машақатлигининг берилиши.

Life is not a bed of roses (Сўзма-сўз таржимаси: Ҳаёт атиргуллардан ясалган тушак эмас).

Life is not a bed of roses (Сўзма-сўз таржимаси: Ҳаёт атиргуллардан иборат гулзор эмас).

No garden without its weeds (Сўзма-сўз таржимаси: Курмаксиз боғ бўлмайди).

Ўзбекча версияси: Гуруч курмаксиз бўлмайди.

No rose without a thorn (Сўзма-сўз таржимаси: Тикансиз атиргул бўлмас).

Ўзбекча версиялари: Тикансиз гул бўлмас, машаққатсиз - ҳунар.

Гулнинг ҳам тикани бор.

Қайд этиш лозимки, ўзбек ва инглиз фитопаремияларда аксеологик мазмуннинг ифодалашда ўзаро уйғунлик кузатилади. Бу эса, ўз навбатида, ҳар икки халқ ҳаётдаги ижтимоий-маиший муносабатларни акс этишда бир хил умумбашарий универсал бадий таффакурга мурожаат этганлигидан далолат беради.

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ДИНИЙ МАТНЛАРДА ИЛЛОКУТИВ АКТИНГ НАМОЁН БЎЛИШИ

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Аннотация: Лингвопрагматика нутқ актлари назарияси; сўзлаш мақсади ва нутқ актлари турлари; суҳбат олиб бориш қоидалари; нутқий этикетнинг аҳамиятли томонлари; мавҳумлаштирилган фикр, қочириқ, кўчирма нутқий актлар; дискурс масалаларини тадқиқ этади (Турдиева, 2020: 41). Нутқий актлар назарияси лингвопрагматиканинг етакчи масалаларидан бири саналиб, ушбу бобда нутқий актларни диний матнлар мисолида ўрганишга эътибор қаратилади.

Калит сўзлар: *Лингвопрагматика, нутқий актлар, нутқнинг лисоний хусусият, суперсегментал бирлик.*

Тилшунослар томонидан XX асрнинг 50-йилларидан бошлаб нутқни актларга бўлиб ўрганиш таклиф қилинди ва бу орқали нутқнинг лисоний хусусиятларини кенгроқ кўламда ўрганиш имконияти пайдо бўлди: “Нутқий актлар нутқ жараёнига алоқадор бўлиб, у нутқий фаолият натижасида юзага келади. Нутқий актлар мулоқот жараёнида сегментал ва суперсегментал бирликлар ёрдамида талаффуз қилиниб, улар гап, нутқ, матн каби бирликлар таркибида воқеланади. Нутқий актлар, асосан, интонация, гап ва матн орқали юзага чиқади” (Ҳакимов, 2020: 36).

Лингвопрагматикада нутқий актлар муаммоси Дж.Остин (Austin, 1975; Остин, 1986), Дж.Серль (Searle, 1975; Searle, 1979, Searle and Vanderveken, 1985), А.Бурхардт (Burkhardt, 1990: аслида ушбу муаллиф нутқий актларни ёқламаган), Ф.Дорж (Doerge, 2006), Н.Арутюнова (Арутюнова, 1976), А.Дорошенко (Дорошенко, 1989), Г.Матвеева (Матвеева Г., Ленец А., Петрова,

2014), М.Ҳақимов каби тилшунослар томонидан тадқиқ этилган. Гарчи Дж.Остин ва Дж.Серль назарияларида социолингвистик таҳлил кўзда тутилмаган бўлса ҳам, улар тилнинг ижтимоий табиати билан боғлиқ масалаларнинг лингвопрагматика объекти сифатида ўрганилишига асос бўлди.

Нутқий актнинг таркибий қисмлари сифатида Дж. Остин уч компонентни: локутив акт (сўзлаш акти), иллокутив акт (сўзловчи нияти акти) ва перлокутив акт (нутқий таъсир этиш акти)ни келтириб ўтади (Остин, 1986: 93). Дж.Серль ва М.Ҳақимовлар эса тўртинчи таркибий қисм – пропозиционал акт ҳам мавжуд эканлигини эътироф этадилар (Ҳақимов, 2020: 36). Бу компонентларнинг барчаси бир вақтда рўёбга чиқиб, бир нутқнинг турли жиҳатларини ифода этади. Локутив акт талаффуз акти ҳисобланиб, нутқни тўғри талаффуз этиш ушбу актнинг асосини ташкил этади. Диний матнлардаги сўзларнинг араб тилидагидек талаффуз қилиниши шартлиги локутив актнинг намоён бўлишига мисолдир. Бунда оддий сўзловчи ўз тили талаффуз меъёрларига асосан сўзлаб, локутив акт талабларини бузса, диний уламолар локутив актнинг рўёбга чиқишига эътиборли бўладилар.

Иллокутив акт сўзловчининг нутқни яратишдан, лисоний воситаларни қўллашдан мақсадини, ниятини ифодалаш вазифасини бажаради. Пропозиционал акт нутқ таркибидаги фикр, унинг мазмун - моҳиятидир. Перлокутив акт эса лисоний воситалар ёрдамида таъсир этиш акти саналади ва бу акт орқали тингловчининг ҳис- туйғуларига, ўй-фикрларига, ҳаракатига маълум маънода таъсир этиш кўзда тутилади.

Ҳар қандай нутқни сўзлашдан маълум мақсад, ният кўзда тутилади. Сўзловчи ўз ниятини лисоний воситалар орқали очик ёки яширин тарзда ифода қилади. Бунда нутқий актларнинг компоненти саналган иллокутив акт юзага чиқади.

Ф.Дорж иллокутив актни “Остин акти” деб номлайди, чунки Дж.Остин бу актга ном бермаган, бу ном кейинчалик қўйилганини изоҳлайди (Дорж: www.researchgate.net). Дж.Остин асосан иллокутив акт устида ишлаган,

ўз тадқиқотларида иллокутив актни локутив ва перлокутив актлардан фарқлашга интиланган. Дж.Остин назариясига кўра, “Туз борми?” деб савол берилганда, локутив акт сифатида сўроқ гап тушунилса, иллокутив акт “тузни узатиб юборинг”, деган маъно ёхуд сўровни англатади. Демак, иллокутив акт орқали бирор фикр билдириш ёхуд лисоний воситаларни қўллашдан кўзда тутилган мақсад, мазмун англашилади.

Иллокутив актнинг ўзи ҳам бир неча қисмлардан ташкил топгани эътироф этилади. Дж.Серль иллокутив актнинг компонентлари сифатида репрезентатив (ассертив) акт, директив акт, комиссив акт, экспрессив акт ва декларатив актларни келтиради.

Иллокутив акт таркибий қисмларидан директив акт диний нутқ, диний матнларда кенг учрайди. Бунда буйруқ, топшириқ, кўрсатма бериш орқали ундаш акти – директив акт намоён бўлади.

“Директив актларда ҳам бошқа нутқий актлар сингари сўзловчининг коммуникатив мақсади борлиқ – сўз муносабатига асосланган ҳолда сўзлашувчиларнинг психологик ҳолатига боғлиқ тарзда хоҳиш, истак каби параметрлар асосида ифодаланади” (Ҳакимов, 2020: 89).

Қуръони карим муқаддас диний матн сифатида ҳукм, буйруқларни ҳам ўзида жамлайди: *Яхшилик ва тақво йўлида ҳамкорлик қилинг. Гуноҳ ва душманлик йўлида ҳамкорлик қилманг (Моида сураси, 2-оят)*. Ушбу мисолда директив акт орқали инсонларни тарбиялаш, яхшиликка чорлаш, ёмонликдан қайтариш мақсади кўзда тутилган. Демак, диний матнларда инсонларни тарбиялаш, одоб-ахлоқ ўргатиш, ёмон амаллардан қайтариш мақсади директив актнинг юзага чиқишини таъминлайди. Чунки Пайғамбаримиз алайҳиссалом таъкидлаганларидек, “дин бу – хусни хулқдир”.

“Одоб масаласини инсоният тарихида илк бор Исломгина тўлақонли равишда бошлаган, унга катта аҳамият берган. Исломда инсон ҳаётидаги ҳар бир нарсанинг ўз одоби бор. Қуръон карим ва суннати мутоҳҳарада ҳамма нарсанинг муомаласидаги одоблар кенг баён қилинган. Ислом таълимотининг

асосини ҳам одоб ташкил қилади”. (Islaminstitut.uz/8381) Демак, диний матнларда, энг аввало инсонларни тарбиялаш, яхшиликка буюриш назарда тутилишини эътиборга олсак, бундай нутқда Қуръондан иқтибос келтирилиши, ҳадисларнинг қўлланилиши, ривоятлар берилиши иллокутив актнинг ифодаланиши учун хизмат қилади. Диний матнларда кўп ҳолларда Қуръони каримдан ёки ҳадислардан иқтибос келтирилиши орқали фикрни далиллаш, исботлаш билан бир қаторда бу далиллар орқали ўқувчини тарбиялаш ҳам мақсад қилинади.

Ҳадислар баёни орқали ҳам дидактик функция кўзда тутилади, чунки суннатга мувофиқ иш тутиш, Пайғамбарнинг ахлоқини ўзлаштириш ислом динининг асосий тамойилларидан биридир. Кундалик турмушга оид директив актларга ҳадислардан кўплаб мисоллар келтириш мумкин: *...Яна бир ҳадисда Расулulloҳ соллalloҳу алайҳи ва саллам: “Эй Абу Зарр, агар шўрва пиширсанг, унинг сувини кўпайтириб, қўшнилариңдан ҳам хабар олгин”, дедилар...* [“Яхши қўшни бўлоламизми?” Зиёуддин Аймуҳаммедов // “Ҳидоят” журнали. 2019 йил. 3-сон. 28- бет]; *Расулulloҳ (саллalloҳу алайҳи ва саллам): “Ҳовли ва уй-жойлариңизни озода тутинглар”, деб буюрганлар (Имом Термизий ривояти).* [“Ҳидоят” журнали, 2018 йил. 8-сон. 15-бет]

Келтирилган мисолларда *хабар олгин, озода тутинглар* феъллари буйруқ-истак майли шаклида берилган бўлиб, директив акт локутив воситалар ёрдамида аниқ намоён бўлади.

Лекин директив акт доим ҳам буйруқ-истак майлидаги феъл орқали ифодаланмаслиги мумкин. Феълнинг хабар майли орқали ҳам директив акт юзага чиқиши, ундаш маъноси англашилиши мумкин: *Қуёш балқиган ҳар бир кунда икки киши ўртасини адолат билан ислоҳ этишинг эҳсондир; Сахийлик бир дарахтдир, унинг томирлари жаннатда, шохлари эса дунёга тушгандир. Ким унинг бир шохига осилса, уни жаннатга олиб боради...; Табассум билан айтилган чиройли сўз садақадир; Ҳақиқий мусулмон бу мусулмонлар унинг тили*

ва қўлидан омонда бўлишларидир; Банда модомики биродари ҳожатини раво қилар экан, Аллоҳ таоло унинг ҳожатини осон қилишда давом этади.

Пайғамбар (с.а.в.)дан келтирилган юқоридаги ҳадисларнинг барчаси инсонларда сахийлик, эҳсон, тили ва қўли билан бировларга озор бермаслик, чиройли сўзлаш, бошқаларга қўлдан келганча яхшилик қилиш каби амалларни бажаришга ундаш орқали олижаноб хислатларни шакллантириш мақсадига хизмат қилади.

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ТИЛШУНОСЛИКНИНГ ЯНГИ ЙЎНАЛИШЛАРИ ВА ЭНИГМАТИКА

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Аннотация: Тилшуносликда тилнинг ички структураси, унинг шаклий ва мазмуний томонлари ўрганилган бўлса, ҳозирда соҳанинг янги йўналишлари пайдо бўла бошлади. Бундай янги соҳалар қаторига социолингвистика, когнитив лингвистика, этнолингвистика, прагмалингвистика, лингвокультурология, психолингвистика, лингвопоэтика, матн тилшунослиги каби йўналишларни киритиш ҳамда бу соҳалар тадқиқига эътибор кучайганлиги натижаси ўлароқ қатор ишларнинг юзага келганлигини эътироф этиш муҳимдир.

Калит сўзлар: *социаллик, тил ва жамиятнинг алоқадорлиги, тилшунослик, мантиқий саволлар, кроссвордлар, ребуслар.*

Тилшуносликда тилнинг ички структураси, унинг шаклий ва мазмуний томонлари ўрганилган бўлса, ҳозирда соҳанинг янги йўналишлари пайдо бўла бошлади. Бундай янги соҳалар қаторига социолингвистика, когнитив лингвистика, этнолингвистика, прагмалингвистика, лингвокультурология, психолингвистика, лингвопоэтика, матн тилшунослиги каби йўналишларни

киритиш ҳамда бу соҳалар тадқиқига эътибор кучайганлиги натижаси ўлароқ қатор ишларнинг юзага келганлигини эътироф этиш муҳимдир. Табиийки, тил моҳиятида бу йўналишлардан бирининг борлиги бошқасининг мавжудлигини инкор қилмайди. Айтайлик, социаллик (ижтимоий жиҳат)нинг мавжудлиги унда психиклик (руҳий жиҳат) ҳам бор бўлиши мумкинлигини рад этмайди. Шунинг учун тилнинг моҳиятини очишда мазкур хусусиятларнинг барчасини ҳисобга олиш лозим.²⁶ Бу эса ўз навбатида тадқиқотчига тил деб аталмиш беназир ҳодисани нисбатан тўлиқ ва мукамал, яъни тизимли ўрганиш имкониятини беради.

Тил ва жамиятнинг алоқадорлик масалаларини ўрганувчи социолингвистиканинг дастлабки илмий асослари XIX-XX асрлардаги бир қатор олимларнинг ишларида бўй кўрсатгани эътироф этилади, аммо “социолингвистика” термини анчадан кейин, хусусан, 1952-йилда (дастлаб америкалик тадқиқотчи Х.Карри томонидан қўлланган) пайдо бўлганлиги қайд этилади.²⁷ Ўзбек тилшунослигида ҳам социолингвистик йўналиш кам ўрганилганлиги боис бу борада бирмунча тадқиқот ишларига эҳтиёж борлиги сезилади.

Маълумки, тил ўзида ижтимоийлик хусусиятини сақлайди. Жамиятнинг турли қатламлари, хусусан уларнинг аъзолари ўзига хос сўзлашув услуби, “тил”га эга. Айнан шу қатлам эгалари фойдаланадиган шундай тил бирликлари, ифодалар мавжудки, уларни социолингвистик ёндашувсиз ўрганишнинг асло имкони йўқ. Шунинг учун ҳам жумбоқли матнлар орасида болалар ва катталар учун тузилган топишмоқлар, мантиқий саволлар, кроссвордлар, ребуслар каби жумбоқ яширинган матнлар социал лингвистиканинг объекти бўлиб хизмат қилиши мумкин. Ижтимоий лингвистика юзасидан олиб бориладиган тадқиқотларда тил ва жамият, тил ва тафаккур, тил ва маданият муносабатлари,

²⁶ Маҳмудов Н. Ўзбек тили социолингвистикаси муаммолари// Ўзбек тили ва адабиёти.—Тошкент, 2020--№3.— Б.5.

²⁷ Абдуллаев Ю.Н., Бушуй А.М. Язык и общество. —Ташкент: Фан, 2002, стр.152

тафаккур ва маданиятнинг шаклланиши ҳамда ривожда тилнинг фавқуллода ўрни мунтазам назарда тутилиши керак. Ҳеч бир жамиятни ушбу юқорида саналган муаммолардан ташқарида тасаввур қилиш мумкин эмаслигини исботлашнинг ҳожати йўқ.

Инсоннинг билиш қобилияти унинг лисоний қобилияти билан ҳамоҳангдир. Ўтган асрнинг бошларида олмон файласуфи (кейинчалик АҚШда яшаб ижод қилган) Эрнест Кассирер инсоннинг билиш фаолиятига борлиқни худди кўзгудек акс эттирувчи эмас, балки предметларнинг ички ёки ташқи моҳиятини акс эттирувчи ҳодиса сифатида қаралиши лозимлигини уқтиради.²⁸ Шу маънода, биз таҳлилга тортмоқчи бўлаётган жумбоқли матнлар ҳам муайян предметнинг ички моҳият (функционал вазифаси) ҳамда ташқи кўринишини нисбатан мавҳум бўлса-да, ўзига хос йўсинда тасвирлайди, дейишимиз мумкин. Табиийки, жумбоқнинг жавобини топишга интилиш билиш фаолиятининг бевосита маҳсули, дея қаралиши ҳам мақсадга мувофиқ. Бунда одатда сўз ўйинлари жавобга элтувчи асосий йўл бўлиб хизмат қилиши шубҳасиздир.

Этнолингвистика тилшуносликнинг тил ва унинг ташувчиси бўлган халқ орасидаги боғлиқликлар ҳамда муносабатларни, тил ривожини, вазифавий хусусиятларига лисоний, этник омилларнинг биргаликдаги таъсирини ўрганувчи соҳасидир.

Этнолингвистика, айниқса, ёзувга эга бўлмаган халқларнинг этнографиясини ўрганишда, уларнинг тилларидаги этник хусусиятлар билан боғлиқ лисоний материалларни тўплаш ва тадқиқ қилишда қўл келади.²⁹ Оғзаки ижод намуналари бўлмиш топишмоқларни ўрганишда ҳам этник омиллар (халқнинг яшаш тарзи, урф-одатлари, миллий анъаналари, фалсафий ва диний

²⁸ Сафаров Ш. Когнитив тилшунослик. –Жиззах: Сангзор, 2006, 23 б.

²⁹ Звегинцев В. А., Этнолингвистика, в его кн.: История языковедения XIX—XX вв. в очерках и извлечениях, т. 2, М., 1965

қарашлари) аҳамиятли жиҳатлар ҳисобланади. Зероки, улар ёзувсиз ҳам муайян халқнинг ўзига хосликларини аجدодлардан авлодлага ташувчилар бўлиб хизмат қилишмоқда.

Прагматика, Ш.Сафаров таъбири билан айтганда, тилшуносликнинг алоҳида соҳаси бўлиб, унинг тадқиқот доирасига мулоқот жараёнида лисоний бирликларни танлаб олиш, уларни қўллаш ҳамда ушбу қўлланишдаги бирликларнинг мулоқот иштирокчиларига таъсири масалалари ўрганиш киради.³⁰ Бинобарин, мулоқот иштирокчиларидан бирининг бошқасига савол бериши, топишмоқ айтиши, оғзаки ёки ёзма жумбоқнинг жавобини топишга ундаши ҳам респондентга муайян таъсир ўтказилаётганини ва бу таъсирдан кутилаётган муддао—унинг қандай жавоб бериши коммуникатив жараёни юзага келтиради. Шу жиҳатга кўра ҳам, энигматик матнларни прагмалингвистик нуқтаи назардан ўрганишга эҳтиёж кучли.

Энг кейинги даврларда ўзбек тилшунослигида антропоцентрик парадигманинг муҳим соҳаларидан бири бўлган лингвокультурологияга бўлган қизиқиш ортганлигини кузатиш мумкин. Жумладан, профессор Н.Маҳмудов, Э.Бегматов, А.Нурмоновларнинг ушбу соҳага алоқадор бўлган мақолалари эълон қилинди.³¹ Албатта, ўзида муайян халқнинг маданий белгиларини намойиш этаётган топишмоқларни лингвокультурологик жиҳатдан таҳлил қилмасликнинг иложи йўқ. Олимларнинг бу борадаги изланишларни ўрганар эканмиз, шуни алоҳида таъкидлаш лозимки, топишмоқларни ўзлари тегишли бўлган маданият фониди кўриб чиқиш мақсадга мувофиқдир. Топишмоқнинг образли компоненти таркибидаги семантикани ўрганиш алоҳида аҳамиятга эга. Бу борада жумбоқни тасвирлаш шартлари ҳам муҳим саналади. Ўзида муайян маданиятга хос ахборотни

³⁰ Сафаров Ш. Прагмалингвистика. Монография. Тошкент. 2008. Б.76

³¹ Маҳмудов Н. Ўхшатишлар – образли тафаккур маҳсули // Ўзбек тили ва адабиёти. – Тошкент, 2011. – № 3. – Б. 19-24; Бегматов Э. Антропонимлар – антропоцентрик тадқиқ объектлари // Ўзбек тили ва адабиёти. – Тошкент, 2013. – № 3. – Б. 35-39; Нурмонов А. Лингвистик нисбийлик ва лингвистик детерминизм назариялари ҳақида мулоҳазалар // Ўзбек тили ва адабиёти. – Тошкент, 2013. – № 5. – Б. 10-19.

сақлайдиган топишмоқларни культурологик жиҳатдан тадқиқ қилиш замонавий тилшуносликдаги истиқболли йўналишлардан биридир. Зероки, топишмоқлар ўзлари тааллуқли бўлган маданият контексти ва паремиологик нутқда таҳлил қилиниши лозим бўлган лингвомаданий ҳодисадир.

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*Modern trends in teaching foreign languages***EXPERIENCE OF FOREIGN UNIVERSITIES IN THE
ORGANIZATION OF E-LEARNING.***Ametova Oyshajon Rozmatovna**ESP teacher, foreign languages department, TSUL*

Abstract. This article analyzes the e-learning that is becoming increasingly prominent in tertiary education. Rationales for its development are wide-ranging, complex and contested, including widening access, pedagogic innovation on-campus, enhancement of distance learning, organizational change, knowledge-sharing and revenue generation.

Key words: *E-learning, ICT, Web supplemented, Web dependent, Mixed mode*

E-learning refers to the use of information and communications technology (ICT) to enhance and/or support learning in tertiary education. While keeping a presiding interest in more advanced applications, e-learning refers to both wholly online provision and campus-based or other distance based provision supplemented with ICT in some way. The supplementary model encompasses activities ranging from the most basic use of ICT (e.g. use of PCs for word processing of assignments) through to more advanced adoption (e.g. specialist disciplinary software, handheld devices, learning management systems, adaptive hypermedia, artificial intelligence devices, simulations, etc.). Different kinds of online presence can be defined as follows:

- None or trivial online presence.
- Web supplemented (e.g. course outline and lecture notes online, use of email, links to external online resources).
- Web dependent: students are required to use the Internet for key “active” elements of the programme – e.g. online discussions, assessment, online project/collaborative work – but without significant reduction in classroom time.

- Mixed mode: students are required to participate in online activities, e.g. online discussions, assessment, online project/collaborative work, as part of course work, which replace part of face-to-face teaching/learning. Significant campus attendance remains.
- Fully online.

The typology is based on the extent to which e-learning reduced rather than simply supplemented time spent in the physical classroom. It assumes both a campus-based institution, and a conception of e-learning tied to the Internet or other online network.

Systematic reform of higher education in the Republic of Uzbekistan, setting priorities, raising the process of training highly qualified personnel with modern knowledge and high moral qualities, modernization of higher education, development of social sphere and economy based on advanced educational technologies development is one of the most pressing issues today. In recent years, research work on the development of higher education in our country has been carried out by SS Gulomov, KH Abdurahmanov, B.Yu. Khodiev, T.Z. Teshaboev, M.Kh. Saidov and others. These scholars have paid special attention to the development of educational services in the higher education system, the management of the higher education system through information and communication technologies, the improvement of the system of financing the higher education system. The quality of education is a factor and a driving force in the development of society. Education serves as a practical tool in the fight against poverty, need, social inequality. Education helps to shape the worldview, expand a person's choice of lifestyle, becomes a mechanism for influencing various aspects of life and activities of man and society. As the high level of education and science has been the driving force of social, technical and economic development throughout human civilization, countries have focused on the priority development of the education system. In particular, South Korea is one of the countries that has achieved high growth rates through the digitization of the national education system. It is important for Uzbekistan to study the experience of advanced

countries, focusing on improving the education system and making it a tool for socio-economic development of the country by bringing it up to international standards. Consequently, South Korea is one of the countries where the education system is based on the digital economy and has reached a high stage of development through highly qualified personnel currently being trained. The national e-learning program has played an important role in achieving this goal. In this regard, it is worth mentioning some aspects of the national program for the formation and development of e-learning, developed by the Ministry of Education and Personnel Management of the Republic of Korea and the Information Service for Education and Research - Korea Education and Research Information Service - KERIS. The South Korean education system is recognized worldwide. In the annual ranking of the effectiveness of national education systems, published annually by the international group Pearson, the country has overtaken Japan, which until recently did not lose the lead in the world on this indicator.

Electronic in the entire continuing education system of the country it is time to develop and adopt a special state program to set up education. Such programs have been adopted not only in South Korea, but also in more than 40 countries, including the United States, the United Kingdom, Japan, China, Germany, Italy, France, the Netherlands, Singapore, and Malaysia.

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THE IMPORTANCE OF IMPLEMENTING PHRASEOLOGICAL UNITS AND THE EFFECTIVE WAYS OF TEACHING

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Abstract. Teaching phraseology is a part of cultural approach in foreign teaching methodology and arranging vocabulary studying though structure of component meaning is linguistic approach. Therefore, the language user needs shared knowledge in order to be able to understand given units properly. The knowledge of connotative meanings of components enables the language user to decode modifications of canonical forms of phraseological units as well as to create their own modifications. The considerable objective of this article was to explore the ways of implementing phraseological units in teaching process.

Key words: phraseological units, idioms, linguistics, component meaning, the context, motivation, ordinary conversation, literal meaning, methods of teaching.

The study of any foreign language is impossible without referring to phraseology, which represents one of the most difficult for learning language levels.

Phraseological units — units of speech communication, therefore their study should be carried out with the help of communicative exercises, the content of which is the students' performance of speech acts in terms of real communication or similar to them. It is now commonly accepted that the people who want to master the foreign language must have knowledge about wide range of complex lexical in foreign language as a language learner. Obviously, in order to command a foreign language deeply, a learner should learn pronunciation, grammar and vocabulary. However, the main of them is phraseological units. Any language is full of phraseological units. Obviously, idioms, phrases and set expressions, aphorisms, maxims, proverbs and sayings are the main units of any language, without them, our language may seem shallow or boring. The ability to use phrasal expressions is a great sign of language. A well-educated person who is a treasurer of phraseology is transforming his mind into a rational, understandable, compact manner. That is why every culture, literate person, a student who wants to be fluent in the language, should use regular expressions in the tongue. [1.]

Word knowledge - the reader knows but does not understand its meaning, just thinks a little and then remembers it. Word acquisition, application - when reading a text, the reader quickly recognizes the word, understands its meaning. Automatically finds a word in speech and can use it with other words. So, the main goal is not to know the words, but to master them. Therefore, the reader must have a certain amount of words. In this case, these words do not depend on what type of speech activity is necessary. There are two layers of vocabulary, the first is the vocabulary that students actively use; the second is the vocabulary learned and understood.

They form the reader's vocabulary and are called active and passive vocabulary. Vocabulary can be entered using both translated and non-translated methods. Phraseologisms are usually recommended to be introduced in a translational way. The phraseologies that are included should be clear to the readers.

The main volume of phraseological material is found in books for reading at home. Students will be able to both understand and translate the text if they are given

the task of crushing them in a special notebook and quoting the translation and commentary. Focusing students' attention on phraseological units contributes to the intensive assimilation of lexical material. In addition, working with phraseology builds reading, crushing, and speaking skills in students.

As teaching materials are of many types including paper-based (textbooks), electronic (corpus, computer software), and audio-visual (video, television programs, audio tapes, visual aids), our focus will be on the paper-based instructional materials, i.e., textbooks. Teacher should choose the best one of teaching methods and teaching materials. It is important not only to teach the meaning of phraseological units, but also to teach how to use them correctly and effectively. When a non-native speaker uses an idiom correctly, he or she will sound very fluent. However, on the other hand, if they bumble the phrase, they will sound the exact opposite. Given the limited number of hours devoted to foreign language teaching in schools, it would be utopian to expect grammar and phraseology to somehow take care of themselves. [2.]

Effective ways of implementing phraseological units in teaching process:

Teach phraseological units in spoken form, not written, and explain to students how they are conversational, rather than formal. Have students practice the phraseological units in dialogue to help them understand they are used in spoken language.

Do not just hand out a long list of phraseological units. Be sure to provide a small selection of 5-10 phraseological units (or less) and explain each one. By using idioms, set expressions, the learners' speaking skills are increased. The original contribution of our study is developing the approach to improve speaking skills through phraseological units as well as increasing motivation of students. [3]

Nowadays, the teaching of vocabulary has become essential in L2 teaching and learning, particularly in the latest years.

1. Use a theme

A great way to teach phraseological units is to use a theme. Most idioms in any language fall into a thematic group. For example, you could use all weather-related

phraseological units or teach sports-related, animal and food phraseological units. By using a common theme to teach idioms, it is easier for students to grasp the meanings of the phrases, and see how similar words can mean very different things.

2. Teach phraseological units with pictures

Provide a picture to explain the context. This works best if you show an image that humorously illustrates the literal meaning of the phraseological units. It will make students laugh, but also help them understand or guess what a phrase means. Phraseological units are full of colorful imagery, perfect for a flashcard or photo. Show the picture to your students and have them guess the meaning of the phraseological units.

3. Use small groups to present dialogues Dialogue

Writing and Role-play in Reading

Dialogues can provide situations for students to practice ordinary conversation and offer students ample practice with basic speaking skills in context. Firstly, dialogues can be viewed as short plays and used for students to act out rather than simply read aloud. Moreover, the dialogues the students write function as basic communication at all levels. In addition, putting pupils into pairs for the role-play in the daily dialogues is an effective way of oral practice for various ages and levels. [4.] Moreover, students learn better when they are provided with collaborative activities because they can interact with peers and share fun in learning. You can use the following idioms to torture by using this way.

4. Guessing Game

Write three or four idioms on the board that all touch on one theme (e.g. animals, body parts). Have students work in groups to see if they can guess the meaning of the phraseological units. Walk around your classroom and check their answers awarding points for any correct definition. Then share the meanings of the phraseological units with your class and give them an example in context. Move on to

another group of idioms around a second theme. Repeat the activity. The first team to reach ten points wins the game.

The importance of reading literature to learn phraseological units

In addition, in our opinion, the next one of the most effective methods of phraseology teaching at universities, at schools can rightly be considered the use of foreign literature. From our point of view, not enough attention is given to the issue of the use of foreign literature in the process of phraseology teaching. The effectiveness of the authentic literary text use that can serve as a support in the training of phraseological units is not fully described and verified. Phraseological phrases are used extensively in artistic work due to their artistic nature. The study of phraseology evokes an emotional response, greatly enhances the interest and increases motivation to language activity and to the subject in.

Reading foreign literature enriches students' vocabulary, expands knowledge of phraseological units and set expressions. The use of foreign literature would increase the efficiency of work, make lessons unusual and memorable. In other words, the use of foreign fiction within the framework of home reading can become one of such methods [5.]

Phraseology is a key factor in improving learners' reading and listening comprehension, alongside fluency and accuracy in production. Speaking activities, discussion or pair-work are challenging and hugely motivating, and a focus on phraseology makes the language natural and authentic. Teaching a phrase effectively and in a fascinating way will not only help you to understand the language, but will also help you to master it consciously. Finally, the above-mentioned activities help to overcome some linguistic challenges caused by studying phraseological units, proverbs and sayings, and give a perfect example of how culture infuses a language.

The advisable ways of teaching can.... - help to learn as easy as quickly - increase learners' interests in learning a language – develop the thinking ability - build a great speech style I guess if teachers use the methods which I have recommended, they will succeed, also learners get the best result. Well, all my aims

have been achieved and I hope my work will be a good stream for teachers and students in their teaching work with phraseological units. Thus, help learner to memorize new phraseology deeply. For that reason, this study investigates ways of teaching phraseology to the learners in effective way.

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CONTEMPORARY TRENDS IN TEACHING MONOLOGUE SPEECH

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Abstract. This article discusses issues related to teaching monologue speech, namely, the main characteristics of monologue speech are given, as well as modern teaching methods at different stages of lifelong education.

Key words: monologue speech, contextual and situational speech, communicative purpose, monologue skill, monologue utterance.

Key words: monologue, speech, culturology, monologue speech, audience, coherence

Monologue speech is a coherent continuous presentation of thoughts by one person, addressed to one or more persons. The goal of this appeal is to achieve the necessary impact on the listener. A monologue is a form of speech that is built by one person, who determines the structure, composition, and linguistic means of utterance.

There are two types of speech: contextual and situational. Contextual speech is a coherent speech that is understandable without taking into account the particular situation in which it is pronounced, i.e. its content is clear from the context. Situational speech is speech, the content of which can be understood only when the situation is taken into account and only that which is generated by the situation and is directly related to it is understood. Contextual and situational speech should never be contrasted, since every speech has at least some context, and every speech is conditioned by some situation. Situationality and contextuality are two of the most important factors parts and properties of oral speech [1].

Contextuality determines the following qualities of monologue speech: consistency, logic, coherence as well as completeness. Sequence - facts are presented sequentially, one phrase predetermines the next. Expansion - a monologue speech consists of several sentences, complete and adverbial, because it is not situational. Completeness - elliptical, truncated sentences are not characteristic of it. Consistency - the presentation can be built inductively or deductively: from the particular to the general or vice versa. Connectivity - the presence of connecting elements between sentences (conjunctions of a compositional and subordinate nature). Completeness (compositional integrity) - the statement has a three-part structure.

In addition, monologue speech is characterized by such psychological characteristics as appeal to the listener and emotional coloring. A monologue statement can be structured at different levels.

1. The level of the sentence, where the idea is only called, but not disclosed.
2. The level of super-phrasal unity, where the disclosure of thought takes place.
3. The level of expanded text at which a monologue utterance can include various combinations of communicative speech types [2].

Depending on the communicative purpose of the utterance, the following functional types of monologue utterance are distinguished: monologue-message, monologue-description, and monologue-narration, monologue reasoning, monologue-persuasion.

- Monologue-description – a method of presenting thoughts that involves describing an object or phenomenon in a static or dynamic state, which is implemented by listing their qualities, characteristics, and features.
- Monologue-message (narration, story) – information about developing actions and states.
- Monologue-reasoning – a type of speech that is characterized by special logical relations between the judgments that make up its composition and form conclusions [3].

For each stage of learning, a certain type of monologue is most relevant.

A complex monologue skill is formed and developed in stages. In primary, secondary and high schools, the following goals and objectives are formulated in this area.

Elementary school: making small monologue statements, for example, a story about yourself, your friend, your family; a description of the subject, a picture; a description of the characters of the fairy tale read based on the picture. The volume of a monologue statement is 5-6 phrases.

Secondary school (grades 5-7): the development of monologue skills involves mastering the following skills:

- speak briefly about facts and events, using such communicative types of speech as description, narration and message, as well as emotional and value judgments;

- transmit the content, the main idea of what you read based on the text;

- make messages in connection with the read / listened text. The volume of a monologue statement is up to 8-10 phrases.

Middle school (grades 8-9): the development of monologue speech at the secondary level provides for students to master the following skills:

- speak briefly about facts and events, using the main communicative types of speech (description, narrative, message, characteristic), emotional and value judgments;

- transmit the content, the main idea of what you read, based on the text;

- make a message in connection with the text you read;

- express and argue your attitude to what you have read/heard.

The volume of a monologue statement is up to 12 phrases.

High school (grades 10-11, basic level): improving the ability to make oral presentations in connection with what was seen / read based on the results of working on a foreign-language project [4].

Skill development:

- make messages containing the most important information on the topic/issue;

- briefly convey the content of the received information;

- talk about yourself, your environment, your plans, justify your intentions/actions;

- talk about facts/events, giving examples, arguments, drawing conclusions; describe the peculiarities of the life and culture of your country and the country/countries of the language being studied. The volume of a monologue statement is 12-15 phrases.

In teaching monologue speech, two methods are used: the path "from above" is deductive, and the path "from below" is inductive. The way "ABOVE" - teaching a monologue based on a sample text, includes 3 stages:

1. Maximum assignment of the content plan of the text, its language material and composition. Tasks aimed at extracting information of various levels from the text are performed:

- answers on questions;
- planning;
- selection of keywords for points of the plan;
- writing out the main sentences from paragraphs;
- drawing up an assogram;
- search for linking words, etc.

2. Various retellings of the original text: close to the text, on behalf of different actors and other forms of text transformation, making additions and ratings.

3. Complete revision of the original text taking into account other components of the situation. The way "BOTTOM" is the development of the utterance from the sentence to the finished monologue. It also includes three stages:

- Performing tasks that stimulate short statements in connection with the topic (situation).
- Concretization and clarification of what has been said, increasing the volume of statements, mastering the ability to use communication means, substitute words, etc.
- An independent, detailed statement, the inclusion of elements of argumentation, assessment [5].

Both approaches are used for both prepared and untrained speech, i.e. either with or without supports. It is clear that the more carefully selected supports at the stage of prepared speech, the better the quality of an untrained monologue will be. The technique has developed a huge number of supports of various properties and orientation. Their creation and application is the subject of the teacher's creativity and

knowledge of the psychological and individual characteristics of students. The path "from above" (deductive) and the path "from below" (inductive) presuppose, in their essence, the presence of a speech pattern at the level of a monologue statement. In the first case, such a speech pattern is presented directly to the students and is the basis for generating an independent statement by them. In the second case, the speech pattern is the basis, first of all, for the teacher, who develops exercises and assignments taking into account its content and gradually leads students to reproduce it. There is a third way to teach a monologue utterance. This path involves developing the ability of monologue speech in accordance with the following levels.

1. Level of reproduction-imitative speaking, non-variative skill. Students construct a statement that is completely identical in form and content to the text that they have read or listened to, i.e. it is a memorized statement.

2. The level of reconstruction (connected-variable utterance). The content of the text is conveyed as close to the given one as possible, however, the main attention is paid to the most important points (for example, retelling close to the text), the student can choose their own language tools when expressing ready-made thoughts. At this level, the student does not yet know how to speak freely, because speaking requires special situations, artificial stimuli, as well as the help of a teacher or various supports.

3. The level of free speech is constructive. The student is independent in choosing both content and language tools. However, in educational activities, the subject of utterance is often set from the outside; it is given in the form of an oral communicative task, the wording of which is clear to the student by ear. When organizing students' statements at different levels, the teacher can apply appropriate teaching techniques. The level of reproduction requires the "memorizing by heart" technique [6].

Learning by heart is very important, especially at the initial stage of learning, because it allows students to assign ready-made utterance samples that are stored for a significant time in long-term memory. What is learned by heart prepares the field,

supplies the memory with language and speech material, which is then used in reactive speaking. Samples of monologue and dialogical texts, poems and songs, speech samples, ready-made expressions are subject to memorization. Poems and songs are the easiest to learn.

Examples of memorization.

1. Read-and-look-up technique. The text for memorization is given to the student in writing. He first reads it quietly in its entirety, and then tries to remember small pieces of it, peering in order to "grab" the whole fragment of the text that he can remember. An exercise performed in this technique several times leads to memorizing the entire text. For this method, texts that are not very wide (for example, text in two columns) are good, so that a single peek can cover a larger piece of text. This kind of memorization is especially suitable for visual learners.

2. Speaking loudly to yourself is an extremely fruitful technique. The utterance turns out to be more qualitative, because it is not only thoughtful, but also voiced (spoken). Your own voice acts as a control that your thoughts are focused only on the text, and this is not always guaranteed in the case of quiet memorization. Speaking out loud, we give the utterance a greater functional orientation, because we imagine our partner. This technique is especially good for auditory users. However, it can be combined with the previous one.

3. In addition, there are techniques such as speaking after someone, to someone, or simultaneously with someone [7].

The level of reconstruction is provided by selective memorization – memorization of individual, most important places in the text. Here it is important to separate the main thing from the minor details and concentrate on the most essential.

Selective memorization is accompanied by:

A. Using visualization techniques:

- The text is placed in front of the student;
- The text is read in its entirety and the so - called optical marking is done - underline, highlight with color, oval, etc;

- The read-and-look-up technique is used, where important passages are spoken out loud;
- Depending on the difficulty, the text is learned in sentences or in large chunks;
- In conclusion, the entire text is reproduced several times in its finished form.

B. Individual notes are executed:

- text in front of your eyes;
- read once;
- optical marking;
- the text is pronounced loudly in sentences and paragraphs;
- repeated several times.

C. Forward reading:

- the student reads the first (important) part and tries to anticipate the next important sentence or part;
- pronounces it and compares it with the original;
- speaks again and anticipates the following;
- finally connects all the correct versions together, covering them with a glance throughout the text, arranging them in the desired sequence[8].

This anticipatory construction of the text evokes images in the student's memory both at the level of meaning and at the level of linguistic lexical and grammatical structures.

Thus, the main goal of teaching monologue speech is to develop a comprehensive monologue skill. Monologue skill is the ability to express one's thoughts verbally in a logically consistent, coherent, sufficiently complete, communicatively motivated, and linguistically correct manner.

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EFFECTIVE STRATEGIES FOR FOREIGN LANGUAGE TEACHING

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The question of learning foreign languages is very important today. Foreign languages are required especially at the present time when progress in science and technology has led to an explosion of knowledge and has contributed to an overflow of information. The total knowledge of humankind is known to double every seven years. Foreign languages are needed as the main and the most efficient means of information exchange between the people of our planet. Especially, English is known as the language of progressive science and technology, trade and cultural relations,

commerce and business, universal language of international aviation, shipping and diplomacy.

There is no universal or ideal method of learning languages. However, we dare to offer you some methods of it.

In the given theoretical part of work, it is necessary to pay attention on those basic statements in which the most essential parts of activity are reflected and generalized. That means the methodical principles underlying teaching. Principles of teaching are understood as starting statements which determine the purposes, the contents, methods and the organization of teaching and are shown in interrelation and interconditionality. In our case, principles are used to define strategy and tactics of teaching English language at all stages practically in each point of educational process. As far as the result of teaching of pupils foreign language is formation their skills of using language as means of intercourse, the leading principle is the principle of a communicative orientation.

Its main function is in creation of all conditions of communications: motives, purposes and problems of intercourse. The communicative orientation defines selection and the organization of languages material, its situational conditionality, communicative value both speech and training exercises, communicative formulation of educational problems, organization and structure of the lesson. This principle assumes creation of conditions for speaking and intellectual activity of pupils during each moment of teaching.

In teaching English language process of integration is realized, it shows, first of all, that mastering of various aspects of language, its phonetics, grammar, lexicon occurs not separately as certain discrete components of language, but is also integrated. Pupils seize and acquire them during carrying out of speech actions which realization can demand the use of a word, word forms, a word-combination, super phrase unity and, at last, the text, caused by situations of intercourse.

In a basis of teaching any subject at school including foreign language, there are general didactic principles. Such principles are: scientific character, availability,

presentation in teaching, an individual approach in conditions of collective work and others. Specific and general didactic principles express typical, main, essential, that should characterize teaching a foreign language at school and, first of all at the beginning stage where bases of mastering are pawned by this subject. The understanding of action of principles of teaching and direct use of rules will allow the teacher to carry out teaching effectively.

The learning is the active process, which is carried out through involving pupils in various activities, thus making it active participant in reception of education. In this bilateral process it is possible to allocate the basic functions which are carried out by each the parts. The teacher carries out organizational, teaching and supervising functions. Functions of the pupil include acquaintance with a teaching material, the training which is necessary for formation of language skills and speaking skills, and application of investigated language in the solving of communicative problems.

The considered methods reflect essence of pedagogical process in which the teacher and pupils cooperate. These methods are used in teaching a foreign language at school, open specificity of a subject and are directed on achievement of the practical, educational and developing purposes.

Each of the considered methods is realized in system of the modes used by the teacher in the organization of teaching pupils, carried out by the latter through the decision of set of the specific targets, which are bound up with cogitative operations and perception by sense organs. Modes as well as methods are structural-functional components of mutual action of teacher and pupil. Nevertheless, if the method names the basic, dominating activity mode is bound up with the concrete action making essence of formed speech activity.

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LINGUISTIC AND CULTURAL STUDIES IN TEACHING A FOREIGN LANGUAGE

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In our time, knowledge of a foreign language is necessary and prestigious, but how to keep students' interest in learning it throughout the learning process? An important role in maintaining motives for learning a foreign language is played by the introduction of elements of regional studies in the classroom. The relevance of the connection of regional studies with teaching a foreign language is caused not only by linguistic and regional studies, but also by social reasons. Learning foreign languages helps people of different countries and different cultures get to know each other better, communicate, and understand each other better.

The growing need for learning English is caused by a number of other, purely practical reasons, primarily the achievements of science and technology. In this regard, every day the number of people who want to study English is increasing, in which scientific, technical, cultural and sociological literature is published in large circulation. An equally important reason is a keen interest in English literature. In addition to the fact that we transfer to students the necessary knowledge of English grammar and English literature, it is also necessary to be able to convey to them the correct idea of the past and present, of the life, traditions and customs of the people whose language they are studying.

Countryknowing, obviously, does not belong to new concepts, although today it requires a new approach to itself, new methodological solutions. It begins with the first lessons in the language, with the assimilation of the primary stock of English words, since words not only express the corresponding concepts, but also through the

concepts they denote - reflect some aspects of the real life of those who speak a given language, the peculiarities of their being, their material and spiritual culture. Accordingly, the methodology of teaching foreign languages should take into account not only the creation of skills in speaking, reading and writing, but also the features of material and spiritual life, which are reflected in the language itself. Although English textbooks contain a certain amount of information on regional studies, they still pursue a different goal - teaching grammar. Comparatively more regional geographic information can be found in textbooks and textbooks on literature, but they also obey the requirements of studying literature, not regional studies.

Sometimes in translations of fiction and other literature, the true meaning of the original is distorted, not because the philologist does not have sufficient training, but also because, assimilating foreign words, he gives them completely the content that he is used to investing in the words of the native language corresponding to them. Here you can recall the words of K. Erdman: The generally accepted expressions, which are usually considered translations of foreign words and which are stored in heaps in dictionaries, for the most part are not equivalents of concepts, but words of a close semantic sphere, therefore there is no reason to expect that they contain semantic and emotional shades of the original.

It is difficult to convey by means of another language without any explanation the semantic shades of words such as marshall, attorney, yankee, etc. Lack of relevant information deprives the student of the opportunity to understand the whole gamut of meanings. The lack of necessary comments on certain words and concepts often leads to all sorts of misunderstandings.

The need for social selection and the study of linguistic units, in which the originality of the national culture is most clearly manifested and which cannot be understood the way native speakers understand them, is felt in all cases of communication with foreigners, when reading fiction, journalism, the press, when watching films and videos, when listening to songs, etc.

When ethnic and cultural material is included in the content of teaching a foreign language, adequate means for its assimilation can be, first of all, authentic materials: literary and musical works, objects of reality and their illustrative images, which can most of all bring the student closer to the natural cultural environment. However, the content should be meaningful for students, have a certain novelty, whether it be general information about educational institutions, about the state structure, about the various organizations of the country of the target language, or about the peculiarities of speech behavior and etiquette.

The selection of units with a pronounced national-cultural semantics is the task of those sections of lexicology and phraseology that act as the linguistic basis of linguistic and regional studies and can be called country-oriented linguistics.

The study of culture, history, realities and traditions contributes to the fostering of a positive attitude to a foreign language, the culture of the people who are the native speakers of this language, there is a constant comparison of the elements of culture and life of the native country and the countries of the studied language, the concept of the role of language as an element of the culture of the people and the need to use it is formed as a means of communication.

It is advisable if textbooks and manuals on the English language will systematically present the necessary information about the country and the people whose language they are studying. This should not create an overwhelming student experience; the variety of material taught will make the subject itself more interesting. All information provided to students will help expand their horizons, facilitate the assimilation of literature, not to mention expanding the vocabulary of students. It seems expedient to compile a separate textbook on regional studies, the material of which should contain more information, especially those industries that are directly related to the specialization of a particular educational institution. The regional studies manual should have meaningful, interesting high-quality illustrative material in the form of photographs, slides, figures, tables, diagrams, multimedia

materials, etc. Also, an educational film on country studies can be an ideal addition to the study guide.

A good example of a textbook on country knowing is the textbook by L.S. Baranovsky. and Kozikis D. D. “Panorama of Great Britain”. This textbook, intended for students of institutes and faculties of foreign languages, can also be used by students and teachers of non-linguistic universities as additional material. It includes information on history, physical and economic geography, state and socio-political structure and culture of modern Great Britain. The tutorial is provided with a chronological table and an index of geographical names and names.

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THE ROLE OF MOTIVATION IN LEARNING A FOREIGN LANGUAGE

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Abstract. This article discusses the types of motivation that prompts the learner to learn a foreign language, and about the factors that influence the study of a foreign language. The methodological solutions proposed in the article can be used in the practice of higher pedagogical education.

Keywords: motivation, speech activity, Internet, vocabulary, games

Stimulation of human behavior is associated with the concept of motivation. This concept includes ideas about the needs, interests, goals, intentions, aspirations, motivations that a person has, about external factors that make him behave in a certain way, about managing an activity in the process of its implementation. The importance of solving the problem of motivation is determined by the fact that the motivation of learning is a decisive factor in the effectiveness of the educational process.

The implementation of an active approach means the possibility and necessity of studying educational motives as a structural element of the activity of learning, emerging in the process of its implementation. The motivational sphere of a person can be influenced by social motives determined by the needs of society; collectively they constitute external motivation. Secondly, the nature of the activity can also influence the motivational-incentive sphere of a person. This is the so-called intrinsic motivation. Both external and internal motivation can be positive and negative.

As for the types of motivation in relation to a foreign language, then the exact characteristic of motivation is given by P.M. Jacobson: “such a motivation for the learning process is connected with a rather acute sense of civic duty to the country, to close people, and is associated with the idea of learning as a way to mastering the great values of culture ... learning as a way to realize one’s purpose in life.”

The main variety of internal motivation is communicative, since communication is the first and natural need for students of a foreign language. The problem here is that this type of motivation is the most difficult to maintain, since a foreign language cannot compete with the native language.

Linguistic recognition motivation is positive students' attitude to linguistic matter itself, to the study of the basic properties of linguistic norms.

An important type of intrinsic motivation is also instrumental motivation, i.e. motivation arising from the positive attitude of students to certain types of work. It is known that the pedagogical effect can be achieved to a greater extent as a result of students' own activity. It is important to include the student in independent learning

activities. It is necessary to equip students with certain techniques of mastering a foreign language, the rational meaning of which would be obvious and impressed by it. Students should be increasingly confronted with the need for independent acquaintance with the new.

Now everyone understands that the Internet has very great information capabilities and no less impressive services. The Internet creates a unique opportunity for students of a foreign language to use authentic texts, listen and communicate with native speakers, i.e. he creates a natural language environment. Students expand their vocabulary, everyday vocabulary, and their spelling improves. Exercises in electronic training courses are suitable for independent work of students. In addition to telecommunication projects in extracurricular activities, students can independently work to improve their knowledge in the field of a foreign language. For this, there is a great variety of courses in networks for different categories of students, intended for self-education or for training under the guidance of a teacher (distance courses). From time to time, it is necessary to conduct joint results and discuss the results, which contributes to active speech activity. Such work is motivated, as all students want to talk about the results.

A powerful incentive to master a foreign language is the game. It acts as an effective teaching tool that activates the students' mental activity, makes the learning process attractive and interesting, makes students worry and worry.

The game performs four functions that are most important for a person: a means of developing a motivational-consumer sphere, a means of cognition, a means of developing mental action, and a means of developing arbitrary behavior. Exercises of a game nature can be different in their purpose, content, methods of organizing and conducting, material equipment, the number of participants.

The fact that the game arouses the interest and activity of students, gives them the opportunity to prove themselves in an activity that is fascinating for them, and contributes to faster and more durable memorization of foreign words. The fact that knowledge of the material is a prerequisite for active participation in the game, and

sometimes a prerequisite for winning, also serves the same purpose. The game provides an opportunity not only to improve, but also to acquire new knowledge, as the desire to win makes you think, remember what has already been done and remember everything new. When planning classes and selecting various games for them, we try to take into account not only the age categories of students, but also the level of their development and awareness. We mainly play games that include vocabulary and grammar exercises on a specific topic, so that students practice using vocabulary in situations close to the natural environment, learn to use speech patterns that contain certain grammatical difficulties.

Thus, the above methods of developing positive motivation to learn a foreign language act not only as a means of increasing motivation, but also as a means of teaching and educating students in a team.

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ON THE ISSUE OF TEACHING INTERCULTURAL COMMUNICATION

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Abstract. This article analyzes the issue of teaching intercultural communication. In today's fast-paced world, teachers must be able to use creatively the most productive educational technologies that provide high-quality training for future specialists in intercultural communication in the process of teaching a foreign language in the system of higher education. This is one of the most significant modern trends in teaching a foreign language and intercultural communication.

Key words: *intercultural communication, professional international cooperation, pragmatics of the speech, cultural identity, stereotypical ideas.*

A future specialist in intercultural communication should be thoroughly prepared to participate in professional international cooperation and be able to take into account the specific ideas and preferences existing in the cultures of foreign business partners in the ways of forming thoughts. In this regard, in professionally oriented teaching of foreign language communication of students of language faculties, special attention should be paid to the development of their ability to choose the correct form to formulate their ideas, taking into account the cultural identity of the native speaker. This is another of the current trends in teaching intercultural communication in the system of higher education.

Our students should take into account the fact, for example, that Americans and British, during their speeches in front of an audience, always aim at "publicity" in communication and rejection of abstract theorizing, which, in their opinion, "repels" the audience. This determines the stereotypical desire of representatives of Western culture to reduce the interpersonal distance with business partners. For example,

representatives of both American and British cultures do not like to saturate their speeches in front of an audience with a large amount of terminological vocabulary, which is explained in the pragmatics of the speech and the cultural identity of these representatives [2].

People's perception of each other occurs through the prism of prevailing stereotypes. When meeting representatives of other cultures, people tend to perceive their behavior from the perspective of their culture. Misunderstanding of speech behavior, symbolism of gestures, facial expressions and other elements of behavior often leads to a distorted interpretation of the meaning of their actions, which easily gives rise to a number of negative feelings: alertness, sometimes even hostility [1].

Knowledge of the stereotypes of speech behavior is very helpful in communicating with other peoples. If we know how we are perceived, communication is greatly simplified, since many features of communication with us are understandable and not offensive. Stereotypical ideas about a particular people often provide a key to understanding its characteristics. To learn how to communicate with representatives of another nation, it is important to have a clear idea of how others see us in order to build our communication taking into account these ideas.

For example, in order to achieve the best results when conducting business negotiations with the British, the knowledge and skills gained in working with representatives of this country should be applied. The style of business communication, its principles and rules, strategy and tactics for achieving results are very significant points in intercultural interaction.

Humor is considered one of the most effective tools in the arsenal of a British manager, and some businessmen from other countries can win the trust of the British by demonstrating that they are just as good at it.

Thus, for those who negotiate with British, it is reasonable to stock up on jokes that have even an indirect relationship to the subject of future conversation. Jokes, anecdotes, introduced into the process of business communication within reasonable

limits and, most importantly, at the right moment, defuse the atmosphere, create a trusting atmosphere, bring people together.

When teaching analyzed communicative actions, students as future specialists in intercultural communication should not only understand the specifics of the speech behavior of carriers of another culture, but also consciously master the methods of establishing and terminating contact, stereotypically preferred by business partners, and compare these methods with their own stereotypes. As a result, students acquire the ability to identify differences, identify their cause and take these differences into account in their future professional activities [3].

The desire to reduce the interpersonal distance is characteristic, for example, of representatives of American culture who implement their speech in accordance with the postulates of "positive" rational politeness: "bring closer to your partner."

Representatives of Western cultures, trying to "interest" business partners and reduce interpersonal distance, often deliberately precede the process of argumentation with colloquial formulas (proverbs, sayings, appeals to their own experience, etc.). This method (according to Western representatives) does not distract from the subject of persuasion, but rather activates thinking and serves as a means of indirect persuasion. It should be noted that representatives of Western cultures are more inherent in proof through real life examples.

For representatives of Western cultures, one of the most preferable ways of showing the objectivity of information is its detailing. The stereotypical methods of showing the objectivity of information, preferred by representatives of Western cultures, also include the logical construction of a speech using chronological references and summarizing conclusions.

The rules of international politeness prescribe certain forms of etiquette speech behavior during business negotiations or public speeches, and the desire to exert the necessary influence on the consciousness of a business partner encourages the speaker to include appropriate situations etiquette formulas not only at the beginning and end of the speech, but also to permeate the entire meaningful part of speech with

them. Caution in the expression of representatives of Western cultures is ensured through the use of neutral lexical units, the use of adjectives and adverbs with a low degree of emotional expressiveness. Naturally, teachers in the process of teaching intercultural communication need to draw the attention of students to such important details. This is another of the current trends in teaching intercultural communication [4].

The culture of communication is an indicator of the general culture of a person and this should be specially and purposefully taught in foreign language classes, taking into account the stereotypes of speech behavior inherent in carriers of another culture. Knowledge and ability to take into account the language stereotypes of business partners will allow a specialist in intercultural communication to prepare an English-speaking presentation, the content-compositional and linguistic structure of which is most consistent with the cultural identity of the native speaker, which will provide a significant increase in the influencing power of speech.

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DEVELOPMENT OF COMMUNICATIVE COMPETENCE IN ESP LEARNERS

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Abstract. This article analyzes the development of communicative competence in ESP learners. Currently, the problem of mastering a foreign language at all levels of the educational process is becoming increasingly important. High school is faced with the task of not only updating the content of education, but also introducing new ways of forming communicative competence by developing its constituent components that are necessary for future specialists in any area of their activity.

Key words: *communicative, linguistic, socio-cultural, strategic, discursive, cognitive competences, ESP, socio-cultural environment.*

According to the State educational standards of the higher education system, learning a foreign language is mandatory, its goal is the formation of foreign language communicative competence of a graduate, his preparation for professional communication in a foreign language in various situations. To solve everyday problems in the modern socio-cultural environment, a young specialist needs a level of proficiency in a foreign language that would be sufficient for the implementation of personal and various industrial contacts, for further professional growth and self-development.

The concept of foreign language communicative competence has been repeatedly considered by a number of methodological scientists, and most of them believe that here we are dealing with a complex phenomenon that includes a number of components. [1].

Since communication is a difficult, multifaceted process, therefore, its component composition is heterogeneous and can be determined by the main

competencies: linguistic, socio-cultural, strategic, discursive, cognitive. Competence as a result of educational activity implies a complex of interrelated knowledge, skills and abilities in combination with the personal experience of students, obtained in the process of completing the assigned tasks, and emotional attitude to various types of educational activities and methods of its implementation [2].

The flexibility of the competence-based approach to the organization of the educational process makes it possible to introduce elements of the basic educational paradigms (knowledge-oriented, personal, cultural) into the competence-oriented educational environment [3].

Higher education today faces the problem of finding effective ways to form competencies that are part of a foreign language communicative competence. Quite effective methodological techniques include project activities related to the collective solution of the assigned tasks, problem discussions, role-playing games with modeling situations of professional communication.

The formation of communicative competence can be imagined in the form of climbing to the top of pyramid, at the highest point of which is the ability to perform tasks for productive thinking, and the whole process of moving to this point is the daily overcoming of educational difficulties for the transition from simple to complex, from reproduction of knowledge to simple mental actions (description), then to more complex operations (argumentation, explanation), and then to the generation of speech utterances.

The effectiveness of the formation of communicative competence depends on the correct choice of the strategy underlying the teaching process. The optimal didactic strategy is related to how correctly the set of target tasks is defined and whether it takes into account the logic of the development of the assimilation process, that is, it is important to clearly understand what the set of target competencies should be at each stage of the educational process, and how to correctly emphasize the priority points in their choice [2].

As you know, language competence as one of the main components of communicative competence implies knowledge of vocabulary, grammar and phonetics of a foreign language, as well as the ability to use this knowledge receptively and productively in various types of speech activity.

The development of linguistic competence requires from teacher such an approach to the organization of training, which would give each student the opportunity to develop and open up as a creative person, who understands that his worldview, feelings, interests are significantly important at every stage of language acquisition. To direct the activities of the students come out to the fore, it is reasonable to use such a form as project development. Working on the project helps to form a universal system of students' speech actions, which are applicable not only for solving a specific educational and communicative task in class, but also for real professional tasks in a multicultural environment. It is important for the student to feel not so much a "student" as a full-fledged partner, on whose activities overall success depends, as a result of which the student turns from a passive listener into an active participant in communicative interaction, and the process of communicating knowledge takes the form of interdependent exchange of knowledge.

Project activity as a didactic method is inextricably connected with the development of team work skills, since a project is, first of all, a problem that needs to be resolved. This method is not new, but its effectiveness is undeniable, because it encourages students to actively, creatively, independently acquire knowledge.

The system-forming components of project activities include the selection of topics, in which not only teachers, but also the most active students should take part, while their interests, potential opportunities, creative and professional needs should be taken into account. Important components are also the organization of the workplace and the formation of working teams, within which the planning of specific directions for the implementation of the project begins, the definition of the role and tasks of each team member, based on his individual linguistic abilities and taking into account the possibility of realizing a subjective position [4].

As an example, we can cite the study of possible unforeseen situations in the intensive care unit and ways to prevent them. The first stage of work in a team is to search for information in various sources. The next stage is work with special dictionaries, study of the found authentic text and video material, accumulation of the necessary vocabulary. The final stage is a role-play game - a "production meeting", at which each team reports on an "incident", asks other teams for help and advice, and then offers their own way to solve this problem. The purpose of this work is to simulate a real situation in the intensive care unit, focusing on the actions of the doctor (anesthesiologist or other specialists), his ability to find a solution and manage the team, as well as the willingness of each team member to do everything possible to find solutions and competent justification of options.

Thus, the project participants are involved in the process, where they are subjects of their own activities, where they are faced with the task of seeing and isolating the problem, formulating and organizing the study and solution of a particular issue, and applying the knowledge gained in speech activity.

It should be noted, that a student, when he obtains knowledge, and does not receive it ready-made, realizes the meaning of educational activity. This contributes to the effective development of his own abilities and general educational competencies. If each subsequent stage is logically based on previous results, it means that the general didactic strategy is defined correctly, and the result is a smooth transition from the formation of skills to the development of competencies that are so necessary for a future specialist.

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WAYS OF INCREASING HIGH SCHOOL LEARNERS' MOTIVATION USING MODERN TECHNOLOGIES IN TEACHING ENGLISH

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Abstract. This article considers the effective use of innovative pedagogical technologies for increasing high school learners' motivation in the process of learning English. One of the strategic tasks of a teacher is to create the need and ability to learn a language independently, to continue education and self - education. Its solution is impossible without the formation of each high school student's persistent learning motivation, a constant desire to delve into the field of knowledge. This is what will determine the success of the younger generation in the future, not only during school years, but also their ability to realize their inner potential in further professional education. The problem of forming and increasing motivation to study, in general, and when learning a foreign language, in particular, has always been and remains one of the most important tasks of didactics.

Keywords: *modern innovative technologies, increasing motivation, motivational sphere, high school learners' motivation.*

The expansion of international contacts, the internationalization of all spheres of life due to Uzbekistan's entry into the worldwide educational and socio-cultural space required the use of a linguo-cultural approach to the study of interference. For

modern linguodidactics, the study of linguistic and cultural interference is also significant in connection with the intensification of professional activities of specialists of different profiles in close contact with foreign colleagues. In this work, interference is considered as a communicative hindrance due to the imposition of linguistic and cultural codes of the contacting languages.

Nowadays, the importance of successful communication between representatives of different countries is growing in the conditions of a high level integration of world politics and economics, development of international relations in such spheres of human activity as politics, science, culture and economy. The First President of Uzbekistan, I.A. Karimov, repeatedly noted in his speeches that "in the conditions of world integration, knowledge of foreign languages is the guarantee of effective cooperation with foreign states". In accordance with Presidential Decree No. PD-1875 on December 10, 2012, special attention is paid to the improvement of the complex system of teaching foreign languages aimed at the formation of a harmoniously developed, highly educated, modern thinking younger generation, as well as further integration of the Republic into the world community.

The President of Uzbekistan Sh.M. Mirziyoyev also stresses that "the priority tasks for us are the development of the sphere of education, upbringing and science, the creation of conditions for the active mastery of profound knowledge, foreign languages by young people...". Undoubtedly, motivation is one of the main roles in the process of teaching foreign languages at school. In most cases, it is high school learners with increased cognitive interest who achieve good success in studying the subject, rather than those who have weakened or no motivation at all.

When high school learners are just beginning to learn a foreign language, they are most often interested in this subject. But after some time, interest significantly weakens, and after a couple of years, 86% of learners completely lose it. The reason for all this is this: learning is knowledge, but you cannot oblige a person to know something, you can only instill interest in him. Therefore, the problem of forming and

increasing motivation to study is the main one at all stages of foreign language teaching.

For the optimal organization of the educational process, it is important, first of all, a deep knowledge of the motives of the learner's teaching, and secondly, the ability to correctly identify them and manage them intelligently.

At present time, thanks to the internet, we are armed with a huge arsenal of various educational materials in English, so teachers need to constantly look for new ways to actively implement it in the educational process, and therefore constantly develop professionally.

It is obvious that creating a comfortable emotional climate is a necessary condition for an interested atmosphere in the classroom, which in turn leads to increased motivation and, as a result, to an increase in the effectiveness of the teacher and high school learners.

However, in the process of learning, high school learners also have to deal with negative emotions. Along with overcoming the emotions of dissatisfaction in learning, there should be a sense of struggle with difficulties. The high school learners should always be aware of his assessment as the result of mental effort. If the assessment does not motivate the learner in any way, or the teacher underestimates him or judges him subjectively, then the child may develop a conniving attitude to the educational process. In this regard, modern innovative technologies are able to create a completely objective control and provide a fair and independent assessment of high school learners' knowledge and skills.

It can be seen that the motivational sphere of high school learners in the process of its formation is regularly influenced both by the immediate environment and, in general, by the external environment. Therefore, the teacher needs to organize the learning process in such a way as to instill high school learners' best motivational guidelines, based on the elements of motivation that have already been formed by this time, in order to use them in the future for the development of the high school learners.

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THE ROLE OF SOCIO-CULTURE COMPETENCE TO TEACH ENGLISH

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Abstract. The article is devoted to the main methods of forming the sociocultural competence of students of secondary general education schools through the integration of the national-regional component into the process of teaching a foreign (English) language. The author studied such authentic materials as translations of Uzbek fiction, foreign articles about Uzbek culture. The article offers practical

recommendations for using these materials in English lessons, in particular, options for working with proverbs of English, Russian and Uzbek origin as one of the methods of socio-cultural development of the personality of schoolchildren

Key words: authentic materials, methods of teaching foreign languages, national-regional component, socio-cultural competence

In the modern world, the goal of teaching a foreign language cannot be only the transfer of linguistic knowledge and the development of speech skills of students. In the context of globalization and integration languages and cultures, the socio-cultural component began to occupy a central place in foreign language lessons, which plays a significant role in the development of the student's personality and expanding his general outlook. Sociocultural competence represented in the state the standard of basic general education in a foreign language, is defined as a set of knowledge about the country of the target language, national cultural characteristics of their speech behavior and the ability to use this knowledge in the process of dialogue of cultures [4]. However, being an important element in the theory of intercultural communication, sociocultural development also involves the ability to represent your country, region and culture. It is at this stage of the formation of sociocultural competence that the teacher is faced with certain problems: the teacher is facing certain problems:

1. Low level of cognitive interest in local history.
2. Inability to present the culture of the native land through the English language.
3. Inability to identify and compare the national and cultural characteristics of the region of residence and countries of the target language [1, p. 187].

One of the possible ways to solve these problems and, as a consequence, to increase the level of sociocultural development of schoolchildren can advocate the implementation of the national-regional component in the classroom of English language. Because the new standards of the Federal State Educational Standard emphasize the need for the personal and socio-cultural development of students, the national and regional content of education, which implies the use of means and forms

of education, taking into account the historical and cultural specifics region is now being brought to the fore. After all, it is knowledge about the native land helps to instill patriotism, respect for one's own culture and the cultures of other countries, tolerance, readiness for intercultural dialogue and cooperation.

The implementation of the national-regional component is continuously associated with interdisciplinary integration, since it entails the use of in the lesson of materials about geography, history, literature, music and other components of the culture of the native land. A foreign language as an academic discipline is most open to such modifications of the content due to its "Pointlessness" [2, p. 146].

In other words, the purpose of his training is not the transfer of knowledge about the objective world, but the implementation of communication and speech activity, the subject of which can vary and be introduced from the outside. Moreover, the use of information on local history topics in teaching English allows you to make learning more personalized, as it brings foreign language communication closer. Sixteen to the personal experience of students and gives them the opportunity to use information and facts that occur in everyday life in speech communication. It is important to note that the content of the training material, taking into account the national-regional component, should correspond to the following criteria:

1. Sociocultural value, implying their assistance in raising the level of general cultural education of students, the formation of base of national and cultural competence, which means an integral system of knowledge about key customs, traditions, realities of the country target language.
2. Regional value.
3. Relevance, that is, the degree of its modernity and focus on the surrounding reality.
4. Attractiveness of educational material.
5. Functionality - the ability to use in training all aspects of speech activity [3, p. 92].

The main material used in the process of teaching a foreign language in order to form socio-cultural competence, is an educational text, which includes fiction texts, regional and thematic orientation, poems, songs, dialogues, interviews, video

and audio materials. In this case, it is necessary that the educational the text was authentic, since it is this factor that significantly increases motivation of schoolchildren.

When introducing a national-regional component in training English language in schools of the Republic of Uzbekistan opens to teachers broad perspectives. Translations of works of outstanding writers and poets of the Republic of Uzbekistan can be used as literary texts. The group of authentic regional geographic materials may include articles and separate clippings from the following textbooks: “Ethnic Groups of Europe: encyclopedia “[5],” Minority Ethnic Mobilization in the Russian Federation “[5],” Native Peoples of the World: an encyclopedia of groups, cultures and contemporary issues “[5], The History of the Uzbeks since Ancient Times.

Another way of integrating the national-regional component into the process of teaching a foreign language is project activity, which makes it possible to develop speech competencies, increase the level of knowledge about the native land, as well as learn to work in micro-groups and master search skills. Any project work starts with setting goals. Considering the project as a way of working with national-regional material, as an educational goal, we highlighted the formation of ideas about a small homeland among students, teaching goal - consolidation of knowledge on the topic passed and mastering skills of working with various sources of information, and the educational goal is to promote communication between schoolchildren and peers both their nationality and those representing a different culture. Per the stage of setting goals is followed by the organizational part, during which the class is divided into microgroups and distribution between them themes of projects. To carry out project work, students can be offered the following topics: "My hometown", "My village", "Famous people Uzbrkistan ", " Cultural monuments of the Republic of Uzbrkistan ", " The history of my small Motherland ", " The nature of the native land ", " National diversity Republic of Uzbrkistan ". The presentation and defense of projects can be

carried out in various forms, for example, in the form of a video report, a newspaper article, a poster, an interview, etc.

Thus, the formation of sociocultural competence in schoolchildren cannot be imagined without using the national-regional component in the content of teaching a foreign language. One of the main ways to integrate it into the educational process is to work with authentic materials, as well as acquaintance with the folklore of the studied language versus the folklore of the native culture. Implementation of such learning approaches positively affects the general motivation of students, makes it possible to get to know another country and deeply.

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THE BENEFITS OF “MIRROR-IMAGE LEARNING” IN TEACHING FOREIGN LANGUAGE

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Abstract. The article explores how the “mirror-image learning” is utilized during teaching process and benefits of this method in order to improve students’ oral English. At the same time, it motivates students are quite interested in their recording which they produced. In addition, this approach offers teachers an effective way to supervise students’ learning after class.

Key words: *survey, mirror-image, cooperation, self-efficacy, autonomous learning.*

Teaching foreign languages, especially English has become an important part of education and is being taught in a number of educational organizations. Nowadays, it is clear that teachers are likely to use traditional and modern methods in their educating process. According to the latest surveys, the whole world teachers tend to use modern methodology all the time. During teaching process, lesson usually requires both methods in our point of view. The main aim of every class is that what teachers and learners want to achieve in a lesson or a course so different classroom activities are planned in order to achieve these aims. To put it another way, the aims of lesson usually show what teachers and learners want to be able to do by the end of a lesson, or what they will have done during it.

Definitely, one of the aims of any methodology in foreign language teaching is to improve the foreign language ability of the student.

According to Jim Scrivener, the teachers’ main role is to help learning to happen” which includes “involving” students in what is going on “by enabling them to work at their own speed, by not giving long explanations by encouraging them to participate talk, interact, do things, etc. [1]

Teaching should be student-centered, motivation springs from within, it can be sparked, but not imposed from without, language learning and teaching are successful when they meet student's needs in particular circumstances, the acquired language skills must serve the students in everyday life. In our point of view, teaching language and learning process are successful if they look like a cooperation process when one's feelings, values and aspirations are revealed either at a very deep level or in surface activities such as games, simulation, dramatizations.

In the following article, we are going to focus on one of the modern methods, which is "Mirror-image approach". Li. Lin provides information about "Mirror-image approach" in her scientific article. According to her view point, this approach includes four steps. Firstly, teachers audio tape students' spoken English in class, individual or paired. That may include student's question-answering, conversations and discussions. Secondly, teachers listen to them carefully and mark those mistakes and mispronunciations. Thirdly, teachers send those audio materials back to the students involved and ask the students to listen to them carefully and correct mistakes, try to avoid them and improve fluency. Last, teachers select the audio materials of high quality to send them to students in class and ask the students to learn. The main advantages of the approach are self-evident. Students can get to know exactly their mistakes and correct them. Data shows it is more effective than teacher's correction in face. At the same time, students are quite interested to listen to such listening materials since they are produced either by themselves or by their friends. At last, the approach offers teachers an effective way to supervise students' learning after class.

In terms of theoretical point, "Mirror-image learning", was initially put forward by Professor Yang Yonglin from Foreign Language department in Tsinghua University as a teaching model of writing [2]

Self-efficacy theory is the kernel of the motivation theory, which is put forward by Albert Bandura in his social learning theory research. It has been defined as the

belief that one is capable of performing in a certain manner to attain a certain set of goals [3].

Self-efficacy is an active judgment of one's ability and self-awareness comes from the experience or information generated by interaction between the individual and the environment. According to the social learning theories, there are mainly four ways of the self-efficacy formation: the experience of success or failure, the experience of replacement, speech persuasion, and emotional reaction [4]. Through this method, learners can take more advantage of the experience or information obtained in the previously mentioned four ways to improve their oral English self-efficacy, adjust their study habits and methods.

It is clear that self-monitoring plays a decisive role in learning process. It can definitely stimulate and promote attention in students, while maintaining a good mood and a high motivation level.

According to Li Lin's investigation, some students were made inquiry into their attitudes about habits in class and out of class. After recording students' speeches or dialogues in class, teachers first analyzed them and then gave them back to students, encouraging them to correct mistakes on their own and then point out their weakness in order to reach an objective evaluation of "mirror-image language learning approach". [5]

After this practice they have proven some benefits of this method:

- promotes interactions between students and teachers;
- shortens the distance between them;
- improves both interest and efficiency of autonomous learning;
- develops learners' oral expression from the experience or information reflected from the "mirror";
- helps students to change in their mental status and attitude;
- widens students' channels of obtaining knowledge and information, develop their practice consciousness and perseverant learning habit, and inspire their spirit of exploration, innovation and independence.

This learning method requires students a lot of patients and working hard. By recording their voice, then listening to their English speaking in such an awkward way and correlating mistakes, make them have a clear awareness of their oral English and they start to improve it.

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THE IMPORTANCE OF COMMUNICATIVE COMPETENCE IN TEACHING PROCESS

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Abstract. At the present stage, in teaching a foreign language, tasks aimed at the formation of communicative competence that contribute to the achievement of the most important goal, consisting in the formation of a secondary linguistic personality, who are able to fully communicate in this language, become especially relevant. Developing competencies become especially significant when it comes to the use of literary texts in the training of future philologists and translators.

Key words: *competence, intercultural competence, discursive competence, foreign language, pragmatics, linguistics.*

Now, more than a decade into the new millennium, the effects of globalization are widely felt. Today, more people around the world have direct and indirect contact with each other than ever before. With the rapid globalization and science advances, the communication between various cultures has become closer and more frequent.

There is growing recognition within the field of teaching foreign languages that it is important to focus not only on developing learners’ linguistic skills, but also on advancing their communicative competence, or their ability to communicate effectively and appropriately in English within a culturally diverse society. Essential elements for building communicative competence include discourse, strategic, functional, linguistic, and socio-cultural competencies. These elements are

interconnected and each helps build communicative knowledge and skills when integrated into curriculum and practice in intentional ways.

M. Byram in his book “Teaching and assessing intercultural communicative competence” classified the following types of competences:

- Linguistic competence: the ability to produce and interpret meaningful utterances which are formed in accordance with the rules of the language concerned and bear their conventional meaning... that meaning which native speakers would normally attach to an utterance when used in isolation.

- Sociolinguistic competence: the awareness of ways in which the choice of language forms... is determined by such conditions as setting, relationship between communication partners, communicative intention, etc. it covers the relation between linguistic signals and their contextual – or situational – meaning.

- Discourse competence: the ability to use appropriate strategies in the construction and interpretation of text.

- Strategic competence: when communication is difficult we have to find ways of ‘getting our meaning across’ or of ‘finding out what somebody means’; these are communication strategies, such as rephrasing, asking for clarification.

- Socio-cultural competence: every language is situated in a socio-cultural context and implies the use of a particular reference frame which is partly different from that of foreign language learner; socio-cultural competence presupposes a certain degree of familiarity with that context

- Social competence: involves both the will and skill to interact with others, involving motivation, attitude, self-confidence, empathy and the ability to handle social situations. [1]

The role of language learning is to achieve communicative competence. Communicative competence has four parts, which we call language competencies.

1. Grammatical competence is how well a person has learned that features and rules of the language. This includes vocabulary, pronunciation, and sentence formation.

2. Sociolinguistic competence is how well a person speaks and is understood in various social contexts. This depends on factors such as status of those speaking to each other, the purpose of the interaction, and the expectations of the interaction.

3. Discourse competence is how well a person can combine grammatical forms and meanings to achieve different types (genres) of speaking or writing.

4. Strategic competence is how well the person uses both verbal forms and non-verbal communication to compensate for lack of knowledge in the other three competencies.

The act of communication among the human beings has been subject to consistent evolution and up gradation from time to time. In the pre-historic times, people used to communicate with their fellow beings through grunts, barks and roars just like the animals. But gradually they developed an elaborate set of sounds to express their feelings and convey their messages. Now it is a systematic use of language that differentiates human beings from animals. Only human beings have been blessed with the gift of language.

The different languages used by human beings do differ from the other codes used by them to communicate among themselves. Human language has the property of reclusiveness and creativity which suggests that there are signals within signals within signals but each signal has its own significance. In any language, with a definite set of graphic symbols and their corresponding phonological symbols it is possible to form and communicate infinite number of messages. On the other hand, other codes only permit a limited number of messages.

In learning English, students need to be constantly alert for shifts in meaning as participants use varying systems and principles of interpretation. Different contexts lead to different expectations which in turn lead to different interpretations of the same object. Similarly, the context of our own culture may lead us to interpret another person's words, behaviour or attitude quite differently from the way in which that person intends them to be interpreted. We may not be aware of the patterns of interpretation which members of a particular culture use.

In addition, English teachers must be capable of mastering the knowledge contained in the teaching material completely and deeply. Mastering the knowledge contained in the teaching material and the supplementary knowledge was the minimum requirement of a good teacher. Besides, he must be good at supplying the theory of education and teaching, give consideration to the student's psychological characteristic and receptivity, choose the most appropriate teaching method and make students master knowledge. Teachers should also train students' internal motive of study.

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DEVELOPMENT OF THE STUDENTS 'RESEARCH ACTIVITY WITH THE HELP OF "WORKSHOP TECHNOLOGY" IN A COLLABORATIVE ENVIRONMENT

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Abstract. This article talks about a teacher of a new generation who is able to focus on the needs of a particular student directly, to reveal his potential with the help of the technology of workshops that allows them to develop themselves individually, to realize themselves and their place in the world, to understand other people, as well as the laws of the world in which they live, perspectives of the "future" that will affect them back.

Key words: *differentiated approach, pedagogical profiles, information literacy, Individualization of education, project approach, collaborative environment.*

An important method of obtaining information on the study of the dynamics of the formation of components of educational activity is the teacher's ability to deliberately observe the activities of each student, make notes, write down, and

correlate the real activities of students with the description of each levels. You can study the dynamics using special techniques and tasks.

The role of educational cooperation in the formation of students' skills of independent educational activity. In its extremely developed form, the ability to build educational cooperation coincides with the ability to learn - to independently expand their own knowledge, skills, abilities. Designing lessons by several types: designing an educational problem, planning and finding a solution, concretizing and applying the method for solving particular problems, monitoring and evaluating the measure of ownership of the method, as well as according to the proposed form of the "lesson" plan: lesson stage, teacher activities, student activities, methodical commentary.

The idea of such lessons is to create conditions for the teacher to maximize the impact of the educational process on the development of the student's individuality. Their implementation is possible in the event that the following are selected as the targets of the training sessions:

- The formation of a system of scientific knowledge among students and their mastery of the methods of human activity based on actualization and "cultivation" of their subject experience;
- Assisting students in finding and acquisition of their own individual style and pace of learning activity, disclosing and developing individual cognitive processes and field of interests;
- Assistance to the student in the formation of a positive self-concept, the development of creative abilities, mastering the skills and abilities of self-knowledge and self-construction.

Modern higher education is going through a new stage MOODLE, European Credit Transfer and Accumulation system in its development. The growing volume of information, modernization, and complication of curricula make the student the highest demands. Any teacher knows very well that students of the same age differ significantly from each other not only in their abilities, the rate of assimilation of knowledge, but also in terms of working capacity, in terms of fatigue under the same

load. Therefore, it is very important that the trainees go through this difficult path, first, without prejudice to their health, without losing interest in learning, without losing faith in themselves, in their strengths. Moreover, this is possible only with a personality-oriented approach in teaching and educating students.

The implementation of a personality-oriented approach to teaching allows, because of a comprehensive study, to create ideas about the character of each of them, about his interests, abilities, the influence of his family and the immediate environment on him, to get the opportunity to explain the act and his attitude to learning in general. Since there are no ready-made recipes in teaching and upbringing, the problem of a personality-oriented approach is of a creative nature. In addition, its necessity is connected, first, with the individual capabilities of each student.

The lesson is the main element of the educational process, but in the system of student-centered learning, its function, the form of organization, changes. A personality-oriented lesson is not only an orientation towards the assimilation of a certain amount of knowledge by students, but also the development of his personality, his cognitive and creative abilities. The purpose of the personality-oriented lesson is to create conditions for the cognitive activity of students. Recognition of the student as the main actor in the entire educational process is, in my opinion, the essence of personality-oriented pedagogy. Solving the problem of revealing the individual abilities of students through a student-centered lesson, we are faced with the resolution of contradictions:

- 1) Between the requirements of the concept of primary education and the real learning outcomes due to the low cognitive activity of students;
- 2) Between the individual way of assimilating knowledge and the mass nature of education;

The relevance is due to the educational activity itself, the renewal of the content of education, the formation in students of methods of independent acquisition of knowledge, the development of activity. Without basic motivation, without the

awakening of interest, the development of knowledge will not happen. Based on this provision, the principles of pedagogical activity are determined, which are necessary for the conditions for the development and improvement of the student's personality:

- 1) The use of the student's subjective experience;
- 2) Actualization of existing experience and knowledge as an important condition that contributes to the understanding and introduction of new knowledge;
- 3) Variability of tasks, providing the student with freedom of choice when performing them and solving problems, using the most significant methods for working out educational material;
- 4) Providing in the lesson personally meaningful emotional contact between the teacher and students based on cooperation, creating the “friendly atmosphere” among the learners, motivation to achieve success through the analysis of not only the result, but also the process of achieving it;
- 5) Generating a situation of success (at each lesson, the student should feel the joy of the successfully completed work);
- 6) Creating a favorable atmosphere for productive search activity (compassion and understanding on the part of the teacher, posing problematic questions that spark and interest learners).

In order to improve the educational results of each student, we must create motivation for him. Our task is to build a school of success for each student. That is why we are talking about educational trajectories, a differentiated approach, and a targeted approach. However, if you do not build such a targeted approach to each teacher, the success of each individual student will not work out.

Humanism, individual approach, communication skills, learning activities. As an example "Workshop technology". A group of French teachers “French group of new education” practices the technology of the workshops; it is based on the ideas of free education of J.-J. Rousseau, L. Tolstoy, S. Freinet, the psychology of humanism of L. S. Vygotsky, J. Piaget, K. Rogers.

In the technology of workshops, the main thing is not to communicate and master information, but to convey the methods of work, whether it is natural science research, textual analysis of a work of art, research of historical primary sources, means of creating works of applied art in ceramics or batik, etc. a very difficult task for a teacher. All the more grateful are the results expressed in the mastery of creative skills by students, in the formation of a personality capable of self-improvement, self-development.

Target guidelines: provide students with psychological tools that allow them to develop themselves personally, to realize themselves and their place in the world, to understand other people, as well as the laws of the world in which they live, the prospects of the "future" that will affect them.

Features of the content: a workshop as a local technology covers a greater or lesser part of the content of an academic discipline. It consists of a series of tasks that direct the work of the learners' in the right direction, but within each task, the students are absolutely free. Each time they are forced to make a choice of the path of research, the choice of means to achieve the goal, the choice of the pace of work, etc.

A workshop often begins with updating everyone's knowledge of a given issue, which is then enriched with the knowledge of group mates. At the next stage, knowledge is corrected in a conversation with another group, and only after that, the group's point of view is announced to the class. At this moment, knowledge is once again adjusted because of comparing its position with the position of other groups.

An algorithm is a formalization of a technological process in the form of a sequence of some steps, blocks of activity that depend on the content of the cognitive area, but also have a prior-subject part, which is determined by the methods of student activity common to all areas.

On April 14, 2020, the Head of the Education and Skills Department of the Organization for Economic Cooperation and Development (OECD), Special Adviser to the OECD Secretary General on Education Policy, one of the founders of the largest international comparative study of the quality of education PISA made a

speech at the XVIII April HSE International Scientific Conference. Andreas Schleicher. In his report, “Global trends in the transformation of national education systems, what will education be like in 2035?” A. Schleicher described 10 key factors for the success of the development of education systems for the next two decades:

- * Information literacy.
- * Application of talents.
- * Less is better, but deeper.
- * Equal access to education.
- * Exchange of experience between teachers.
- * Rejection of system control.
- * Individualization of education.
- * High productivity of studies.
- * New quality assessment.
- * Borrowing the best.

Students were asked to make their own decisions, and not just state the correctness or incorrectness of judgments - this meets the requirements for the development of independence and responsibility in the learning process, a non-standard approach to professional activity. Evaluation of the results of the design of pedagogical technologies with a focus on the selected criteria. The designed pedagogical technologies correspond to the selected criteria.

Thus, the didactic goals set during the design of pedagogical technologies aimed at solving the problems of the learning process can be considered as an achievement. The creative level of mastering the educational material is ensured through the choice of the didactic component of pedagogical technologies: the content of the designed tasks, as well as direct discussion of them in the process of conducting a learning game (choosing an organizational form of training).

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standard approach to professional activity. Evaluation of the results of the design of pedagogical technologies with a focus on the selected criteria. Thus, the didactic goals set during the design of pedagogical technologies aimed at solving the problems of the learning process can be considered achieved. The creative level of mastering the educational material is ensured through the choice of the didactic component of pedagogical technologies: the content of the designed tasks, as well as direct discussion of them in the process of conducting a learning game (choosing an organizational form of training).

The professional activity of any skilled worker and specialist necessarily includes a number of actions, for the performance of which unconditional clarity, systematized knowledge, and practiced skills are required. The reproductive methods used in this case, associated with simple reproduction of information, even without its transformation, give the learning process monotony, because students to lose motivation and, as a result, a negative attitude towards the information itself will grow.

Formulation of design goals (requirements for pedagogical technologies). Experimental work has shown that pedagogical design is an endless process, in this regard, motives for improving the training course can be motives:

- internal motives - striving for professional self-realization;
- external motives - advanced training or changes in the external conditions of pedagogical activity (change in the composition and nature of external requirements for the course, change in hours for classroom lessons, etc.), the vagueness of the boundaries of the existence of pedagogical innovations.

It is not always possible to fully implement in practice what was conceived in the work program of the academic discipline due to the unavailability of both the socio-pedagogical environment, and the teacher himself to follow his own project in practice, which requires him to spend more than usual on restructuring the usual rhythm of classes, refusal from stereotypes in teaching; the complexity and ambiguity

of determining the results of innovations, and also much depends on the personality of the students.

Conclusion: The main criteria for comprehending and evaluating what is observed in the lesson:

- the effectiveness of the work of each student in achieving the planned results;
- formation of students' independent thinking, initiative;
- the effectiveness of the lesson in the implementation of the tasks of spiritual and moral education;
- teacher's activities for the development of student activities.

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THE ESSENCE OF CRITICAL AGE HYPOTHESIS IN SECOND LANGUAGE ACQUISITION

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Abstract. Many studies of second language acquisition look at how the first language influences the production of the second, but studies that look at how the acquisition of a second language affects the first are rare. Some scholars argue that the second language cannot be acquired after puberty, while others argue that age isn't a factor being an obstacle to learn a new language and they assume that people in older ages may be successful as the ones whose minds are fresh (adults). The current paper aims at discovering the age and gender influence of second language acquisitions.

Key words: *acquisition, puberty, Critical Age Hypothesis, age, SLA, human's lifespan*

Second language acquisition is a complex process that is interested in all factors starting from age, gender to learner's interests, methods, techniques, etc. The main point of SLA is to gather information by observing learners' strategies, interests to find solutions in case of problems. Even though there are a plethora of topics grabbing attention to discuss, the influence of age on the learning process is the pivot of this research. This is very topical in contemporary society in which people after puberty people show interest in acquiring a foreign language, or parents want their children to speak in other languages from childhood before puberty.

This paper will probably entail information about the different successes and weaknesses of learners before and after puberty in second language acquisition. Even though there haven't been so much researches on the age influence of grammar, this paper will clarify whether young or old learners make progress faster in grammar.

Having read this article, a reader is likely to understand that older learners can perform also be as good learners as young learners. In the article, the utmost is to understand that age isn't a barrier for learners to master foreign languages and they may start learning at all ages.

According to Lenneberg (1967), there is a time in a human's lifespan where the brain starts to receive information at a slow tempo, while some linguists believe that brain doesn't stop working and a learner of old age is supposed to succeed as young learners. However, it is likely to be connected not only the age, but also with learner's life factors like at old ages people probably have little free time from work and family, or be shy in front of others to express their opinion not to be laughed at, or they want to share complex ideas, yet the lack of vocabulary makes them feel awkward. On the contrary, a young learner has enough free time and in this period they primarily tend to the educational process. Thus, they may commit to receiving extra knowledge.

Moreover, globalization is occurring around the world so rapidly that learning languages are also becoming so popular among people. Motivation also plays an enormous role in acquiring a new language not depending on age and can accelerate the process of acquisition. Older learners, for instance, set a goal of mastering one language if they want to be employed in a foreign country. Similarly, there are opportunities in bulk for young learners who willingly plan to go abroad to study since some institutions offer scholarships and grants for free or for some amount of money. All of them encourage people of different ages to learn a language as a tool of communication.

Concerning age and language acquisition, many types of research were conducted where some linguists put young learners as good ones, while some argued that older learners surpass them. To be more precise, Fledge (2006) has found that young learners perform better in phonology and morphosyntax and he proposed that learners can reach native likeness if the process starts before puberty. However, Slavoff and Johnson (1995) contradict Fledge indicating that age deviation doesn't

affect learners' success in phonology, morphology, and syntax. Besides, it is argued that young learners attain native-like abilities, yet second language acquisition from young stages doesn't guarantee that all young learners reach this competence.

Lenneberg (1967) as the originator of the concept Critical Age Hypothesis was interested in biological factors having relations with learning. According to him, learners between two and around puberty have well-developed receptive aptitudes which may lead to native-likeness in input production. Moreover, he claims that the younger is the learner, the more successful they are in the learning process and input processing starts to decline in the hemispheric lateralization in the brain after puberty. In contrast, Snow and Hoefnagel-Hohle (1978) experimented with people with old ages to clarify whether age had an impact on learning and they came to the conclusion that their exposure to learning a language was higher than younger ones. Besides, they proposed that motivation might be one of the key factors affecting learners' accomplishment in learning whether they were in the young or old stages of a lifespan.

Albeit the age effect occurs in mostly morphology, syntax, and phonology, this paper will underline the difference in morphosyntax. According to Johnson and Newport (1989), grammar acquisition emerges with a good speed till the age of 7, yet then a gradual decline in acquisition starts in the brain between seven and sixteen. Afterward, outcomes seem tedious in post-puberty. Nevertheless, Bialystok and Hakuta (1999) have found that grammar engages older students more in which they experience similar structures in L1 and they endeavor to produce L2 grammar the same as L1 firstly. Periodically, they discover peculiarities of each and the application of L2 grammar starts to be in the process even with fossilization after a short period. Moreover, De Keyser (2000) holds the view that grammar cannot be acquired without explicit, analytic, problem-solving capacities. On account of life experience, older learners develop those abilities leading to progress in grammar.

For this research, Saya and Max were chosen with the age of 12 and 39 respectively. The former is a young girl who studies art and music at a specialized

school of art. By nature, Saya is an introvert who prefers being alone all the time. However, she burns with the curiosity of art and she invariably surrounds herself with talented people. On the contrary, Sam seems to be an extrovert with a good sense of humor. In reality, his character is outgoing and he always energetic to start exciting adventures. Neither Saya nor Max speaks English well and even they have a little background experience of English. Saya, for instance, studies at school where French is implemented into educational package and students are taught this subject twice a week. Even though French is given as mandatory, she isn't interested in these languages and she doesn't spend time learning French at all. Similarly, Max also learned German at school times, and from that time he hasn't attempted to drive his level from pre-intermediate to advanced. Ergo, his German remained constant without further development.

Although there is no relic of English in their life from the retrospective, the zone of proximal development(ZPD) aided them to be slightly acquainted with this language. Having analyzed experimented learners' life, it was ostensible that both participants opted to be ambitious and single-minded since they attained numerous achievements in their life. To clarify, Saya was awarded in many Republican contests including “Iste'dod” with a gold medal, in “Zulfiya” with the third placement which enabled her to achieve public recognition. In terms of Max, he was military when he was young and his title firstly was an ordinary soldier, yet periodically he showed his talents and later he was named as a colonel. Nowadays, with the development of the economy and politics of great powers, the demand for English is also increasing. Thus, the participants displayed an eagerness to learn English from the start to catch up with their friends.

Having a lack of information about participants' level, I decided to interview to detect whether they know frequently used words or it was problematic for them to understand the utterance. In this interview, I had prepared ten yes/no questions in order not to make them feel under pressure when they were asked to give full answers. Questions dealt with life, work, study, surroundings of the learners. Having

dissected the interview, it was obvious that the participants were in the elementary level, yet it also clarified that using their affective factor-like friends, siblings, parents, who knew English, their reception of discourse was somewhat improved.

Speaking about John, he also seems to have abilities to learn a language with his analytical skills and good memory. When he was asked questions, the answers weren't given promptly, but deliberately. Undeniably, it appears that reaching native-likeness is possibly difficult for him as his articulation has already been formulated, and in his speech, he tended to put the stress on the last syllabus of the word when he wanted to ask something. His level looks like A1 as Tina's.

After gaining information about the level of the learners, GTM (Grammar Translation Method) was applied to use in which "To be" and "Present Continuous" were the topics of the survey. It should be admitted that the audio-lingual method was to be implemented, yet it was supposed to overburden learners whose level was vague. Thus, GTM replaced that method having taken into account its convenience, namely usage of L1, drilling, repetition, to the learners.

A ten-day process of grammar teaching was split into 3 steps, including explanatory, practical, and checking parts. Initially, the learners acknowledged the rules of the aforementioned grammar elements. Subsequently, they were provided a timeline to practice them inside with some topic-based exercises and outside the classroom by recording their voice (all used materials are attached to the appendix part). Moreover, that step assisted them to relate and find alternatives of "to be" and "Present Continuous" in their mother tongue. Lastly, when this input processing reached its end, our processing started to dominate. For this step, a Jeopardy game has been implemented with two determinations, such as to show the learners how technology may be incorporated in the educational context and make the checking process with a little contest between these two participants.

Afterward, when data was obtained about their level, the Grammar translation method with instructions of "To be" and "Present continuous" was supposed to start with. Firstly, they have explained the rules and their application in sentences. They

worked on these topics for several days by doing exercises, translating small texts with continuous actions, and finding present continuous from given text. During these periods, they acknowledged what was "to be", "Present Continuous" in their mother tongue. Before the interview, using the audio-lingual method was going to be the target method, yet results gained from it changed the way into Grammar translation one. One of the peculiarities of this method is using L1 in the teaching and learning process not to overburden learners with a language they don't know.

After a few days of training, the revision game “Jeopardy” was displayed to check the input. In this part, there were two sections (Section 1-To be and Section 2-Present Continuous Tense) with five queries in each. The questions were hidden behind the numbers (100, 200, 300, 400, 500) and when a learner was asked to open one number from any section, they were supposed to answer that question and collect numbers. They took turns to open numbers. Frankly, it was both an informative and interactive game for learners to examine what they had learned.

The interview was one of the most crucial parts of data collection as it was able to elucidate learners' strengths and weaknesses. For instance, Tina's imitation was a notable feature that might aid her to master the English accent without any difficulties. It was clear that she wanted to imitate how the interviewee pronounces and spells words and her attempts were close to the speakers. The reason for this may be her study at a specialized school of art where she is taught from vocal. Singers tend to practice with ears (they listen to a song live or use earphones for recorded audios) and mouth movement simultaneously which helped Tina to do the same in the interview. If she continues learning English intensively, it is supposed that she may learn it faster with her imitation talent.

During the interview, Tina explained that she wasn't so keen on learning languages, but her core aim was to improve vocally. Moreover, Not English but French is taught for them at school as a second language in which she can't see her progress. Since she is on musical tours abroad very often, her exposure to English is more than French. When she was asked permission to take part in this research, she

without any hesitation agreed to say that they were going to America after the pandemic to spread the fame of Uzbek folklore. Till that time, she is going to improve her English and the research was her first trial to learn the language intensively. Moreover, her English surrounded atmosphere will be also an aid for her to accelerate the second language acquisition.

Speaking about John, who is smart and nimble, he is also surrounded by English-speaking friends and acquaintances helping him to make success in language learning. When he was asked about participating in the research, he expressed his resolution from being committed to it. According to him, they have a meeting that will be held in the United Arab Emirates in January and he will have to speak to his partners there. He stated that in previous events, he used to miss a lot of information that led to some eventual problems. Therefore, he is aimed at participating in the survey to enlarge his English performance. However, he also mentioned that he didn't want to acquire a new language sacrificing his native language that was common among youngsters, yet he wanted to be an additive bilingual. From his speech, it was clear that his friend impacted him by adding English words into his bank of vocabulary which was seen in his comprehension of most words of the interview. Unlikely, Tina's vocabulary needed to be enhanced since she asked to repeat the question several times, but her speaking was much better than John's who kept on talking English with Uzbek intonation, accent, and pauses. All in all, both of these participants have similar cases to learn the language, like being surrounded by an English environment. Even though they fossilize English by mixing Uzbek, their effort is making them explore English promptly. Furthermore, English songs in their playlist may foster second language acquisition. The scrip of the interview is provided in the appendix part.

It should be admitted that the audio-lingual method was to be implemented, yet it was supposed to overburden learners whose level was vague. Thus, GTM replaced that method having taken into account its convenience, namely usage of L1, drilling, repetition, to the learners. In the initial stage, the learners were explained how to why,

how, and when to use "to be" and "Present Continuous" which was followed by interconnecting these two elements of grammar. Indeed, those topics were chosen deliberately for their interrelation as to form Present Continuous the verb "to be" is demanded and it is altered according to the subject of the action that was instructed to the participants. From the endeavors of the learners, it was transparent that they were engrossed in English and it seemed that they may reach their aims of English learning with their curiosity. Nevertheless, they also encountered some problems, like Tina found it challenging to form an interrogative sentence that made her think over before giving a question. On the contrary, John made minor mistakes in the practice part and it was for his more analytical skill and experience gained throughout his life. It showed that learners after puberty have developed metacognitive strategies and second language acquisition may also be successful as in the learners' before puberty. Moreover, he draws a schema for his comprehension and was active after watching videos related to the topic, but it was so to his creativity and self-study. Unlike John, Tina limited herself only to classroom-based and provided rules, examples not adding something extra.

After mastering "to be" in which they tried to use it with different personal pronouns, the participants were instructed how to form "Present Continuous" by adding "ing" to the verb which is corresponded to "to be". To comprehend it with exercises, a gap-filling is given to them to form Present Continuous with provided bare infinitives. The activity caused some problems due to the lack of vocabulary for the participants who had to look up a couple of words from a dictionary that was unknown to them. Subsequently, the task was checked altogether and it revealed that Tina's pronunciation and reading were better than that of John. However, her results weren't as accurate as John's as she made relatively more mistakes. John accomplished the task with approximate error-free thanks for his additional commitment outside the classroom. Nevertheless, his pronunciation was one of his weak points that needed more concern. That is perhaps for his L1 articulation usage all the time in his life and he got used to speaking in that language that halts him to

reach native-like pronunciation of words. His speech may give a feeling that the nonnative speaker is talking.

Coming to the following task, pictures with some actions were provided to the learners in the handout and their task was to form an interrogative sentence by replying to them. In this task, again John's performance was successful than Tina's who made three mistakes out of six. The process was continued with different a picture depicting various settings, namely fishing man, lying woman on the beach, a woman drinking lemonade, girls playing with the sand. There was the provision of statements that were incorrect and the task was to correct them with. John skillfully did the task in a couple of minutes by applying the rules correctly, while Tina couldn't find and correct all the mistakes because of inattentiveness during the classes. That also showed that how older the person, the more cautious and attentive he is in gaining input, learning a language. Perhaps, John made progress because he used to practice all the rules with his friends by sending the recording to check his speech. Conversely, Tina confined herself with the class materials only, and this quite common among young learners who show a lack of extra effort besides the classroom. What is more, she wanted an excellent speech and put the stress only on speaking which reinforced her fluent pronunciation, but failed inaccuracy of the speech. It was clear as crystal that she can reach native likeness in speaking English but reach accuracy with some problems.

The third task was to translate a simple text into English using Present Continuous and To be. John made few mistakes which weren't covered to them yet (the article) and Tina made visible errors. It should be acknowledged that Tina's speech sounded more fluent than John's and Tina was able to put the word and sentence stresses in a proper way making her speech more coherent. The Grammar Translation Method was useful to work with beginners who need more instructions in their mother tongue and this kind of translator task, drilling may strengthen learner's comprehension of a foreign language. The tasks indicated that the age hypothesis isn't as problematic for the older generation to start acquiring a new language since

they may perform better than the young generation operating with analysis. However, it seems easy for learners before puberty to gain native likeness that is a bit impossible after puberty. The used materials are given in the appendix part.

Lastly, for the checking part, the "Jeopardy" game was implemented where "To be" and "Present Continuous" sentences were hidden behind the score that was to be gained by the participants. It is a good method for measuring comprehension with a contest among learners. The game comprises two sections separating To be and Present Continuous. Each of them included questions related to their own rule, but the questions were behind 100, 200, 300, 400, 500 scores. The learners were to select a score firstly and be shown a question to answer. By this, they were supposed to gather points and the learner with the highest score was to be the winner.

The procedure attracted the participants' attention and they tried hard to precede each other. Tina chose 200 points to put "To be" in "I and Jim...friends". To the misfortune, she had a misconception that Jim was the subject and put "is" instead of being. , John attempted to choose 300 points from "Present Continuous ", "I'm writing an essay now. Question?" and his attempt was successful. Tina's next question was to open the box in the negative sentence which gave her 200. The game proceeded in that manner and the participants were fully involved in it. According to the results, John's performance was successful as he managed to answer all the questions. However, Tina couldn't act as John which showed that she needed more practice. The portion of the results are given below in the chart:

The research exhibited that learners before puberty are more dependent on teachers who learn with repeating, drilling by concentrating only on what the teacher delivers, whereas learners after puberty tend to do more self-study and extensive research on the materials given during the class. The script of the game is provided in the appendix.

To do research and see whether age plays a pivotal role in learning and acquiring a language, a plethora of case studies, articles and dissertations were looked through. During that process, it was deduced that the theme is quite topical among scholars who share different points of view. Some linguists opine that a person's second language acquisition is effective when he/she starts from early years as in Lenneberg's hypothesis and if not, then they may not perform it well, while others presume that age isn't a factor triggering a problem for learners to get exposed to a new language. They claim that it depends on individuals how to make success in SLA regardless of age.

To check this ambiguity, the current research was done with two volunteers who were taught grammar rules, practiced, and measured their comprehension of the process. It was inferred that the brain is capable to perform well in SLA not only before, but after puberty as well. Undeniably, there are some discrepancies in the learning of young and older generations. For instance, the research showed that young learners may reach native-likeness and their articulation may be altered as a foreigner, while the old generation may reach the accuracy but not native-like speech. Nevertheless, learners after puberty have developed the analytical skills that help them to analyze and synthesize the input by thinking about the relations of one rule with another, whereas young learners are less attentive than old ones and they are likely to approach the rules, not in detail. Thus, young learners may have an instant improvement in phonology and

The research also drives a message that the learning process not considering the age can be accelerated with instrumental or integrated motivation. In the case study, Max states that he is eager to acquire a second language for visiting his aunt

dwelling in the United States of America. Saya also sets a goal to learn English to receive a higher education abroad which keeps her to stay motivated in an integrative way.

Having analyzed all factors, a conclusion has been made that Lenneberg's hypothesis may not be referred to all age learners that post-puberty learners' brain declines to store input and Snow and Hoefnagel-Hohle's opinions that learners in their old ages can also succeed seemed to coincide with the outcomes of this case study.

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TILNI YANGI O'RGANUVCHILARGA O'RGATISHNING ENG SAMARALI USULLARI

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Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqolada ingliz tilini o'rgatishning eng maqbul usullari haqida ma'lumotlar berilgan bo'lib, til o'rganishning boshlang'ich davrida bo'lgan talabalar qaysi metodlarni qo'llaganda til ko'nikmalarini tezroq hamda samaraliroq egallashi mumkinligi bayon etilgan. Bundan tashqari, maqolada o'rin olgan har bir til o'rgatish texnikasining qisqacha tarixi hamda guruhlar ta'riflab berilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: *ko'nikma, kommunikativ metod, axborot, kodlash, analiz, sintez, mantiqiy fikrlash, anglab tushunish metodi, teskari zanjir, filtr, tarjima metodi, oyna metodi*

Til o'rganish zamon talabi bo'lib qolgan bir davrda boshlang'ich til o'rganuvchilarida ko'nikmalarni hosil qilish hamda materiallarni qisqa vaqt ichida anglab olishga yordam beradigan metodlar ro'yxatini tuzish eng dolzarb vazifalardan biri sanaladi. Ushbu maqolada til o'rganishni endi boshlagan o'rganuvchilar uchun qo'llanilishi kerak bo'lgan eng foydali hamda natijali o'qitish uslublari tilga olinadi.

Zamonaviy til o'qitish uslublaridan eng ko'p qo'llaniladigan hamda tezroq natija beradigani bu Kommunikativ metod, ya'ni gapirish orqali tilni o'rganish. Ushbu metodni 1966-yil amerikalik lingvist va antropolog Del Haymes yaratib, yana bir qator hamkasblari tomonidan rivojlantirildi. Ushbu metodning asosiy maqsadi chet tilida ravon gapirishni o'rgatish bo'lib, bunda til o'rganuvchi o'rganayotgan tili bial o'rab olinadi, ya'ni o'z ona tilidan foydalanish ta'qiqlanadi. O'qituvchi o'quvchini xatolar qilishdan qo'rqqmaslikka da'vat etib, turli xil o'yinlar, qiziqarli mashg'ulotlar hamda rol o'yinlari tashkil etish orqali o'z fikrini o'rganayotgan tilida bayon etishni so'raydi. Boshqa metodlardan farqli o'laroq, kommunikativ metodda nafaqat tilni tushunish balki til yaratishga alohida e'tibor beriladi.

Til o'rgatish darslarida eng ko'p qo'llaniladigan o'qitish uslublaridan yana biri –bu vazifalarga asoslangan o'qitish hisoblanib, u Kommunikativ metoddan ajralib chiqqan. Bunda o'quvchilarga maqsadli vazifalarni bajarish buyuriladi va real hayotda kerak bo'ladigan ko'nikmalar shakllantiriladi. Bular qatoriga doktor ko'rigiga borish, mashhur odamdan intervyu olish, restoranga tashrif buyurish tez mijozlarga xizmat ko'rsatish guruhini chaqirish kabilar misol bo'la oladi. Bunday topshiriqlarni bajargan o'quvchilar chet elga yoki xorijliklar davrasiga tushib qolganda vahimaga tushmasdan, tezda vaziyatdan chiqib keta oladi. Ushbu uslubni mukammalashtirgan hind lingvisti Prahbu til o'rganuvchilariga beriladigan mashg'ulotlarni 3guruhga bo'lgan:

- 1) Bo'sh axborotni to'ldirish, ya'ni bunda axborot bir odamdan ikkinchi odamga, bir shakldan ikkinchisiga yoki bir joydan boshqasiga ko'chiriladi. Qisqa qilib aytganda ma'lumotni kodlash yoki tildan yoki tilga ko'chirish. Bunday mashg'ulot sirasiga talabalarni juftlikka bo'lib, ma'lumotning birinchi yarmini bir o'quvchiga, qolgan yarmini ikkinchi o'quvchiga bergan holda bir-biri bilan og'zaki suhbat qilib berilgan rasmning yoki matnning ikkinchi bo'lagini topish vazifasi topshiriladi.
- 2) Fikrlash talab etadigan mashg'ulotlar, ya'ni berilgan ma'lumotdan analiz, sintez, mantiqiy fikrlash usullari orqali yangi ma'lumot ishlab chiqarish.
- 3) Fikr-mulohaza mashg'ulotlar berilgan holat yuzasidan shaxsiy fikr hamda hissiyotlarni ifoda etishni talab etadi. Bunga misol qilib aks ettiruvchi tavsif(reflective description)ni olishimiz mumkin, bunda o'quvchi berilgan rasm yoki matn haqida o'z fikrini bildirishi kerak.

Navbatdagi samarali metod bu Anglab tushunish metodi (Comprehensive method) bo'lib, bir guruh amerikalik lingvistlar Harris Units, Stefen Krashen hamda Jeyms Asherlar tomonidan ishlab chiqilib mukammallashtirilgan. Bu metod asosiy e'tiborni tilni ishlab chiqarishdan ko'ra tushunishga qaratadi. Ya'ni bunda o'rganilayotgan tilda matnlar o'qish, audiolar eshitish, so'zlarning to'g'ri talaffuzi ustida ishlash, videolarni subtitrlar bilan ko'rish kabi mashg'ulotlar o'quvchilarga taqdim etiladi hamda ularga tilga ko'nikish uchun jimjitlik davri beriladi. Bu davr mobaynida o'quvchilardan tilda so'zlashish, o'z fikrini bayon etish talab etilmaydi, ular o'zlarini yetarlicha tayyor deb his qilishganda o'z xohishlari bilan gapirish ko'nikmalarini namoyon etadilar. Tushunish yondashuvining eng muhim tamoyillaridan biri bu ma'lumot yig'ish davri tushunchasidir. Ma'lumot yig'ish davri o'quvchining nutq qobiliyatiga yetarlicha ishonmaydigan yoki gapirishni boshlash uchun tilni yetarli darajada bilmagan vaqtini anglatadi. Shu vaqt ichida o'quvchilar iloji boricha oddiy ma'lumotlarga duch kelishadi va ularning ongida grammatik qoidalar va tarjima qilinadigan tilning so'z boyligi shakllanib boradi. Ular ko'proq til ko'nikmalariga ega bo'lib, asosiy grammatika va so'z boyligini yig'gandan keyingina tilda gaplashishni boshlaydilar va muloqot qilishga harakat qiladilar. Ushbu

yondashuv asoschisilaridan biri Krashen ikkinchi tilni o'rganish birinchi tilni o'rganishga o'xshaydi deb taxmin qildi. Va anglab tushunish va jimjitlik davri o'quvchilar o'zlarining til haqidagi tushunchalarini shakllantirishlari va gaplashishdan oldin bu aloqalarni o'rnatishi uchun juda zarur edi. Jimjitlik davridan tashqari yana bir muhim konsepsiya - samarali filtr g'oyasi. Stiven Krashen o'quvchilarning hissiy holati ularning ongida zaruriy aloqalarni o'rnatish qobiliyatiga jiddiy ta'sir ko'rsatishi va tilni xohlagancha tezda o'rganishiga to'sqinlik qilishi mumkin degan fikrni ilgari surdi. Talabalar ko'p miqdordagi tashvish yoki stressni his qiladigan ya'ni samarali filtr yuqori bo'lgan holatlar o'quvchilarning e'tiborini tilga qaratishni qiyinlashtiradi, chunki ular o'zlarining yetishmovchiligiga ko'proq e'tibor berishadi. Ta'sirchan filtrni pasaytirish yoki o'quvchilar his qilayotgan stress va xavotirni kamaytirish orqali siz ularning tilga e'tiborini va shu bilan tilni o'rganish qobiliyatini oshirasiz deydi. Talabalarga jimgina davrni berish, ularga so'zlashish talab qilinmasdan oldin tilni tinglashlari va o'zlashtirishiga imkon yaratib, filtrning ta'sirini pasaytiradi va talabalarga tezroq tilni egallashga yordam beradi.

So'zlarning to'g'ri talaffuz etilishi hamda gap strukturasi o'rganishda Audio-lingual metoddan foydalanish yaxshi natija beradi, chunki so'zlarni hamda gaplarni eshitib ularni takrorlash o'quvchilarga ularni yaxshi eslab qolishga yordam beradi. Teskari zanjir texnikasi qiyin so'zlar yoki so'z birikmalarini o'rgatishda yaxshi natija beradi, chunki bunda uzun so'z oxirgi bo'g'inidan boshlab avval o'qituvchi tomonidan so'ngra esa talaba tomonidan takrorlanadi. Masalan, Incomprehensibilities so'zini birdaniga talaffuz qilish mushkullik tug'ilganda oldin-sibilities, keyin – comprehensibilities, va nihoyat incomprehensibilities so'zlari takrorlanadi.

Tilni umuman bilmaydigan hamda ushbu til muhitiga tushib qolganda o'zini noqulay his etadigan talabalarga Tarjima metodi dastlabki davrda juda yaxshi samara beradi. Chunki talaba o'z ona tilidagi tarjima bilan so'zni solishtirib, yodlaganda uni yaxshi eslab qoladi. Tarjima metodining bir nechta usullari mavjud bo'lib, bular qatoriga oyna metodi va sendvich texnikasi kabilar eng ko'p uchraydigan texnikalar sanaladi. Oyna metodi so'zlarni so'zma-so'z tarjima qilishni til ta'limida

moslashtirishdir. Maqsad chet el konstruktsiyalarini o'quvchilar uchun ravshan va shaffof qilish hamda ko'p hollarda ularni grammatik tahlilning texnik terminlari bilan chalkashtirmaslik. Ushbu usul asosan so'z birikmalari yoki qo'shma so'zlarni tarjima qilishda yaxshi natija beradi, chunki o'quvchilar qo'shma so'zning har ikkala qismi alohida tarjima qilish bilan uning ma'nosini keltirib chiqarishadi. Masalan, fire fighter so'zma-so'z tarjima qilganda olov kurashchisi deb tarjima qilinadi, idiomatik tarjimada esa o't o'chiruvchi bo'ladi. Keyingi tarjima metodi sendvich deb atalib, u idiomatik tarjimaning og'zaki variant sanaladi. Bunda aytilayotgan gap darhol og'zaki ravishda tarjima qilinib ketiladi.

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COMMUNICATIVE APPROACH IN LANGUAGE TEACHING

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Abstract. The Communicative approach emphasizes the ability to communicate the message in terms of its meaning, instead of concentrating exclusively on grammatical perfection or phonetics. Therefore, the understanding of the second language is evaluated in terms of how much the learners have developed their communicative abilities and competencies.

Key words: *notion, language competence, spontaneous situations, retention, deductive teaching method, concept, inductive teaching method, interpersonal activity.*

What is communication? Communication is first exchanging opinions, information, notions of social, cultural, political and other aspects of everyday life. The world around us is the world of communication in various spheres. And only at language lessons the only means of communication are textbooks and the lecturing teacher. In the classroom, the teacher is the source of information. And this communication is under control rather than free. In this case, the purpose of a teacher is to transform the communication with students to a pleasant, attractive and emotional lesson.

Real communication is always informative, unpredictable and unexpected. If the teacher is always informative, interesting and unexpected, then even before the beginning if the lesson students will be disposed for a good lesson. But if the previous lesson is just the same as the next one, students will be bored with it before

the lesson start. Even the most trivial dialogue can be transformed to a communicative one if no one knows a word of what will be said about. If the dialogue starts: A: - How are you? B: - And you? Then it all can be boring, definite and predictable. This dialogue is not informative, and rather similar to those, which the students must learn by heart in terms of a prepared situation recipe. By contrast, the dialogue below is unpredictable, interesting and informative: A: -How are you? B: -Is it true, that you... or A: -What is the result of the match? B: - Tell me, where I can get repaired my Japanese TV set? It broke down in the middle of the match [1].

The answer is unexpected and related to the questions only associatively. During a language lesson, such dialogues can reflect spontaneous situations. Those unexpected dialogues are communicative and built according to the scheme "stimulus - response". This principle stimulates active thinking process, intuitive thought and use of language in the frame of fixed communicative habits.

Communicative language teaching makes use of real-life situations that necessitate communication. The teacher sets up a situation that students are likely to encounter in real life. Unlike the audio-lingual method of language teaching, which relies on repetition and drills, the communicative approach can leave students in suspense as to the outcome of a class exercise, which will vary according to their reactions and responses. The real-life simulations change from day to day. Students' motivation to learn comes from their desire to communicate in meaningful ways about meaningful topics. The communicative approach could be said to be the product of educators and linguists who had grown dissatisfied with the audio-lingual and grammar-translation methods of foreign language instruction. They felt that students were not learning enough realistic, whole language. They did not know how to communicate using appropriate social language, gestures, or expressions; in brief, they were at a loss to communicate in the culture of the language studied. Development of communicative-style teaching started in the 1970s; authentic language use and classroom exchanges where students engaged in real communication with one another became quite popular. In the intervening years, the

communicative approach has been adapted to the elementary, middle, secondary, and post-secondary levels, and the underlying philosophy has spawned different teaching methods known under a variety of names, including notional-functional, teaching for proficiency, proficiency-based instruction, and communicative language teaching. Margie S. Berns, an expert in the field of communicative language teaching, writes that "language is interaction; it is interpersonal activity and has a clear relationship with society. Language study has become as the use (function) of language in context, both its linguistic context (what is uttered before and after a given piece of discourse) and its social, or situational, context (who is speaking, what their social roles are, why they have come together to speak) [2].

In communicative language teaching when teachers deal with grammar function they try to use more the inductive method of teaching grammar involves presenting several examples that illustrate a specific concept and expecting students to notice how the concept works from these examples. No explanation of the concept is given beforehand, and the expectation is that students learn to recognize the rules of grammar in a more natural way during their own reading and writing. Discovering grammar and visualizing how these rules work in a sentence allow for easier retention of the concept than if the students were given an explanation that was disconnected from examples of the concept. The main goal of the inductive teaching method is the retention of grammar concepts, with teachers using techniques that are known to work cognitively and make an impression on students' contextual memory unlike deductive method of teaching grammar, which is an approach that focuses on instruction before practice. A teacher gives students an in-depth explanation of a grammatical concept before they encounter the same grammatical concept in their own writing. Deductive teaching methods drive many students away from writing because of the tediousness of rote learning and teacher-centered approaches. Each teaching method is based on a particular vision of understanding the language or the learning process, often using specific techniques and materials.

Summing up, it should be pointed out what method to choose for your learners, depend on their background knowledge of a language. The usage of communicative approach in language teaching in classrooms shows that students are motivated to learn the language when they can use the language in communication. We, the teachers of foreign language should teach students not language but teach how to use language in communication.

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THE IMPORTANCE OF TEACHING ENGLISH IDIOMS

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Abstract. Teaching vocabulary is regarded as an important aspect of developing learners’ language skills and teachers are responsible for coming up with different ways of helping them memorize seemingly hard words in English. One of such challenges is connected with idioms, as idioms are rather tedious to learn by heart especially considering the variety of idioms existing in various spheres of life.

Key words: *grouping, idiomatic expression, contextualization.*

Idioms are significant cultural element of any language and it is considered an important stage in learning foreign language. An idiom itself is an expression that has figurative meaning from combination of certain words and cannot be translated directly when in collocation and different from the meaning of the individual words. Consequently, you cannot guess the meaning of an idiom from the words it contains. And so people experience problems while translating. However, idioms make speakers' language colorful and when non- native speakers use idioms in their speeches, they will sound very fluent. However it is not less important to use them correctly, otherwise speaker will “destroy” the phrase, and therefore teacher should approach to teaching idioms wisely and sparingly.

It will be better if teacher chooses the idioms that can be easily grouped, for instance, most of them fall into categories, like idioms with colors, animals or parts of the body. To succeed in teaching idioms from each category will be enough for the first time as overwhelming students will fail the process.

Idioms should be introduced in context, for example, in simple conversations, where the meaning of the idiom would be clear as student understands the situation where the idiom is used and give the synonyms for better comprehension. To introduce the idiom *Blue*, present a dialogue like following one:

-Sarah: Angela seems pretty unhappy these days, I wonder why she is feeling *blue*.

-Carlos: She has been pretty *blue* since her pet dog died.

-Sarah: Oh! Let's try to cheer her up.

Students may be asked to guess or figure out the meaning of the idiom from the context of the conversation and provide other examples of what it means *to feel/be blue*, and then teacher may give synonymic idioms, for example, *down in the mouth*.

The main goal is to get students not only understand, but also learn to use idioms effectively. Creating their own conversations using idioms and acting them out will help. In addition, teacher can teach idioms providing pictures to explain the context. This kind of exercises works best when pictures are colorful or humorous

illustrations. By showing pictures or flashcards and having students guess the meaning of the idiom you will help them to understand and make them laugh too.

It is important that teachers use real life, authentic materials to show learners how some idioms are used in newspapers and magazine articles, advertisements, videos or cartoons. First of all students must realize that native speakers always use idioms and they are closely related to culture realia, therefore they cannot be translated into mother tongue straightly. As it was mentioned above, idioms are the elements of culture and while learning language it is necessary to learn the culture of the country, which is language you are learning.

There are tens of thousands idioms used in English language and people whose first language is not English face problems in dealing with definitions. Besides, native English speakers in Great Britain sometimes cannot understand American idioms. Sometimes American idioms are known around the world, and sometimes an expression is known just in a particular state. As vocabulary and culture are linked together, speakers can gain more vocabulary through idioms and contrarily, can learn more about idioms from being unconcealed to the target culture.

An idiom's meaning can be influenced by culture, national coloring. There are many cases when idioms are based on an old prejudice, and the same prejudice may lead the listener or reader from other culture to misunderstanding. For instance, “*A black cat crossed her way*” would not mean the same things to people of different nationalities. To the English people a black cat means “good luck”, to Americans the opposite. Also the topics into which idioms are categorized are according to the culture, for example in America there are many idioms concerning sports and for people who don't understand American baseball, the expression ‘he struck out’ may have quite different, or no meaning. However, native speakers will know that this idiom is referred to someone who couldn't achieve a goal.

Many idioms were come from work and technology or referring to farm animals, such idioms like “*the black sheep of the family*” “*take the bull by the horns*”.

Some of them came to existence from literature and history. *Sour grapes, the goose that laid golden eggs*". There are some that came from feelings and emotions, for example, *give him a black look*. Also idioms can be formed from conjunctions, prepositions and nouns, for example, *ifs and buts, the ins and outs*. Verbs as nouns, the *do's and don'ts, on the make*. All these can easily confuse the learner.

As it was mentioned before, while learning idioms students should be given special tasks as making up dialogues, or situations using the idiom they have learned, it helps to develop their language skills. Moreover the main aim is to develop communicative competence, in order students could communicate in English in academic purposes and real life situations, also it develops socio-cultural competence, and therefore it is important to teach idioms in a correct way.

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DEVELOPING LEXICAL COMPETENCE TEACHING ESP VOCABULARY

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Abstract. This article considers the problems of teaching English vocabulary for specific purposes. The author reveals theoretical questions and suggests some practical activities

Key words: *ESP vocabulary, specific terminology, subject, integrated.*

Vocabulary is obviously a very important element within a language as the overwhelming majority of meaning is carried lexically. The most relevant issue of teaching vocabulary is to make a research for the proper tools in this process and applying them in the classroom with the purpose of giving them to the students, namely, to provide them with a large and rich vocabulary to be successful not only in educational terms, but also in life as overall.

English is learnt and taught in many different contexts and in many different class arrangements. Such differences will have a considerable effect on how and what it is we teach.

Learning a language cannot be reduced, of course, to only learning vocabulary, but it is also true that «no matter how well the student learns grammar, no matter how successfully the sounds of L2 are mastered, without words to express a wide range of meanings, communication in an L2 just cannot happen in any meaningful way.

Learning vocabulary is a rather more complex process than it might at first sight appear. It does not mean acquiring the same amount of knowledge for every word in a language. After all, we must take into account that even native speakers of a language can understand many more words than they actually use.

There are different things that can go wrong in learning vocabulary. Probably the most basic type of problem is the inability to retrieve vocabulary that has been taught. In this situation either communication breaks down altogether or else the student has to convey the message in a different way by drawing on his strategic competence. The use of vocabulary inappropriate to a given situation is another fault. Thus, for instance, «right / left» are usually acceptable ways of indicating direction, although not on a ship, where «starboard / port» are more appropriate.

Another common error is the use of vocabulary at the wrong level of formality, e.g. «Be seated, ladies and gentlemen» vs. «Sit»; or possessing the wrong kind of vocabulary for one's needs, e.g. academic instead of conversational English. It is clear then that learning vocabulary is something more than just memorizing lists of words.

When making decisions about content, one of the first questions the language teacher will have to address is what vocabulary to teach. For many of them this will be determined by the choice of the course book, the syllabus designers, or other factors. Even so, the teacher should be concerned about the different criteria used when designing their syllabuses and materials, the ones followed in making decisions about vocabulary content in language courses, and what the objectives of these particular decisions are. Otherwise, it becomes difficult to evaluate syllabus and materials, to understand why particular vocabulary is to be taught as well as to explain to learners why they must learn particular words. Nowadays, different criteria can be employed to select the particular words to be taught, but before dealing with this it is important to point out that every teaching situation is different and so essential items in one context may be quite useless in another (for example, in ESP). The relative importance we attach to the various criteria will therefore depend on our own teaching situation.

The criteria which may be used to select vocabulary are as follows: it seems self-evident that it is sensible to teach the most frequent words in any language before the more unusual ones are taught as they are likely to be the most useful ones for learners of that language. But frequency is a more complex matter than it looks, and it is unlikely that any syllabus or course book would want to stick to frequency lists alone.

If we want to organize our vocabulary teaching on a subject basis it may be a good idea to work out what the most frequent words are in that subject area either intuitively, with the aid of teachers of other subject matters (ESP), through the study of a limited set of related texts or with the help of a dictionary, for example, topic dictionaries.

A word may be quite frequent, but a majority or even all of its occurrences might be in just one or two texts. In this case, although its frequency might look significant, its range might be quite small. The most useful words for the learner then are those which are frequent and occur across a wide variety of texts.

Another area of classroom language has to do with the items which often appear in language activity instructions. Although constant exposure alone usually guarantees that these items will eventually be assimilated, it is possible to speed up the process by designing classroom activities containing many of these items and so avoid confusion or misunderstanding. It is possible for students to feel they need or to be interested in different words to those suggested by the teacher or course book, something to be taken into account for the sake of motivation. In fact, their needs or interests perhaps do not even coincide with those of the group or class. Our challenge here as teachers is to combine the collective and the individual.

It is also worth stating that, if the learner perceives the vital personal relevance of an item, he may acquire it whether the teacher pays great attention to it or not. On the contrary, the learner may consciously or subconsciously reject some of the items being taught.

Students enrolled at the University can take an English course, which is either general or ESP courses. From my teaching experience I can say that students face difficulties while learning new English words. It is difficult to learn words especially ESP words because they are low frequency words and are not encountered very often. Learning concrete words is easier than learning abstract words. Learners can more easily remember words like: peach, house, and horse if they appear on a list than words such as transmission and device.

In order to develop an ability to learn new vocabulary, for both general English and legal vocabulary in learning ESP (English for Specific Purposes), the students should become aware of the importance of language learning strategies and be trained to use them appropriately. The teachers put a lot of effort toward helping them to learn vocabulary related to their field of study.

It is widely believed that reading is the major source of vocabulary growth in L1. Students with strong reading skills who read a variety of texts may realize substantial gains in their vocabulary without direct instruction. These students may also realize some incidental vocabulary gains through independent reading, however.

I believe that ESP teachers should teach words. A suitable approach for teaching ESP words is the lexical approach. The lexical approach follows the principle that lexis is the most important part of any language and should be treated that way.

Most of the students taking ESP identify it with specific terminology related to their field of study. So, ESP relates to the learners, the language required and the learning context, and thus establishes the primacy of need. Need is defined by the reasons for which the student is learning English.

It is my opinion that language teachers who teach ESP courses should be familiar with the core vocabulary of the field of study and design curriculum that integrate both content area and English language. The teachers' responsibility is to follow different procedures suggested by researchers in this field and try to make the learning of words as easy as possible for the students.

All in all, teachers should strive to help learners become independent learners and show them there are many vocabulary learning strategies that can be used to learn ESP words.

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DEVELOPING INDEPENDENT LEARNING ON ENGLISH OF MEDICINAL AND PHARMACEUTICAL STUDENTS VIA BLENDED LEARNING

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Abstract. In this article, it is described that some samples for organizing students independent learning in pedagogical circumstances, it is also mentioned to increase educational efficiency and motivate students learning English, which related to their profession with forming innovative atmosphere. Blended learning plays an important role to improve learning English independently for the medicinal and pharmaceutical students.

Key words: *blended learning, independent learning, continuing education, intensive working, individual approach, Moodle distance teaching system.*

It is known that today being on the top of the world market and the improvement of socio-economic ties, the intensification of international relations also depends on the quality and skills of personnel. However, in the training of specialists in various fields, graduates of non-philological education must have sufficient knowledge, skills and qualifications in their specialties, but their low-level knowledge of foreign languages is a major obstacle to the development of interior and external infrastructure. In particular, although the level of foreign language proficiency of future medicinal and pharmaceutical staff is expected to be B2, according to state educational standards, but it is impossible to say that the level of language skills of non-philological students fully meets these requirements. One of the factors that make it difficult for specialists in the field of medicine and pharmacy to enter the world market is their low level of knowledge from foreign language. The analyses show that the majority corresponds to the range of A1 and A2 levels from

four strands on English among the first year students of higher institutions. This situation puts a serious problem in teaching students with different levels of English on a single state program and the diversity of professional areas in non-philological educational institutions raises the issue of developing textbooks and manuals for them. The formation of textbooks and manuals requires taking into account of different areas in the professional, social innovations, the needs of students, levels of knowledge and the requirements of the customer. However, the insufficiency hours from English in non-philological areas indicates the usage of distance education is one of the most effective and expensive way for hours, which given for independent study for students from English subject. Therefore, the development of forms of distance education has become the main essence of pedagogy, and the organization of independent learning activities of students through distance learning has become a pedagogical necessity.

The study of students with different levels of English in non-philological universities requires the organization of foreign language classes based on the principles of differentiated, individualized, and corporate (collective) and collaborative (pair) principles of education, as well as approach independently to students' independent learning. In such a situation, the educator will have to balance the levels of students through continuous and intensive work based on an individualized approach to education. In this regard, the opportunities of distance education are very wide and in the opinion of S.A. Mukhanov, “individualization can give a student the opportunity to choose their own path to study a particular course”.

It should also be noted that the exchange of ideas between students also educate them for the qualities of collaboration, cooperation, learning from each other and the sense of supporting each other. In the process of exchanging ideas, the students not only gather information provided by the teacher, but also have the opportunity to use the new thoughts and ideas of others. This process also increases their ability to analyze the independent opinions they have generated across their fields. However, in this case, the interaction of students and teachers will be

somewhat limited. In particular, Natalia Serdyukova and Peter Serdyukov argue that in online education, students have limited contact with the teacher, few opportunities to collaborate with their peers, and no opportunity for critical communication due to a lack of continuous and coherent collaboration with other team members. However, this can be easily done in a live audience atmosphere. Therefore, distance education also has its own difficulties and disadvantages.

It was also seen that the opportunities for offline learning are great in the formation of aspects such as teacher-student interaction, demonstration of knowledge and skills in practice, motivation, competition. At the same time, the prospects and effectiveness of distance learning depend on the Internet and its slow working prevents the full use of all the opportunities of distance learning. In some cases, even teachers themselves have understood that only putting their lectures or tests is enough for teaching from distance. Therefore, the full transition to the online mode has slightly undermined the quality of education and quality training. Due to the pandemic period, the academic year, in September 2020, began in the online education system of all higher education institutions of the republic. After almost half a year of online learning experience, it was observed that the level of knowledge of students decreased, students lost motivation to study. The reasons for this are, firstly, the unpreparedness of professors and teachers for distance education, some teachers, who are highly experienced in their field and have high knowledge and potential, do not have enough knowledge of information technology and need to use a separate assistant for using different software platforms when teaching online, in some cases, students do not have sufficient financial budget and on the other hand they are not ready to study independently, as a result of the inability to self-study and the inability to find a firm will to master the sciences independently, knowledge has become extremely empty. It was also acknowledged by the students that in traditional education, students' independent work outside the classroom is not at the required level, and its control is not organized correctly and objectively.

Today, the combination of online and offline education is the most convenient way to ensure the quality and effectiveness of education. The formed skills will be further strengthened and become qualifications. It seems that the situation that has arisen as a result of the conditions is leading to the reform of the educational process, a radical change in the attitude of both teachers and students to the educational process. Independent learning, creative approach to the acquired knowledge, individual work with each student, which is always behind the scenes, has become a basic principle of the educational process. In addition to online classes, educators have been able to constantly improve their skills through online webinars, conferences and seminars in their fields. As Nari Kim points out, the significant impact of offline learning combined with online learning is that many online courses focus on developing students' ability to work as part of a community and include presentations, projects, challenging situations, reports, debates, debates [1, 171] (Look at the 2.1-picture):

2.1- picture. Forming of Blended Learning

In the Blended Learning the teacher will be able to provide students with some of the materials that are not developed in the classroom as independent work. This process requires individual work with students, as well as individual work with students with low levels of foreign language skills and language skills, as well as the opportunity to give them assignments to work on those who have less language skills. Cem Balcikanli has also been able to engage students in the use of teaching materials through a combination of individual and pair research, to ensure a variety of classroom activities and homework through a variety of approaches, and to encourage students to work independently [2, 142]. It seems that in such a situation, the weight

of independent work is growing and becoming more and more individualized. Of course, this also increases the desire and interest of students to learn.

The online environment provides students with ample opportunities to use additional internet resources to fill in the gaps in their four types of speaking activities. Independent work done and submitted online on the Moodle platform will be stored for a long time. The comments and grades are sent to the students individually. Topics not suitable for medical-pharmaceutical direction, high level of difficulty of exercises, development of speech activity and formation of students' creative activity through independent study are not taken into account, which shows that this textbook is mainly adapted for students of philology.

According to I.A. Popova, the peculiarities of teaching English in non-philological universities, sectoral concepts and terms of maximum consideration of specific field goals, their lexical-syntactic and grammatical features, oral and written texts focused on specific professional goals and objectives, situational tasks is given. Topics that reflect modern professional problems and ways to solve them in practice should be based on the selected grammatical materials, as well as take into account the possible situations of communication with native speakers [3, 67]. Teaching distance communication is more complex, and it may not be possible to fully ensure that students learn English perfectly. In this case, the selected teaching materials, methods of organizing the learning process, tools taken into account the interests, knowledge levels, personal and sectoral needs of language learners help the teacher to effectively organize and manage the independent learning process of the subject. Independent learning of the language learner under the supervision of the teacher through distance learning becomes the leading subject of this process as an active participant who meets the requirements of educational technology from the subject of theoretical knowledge.

The main condition for the formation of independent work of students is the need to present the content and methods of teaching based on the practical needs of students, which requires in-depth study of medical and pharmaceutical goals and

objectives, taking into account the interests and motivation of students. Lack of motivation extinguishes the desire of students to learn a language. Batunova's comments also confirm our opinion: “Projects, festivals, theaters, scientific conferences organized by the Department of Foreign Languages on the basis of the institute in order to increase student activity not only increase students' interest in learning a foreign language, but also help to develop teamwork and other skills necessary for future engineers. Keep in mind that all activities other than training classes take a lot of time to prepare. But even the least participation in activities gives the student a sense of accomplishment, and when he succeeds, his activity increases, which leads to an increase in motivation” [4, 121]. Such increases in student motivation are especially noticeable when preparing presentations and when the student is working in groups. Collaborative creative activities bring students together and teach them to work collaboratively in a competitive environment. It also develops students' ability to speak in front of a large audience, expressing their opinions or critical views to people. Speaking in English, in particular, leads to a strengthening of self-confidence. Definitely, such requirements pose a challenge for the 1 course students with a lack of knowledge from English. For example, it may not be difficult for the 1 course students to gather new information if it is in their native language, but it is difficult to collect and analyze data in a foreign language and at the same time weaken motivation for subject.

The use of authentic materials enriched with real-life examples in the organization of independent work, the formation of basic skills in students for independent work is one of the first important issues. In the second place, it is effective to teach students to work together, to acquaint them with the production environment, to demonstrate team role-playing games on social and sectoral topics, to prepare interviews in hospitals, pharmacies, factories and organizations. The formation of such independent activity in medical-pharmaceutical students not only helps them to learn English effectively, but also helps to develop their professional competence. According to I.V. Sokolova, distance education is designed to realize the

right to education and knowledge, and provides equal opportunities for education through more active use of the scientific and educational potential of leading universities, institutes, training centers, additional education centers and other educational institutions. Distance education leads to the creation of favorable conditions for the development of the student as an individual by reducing the number of theoretical lessons and increasing the focus on independent study of the material. Distance learning provides students with the opportunity to quickly learn in a new environment, interact with each other at a distance, perform tasks intensively, study unexplored materials, increase their knowledge in new areas without limiting their area of interest [5, 98; 134]. For students studying in higher education institutions, it is necessary to make changes in the organizational aspects of independent work on the subjects covered at the end of each semester. Definitely, the teaching of English in the field of medicine and pharmacy is served based on modern methodological concepts aimed at improving the level of knowledge of students in the design of independent learning activities through distance learning, methodical recommendations enriched with authentic materials taking into account the interests of students.

Conclusion: to increase the effectiveness of independent learning, first of all, it is necessary to inform and didactic design of independent study hours and develop its methodological support. It should reflect the place of knowledge in the project, what principles and principles of didactics should be followed in the process, what types and stages of lessons, what methods, information technology and didactic materials should be used in the learning process.

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DEVELOPING COMMUNICATIVE COMPETENCE OF STUDENTS THROUGH TEACHING SPORT IDIOMATIC EXPRESSIONS

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Abstract. The present article aims at demystifying the cultural relationship of sport terms and expressions, which are used in different contexts in daily life communications. The British use lots of idioms in their speeches, which is tend to be quite difficult to understand by most of the English language learners.

Key words: *sports terms and idioms, linguistic competence, sociolinguistic competence, non-sporting situations, common culture, linguocultural traditions.*

In recent years, an extensive number of researches are being done to modify effective methods and approaches of learning foreign languages. The results show that traditional ways of foreign language learning which are based on developing only linguistic competence is not enough and suggest you should develop the other competencies such as sociolinguistic and pragmatic competencies as main parts of communicative competence. We tried to display the interrelationship of these competencies through the studies of some sport idioms and expressions in non-sporting situations. Members of common culture have a lot in common in the ways of

delivering, interpreting information based on their own social rules, rituals, traditions and customs. Moreover, every nation has its unique way of understanding and perceiving any sport or game in its own way, thus attaching some symbolic significance to it understandable within the scope of the linguocultural traditions of the country it has originated in. Our observations indicate that the wide use of sports idioms and expressions in non-sporting situations, particularly in everyday speech, may lead to misunderstanding in the communication because of a lack of sociolinguistic competence. “Obvious is the fact that the character and essence of cross-cultural interrelations depends, to a great extent, on the participants’ ability to understand each other in order to reach an agreement. It is also well known that mutual understanding is in most cases defined by the ethnic culture of each side and the psychology of the ethnic group.”³²

It is obvious that language is a mean of expressing one’s identity. Therefore, it is impossible to understand a foreign language unless you at least have some idea about the culture of the nation. On top of that, Native English speakers use all kinds of idioms. Idioms are expressions that say things that aren’t literal. If you don’t know someone is using an idiom, it might sound like they’re talking about something else. Idioms are essential for those who wish to become more fluent. Any student can get confused after watching some English TV shows or in the communication with English native speakers. He may know all of the words and their individual meanings, but he can not work out what they meant when put together. After all, even native speakers may not know every single idiom in the English language. The British love football, rugby and cricket, and they watch tennis once a year when it’s Wimbledon.

During our lessons, we often come across such kind of situation: some students who speak English very well whereas some speak like native speakers. Mostly, the

³² Gevorg Barseghyan. Sports idioms and their interpretation in different dimensions. *Armenian Folia Anglistika*. International Journal of English studies.

difference between them is related to the ability to understand idioms and cultural references and slip them into conversation.

Sports are a great source of enjoyment and competition for people around the world. There are many expressions related to sports in English that we use in our daily lives. We often use sports-related terms in our daily lives to describe moments of success, difficulty, failure and fairness. Reading and understanding definitions is helpful. But, the more you are **exposed to** idioms by hearing them used, the more understanding and using them will come naturally to you. Here we have given some sport idioms and their explanations to help you understand well and use them effectively in non-sporting situations.

Get the ball rolling – It is really common expression used in our daily life communications. Originally, if the ball is rolling in a ball game, it means the ball is in the game and the game has already started. Therefore, this idiom is often used when you are about to start something as in the meaning “start/begin” in situations not related to sports:

a) *I was held up in the bank. Accept my sincere apology for being late for the meeting. Let's **get the ball rolling**.*

b) *I always find some difficulties to **get the ball rolling** before knowing all details.*

That's not a cricket – this term means unsportsmanlike, unfair and dishonorable. Eric Partridge traced this term to 1867 but believed it was not widely used until the early twentieth century. Among the early references in print is Stanley Houghton's 1914 play, *The Partners*, “. . . *but it is not playing the game. In other words, Cynthia, it is not cricket.*” Although cricket is a sport popular exclusively in Great Britain and most of its former colonies, the term crossed the Atlantic and became a cliché in the United States as well. Cricket is one of the ethnic values which is idiomatically used in other spheres of life, and its significance is ascribed to the universal concept of fair versus unfair.

a) *I know you want to avoid confrontation, but **it's not cricket** to break up with someone by text message.*

b) *I don't see why you think **it's not cricket** – everyone else does it all the time.*

Keep one's eyes on the ball – this idiom originates from the game of baseball. Focusing on the ball is really important thing in the ball games. Losing your focus on the ball equals with your defeat and failure. To achieve any success you have to keep paying attention.

a) I wish you could **keep your eye on the ball** or you will never make any progress with your Italian.

b) To do well in this office, you'll have to **keep your eye on the ball**.

This is a slam dunk - A very forceful move. This term comes from basketball, where it denotes a strong and often dramatic shot in which the player leaps up and thrusts the ball into the basket from above. Both term and technique date from the 1960s, and by the 1980s the term was being used in business, politics, and other areas, both as a noun and as a verb (to slam dunk). So if something is a slam dunk, it is a sure thing; it is very easy thing to do/accomplish.

a) *So it's an easy decision. **It is a slam dunk**.*

b) *There's no doubt that he's guilty. **The case is a slam dunk**.*

Get into the swing of things - This idiom originated from tennis in the 19th century and means getting associated with anything is going on. If you get into the swing of things or get into the swing of it, you get used to doing something and you start doing it well or start enjoying it.

a) *She only started work last week, but she quickly **got into the swing of things**.*

b) *It didn't take people long to relax and **get into the swing of things**.*

Somehow the above mentioned sport idioms and expressions help us to reveal the problems on idioms as an obstacle for English learners. These problems deal with difficulties related to comprehension and usage of idioms and the connection of the language with culture. Idioms can be considered as an unseparable lexical unit and to

know its features characterized by linguistic competence of a learner whereas the sociolinguistic competence deals with idioms related to culture. The usage of idioms in speech based on contextual meaning is estimated as pragmatic competence. Our observations allow us to conclude that idiomatic expressions originating from sports will continue to be in great essence in the English language for international communication.

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AUTHENTIC VIDEO MATERIALS IN ESP TEACHING

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Abstract. The purpose of the article is to investigate the effectiveness of application authentic materials in ESP teaching at a higher school for enhancing future petroleum engineers' professional communication in English and improving their English proficiency.

Key words: *video materials, authentic, ESP*

Introduction. It is well known, that the oil and gas industry is the most international one, from geological exploration to chemical treatment and marketing,

including high-tech processes. This business involves specialists from a wide variety of fields, with production spreading all over the world. It should be noted, that the basic international language of the oil and gas industry is still English.

Despite the different language training of specialists, there is a consensus that teaching a foreign language is based on four skills: reading, writing, speaking and listening.

Recent studies have used authentic video materials taken in the target language. Our method offers videos filmed in Russian, which is the native language of the students. In order to understand the level of authenticity of our material, we need to figure out what is an authentic linguistic text in general.

According to Adams, Thomas W., materials are authentic if they represent immutable language data and are created by native speakers and shared with native speakers and, and not for learners of that language as a second. (What Makes Materials Authentic. Adams, Thomas W.) On the other hand, the term "authenticity" is associated with a concept that came from the Greek language. This concept indicates the correctness, authenticity, truthfulness of judgments, meanings, properties, views. This concept is interpreted in almost the same way by modern linguists. Authentic (adjective): valid, genuine, corresponding to genuine // ex. authenticity - and, well. Authenticity (noun) - from the Greek. [authentikos].

Authenticity, compliance with the original, the original source. The meaning of authenticity in the text, despite the similarity with the Greek original source, has certain significant differences.

The authenticity of the text can have a "narrowed" number of problems, for example: specific authorship, belonging to the genre in which the text is realized, the time frame of its creation and is related to such phenomena as the functional purpose of the text content, the meaning of the text as a means of linguo-cognitive knowledge of the world and the interpretation of the text by the recipient. (3)

In the theory of a speech act according to the classification of R.O. Jakobson, they distinguish the following basic options for the functions of using text to achieve

certain goals: representative; directive; phatic; expressive; aesthetic. We will analyze two of them, since they directly perform their functions in our learning process. The peculiarity of this function lies in the fact that by means of representation, the presentation of one object is formed by means of another. The representative function dominates in authentic texts both in importance and in the scope of its use.

The phatic function plays the role of a bridge from one communication participant to another. In authentic texts, the choice of means that implement the phatic function is ambiguous. Much depends on which reader the text is addressed to. The author sometimes has to adjust to the level of perception, emotional state, intellectual capabilities of the addressee, and the text gets some consumer coloring.

(3)

Thus, the authenticity of the situation filmed in the video by a specialist at production is not in doubt, and the great availability of this kind of information makes this material useful in its implication in teaching a foreign language to specialists.

In the context of the presented two functions of authentic material, representative and phatic, we can talk about a bias towards the development of translation skills of this audience, namely, teaching students to translate educational video materials as a subspecies of audiovisual translation. Educational video material is understood as a holistic audiovisual work aimed at facilitating the assimilation and consolidation of subject concepts by combining text and image, noise and music series and other methods of influencing the viewer. (1)

Educational video materials as an object of translation. Educational video material can be defined as a holistic audiovisual work aimed at facilitating the assimilation and consolidation of subject concepts by combining text and image. In educational videos, it is allowed to use such methods of influencing the viewer as noise and music series.

However, unlike entertainment audio-visual materials, the task of controlling the viewer's emotions is secondary here, although no less urgent. The main goal of creating and using educational audiovisual works is didactic, and in the first place is

the content, which includes scientific facts, concepts, concepts, statistical and other quantitative data, proper names, etc. Nevertheless, it is through the stimulation of interest and a positive emotional series due to the components accompanying information-factual content that a more effective assimilation of the material is achieved through audiovisual educational programs in comparison with traditional printed textbooks.

The curriculum of our university provides the following English textbooks for oil and gas engineers: Oil and gas, Oxford English for Carriers, parts 1,2; English for students of Petroleum Engineering, which provide excellent material for developing four basic skills. At the same time, in order to update and improve this material, we needed educational video material, which would be reliable information about the production process studied by our students.

Graduates and teachers of the university helped us in the preparation and collection of such video material. To create our lessons, we took as a basis short videos filmed at various stages of the production process, with comments by the authors in Russian. The tutorial program consists of 12 lessons starting with a video on a specific topic, relevant texts and subsequent exercises.

The purpose of the lesson is to reveal the topic and consolidate skills, the task is to master special vocabulary, develop critical thinking, communication and translation skills. In addition, the methodology has a psychological aspect in language learning - motivation by the professional success of yesterday's graduates and the consciousness of belonging to the profession.

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THE ROLE OF COMMUNICATIVE METHOD IN TEACHING FOREIGN LANGUAGES

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Abstract. This paper intends to describe communicative method, its brief history, application in the classroom as well as its activities. In fact, unlike conventional teaching strategies, this method greatly benefits to enhance communicative competence with the help of differentiated activities. Presently, in many institutions much emphasis is laid on employing this very method in order to encourage the learners to speak L2 more confidently. Before highlighting its importance in education, the author focuses on its way of emergence and usage in teaching along with the perceptions of other scholars. Overall, in a bid to succeed in the target language the implementation of communicative method is highly proposed by a host of teachers and other stakeholders.

Keywords: *communicative competence, communicative method, teaching strategies, language proficiency, concept, content, games*

Indeed, throughout the history of foreign language teaching techniques, there have been many attempts to find the most successful way of SLA and there has been a consensus that the communicative method of learning a foreign language is more productive to learn foreign languages as opposed to other approaches. Dating back to its history, it could be stated that the communicative method was introduced in the United Kingdom in the 1960s and 1970s, when English started to gain international recognition as a language of communication [1, 13]. The conventional methods that were widely employed at the time (audio-lingual, grammatical translation, and others) turned out to be insufficient to fulfill the needs of the foreign language learners. The explanation for this was a new group of students known as "pragmatists," who took a strictly functional approach to language as a communication tool, and what they expected was not a deep, systematic mastery of the language being learned, which was the goal of conventional learning programs, but the ability to put their experience into practice right away. In a bid to achieve this goal, the Council of Europe took a series of steps in the 1960s to establish a program to improve the teaching of foreign languages throughout Europe. A group of experts was tasked in 1971 with researching the feasibility of developing a method for teaching foreign languages to adult learners. In this respect, in 1971, the English specialist D. Wilkins was confronted with justifying the principles and content of a modern approach to teaching foreign languages, and in 1972, the Congress of Linguists and Economists of Europe, held in Stuttgart, reaffirmed the need for a new teaching method capable of addressing a critical sociocultural challenge-to achieve a high level of proficiency in a foreign language [2, 67]. Following that, in the 1980s and 1990s, a variety of research projects were carried out with the aim of developing a communicative education system. Project No. 12: "Learning and teaching modern languages for communication" took a prominent position among them. The communicative focus of training sessions and instructional materials used to teach a foreign language as a means of communication is given special emphasis in the integrated communicative method, which was systematized on the basis of theoretical

advances and practical experience in teaching foreign languages in the United Kingdom, France, Germany, Italy, Spain, and other Western European countries. Finally, three levels of initial (basic) language acquisition were identified:

Based on these levels, detailed standards and material have been established for a variety of Western European languages. The training materials were expected to develop linguistic competence (the ability to use linguistic units in accordance with communication situations), sociolinguistic competence (the ability to use linguistic units in accordance with social situations), and discursive competence (the ability to use linguistic units in accordance with communication situations) (the ability to understand and achieve coherence in the perception and generation of individual utterances), "strategic" competence (the capacity to compensate for language proficiency deficits by verbal and nonverbal means), socio-cultural competence (familiarity with the socio-cultural context of language functioning), social competence (ability and readiness to communicate with others). Since the 1970s of the twentieth century, there has been a surge of interest in communicative language teaching in Russia. Passov, his colleagues, and students conducted scientific research on such teaching. They coined the word "communicative method," which has its theoretical foundation in a number of scientific works [3, 233]. In a methodological textbook, V.G. Kostomarov and O.D. Mitrofanova substantiated "the concept of active contact as the leading principle of teaching a foreign language." Its content is revealed in more specific concepts that define the communicative method [4, 52]:

- practical orientation of training;
- functional approach to the selection and presentation of language material;
- situational-thematic presentation of educational material;
- study of vocabulary and morphology on a syntactic basis;
- concentric arrangement of educational material and highlighting several stages of training.

The communicative approach was aimed at teaching speaking at first. Its use has broadened dramatically in recent years, and it is now used to teach all forms of speech interaction, including productive (speaking, writing) and receptive (listening, reading). The communicative method as the ultimate goal of learning involves the formation of communicative competence, which consists of linguistic, speech, subject, socio-cultural and educational competencies. More precisely, the term "competence" first appeared in the works of American linguist N. Chomsky in 1972, and it is now used to describe general and precise educational objectives and content in language teaching methodology. It's important to differentiate between the terms "competence" and "competency." Shukin states that competence is "a complex of knowledge, skills, and abilities acquired in the course of classes and constituting a meaningful component of learning", whilst competency is "personality traits that determine their ability to perform activities based on the formed competence" [5, 212]. According to Fast, communicative competence is described as "the capacity and genuine readiness to communicate adequately to the aims, spheres, and circumstances of communication, readiness for verbal contact, and mutual understanding" [6, 18].

In our view, communicative language competence, when teaching a foreign language, is a body of knowledge about the language system and its units, their construction and functioning in speech, the ways of formulating thoughts in the target language and understanding the judgments of others, the national and cultural characteristics of the speakers of the target language, the specifics of various types of discourses; it is the ability of a language learner to communicate by means of his means in various types of speech activity in accordance with the communicative tasks to be solved, to understand, interpret and generate coherent statements.

For the improvement of CC of L2 users, the following methods can be applied:

- **Pair work.** It's also divided into two categories: "open" and "closed." Open work in a pair, depending on whether only one couple talks to the entire class, setting an example for others. Alternatively, the whole class can be split into pairs and work at the same time - this is known as closed work in pairs.

- **Games.** These are short, entertaining English games and designed to pass the time, provide a break, and change activities. The same can be said for larger-scale "Role-playing games," which are pre-planned and simulate a variety of scenarios in order to meet the learning objectives.

- **Discussions/debates.** Prepared in advance, critical thinking skills are developed, and both prepared and unprepared speeches are practiced. In most cases, the whole party participates in the discussion, and there are leaders. Debates and discussions aid in the use of the language in circumstances as similar to real-life speech contexts as possible, in order to address issues in the political, social, and cultural spheres of life.

- **Presentations.** Learners are required to present their topics in front of others and it shapes their self-assurance, motivation and communicative competence. In fact, speaking skills are more likely to be enhanced with the help of oral speeches.

Other activities including drama, role-plays, interviews, open talks and etc. can also be integrated to the lesson content for the improvement of CC.

In sum, the communicative method as the ultimate goal of training involves the formation of communicative competence, which consists of linguistic, pragmatic, socio-cultural and strategic competencies. Furthermore, all of the abovementioned activities are intended at the formation and development of the communicative competence of students. It is advisable that the types of activities replace each other in the lesson. Therefore, it is necessary to plan the course of the lesson in advance, select the appropriate exercises for each type of activity.

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**INSTRUMENTAL AND INTEGRATIVE MOTIVATIONS IN EFL
CONTEXT: IN THE CASE OF TWO UNDERGRADUATE STUDENTS OF
TASHKENT STATE INSTITUTE OF ORIENTAL STUDIES**

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Abstract. It has been widely known that motivation is one of the main indicators of success in second language acquisition. For EFL (English as a Foreign Language) students, the importance of motivation has also been significantly emphasized through multitude of scholarly works. In any educational settings, motivation serves as the determinant of success or failure in terms of foreign language acquisition.

Key words: *motivation, foreign language acquisition, L2, instrumental motivation, Second Language Acquisition (SLA)*

Saville-Troike states that “motivation is the second strongest predictor (after aptitude) of second language success and largely determines the level of effort that learners expend at various stages in their L2 development, often a key to ultimate level of proficiency” (p. 17). In fact, “movere” is the Latin alternative of the word motivation and it means “to move”, which can linguistically be divided into integrative and instrumental motivations. According to Gardner and Lambert (1972) the underlying reason behind integrative motivation is the learner’s inclination

towards cultural aspects of the target language, whereas instrumental motivation deals with career purposes such as educational, professional and business goals.

In Uzbekistan, as in many parts of the world, English language is growing in importance, especially in educational institutions. However, the shortage of authentic input outside the classroom poses a real challenge for students to learn English language, which in turn generates various learning outcomes. Additionally, students' motivation levels vary when it comes to learning a second language and its components. As such, understanding student motivation and the principal obstacles behind it will help educators take facilitative approaches in assessing student needs.

In this sense, the objective of this study is to identify whether two undergraduate students at Tashkent State Institute of Oriental Studies are instrumentally or integratively motivated to learn English language.

Literature review:

In broader sense, motivation is an extraordinary psychological power which accelerates the achievement of predetermined goals. In Second Language Acquisition (SLA), it is closely associated with perseverance and persistence in pursuit of acquiring all components of second language. Dornyei (2001) claims that “motivation is related to a person's behaviors that include decision making of doing something, duration of doing it and how much effort will they put in it” (pp. 273-274). Kissau (2006) pointed out that “in the context of L2 learning, motivation was seen as the extent to which the individual works or strives to learn the language because of a desire to do so” (p. 76). Ortega (2009) asserts that “motivation is usually understood to refer to the desire to initiate L2 learning and the effort employed to sustain it, and in lay terms we all understand it to be a matter of quantity, as in the everyday observation that some learners are highly motivated and others have little or no motivation” (p. 168). With regard to integrative motivation, Masgoret and Gardner (2003) labeled “integratively motivated learners as being open to other language communities, plus having positive and favorable attitudes throughout the learning process” (pp. 123-163). Moreover, we should also consider that “integratively

motivated learners tend to have more persistence in their learning, especially when they encounter challenges or difficult tasks. This is because they have internalized their motive of learning into their self-value system, which explain why integratively motivated learners put more effort into learning and obtain greater achievements in second language acquisition” (Wang, 2008, pp. 633-646). On the other hand, Gardner et al. (1983) described “the objective of instrumentally motivated learners as learning for perceived utility” (p.219-240). Studies have also investigated the significance of integrative and instrumental motivation. Hedge (2000) conducted research on 30 Japanese students. Results of the research indicated that students were both integratively and instrumentally motivated to learn English language. Rahman (2007) also examined Bangladeshi students’ motivation for learning English language and came to the conclusion that instrumental motivation of learners outweighs their integrative motivation.

Participants of the study:

Overall, two undergraduate Uzbek students were invited to participate in the case study. Both of them are males and aged between 20 and 26. For the privacy of participants, their real names were changed to Bakir and Zakir. Currently, they are studying at Tashkent State Institute of Oriental Studies in a major of world politics. Since their first language is Uzbek, English is taught as a foreign language at this university. However, all of them had an early exposure to English language at school, even though the instruction method was mainly based on textbooks. Speaking of Bakir, he started learning English language with a tutor in order to accelerate his learning process. He initially studied first and second edition of “English grammar in use” and “headway”. By contrast, Zakir resorted to self-study and began with “fly-high”, “headway” and other macmillan books. At university, their English classes are closely associated with politics, that is, language components such as speaking, reading, writing and listening focus on political issues. It is necessary to state that students have limited access to native-like English environment, which makes it interesting to identify their motives for learning English language.

Research design:

The present case study adapted motivational questionnaire from Gardner's Attitude/Motivation Test to be in accord with the needs of the study. Questions include two separate parts:

1. Section one entails the background of students such as gender and age
2. Section two focuses on integrative and instrumental motivations of students.

Data collection:

Two undergraduate politics students were selected from Tashkent State Institute of Oriental Studies, which is located in Tashkent, Uzbekistan. After expounding the whole procedure and purpose of the study such as participants' confidentiality, students agreed to take part in the questionnaire. Motivational questionnaire was distributed to participants to explore whether they are integratively or instrumentally motivated. First ten questions were dedicated to identify the instrumental motivation of students whereas questions from 11 to 20 dealt with integrative motivation.

For the first question of instrumental motivation items, both Bakir and Zakir answered positively by saying that they use English for assignments and exams. They also indicated that their communication in English is confined to speaking in the classroom. It appears that reading English newspapers and magazines is less desirable than English textbooks, mainly due to university requirements. Again, both of them consider English language competency as an ancillary for job promotions. In item 5, Bakir stated that he prefers pursuing his Master's degree in a major of public politics, for which English is not of paramount importance. Meanwhile, Zakir intends to continue his higher education abroad and considers English language as a necessity for traveling abroad. In items 7, 8, 9 and 10, both of them agreed that learning English language makes them more educated and skillful, which as a result leads to bright and promising future in life.

With regard to integrative motivation, Bakir sometimes reads English books and watches sci-fi movies and serials in English. He also pointed out that he has a few acquaintances in English-speaking countries, with whom he practices and improves his English. Likewise, Zakir believes that learning English facilitates the communication with people from other national backgrounds. Interestingly, both participants did not show much interest in items 16, 17, 18, 19 and 20, which reveals that their integrative motivation for learning English language is much lower their instrumental motivation.

This study investigated the instrumental and integrative motivation of two students who study at Tashkent State Institute of Oriental Studies. A questionnaire of 20 items was utilized to determine the type of motivation students have towards learning English language. Findings reveal that instrumental motivation of both students outweigh their integrative motivation, as they learn English language for educational and career purposes.

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ЎЙИН – ХОРИЖИЙ ТИЛНИ ЭРТА ЎРГАТИШДАГИ БЕБАҲО ФАОЛИЯТ

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Бугунги шиддат билан одимлаб бораётган бир даврда чет тилларини ўрганиш замон билан ҳамнафас бўлишнинг асосий зарурияти эканлиги барчамизга маълум. Бу масалага давлатимиз томонидан катта эътибор берилётгани, тил ўрганиш давлат сиёсати даражасида эканлиги ҳеч кимга сир эмас. “Чет тилларни ўрганиш тизимини янада такомиллаштириш чора-тадбирлари тўғрисида”ги Президент Қарори, “Таълим муассасаларида чет тилларини ўқитишнинг сифатини янада такомиллаштириш чора-тадбирлари тўғрисида”ги Ўзбекистон Республикаси Вазирлар Маҳкамасининг Қарори, Президент Ш.Мирзиёевнинг Мурожаатномаси, бир қатор давлат дастурлари ва уларнинг бажарилиши ҳозирги кунда ўзининг муносиб ечимини топмоқда.

Маълумки чет тилни ўрганиш узоқ муддатли жараён бўлгани боис уни эрта яъни мактабгача ёш давридан бошлаб ўргатиш кўзланган мақсадга эришишимизга имкон беради. Унинг ўзига хос ижобий томонлари мавжуд. Биринчидан, бу даврда чет тилини ўрганиш барча болалар учун фойдали, чунки у боланинг психик функциялари: хотираси, диққати, тафаккури, идроки, тасавури кабиларнинг ривожланишига, чет тилини муваффақиятли ўрганишни белгиловчи, унинг нутқий қобилиятини оширувчи жараёнларга ижобий таъсир кўрсатади. Иккинчидан, таълимнинг ушбу босқичида кўзда тутилган гуманитар предметлар спектрини кенгайтиради ва тил ўрганишнинг муваффақиятини таъминлайди. Шунингдек ушбу масала бола камолотининг муҳим омили сифатида боланинг интеллектуал қобилиятини ривожлантиради, чет тилда мулоқот қилиш орқали умуминсоний маданиятга эртароқ киришига замин яратади.

Маълумки, чет тил ўқитиш жараёни турли усул ва воситалар, жумладан шеър ёдлатиш, кўшиқ, ҳикоя, эртаклар, сахна асарлари ижро этиш орқали амалга оширилади. Улар орасида энг етакчи фаолият ўйин бўлиб, у орқали бола шахс сифатида шаклланади. Ўйин бола ҳаётининг бебаҳо гавҳари. Шу боис у асрлар давомида илм-фан вакиллариининг диққат-эътиборида бўлиб келган. Болалар ўйини назариясига (1920-30-йиллар) Э.А.Флерина, Э.И.Тихеева, Э.А.Аркин каби олимлар асос солганлар; кейинчалик Р.Лехтман-Абрамович, Ф.И.Фрадкина, Н.М.Аксарина, А.П.Усова, Е.В.Зворигина ва бошқаларнинг тадқиқот ишлари болалар ўйини мавзусини ишлаб чиқишга бағишланган.

Бола ўйинининг тарихи, психологияси, унинг ривожланиш қонуниятлари рус психолог олимларидан Л.С.Виготский, А.Н.Леонтьев, Д.Б.Елконин, З.В.Мануйленко, А.В.Черков, З.М. Богуславскийлар томонидан ўрганилиб, илм-фанга тақдим этилди.

Ўйин бола ҳаётининг мазмуни экан, унинг тил ўрганиш жараёнида ҳам муносиб ўрин эгаллаши шак-шубҳасиз. Carol Read ўзининг “500 Activities for the Primary School” номли ўқитувчилар учун ёзилган китобида чет тилни эрта ўрганиш/ўргатишдаги асосий фаолиятлар қаторида ўйин жараёнига оид қатор маълумотларни келтириб ўтган. Унда ёзилишича, ўйинлар ўқув фаолиятининг асосий бўлаги сифатида ўзининг жараёнга хилма-хиллик бериши, тил ўрганувчига таъсир кўрсатиши, уни қизиқтириши каби хусусиятлари билан намоён бўлади. Ўйин боланинг машғулотдаги актив иштирокини таъминлайди, унда ўз-ўзига бўлган ишонч, ўз-ўзини баҳолаш, назорат қила олиш ҳисларини ривожлантиради. Ўйин чет тил ўрганиш жараёнининг асосий, муҳим ажралмас қисми бўлиб, уни тўғри танлаш ва амалга ошириш асосий омилдир. [6]

Ўйин бола ҳаётидаги бебаҳо кадр-қимматга эга бўлган фаолият. Чунки у боладаги когнитив жараённи таъминлайди, нутқ кўникма ва малакаларини ривожлантиради, ҳамда боланинг ижтимоийлашувига олиб келади. Ўйин орқали хилма-хил интерактив усуллардан фойдаланилади.

Шу ўринда ўйин турларига тўхталиб ўтсак. Ўйин турлари сафига куйидагиларни киритиш мумкин: “name games”(номлаш ўйинлари), “miming games”(таклид ўйинлари), “playground games”(ўйин майдончасида ўйналадиган ўйинлар), “music games”(музикий ўйинлар), “team games”(жамоа ўйинлари), “revision games”(мустаҳкамлаш ўйинлари), “drawing games”(расм чизиш ўйинлари). Бу каби ўйинларнинг чет тил машғулотида мунтазам равишда қўлланилиши боланинг ўйин шартларини эркин ҳолда бажаришга ўргатади. Шундан сўнг тил ўргатувчи бошқа янги ўйин турларини таклиф қилади. Ҳатто кейинчалик болаларнинг ўзлари ҳам янги-янги ўйинларни ихтиро қилишлари мумкин. Ўйинлар сарасига мусобақа тарзида ўтказиладиган қоида ҳаракатли ўйинларни киритиш мумкин. Бундай ўйинларни ўтказиш натижасида болада ўз-ўзини назорат қилиш, шахслараро муносабатни таркиб топиши, тез фикрлаш қобилиятларининг ўсиши кузатилади. Ёш болаларда “ўз дунёсини”, ўзлигини ўйин орқали акс эттиришда табиий мойиллик мавжуд. Бу эса ўз навбатида чет тил ўрганишга ҳам асос бўлиши мумкин. Турли ҳаракатлар орқали ўйнаб тил ўрганиш унга хорижий тилни осонроқ англаш имкониятини беради. Шунингдек, ўйин жараёнида кузатиладиган, болани завқлантирувчи муҳит бевосита чет тилни ҳам катта қизиқиш ва хоҳиш билан ўрганишини тақозо этади.

Ўйин орқали тил ўргатиш боланинг жисмоний, ижтимоий эмоционал ва когнитив ривожланишини таъминлайди. Шунингдек ўйинлар болада ўзаро ҳамкорлик, навбат алмашиш, ўзгаларни тинглаш, уларни ҳурмат қилиш, турли қоидаларга амал қилиш каби ижтимоий малакаларни ҳам ривожлантиради. Ҳаракатли ўйинлар болаларда жисмоний мувозанат ва психомотор қобилиятларини ривожлантирса, бошқалари тасаввур қилиш, ижодий тафаккурини, идрокини ўстиради. Яна шуни айтиш мумкинки, ўйинлар болада диққатни жамлай олиш қобилияти ва унинг хотирасини ривожлантиради.

Маълумки, кўпчилик болаларда эгоцентрик хусусият мавжуд бўлиб, бу ҳолат боланинг боғчадаги дастлабки кунларида, дастлаб атрофдагилар билан

муносабатида, уни ўраб турган муҳитга мослашишидаги қийинчиликларда ўз аксини топади. Бундай вазиятда чет тил ўргатиш машғулоти ва унда қўлланилган ўйинлар боланинг ўзи хоҳлаган тарзда бошқалар билан мулоқот қилишига, бир сўз билан айтганда боғча ҳаётига киришишга, унга мослашиш, ўрганишига учун энг қулай, самарали восита бўлади. Боғчада ўз уйида бўлгани каби ўзини эркин ҳис қилади.

Болаларга хорижий тил (инглиз тили) ўйин орқали ўргатилар экан ўйинлар боланинг ёши, психо-физиологик хусусиятларини ҳисобга олган ҳолда танланиши лозим. Шунингдек тил ўргатувчининг машғулоти давомида қуйидаги талаб-таклифларга амал қилиши ҳам ўз самарасини беради:

- Оддийликка эътибор бериш. Осон ўйналадиган ўйинлардан кўпроқ фойдаланиш. (Айниқса кўп сонли болалар гуруҳларида);
- Ўйиннинг ҳар бир дақиқасида боланинг актив иштирокини таъминлаш;
- Ўйин шартларини болаларга аниқ тушунтириш. Кўпчилик ўйинларни дастлаб бутун гуруҳ билан ўйнаш;
- Ўйин жараёнига тегишли бўлган инглизча иборалардан фойдаланишга ўргатиш. Масалан, It's my / your turn;
- Болалар севиб, хоҳлаб ўйнайдиган ўйинлардан фойдаланиш;
- Боладаги қизиқиш сўнмасдан туриб ўйинни якунлаш.

Шунингдек юқорида санаб ўтилган ўйинлар ва уларнинг яна бошқа турларини таълимнинг мақсад ва вазифаларига мос бўлган ҳолда чет тил дарсларида қўллаш, ҳар бир ўқитувчи ўз тажрибасидан келиб чиққан ҳолда қўшимча ўйин усулларида фойдаланиши мумкин.

Тил ўргатиш жараёни бевосита ўйинлар орқали амалга оширилар экан бу борада қуйидаги фикрларни ҳам беришни лозим топдик. Юқорида санаб ўтилган ўйинлар қаторида тил ўргатувчи болаларбоп ўзбек миллий ўйинларидан чет тилда фойдаланиши ҳам мумкин. Унинг афзаллиги шундаки, бола ўйин мазмунини аввалдан билгани боис унда мотивация жараёни кучли бўлади, ундаги ҳаракатларни бажариш ҳеч қандай қийинчилик туғдирмайди,

бола завқ билан ўйнайди. Бу билан муаллим чет тил машғулотида миллийлик руҳини олиб киради. Фарзандларимиз ватанимизни севиш, уни асраб-авайлаш кераклигини ҳис қиладилар. Қолаверса халқимизнинг бой меъросини чет тилда бошқа халқларга танитиш имконига эга бўладилар.

Хулоса ўрнида шуни айтиш лозимки, ўйин бола ҳаётининг мазмуни эканлиги, бебаҳо кадр-қимматга эга бўлгани боис, чет тил ўқитиш жараёнининг ҳам энг етакчи, энг зарурий фаолият тури бўлиб қолади.

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ПЕРЕХОД ОТ ТРАДИЦИОННОЙ ОЦЕНКИ К АЛЬТЕРНАТИВНОЙ И АУТЕНТИЧНОЙ В ПРЕПОДАВАНИИ ИНОСТРАННОГО ЯЗЫКА

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Аннотация. Оценка играет важную и решающую роль в учебном процессе. Путем выставления соответствующей оценки учителя могут классифицировать и оценивать своих студентов, давать отзывы и соответствующим образом структурировать процесс обучения. В последнее время преподаватели и ученые все больше интересуются требованиями процедур оценивания в рамках преподавания иностранного языка и процесса обучения, поскольку формы оценивания меняются. Процедуры оценки касаются аутентичности, практичности, надежности, обоснованности и обратной связи и считаются основными принципами оценивания при преподавании и изучении иностранного языка.

Ключевые слова: *оценка, формы, оценка, тестирование, отзыв.*

Методика, ориентированная на обучающегося, поддерживает представление о том, что студенты должны быть активными членами аудитории, и это является одним из критериев нового подхода к обучению иностранных языков. В этом ключе, оценочные задания в классе используются преподавателями для проверки уровня знаний студентов. Можно сказать, что оценивание - это длительная процедура, включающая информацию и данные о развитии знаний и навыков студентов.

Оценка имеет жизненно важное значение в образовательном процессе для информирования и улучшения текущего обучения и является важной частью любой учебной и преподавательской деятельности. Она не только информирует об учебных решениях, принимаемых на повседневной основе, но и помогает диагностировать сильные и слабые стороны студентов, в процессе обучения в классе, для формирования своей педагогической деятельности в соответствии со стилями обучения своих учеников. Чтобы оценить успеваемость студентов и выставить оценки, учителя должны использовать разные тесты. Тесты, экзамены и модели оценки являются важными инструментами, используемыми для измерения результатов обучения.

В целом оценивание считается одной из очень важных частей обучения, где преподаватели могут определить уровень навыков и знаний своих учеников. Таким образом, это помогает преподавателям оценивать сильные и слабые стороны своих студентов и мотивировать их. [Taras, 2005; Stiggins, 1992].

Оценивание преподавания в изучении иностранного языка проводится по разным причинам. Во-первых, оно показывает, сколько студентов достигли своих целей, у кого есть какие-либо трудности или проблемы, и какие методы полезны при обучении иностранному языку. Во-вторых, преподаватель может решить продолжать ли программу обучения иностранному языку. [Журнал исследований образования и обучения Vol. 6, № 9; Сентябрь, 2018].

Для того чтобы основательно решить проблему волнения студентов по поводу оценивания, необходимо наряду с современными методами тестирования использовать традиционные. Основная цель традиционного оценивания состоит в том, чтобы проверить успеваемость учащегося при помощи таких методов оценивания, как контрольные вопросы, альтернативные варианты, а также закрытые тесты или заполнение пропусков. Такие ориентированные тесты могут позволить студентам краткосрочно добиться успеха. В сущности, предпочтение оценивания может иметь значительное

влияние на процессы преподавания и обучения иностранному языку. [Shapiro, 1987].

Сегодня преподаватели английского языка начинают понимать, что необходимо разработать новые альтернативные стратегии оценивания, для того, чтобы лучше контролировать своих учащихся и помогать им в процессе обучения. Эти новые формы оценивания концентрируются на измерении знаний студентов, позволяющих спонтанно использовать язык в реальной жизни, и реализуются в течение определенного периода. В дополнение к этому, все более распространенным становится более достоверное разнообразие оценок, таких как проекты, служебные задания, концептуальные карты, самооценка, взаимная оценка, наблюдение, портфолио, драма, диагностическое дерево, журналы, плакаты, инструкторы и собеседования со студентами. в классе. [Anil & Acar, 2008; Büyüktokatlı & Bayraktar, 2014].

«Альтернативное оценивание реализуется в аудиторных занятиях, в соответствии с требованиями учебной программы. Более того, оно дает информацию о сильных и слабых сторонах студента, и основывается на заданиях из реальной жизни. Благодаря альтернативному оцениванию обучение становится более аутентичным, поскольку помогает учащимся улучшить свои навыки принятия решений и решения проблем. Преподаватели также могут получить представление об эффективности своего курса и при необходимости внести изменения». [Ричардс и Ренандия, 2002].

Оценка включает информацию об осведомленности, понимании, восприятии и отношении студентов к обучению. Оценка отвечает потребностям учащегося и занимает центральное место в планировании учителем, включая тестирование. В этом ключе стандартизированные тесты чаще всего ассоциируются со следующими принципами оценки: подлинность, надежность, достоверность и эффект обратной связи. [Brown & Abeywickrama, 2010], [Sarıçoban, 2011].

Использование принципа подлинности в тесте используется для выполнения задания в реальной жизненной ситуации. Таким образом, в тесте подлинность представлена следующими способами:

- а) включает как можно больше естественного языка;
- б) содержит контекстуализированные компоненты;
- в) имеет значимые, актуальные темы из реальной жизни;
- г) обеспечивает некоторую тематическую организацию элементов, например, сюжетную линию или эпизод;
- д) предлагает задания, которые повторяют задания из реального мира.

Стабильность и постоянство результатов надежных испытаний должны быть последовательными и надежными. [Badjadi, 2013; Genesee & Upshur, 1999]. Например, если преподаватель дает один и тот же тест одному и тому же студенту или подбирает студентов в двух разных случаях, тест должен показать одинаковые результаты. Итак, принцип надежности;

- а) соответствует своим условиям;
- б) дает четкие указания для оценки;
- в) имеет единые рубрики для оценки;
- г) содержит задания, однозначные для тестируемого. [Brown & Abeywickrama, 2010].

Возможный уровень реализации чрезвычайно высок, например, если студент, написавший рассказ, имеет те же или, по крайней мере, очень похожие характеристики его / ее последующего написания. (Ричардс и Ренандия, 2002).

«Достоверность оценки воспринимается методом оценки, соответствующий преподаваемому материалу и учебной программе, и, если результаты оценки точны.» [Brown, 2002; Gür, 2013].

Четвертый основной принцип тестирования по иностранному языку - это обратный эффект. Согласно Брауну [2004] и Андерсону, Рурку, Арчеру и Гаррисону [2001], этот принцип определяется влиянием тестирования на

преподавание и изучение иностранного языка. При использовании обратной связи необходимо учитывать следующие моменты:

- а) положительно повлиять на то, как и что преподают преподаватели и как учатся студенты;
- б) предлагать студентам возможность подготовиться;
- г) предоставить студентам данные для оценки языковых достижений;
- д) обеспечить условия для максимальной успеваемости обучающегося. [Brown & Abeywickrama, 2010].

Таким образом, при планировании обучения иностранным языкам в отношении оценивания преподаватель должен учитывать следующие вопросы:

- Обучение и оценка должны отражать друг друга.
- При использовании иностранного языка значимы все виды оценок.
- Оценка должна занимать главное место в обучении.
- Принципы оценивания должны приниматься во внимание преподавателями при создании учебных материалов для студентов.
- Негативные факторы, влияющие на студентов, такие как тревога и беспокойство, должны быть в центре внимания преподавателя.

Подводя итог хотелось бы отметить, что в последнее время важность оценивания в процессе обучения языку стала популярна. Оценка очень важна для студентов в овладении языком. Он играет решающую роль в процессе обучения и дает обучающимся возможность получить новые знания, используя их текущие способности, а также является мотивацией в образовательном процессе.

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НАУЧНО-МЕТОДИЧЕСКАЯ ОСНОВА ПОДГОТОВКИ УЧЕБНОГО МАТЕРИАЛА ПО РУССКОМУ ЯЗЫКУ ДЛЯ РАЗВИТИЯ РЕЧИ

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Аннотация. Данная статья посвящена актуальной на сегодняшний день теме – подготовки учебного материала по русскому языку для развития речи в

национальной аудитории. В статье излагаются основные методические приёмы подготовки учебного материала для студентов неязыкового вуза.

Ключевые слова: учебный материал, профессиональная коммуникация, монологическая речь, речевое общение, языковая среда.

В области преподавания русского языка как иностранного самая актуальная проблема – это решение вопроса обеспечения студентов учебным материалом по русскому языку.

Более подробно хочу остановиться на вопросе о подготовке учебного материала по русскому языку для нефилологического профиля. Это вопрос сложный, поскольку и в учебной аудитории слушателями являются в основном студенты- нефилологических направлений.

Для студентов-нефилологических направлений русский язык – не профилирующий предмет, он не является объектом специализации, а является лишь средством ее приобретения. Отсюда следует, что преподавание языка должно как можно раньше приобщить их к коммуникации, знакомить со спецификой разговорной речи.

И перед нами встает вопрос: к какой профессиональной коммуникации будем приобщать иностранного слушателя? Ведь в одной группе можно встретить студентов с разной профессиональной ориентацией: юриста, экономиста, физика, математика, филолога, историка и просто любителя русской культуры, литературы и языка.

Студенты должны приобрести способность участвовать в языковой коммуникации на русском языке, особенно в главных видах речевой деятельности языкового общения, имеется в виду слушание, чтение, говорение и письмо. Объективной основой данной коммуникации является субъязык изучаемой области, представленной определенной тематикой, определенными ситуациями и определенным набором языковых средств.

Подготовка учебного материала по русскому языку для иностранной аудитории имеет еще и свои трудности. Мы должны всегда помнить, что дисциплину «русский язык» надо рассматривать как практическую, и ее теоретический аспект подчинен практическим целям. Другими словами, основной целью является активизация навыков речевого общения в устной форме на основе изученного материала. Для выполнения этой цели дополнительные трудности создает, прежде всего, отсутствие языковой среды, а также то, что все преподаватели ведут занятия по другим предметам на родном языке студентов, и это вполне нормально. Таким образом, студент может практически использовать свои знания в устной разговорной речи

Как уже было сказано выше, контингент слушателей в иностранной аудитории очень разный, поэтому преподаватель всегда должен ставить перед собой два вопроса при подготовке учебного материала.

1. Учим ли мы студентов русскому языку в целом?

2. Можно ли, овладев только определенным стилем речи, пользоваться русским языком в других сферах общения?

И чтобы справиться с вышеизложенными задачами, которые необходимо учитывать при подготовке учебного материала по русскому языку, уместно сказать и об авторе.

Автор прежде всего должен правильно определить тематику будущей работы. Качество ее во многом будет зависеть и от того, насколько правильно будет подобран материал, насколько методически целесообразно будет он изложен, насколько правильно будет отобран лексический и грамматический материал и насколько правильно будет построена система упражнений. Только учет всех этих требований при составлении учебного материала будет способствовать активизации речи учащихся, практическому владению языком.

Ясно здесь одно: чтобы подготовить учебный материал с учетом вышеназванных требований, необходимо быть прежде всего квалифицированным специалистом по русскому языку, а также знать основы

методических и дидактических принципов в педагогической деятельности, знать психологию.

При определении тематики учебного материала встает не менее сложный вопрос: как должна решаться проблема отбора текстов.

Работая с текстом, студенты учатся извлекать информацию, предъявляемую в разнообразной форме: в виде связного текста, таблицы, схемы, составление планов, работа с различными видами словарей. В учебнике много игровых технологий, кроссвордов, шарад, которые дают возможность студентам с интересом изучать русский язык. Каждая тема сопровождается списком ключевых терминов, подлежащих активному усвоению.

Прежде всего надо сказать, что сам текст является и должен быть объектом изучения. Почти традиционным сейчас стало деление текста на четыре основных типа: описание, повествование, рассуждение и доказательство. Основанием такого различия является прежде всего логическая структура текста, представленная определенным набором грамматических средств. Анализ самого текста отмечает связь между логическим построением и выбором грамматических средств.

При определении учебного материала и подбора текстов для иностранной аудитории, на наш взгляд, необходимо привлечь и самих студентов, т.е. мы должны услышать мнение студентов. Только тогда преподаватель может учитывать интерес студентов. Если же они имеют некоторые знания по русскому языку, то в этом случае в какой-то степени можно определить и знание грамматического материала, а также лексический запас слушателей. В иностранной аудитории особенно важно методически правильно организовать материал: тексты должны отбираться именно по тематическому принципу, так как это способствует прежде всего накоплению лексики. Грамматический же материал здесь можно подавать свободно, ибо тексты различны по грамматической наполняемости. Последовательность подачи грамматического материала в этом случае также определяет сам текст. И грамматика в силу этого

отрабатывается «по мере встречаемости» в тексте, что не способствует системности в подаче грамматических явлений. Основные требования к тексту:

- 1) текст должен вызвать интерес учащихся;
- 2) текст должен представлять определенную коммуникативную ценность;
- 3) текст должен нести основную информацию, стилевую принадлежность, логическую четкость;
- 4) текст должен отражать основные стилистические особенности языка.

Каждый преподаватель в процессе обучения должен научить студентов различать типы текстов, узнавать его структуру, видеть связь языковых форм и смысловых категорий. Все это влияет на глубину понимания и воспроизведения.

И преподаватели так должны строить свои занятия, чтобы у студентов появилась потребность в развернутом монологическом высказывании. Или, выражаясь другими словами, высказывания на уровне предложения должны перейти на более крупную единицу – текст. Необходимо всегда помнить, что при восприятии чужого иноязычного высказывания и оформлении своего, кроме знаний лексики и грамматических правил, следует осознать программу построения речевого высказывания, постичь его структурно-смысловую организацию.

Учебный материал должен подаваться таким образом, чтобы с первых занятий учить студентов умению строить собственное высказывание по аналогии с предложенным учебным текстом. Содержание текстов, его языковое оформление и структурно – композиционный состав выступают для студентов как своего рода ориентир для построения собственного высказывания.

В конце хочу отметить, что для успешной организации занятий недостаточно иметь только хорошие, подготовленные с учетом всех научных требований, учебные материалы. Не меньшую роль в организации занятий играет личность преподавателя. Каждый преподаватель должен знать основные принципы научной организации взаимопонимания преподавателя и студентов.

Бесспорно, что педагогический эффект и конечный результат обучения обуславливаются характером взаимоотношений студентов с преподавателем. И этот существенный момент должен учитываться преподавателями при организации всей учебной работы.

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РОЛЬ ИЗУЧЕНИЯ ТЕКСТОВ В ОБУЧЕНИИ МОНОЛОГИЧЕСКОЙ РЕЧИ УЧАЩИХСЯ И СТУДЕНТОВ (НА ПРИМЕРЕ ТВОРЧЕСТВА ГАФУРА ГУЛЯМА)

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Аннотация: В статье рассматривается роль чтения художественного литературы, значение слова в духовно-нравственном развитии студентов. В качестве примера изучения художественной литературы, автор статьи остановился на творчестве узбекского писателя и поэта – Гафура Гуляма.

Ключевые слова: *литературное чтение, художественный вкус, нравственное понимание, узбекская литература, творчество Гафура Гуляма, творческое наследие, рассказ.*

На современном этапе роль литературного чтения, наряду с изучением русского языка, имеет большое значение в духовно-нравственном развитии студентов. Художественное слово воздействует не только на сознание, но и на чувства и поступки подрастающего поколения. Слово может вызвать желание стать лучше, сделать что-то хорошее, помогает осознать человеческие отношения, познакомиться с нормами поведения. Чтение художественной литературы – основа воспитания и гордости народа. Любая тема в литературе может рассматриваться с точки зрения нравственного понимания. Чтение литературы учит жизни в широком понимании слова, формирует опыт, развивает чувства. К тому же чтение книг обогащает человека духовно, воспитывает его эстетический вкус. В качестве примера изучения художественной литературы, остановимся на творчестве узбекского писателя и поэта – Гафура Гуляма.

Сегодня, говоря о прозе начала XX века, нельзя не упомянуть о весомом вкладе крупного представителя узбекской литературы первой половины прошлого столетия Гафура Гуляма в реалистическую и юмористическую прозу.

Произведения народного поэта Узбекистана Гафура Гуляма пользуются признанием и любовью миллионов читателей в нашей стране и за рубежом. Мы знаем его как поэта, прозаика и публициста. Стихи и проза Гафура Гуляма переведены на английский, русский, персидский, испанский, польский, болгарский и другие языки.

Тридцатые годы прошлого века характеризуются движением коллективизации, образованием гигантов индустрии. Писатель активно включился в борьбу за ликвидацию неграмотности. Кроме этого, он стал одним из организаторов борьбы с беспризорностью детей (руководил интернатом). Гафур Гулям очень рано начал писать стихи, вначале подражая узбекским классикам. Развился его талант под воздействием самой жизни. Поэт имеет

ввиду труд свободных людей, который превратил его Узбекистан в цветущий сад («Лето», «Узбекистан», «На путях Турксиба»).

На формирование мировоззрения и художественного вкуса Гафура Гуляма огромное влияние оказали произведения Владимира Маяковского. В одной из статей он писал: «Я ... знаю и люблю русских классиков и перевел немало их произведений на свой родной язык. Но больше всего мне хочется назвать себя учеником Маяковского», который «открывал для меня самые разнообразные и неисчерпаемые возможности в области ритмики, словаря, образа, звукового строения стиха. Кроме гневной, бичующей иронии в сатирах, потрясающе огромной силы чувства в лирике Маяковского, я старался вобрать в себя... всю мужественную ораторскую силу его ритмов, интонаций, смелость метафор, выразительность гипербол. Даже разбивку стиха, повышающую его ритмическую, интонационную и смысловую выразительность, мне удалось применить в узбекском стихосложении» Это подтверждается многими произведениями Гафура Гуляма, например, «На путях Турксиба», «Родная земля», «Да здравствует мир!»).

Особое место в творческом наследии писателя занимают произведения, адресованные юным читателям. Говоря о произведениях для детей, следует особо отметить одно из самых замечательных творений выдающегося художника – повесть «Озорник». В повести, рассказывая читателю о скитаниях своего юного героя, Гафур Гулям пишет о годах собственного детства, отмечает близость судьбы главного героя с судьбой самого автора. Оригинальность и своеобразие повести «Озорник» в огромной мере заключены в затейливом, бесконечно разнообразном переплетении подлинного, достоверного автобиографического материала с неистощимой фантазией автора. Следует подчеркнуть глубокую народность этого произведения. У веселой выдумки Гафура Гуляма – глубоко народные истоки. Различные истории, которые происходят с героем, напоминают сюжеты сказок, окрашенных фольклорным колоритом. Весь арсенал художественных средств

народного поэта направлен на то, чтобы воспеть вольную душу народа, никогда не мирившегося с бесправием и рабством.

Гафур Гулям известен и как мастер короткого, остросюжетного рассказа, где вводится в качестве повествовательного приема авторская речь и свободное обращение к читателю в форме живой дружеской беседы-спора, переполненной вопросами и ответами самого писателя. Большинство прозаических произведений, созданных писателем, посвящено человеческим взаимоотношениям. Основные проблемы, которые он ставит и разрешает в произведениях, – это борьба за нравственное воспитание человека, за его моральное и культурное развитие, обличение пороков, отношение к женщинам («Друзья», «Тени», «Счастье разбойника»). Кроме того, писатель создает в своих прозаических произведениях яркие положительные образы. Положительным героем, человеком с большой душой изображен Джура в повести «Ядгар». Он воспитывает чужого ребенка. Именно в отношении обыкновенного человека к чужому ребенку автор показал высокий нравственный уровень Джуры.

В годы войны Гафур Гулям проявляет свой истинный патриотизм, пишет талантливые произведения, которые точно и ярко передают общее настроение народа, его дух и веру в неизбежную победу над фашизмом.

Я в возрасте Пушкина. Враг мой, держись!

Но здесь не дуэль, здесь возмездье и суд.

В дуэли - лишь смерть. А в борьбе нашей - жизнь.

Свободу войска наши миру несут.

В годы войны в Узбекистан были эвакуированы десятки тысяч человек. Огромное количество детей-сирот бежало сюда в поисках тепла и пищи. Гафур Гулям не мог не откликнуться в своем творчестве на эту животрепещущую тему. В начале 1942 года поэт пишет объемное стихотворение «Ты не сирота»:

Разве ты сирота?..

Успокойся, родной!

*Словно доброе солнце,
склоняясь над тобой,
материнской,
глубокой
любовью полна,
бережет твое детство
большая страна...*

Это стихотворение стало чрезвычайно популярным.

Творчество Гафура Гуляма послевоенного периода сыграло значительную роль в развитии узбекской литературы. Если в военные годы в его стихотворениях находим глубокие переживания и думы людей, с оружием в руках, защищающих то, что было ими создано до войны, то в его послевоенной лирике с поэтической непосредственностью и душевной взволнованностью звучат переживания тех же людей, отстаивающих мир на земле. Послевоенная лирика поэта, таким образом, является логическим продолжением и развитием его лирики военных лет, а стихотворения «Запомни, тебя Родина ждет!» и «Праздник победителей» – как бы связующее звено этих двух периодов творчества писателя.

Таким образом, большое количество замечательных произведений Гафура Гуляма пронизаны взволнованной поэтичностью, ощущением внутренней свободы и красоты мира; чистое его сердце всегда останется открытым всему прекрасному.

В заключении отметим, что наблюдение над текстом при изучении творчества писателей и поэтов, его внимательное прочтение нужно для того, чтобы читатель понял главное: зачем автор пишет свой рассказ или повесть. А, следовательно, прийти к выводу о том, в чем помогает герой разобраться читателю, чему учит данное произведение. Если человек научится проникать в эмоциональный мир героев, выявлять авторское отношение к ним, а затем вырабатывать собственную оценку персонажей, то это будет способствовать

развитию читательских навыков, глубокому постижению произведения искусства, повышению уровня нравственной воспитанности студентов формированию их нравственных идеалов.

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ВАЖНОСТЬ ВНЕДРЕНИЯ ФРАЗЕОЛОГИЧЕСКИХ ЕДИНИЦ И ЭФФЕКТИВНЫХ СПОСОБОВ ОБУЧЕНИЯ

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Аннотация: Преподавание фразеологии является частью культурологического подхода в методологии иностранного обучения, а организация изучения лексики - это лингвистический подход к структуре компонентного значения. Следовательно, пользователю языка необходимы общие знания, чтобы правильно понимать заданные единицы. Знание коннотативных значений компонентов позволяет пользователю языка

декодировать модификации канонических форм фразеологизмов, а также создавать свои собственные модификации. Значительной целью данной статьи было изучить способы использования фразеологизмов в учебном процессе.

Ключевые слова: фразеологизмы, идиомы, лингвистика, компонентное значение, контекст, мотивация, обыкновенный разговор, буквальное значение, методы обучения.

Изучение любого иностранного языка невозможно без обращения к фразеологии, которая представляет собой один из самых сложных для изучения языковых уровней. Фразеологические единицы - единицы речевого общения, поэтому их изучение должно осуществляться с помощью коммуникативных упражнений, содержанием которых является исполнение учащимися речевых актов в условиях реального общения или подобных им. Сейчас общепринято, что люди, которые хотят овладеть иностранным языком, должны знать широкий спектр сложных лексических слов в иностранном языке как изучающие язык. Очевидно, что для того, чтобы хорошо владеть иностранным языком, ученик должен выучить произношение, грамматику и словарный запас. Но главный из них - фразеологизмы. Любой язык полон фразеологизмов. Очевидно, что идиомы, фразы и устойчивые выражения, афоризмы, максимы, пословицы и поговорки являются основными единицами любого языка, без них наш язык может показаться поверхностным или скучным. Умение использовать фразовые выражения - отличный признак языка. Образованный человек, хранитель фразеологии, трансформирует свое сознание в рациональную, понятную и компактную манеру. Вот почему каждый культурный, грамотный человек, студент, который хочет свободно владеть языком, должен использовать регулярные выражения в языке. [1.]

Знание слова - читатель знает, но не понимает его значения, просто немного думает, а потом запоминает. Получение слова, применение - при чтении текста читатель быстро узнает слово, понимает его значение. Автоматически находит слово в речи и может использовать его с другими словами. Итак, главная цель -

не знать слова, а овладеть ими. Следовательно, у читателя должно быть определенное количество слов. В этом случае эти слова не зависят от того, какой вид речевой деятельности необходим. Есть два уровня словарного запаса: первый - это словарный запас, который учащиеся активно используют; второй - это выученный и понятый словарный запас.

Они формируют словарный запас читателя и называются активным и пассивным словарем. Словарь можно вводить как переведенными, так и непереуведенными способами. Фразеологизмы обычно рекомендуется вводить переводным способом. Включенная фразеология должна быть понятна читателям.

Основной объем фразеологического материала составляют книги для чтения в домашних условиях. Студенты смогут как понимать, так и переводить текст, если им дадут задание растолочь их в специальной тетради и процитировать перевод и комментарий. Акцентирование внимания студентов на фразеологизмах способствует интенсивному усвоению лексического материала. Кроме того, работа с фразеологией развивает у учащихся навыки чтения, сокращения и разговорной речи.

Поскольку учебные материалы бывают разных типов, включая бумажные (учебники), электронные (корпус, компьютерное программное обеспечение) и аудиовизуальные (видео, телевизионные программы, аудиокассеты, наглядные пособия), наше внимание будет сосредоточено на бумажных учебных материалах. материалы, то есть учебники. Учитель должен выбрать лучший из методов обучения и учебных материалов. Важно не только научить значения фразеологизмов, но и научить их правильно и эффективно использовать. Когда человек, для которого язык не является родным, использует идиому правильно, он или она будет говорить очень бегло. Но, с другой стороны, если они запутаются в фразе, они будут звучать прямо противоположно. Учитывая ограниченное количество часов, посвященных преподаванию иностранного

языка в школах, было бы утопично ожидать, что грамматика и фразеология как-то позаботятся о себе сами. [2.]

Эффективные способы внедрения фразеологизмов в учебный процесс:

Обучайте фразеологизму в устной, а не письменной форме и объясните учащимся, как они разговорные, а не формальные. Предложите учащимся попрактиковаться в использовании фразеологизмов в диалоге, чтобы помочь им понять, что они используются в устной речи.

Не раздайте просто длинный список фразеологизмов. Обязательно выделите небольшой набор из 5-10 фразеологизмов (или меньше) и объясните каждую из них. Использование идиом, устойчивых выражений улучшает разговорные навыки учащихся. Оригинальным вкладом нашего исследования является разработка подхода к совершенствованию разговорных навыков с помощью фразеологизмов, а также повышение мотивации студентов. [3]

В настоящее время преподавание словарного запаса стало важным в преподавании и обучении L2, особенно в последние годы.

1. Используйте тему

Отличный способ научить фразеологизмы - использовать тему. Большинство идиом любого языка попадает в тематическую группу. Например, вы можете использовать все фразеологизмы, связанные с погодой, или обучать фразеологическим единицам, связанным со спортом, животными и продуктами питания. Используя общую тему для обучения идиомам, учащимся легче понять значения фраз и увидеть, как похожие слова могут означать очень разные вещи.

2. Учите фразеологизмы с картинками.

Предоставьте картинку, чтобы объяснить контекст. Лучше всего это работает, если вы покажете изображение, которое юмористически иллюстрирует буквальное значение фразеологизмов. Это рассмешит учащихся, но также поможет им понять или угадать, что означает фраза. Фразеологические единицы наполнены красочными образами, идеально

подходящими для флеш-карточки или фотографии. Покажите картинку своим ученикам и предложите им угадать значение фразеологизмов.

3. Используйте небольшие группы для представления диалогов Диалог Письмо и ролевая игра в чтении

Диалоги могут предоставить учащимся ситуации, в которых они могут практиковаться в обычном разговоре, и предложить учащимся достаточную практику с базовыми навыками речи в контексте. Во-первых, диалоги можно рассматривать как короткие пьесы и использовать их для разыгрывания учащимися, а не просто чтения вслух. Более того, диалоги, которые пишут ученики, служат базовым средством общения на всех уровнях. Кроме того, разделение учеников на пары для ролевой игры в ежедневных диалогах - эффективный способ устной практики для разных возрастов и уровней. [4.] Более того, учащиеся лучше учатся, когда им предоставляются совместные действия, потому что они могут взаимодействовать со сверстниками и делиться удовольствием в процессе обучения. Вы можете использовать следующие идиомы, чтобы пытаться таким образом.

4. Угадайка

Напишите на доске три или четыре идиомы, которые касаются одной темы (например, животные, части тела). Попросите учащихся поработать в группах, чтобы посмотреть, смогут ли они угадать значение фразеологизмов. Пройдитесь по классной комнате и проверьте их ответы, присуждая баллы для правильного определения. Затем поделитесь с классом значениями фразеологизмов и приведите им пример в контексте. Перейдите к другой группе идиом по второй теме. Повторите упражнение. Команда, первой набравшая десять очков, побеждает в игре.

Важность чтения литературы для изучения фразеологизмов

Также, на наш взгляд, следующим одним из наиболее эффективных методов преподавания фразеологии в вузах, по праву можно считать использование иностранной литературы. С нашей точки зрения, недостаточно внимания

уделяется вопросу использования зарубежной литературы в процессе обучения фразеологии. Эффективность использования аутентичного художественного текста, который может служить опорой при обучении фразеологизмов, полностью не описана и не проверена. Фразеологические фразы широко используются в художественном творчестве в силу своего художественного характера. Изучение фразеологии вызывает эмоциональный отклик, значительно повышает интерес и мотивацию к языковой деятельности и к предмету.

Чтение иностранной литературы обогащает словарный запас студентов, расширяет знания фразеологизмов и устойчивых выражений. Использование зарубежной литературы повысит эффективность работы, сделает уроки необычными и запоминающимися. Другими словами, одним из таких приемов может стать использование иностранной художественной литературы в рамках домашнего чтения [5].

Фразеология - ключевой фактор в улучшении навыков чтения и слушания учащимися, наряду с беглостью и точностью произношения. Разговорная деятельность, обсуждение или работа в паре являются сложными и очень мотивирующими, а акцент на фразеологии делает язык естественным и аутентичным. Эффективное и увлекательное обучение фразе не только поможет вам понять язык, но также поможет вам осознанно овладеть им. Наконец, вышеупомянутые мероприятия помогают преодолеть некоторые лингвистические проблемы, вызванные изучением фразеологизмов, пословиц и поговорок, и дают прекрасный пример того, как культура влияет на язык.

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ИЗУЧЕНИЕ ИНОСТРАННОГО ЯЗЫКА В РАННЕМ ВОЗРАСТЕ

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специализированной школы № 300*

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Аннотация. В данной статье предпринята попытка прояснить важность изучения иностранного языка в раннем возрасте. Среди философов, эмпириков и психологи считают, что язык является социальным существом и, как и другие формы социального поведения, приобретает. Это, пожалуй, самый сложный и спорный вопрос, который поднимался среди лингвистов, психологов и философов о языке: как ребенок изучает иностранный язык? Изучение языка естественно.

Дети рождаются со способностью учиться этому, и это обучение начинается с рождения. Многие эксперты считают, что изучение языка в возрасте до десяти лет позволяет детям говорить правильно и свободно, как коренному жителю. Поэтому, каким бы ранним ни был ребенок, знакомый с иностранным языком, у него больше шансов овладеть им. Исследования показывают, что с рождения до 10 лет-лучшее время для того, чтобы познакомить ребенка с новыми языками. В этой статье ребенок быстрее выучит язык, лучше сохранит его и чаще всего будет говорить на нем с почти родным произношением. Наконец, в этой статье освещаются преимущества и недостатки изучения иностранного языка в детстве.

Ключевые слова: дети, иностранный язык, детство

1. ВСТУПЛЕНИЕ

Многие эксперты считают, что изучение языка в возрасте до десяти лет позволяет детям говорить правильно и свободно, как коренному жителю. Поэтому, каким бы ранним ни был ребенок, знакомый с иностранным языком, у него больше шансов овладеть им. С другой стороны, изучение языка, за исключением родного языка, может обеспечить развитие на протяжении всей жизни способности к большему общению с другими людьми. Одним из важных преимуществ овладения иностранным языком является доступ к лучшим возможностям трудоустройства, и человек найдет более глубокое понимание своей собственной культуры и других народов. В том числе преимущества знания иностранного языка в современном обществе, повышение экономической конкурентоспособности на внешнем рынке, улучшение глобальных коммуникаций, а также поддержание и управление политическими интересами и интересами безопасности страны. Исследования показали, что, если языки изучаются у детей до полового созревания, у детей больше шансов говорить на иностранном языке с полностью родным произношением. Кроме того, знакомство ребенка с культурой других народов распространяет его взгляды и взгляды и дает ему возможность общаться с другими людьми. Теперь

мы знаем, что изучение иностранного языка дает детям удивительные преимущества. Исследования продемонстрировали улучшенную способность к общению, лучшее когнитивное развитие, более широкую культурную осведомленность и, в конечном счете, лучшие возможности трудоустройства для тех, кто знает иностранный язык Феррейра, Ф. и Моррисон, Ф. Дж. (1994). Более того, все сегодняшние дети должны будут владеть двумя языками к тому времени, когда они поступят в колледж, Исследования показывают, что с рождения до 10 лет-лучшее время для того, чтобы познакомить маленького ребенка с новыми языками. В этой статье ребенок быстрее выучит язык, лучше сохранит его и чаще всего будет говорить на нем с почти родным произношением. Недавние исследования показывают, что маленький ребенок в возрасте до 5 лет может изучать и обрабатывать до пяти языков! Многие родители размышляют над тем, как привнести новый язык в жизнь своего малыша. Многие эксперты сходятся во мнении, что двуязычный подход для самого маленького ребенка лучше всего. Сегодняшние родители знают, как важно быть двуязычными. Теперь им просто нужно знать, куда обратиться за помощью в поиске веселых и доступных двуязычных продуктов, которые привнесут целевой язык в жизнь их ребенка. Интернет сделал их поиск намного проще, чем пять лет назад. Ищите двуязычные программы, которые позволяют вам пробовать их визуальные или аудиопродукты в режиме онлайн, чтобы вы могли хорошо понять содержание и стиль изучения языка в рамках этой конкретной программы.

1.1. Овладение языком детьми

Эти примеры изучения языка, обработки и создания представляют собой лишь некоторые из многих событий, произошедших между рождением и лингвистической зрелостью. В течение этого периода дети обнаруживают исходные материалы в звуках (или жестах) своего языка, узнают, как они собираются в более длинные строки, и сопоставляют эти комбинации со значением. Эти процессы разворачиваются одновременно, требуя, чтобы дети

интегрировали свои способности по мере обучения, чтобы взломать код общения, который их окружает. Несмотря на уровни сложности, каждый из которых в настоящее время недоступен современным компьютерам, маленькие дети с готовностью решают лингвистические головоломки, стоящие перед ними, даже превосходя их входные данные, когда им не хватает ожидаемой структуры.

Не менее решительно исследователи разрабатывают различные методологии, чтобы раскрыть механизмы, лежащие в основе овладения языком. За несколько месяцев до того, как младенцы произнесут свое первое слово, их ранние механизмы изучения языка могут быть изучены путем записи тонких реакций на новые комбинации звуков. Как только дети начинают связывать слова вместе, эксперименты с использованием показателей языковой обработки в реальном времени могут выявить способы интеграции лингвистической и нелингвистической информации во время прослушивания. Естественные эксперименты, в которых дети сталкиваются с минимальным воздействием языка, могут выявить степень врожденных способностей к изучению языка и их влияние на создание и изменение языка. По мере развития этих и других методов исследования сознания ребенка и интеграции их результатов они откроют ребенку решение головоломки изучения языка.

1.1.2. Лучшее время для изучения иностранного языка

Сегодня просвещенные школьные системы знают лучше. Иностранные языки ознакомились в начальной школе. Маленькие дети учатся легче, чем старшеклассники. Но современные исследования говорят, что для того, чтобы действительно сделать это правильно, начните еще раньше. Начните, когда ребенок изучает первый язык. Младенцы обладают удивительной способностью к поглощению. И в современном сложном мире иностранный язык – это не роскошь, а необходимость. Теперь мы знаем, что изучение иностранного языка дает детям удивительные преимущества. Исследования продемонстрировали улучшенную способность к общению, лучшее

когнитивное развитие, более широкую культурную осведомленность и, в конечном счете, лучшие возможности трудоустройства для тех, кто знает иностранный язык Феррейра, Ф. и Моррисон, Более того, все сегодняшние дети должны будут владеть двумя языками к тому времени, когда они поступят в колледж. Исследования показывают, что с рождения до 10 лет-лучшее время для того, чтобы познакомить ребенка с новыми языками. В этой статье ребенок быстрее выучит язык, лучше сохранит его и чаще всего будет говорить на нем с почти родным произношением. Недавние исследования показывают, что маленький ребенок в возрасте до 5 лет может изучать и обрабатывать до пяти языков!

1.1. Начните изучать язык

Дети начинают изучать языки с рождения (младенцы обращают внимание на голоса своих родителей, в отличие от случайных шумов или даже других языков), и по-настоящему не овладевают ими до десяти лет. Действительно, мы никогда по-настоящему не прекращаем изучать наш язык. (Дэвид Синглтон.) Это не совсем то поведение (например, жеребята, гуляющие через час после рождения), которое мы называем "инстинктом" у животных.

Но, по крайней мере, это не требует усилий, не так ли? Ну, нет, как мы видим, когда у детей есть выбор языков для изучения.

Мы обнаружили, что, откровенно говоря, дети не учат язык, если им не удастся его выучить.

Основные этапы изучения языка

Первый этап – Изучение звуков

Когда рождаются дети, они могут издавать и слышать все звуки на всех языках мира. Это около 150 звуков примерно на 6500 языках! Однако ни один язык не использует все 150 звуков. Звуки, которые использует язык, называются фонемами, а в английском языке их около 44. Некоторые языки используют больше, а некоторые-меньше.

На этой стадии дети узнают, какие фонемы принадлежат языку, который они

изучают, а какие нет. Способность распознавать и воспроизводить эти звуки называется “фонематической осведомленностью”, что важно для детей, обучающихся чтению.

Второй Этап – Изучение Слов

На этом этапе дети, по существу, узнают, как звуки в языке сочетаются друг с другом, чтобы придать смысл. Например, они узнают, что звуки “*m*”, “*ah*”, “*m*” и “*ee*” относятся к тому “существу”, которое их обнимает и кормит – маме. Это важный шаг, потому что все, что мы говорим, на самом деле просто поток звуков. Чтобы понять смысл этих звуков, ребенок должен уметь распознавать, где заканчивается одно слово и начинается другое. Они называются “границы слов”.

Однако дети учатся не совсем словам. То, что дети на самом деле изучают, - это морфемы, которые могут быть или не быть словами. На самом деле это не так запутанно, как кажется. Морфема-это просто звук или звуки, которые имеют значение, как слово “*тотту*.” Слово *тотту*, однако, имеет две морфемы: *тотту* и *±s*. Дети на этой стадии могут распознать, что *±s* означает “более одного”, и будут знать, что, когда этот звук добавляется к другим словам, он означает то же самое – “более одного”.

Этап Третий – Изучение Предложений

На этом этапе дети учатся составлять предложения. Это означает, что они могут расставлять слова в правильном порядке. Например, они узнают, что по-английски мы говорим “Я хочу печенье” и “Я хочу шоколадное печенье”, а не “Я хочу печенье” или “Я хочу шоколадное печенье”.

Дети также узнают разницу между грамматической правильностью и значением. Ноам Чомский создал пример этого различия в предложении “Бесцветные зеленые идеи спят яростно.” Дети будут знать, что, хотя предложение грамматически правильно, оно не имеет смысла. Они знают, что зеленый-это цвет и поэтому не может быть бесцветным.(Harrison, B., & Pava, R. (2005)

1.1. ДЕТИ ЛЕГКО УЧАТ ЯЗЫКИ

Представьте, что вы столкнулись со следующей проблемой. Вы должны обнаружить внутреннюю структуру системы, которая содержит десятки тысяч единиц, созданных из небольшого набора материалов. Эти блоки, в свою очередь, могут быть собраны в бесконечное количество комбинаций. Хотя только подмножество этих комбинаций является правильным, само подмножество для всех практических целей бесконечно. Каким-то образом вы должны сойтись на структуре этой системы, чтобы использовать ее для общения. А ты еще очень маленький ребенок.

Эта система-человеческий язык. Единицы-это слова, материалы-это небольшой набор звуков, из которых они построены, а комбинации-это предложения, в которые они могут быть собраны. Учитывая сложность этой системы, кажется невероятным, чтобы простые дети могли обнаружить ее основную структуру и использовать ее для общения. И все же большинство делает это с готовностью и легкостью, и все это в течение первых нескольких лет жизни.

Маленькие дети идеально подходят для изучения иностранного языка. Развивающийся мозг запрограммирован на овладение языком-никогда больше это не будет так естественно или так легко!

1.4.1. Дети учат иностранный язык естественным путем

Знакомство вашего ребенка с иностранным языком в раннем возрасте позволяет ребенку оптимизировать свой потенциал в обучении, помогая формировать мозг на его наиболее гибкой стадии. Маленькие дети идеально подходят для изучения иностранного языка. Изучение иностранного языка в молодом возрасте когнитивно так же просто, как изучение родного языка.

Маленькие дети могут овладеть беглостью, подобной родной, так же легко, как они научились ходить. Там, где взрослым приходится работать с устоявшейся системой первого языка, изучая явные грамматические правила и практикуясь в зубрежке, маленькие дети учатся естественным образом,

интуитивно впитывая звуки, структуры, интонационные паттерны и правила иностранного языка, как они это делали на своем родном языке. Молодой мозг по своей природе гибок, уникально запрограммирован на естественное овладение языком.

Раннее детство-лучшее время для овладения языком. Легкость изучения иностранного языка уменьшается с возрастом. Между рождением и подростковым возрастом мозг запрограммирован на естественное овладение языком. По мере того как ребенок приближается к половому созреванию, характер изучения и хранения языка меняется, становясь менее гибким.

Почему дети хорошо изучают языки, когда даже взрослые, которые хотят их выучить, испытывают с ними проблемы? Помимо врожденных способностей, у детей есть ряд мощных преимуществ:

- Они могут посвятить этому почти все свое время. Взрослые считают, что полчаса занятий в день обременительны.
- Их мотивация очень сильна. Взрослым редко приходится проводить много времени в компании людей, с которыми им нужно поговорить, но они не могут; дети могут получить очень мало того, что они хотят, не изучая язык(языки).

Если бы взрослые могли оказаться в подобной ситуации, они вполне могли бы изучать языки так же легко (я не говорю "легко"!), Как и дети. Самая близкая такая ситуация, которую я могу себе представить, - это межкультурный брак. И действительно, это работает довольно хорошо. Моя жена, например, носительница испанского языка, которая приехала сюда в конце 20-х годов, выучила исключительный английский, так как мы говорим на нем дома. Напротив, некоторые из ее испаноязычных друзей того же возраста, женатых на других испаноязычных, говорят по-английски запинаясь и с сильным акцентом.

2. ВЫВОД

Английский язык должен быть более чем одним курсом, и его можно использовать в качестве научного языка и других учебных курсов. Например,

курсы естественных наук, истории, социальных наук или биологии должны преподаваться на английском языке. Таким образом, значительно увеличивается мощность и скорость изучения языка. Начальная школа и дети-лучший курс для изучения языка. Потому что изучение языка с родным языком в первое десятилетие жизни обеспечивает студентам-инвалидам самостоятельность и направляет язык без перевода, устного перевода и меняет его значение с персидского на изучение английского языка в своем уме. Это означает, что человек сможет говорить как на родном языке, не включая в свой разум персидский и английский. Раннее детство-лучшее время для овладения языком. Легкость изучения иностранного языка уменьшается с возрастом. Между рождением и подростковым возрастом мозг запрограммирован на естественное овладение языком. По мере того как ребенок приближается к половому созреванию, характер изучения и хранения языка меняется, становясь менее гибким. Многие эксперты считают, что изучение языка в возрасте до десяти лет позволяет детям говорить правильно и свободно, как коренному жителю. Поэтому, каким бы ранним ни был ребенок, знакомый с иностранным языком, у него больше шансов овладеть им. С другой стороны, изучение языка, за исключением родного языка, может обеспечить развитие на протяжении всей жизни способности к большему общению с другими людьми.

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ИНГЛИЗ ТИЛИ ДАРСЛАРИДА МАҚОЛ ВА МАТАЛЛАРДАН САМАРАЛИ ФОЙДАЛАНИШ УСУЛЛАРИ

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Аннотация: Ушбу мақола талабаларга мумтоз адабиёт “Бобурнома”да қўлланилган мақол ва маталлар, фразеолгик бирликларнинг мазмун ва аҳамиятини мисоллар таҳлили ва инглиз тилига таржимаси орқали қизиқарли ва мунозарали ўқитишга қаратилган

Калит сўзлар: мақол, матал, фразеолгик бирликлар, таржима, Бобурнома

Олий ўқув юрти талабаларини инглиз тилига ўргатишга қизиқтириш, ўқув режасидаги белгиланган мавзунини тўла тўқис етказиб бериш учун дарс жараёнида мақол ва маталлардан фойдаланиш муҳим омил бўлади. Қизиқтириш оддийгина даъват этишгина эмас, балки талабанинг ҳис хаяжонини олмасдан туриб, кўзда тутган мақсадга эришиб бўлмайди. Шунинг учун ҳам ҳар бир тил ўқитувчиси талабаларни идрок этишга ўргатиши лозим. Идрок этиш-ўрганилаётган нарса моҳиятини англаб етмоқ, уни маълум нарса билан қиёслаш, қўлланиш усуллари билиши демакдир. Агар талабалар эътиборига ҳавола қилинаётган материални тушунмасалар, демак идрок этиш кузатилмайди [3. 166-167]. Тушуниш тафаккур қуроли ва амалий ҳаракат орқали содир бўлади.

Лексикологиянинг энг катта бўлими фразеология соҳаси доимо баҳс мунозаралрига бой ва эскирмайдиган, янгиланиб турувчи қатламдир. Мақол ва маталлар, фразеолгик бирликлар халқ хазинаси бўлгани каби уларнинг таржималарини талабаларга ўргатишда ҳам энг қизиқарли жараён.

Мумтоз адабиёт “Бобурнома” инглиз тилига Ж. Лейден ва В. Эрскин (1826) С. Бевериж (1921) ва В. Текстонлар (1996) томонидан таржима қилинган. Бир неча йиллар давомида ўрганилган ва дунё тилларига қайта қайта таржима қилинишининг сабаби ундаги ҳаётий мисоллар ва маълумотларни кўплиги ва ишонарлилигида.

Дарс жараёнида талабаларга мумтоз асарларимизда қўлланган мақол орқали ўргатганимизда дарс янада қизиқарли бўлади. Шу мақсадда “Бобурнома”дан *Тоглари элларига муносиб тушубтур, нечукким, “тенг бўлмагунча тўш бўлмас”* Оламда мундоқ ярамас вазълиқ тоғлар кам бўлгай[2,115] парчасини мисол қилиб оламиз. Ушбу келтирилган парчада ажратиб ёзилган жумлалар Бобур томонидан қўлланган мақолдир. “Бобурнома” лексикаси ҳозирги кун ўқувчисига тушунарли эмас, шунинг учун талабаларингиз аслият матни ёки мақол мазмунини тўлиқ тушунишини тامينлаш учун уларга мавҳум бўлган мақол *“тенг бўлмагунча тўш бўлмас”*ни мазмунини очиб беришимиз керак. Шунини айтиш лозимки бу берилаётган мисолларни инглиз йўналишидаги юқори курс талабаларига таржима назарияси, бадий таржима фанларида олиб бориш мумкин.

Энди биз *тўш* сўзининг маъноларини луғатдан аниқлаб оламиз: 1. гўшт; 2. ҳайвоннинг кўкрак қисми; 3. дўст. Биз учун учинчи *дўст* маъноси тўғри келади. Аслият матни талаба учун ойдек равшан бўлди. Берилган парчани инглизча таржималарини қиёслаб олишга имконият яратилди.

Мақол таржимасини амалга оширишда мақол мазмунини яхши англаган ҳолда “Бобурнома” асарида келтирилган *Тоглари элларига муносиб тушубтур, нечукким, “тенг бўлмагунча тўш бўлмас”* Оламда мундоқ ярамас вазълиқ тоғлар кам бўлгай ни уч турдаги Ж. Лейден ва В. Эрскин (1826) С. Бевериж (1921) ва В. Текстонлар (1996)нинг таржималарида қиёсан ўрганамиз.

Ж.Лейден ва В. Эрскинларнинг 1826 йилда амалга оширилган таржимасида: *At the same time, the mountain are worthy of the men; as the*

proverb says, “*A narrow place is large to the narrow-minded*”. There are perhaps scarcely in the whole world such dismal-looking hillcountries as these [4, 152]. Талабалар билан биргаликда таржима қилинади. Мазмуни: Шу билан бирга тоғлари ҳам эркакларига мос; шундай мақол борки, “**Топ жойда ақли топ кишилар**” Бу балки мамлакатдаги энг хунук, нотекис жойдир.

Яна худди шу аслият матни таржимаси Сусанна Беверижда: *Their people take after them, just as has been said, Ting bulmaghuncha tush bulmds. "A narrow place is large to the narrow-minded" Likely enough the world has few mountains so useless and disgusting* [1, 223, and 289]. Мазмуни: Одамлари ҳам ўзларига ўхшаган, худди айтишларига кўра, “**Топ жойда ақли топ кишилар**”. Бу каби бефойда ва ифлос тоғлар дунёда кам ёки ҳеч бўлмас. Талабалар ўзларининг таржима вариантларини берадилар.

Ниҳоят 1996 йилда “Бобурнома” нинг инглизча таржимаси Вильер Текстонда: *They are worthy of their inhabitants, as the proverb says, “There is no noon without a dawn.” There are few such worthless mountains in the world* [5, 167]. Мазмуни: Аҳолиси ҳам ўзларига муносиб, мақол борки, “**Тонг бўлмаганча туш бўлмас**”. Бунчалик қадри паст тоғлар дунёда кам бўлур. Кўриб турибмизки аслиятдаги мақол мазмуни, *тенгни тонг маъносида, тўшни туш* инглизча *noon-afternoon* даги *noon* каби тушунган. Аслида *ижтимоий ва манавий келиб чиқиш нуқтаи назардан ҳар қандай инсон дўст бўлолмайдди, тенг бўлмагунча дўст бўлолмас* “**тенг бўлмаганча тўш бўлмас**” эди.

Юқоридаги таржималарнинг хато берилиши аслиятдаги мақол мазмунини таржимон яхши англаб етмаганлигидандир. Баҳс мунозарага сабаб бўладиган мақоллар таржимаси анча мушкул вазифа. Бунинг учун мақолларни таржима қилишда таржима методларидан: эквивалентларини қўллаш, аналогларини топиш, калька усулида ва тасвирий таржима, трансформацион методларидан фойдаланиш даркор. Таржимонлар Жон Лейден ва Вильям Эрскин, Сусанна Беверижлар тасвирий таржимани

қўллаган, Вильер Текстон калька методини қўллаган лекин барча таржималар хато бўлиб чиққан, сабаби улар аслиятдаги мақол “*менг бўлмагунча тўш бўлмас*” ни яхши идрок этмаган. Энди тўғри вариантни бериш ўқитувчи зиммасига юкланади ва у ниҳоят “*No equals never make friends*”, -деб берилиш керак эди, дея талабаларга кўмаклашади.

Талабаларга вазифа қилиб яна шу каби мақолларни таржима қилиш учун топшириқлар берилади. Масалан, *Қуйидаги мақолларни мақолларни таржима методлардан фойдаланиб таржима қилинг:*

1. **Шўр тупрок ерда сунбул битмайди, ундай ерда умид уруғини нобуд қилма, шунга ўхшаш ёмонларга яхшилик ва яхшиларга ёмонлик қилиш ҳам ўрнида бўлмайди**

[2, 149].

2. **Ҳарчи дар оина жавон бинад, Пир дар хишти пухта он бинад.** Аслиятдаги тожикча иборалар талабага тушунарли бўлмаганда унинг табдил варианты ҳам берилиши шарт. “**Ёш киши ойнага қараб нима кўрса, кекса одам хиштга қараб, ундан ҳам яхшироқ кўради**” [2, 159].

3. **Масал борким, “Қопудағини қопмаса, қаригунча қайғурур”** Вақти чоғ ишни қилмаса қаригунча ундан афсусланиб юради.

4. **Ишлар вақтида бажарилиши керак, вақтида бажарилмаган иш суст бўлади, суст** [2, 74].

Ўқув дастурида режалаштирилган мавзуни мукамал ўтиш учун вақт етмаслиги мумкин, шунинг учун фразеологик бирликлар ва мақоллар, маталлар ва афоризмларнинг таржималари билан ишлаган ўқитувчи мустақил иш, курс иши учун материал танлайди ва тавсия қилади, уларни ишга ҳозирлайди. Кўзда тутган матнни ўргатиш учун махсус саволлар қўйиб, топшириқлар беради. Мақоллар, фразеологик бирликлар билан ишлаётган талабаларни кузатади, уларнинг саволларига жавоб бериб, мустаҳкамлаб боради. Тушунмаган қоидаларни тушунтиради, топшириқларни бажаришга кўмаклашади.

Тавсиялар. Мақоллар мавзусини ўрганишда аниқ (ёки таниш) адабиёт кўрсатилиши лозим, танланган мақоллар баҳс мунозарага сабаб бўладиган фаол бўлиши керак, келгусида талабалар томонидан турли хил саволларга ўқитувчи жавоб беришга аввалдан тайёр бўлиши лозим, мақолларни ўргатиш жараёнида талабалар томонидан берилиши мумкин бўлган муаммо ечими ишлаб чиққан бўлиши керак.

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**ЛИЦЕЙ ЎҚУВЧИЛАРИ ЎРТАСИДА ОЎЗАКИ ХОРИЖИЙ НУТҚНИ
РИВОЖЛАНТИРИШ УСУЛЛАРИНИНГ ЎЗИГА ХОС ХУСУСИЯТЛАРИ
ТЎҒРИСИДА**

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Чет тилини ўқитишнинг замонавий усуллари оғзаки-тилшунослик каби тоифаларга асосланган: вазият, рол, мавқе, жамоат, алоқа тури ва соҳаси, улар замонавий илм-фанда оғзаки мулоқот моделлари сифатида қаралади.

Коммуникатив вазиятни яратиш учун тўртта омилни ажратиш мумкин: 1) алоқа амалга ошириладиган ҳақиқий (вазият) ҳолатлар; 2) суҳбатдошлар ўртасидаги муносабатлар; 3) нутқ истаги; 4) нутқ учун янги муҳитни яратадиган алоқа ўрнатиш.

Ушбу омилларнинг ҳар бири, нутқка ўргатишнинг кўриб чиқиладиган усули, суҳбатдошларнинг нутқига маълум даражада таъсир қилади (мавзуни танлаш ва унинг ривожланиш йўналиши, тил воситаларини танлаш, унинг ривожланиши, ва бошқалар.)

Нутқка ўргатиш услубининг яна бир муҳим таркибий қисми - бу алоқа тури. Одамларнинг нутқий алоқалари мулоқотда иштирок этадиган шахслар

сони, улар ўртасидаги муносабатларнинг моҳияти, маърузачининг ва тингловчининг ролларини алоқанинг бир ҳаракатида ўзгариши билан фарқ қиладиган шароитларда юзага келади - бу индивидуал, гуруҳлараро ва жамоавий алоқа.

Индивидуал мулоқотда икки киши иштирок этади. Гуруҳ мулоқотида бир нечта одамлар битта алоқа актида катнашадилар (дўстлар билан суҳбат, ўқув машғулотли, учрашув). Жамоавий алоқа нисбатан кўп сонли шахслар билан амалга оширилади.

Ўз навбатида, мулоқотни расмий ва норасмийга ажратиш мумкин. Расмий алоқа ўзаро муносабатлари муайян ижтимоий вазифаларни бажариши билан белгиланадиган одамлар (ўқитувчи - ўқувчи, бошлиқ - бўйсунувчи) ўртасида пайдо бўлади. Бунга учрашувлар, интервьюлар, брифинглар, музокаралар кириши мумкин. Расмийлик ҳар қандай шаклда оммавий мулоқотга хосдир. Норасмий мулоқот одамларнинг хатти-харакатларида ҳам, нутқ охангида ҳам осонлик, эркинлик, кўпинча танишлик, лисоний воситаларни танлаш эркинлиги билан ажралиб туради.

Нутққа ўргатишнинг замонавий методикаси норасмий мулоқотнинг икки турини - иш юзасидан суҳбат ва эркин суҳбатни ажратиб туради. Иш юзасидан суҳбатни оғзаки бўлмаган фаолиятнинг зарур бўғини, оғзаки бўлмаган ҳаракатлардан келиб чиқадиган муаммоларни ҳал қилиш воситаси сифатида кўриш мумкин. Эркин суҳбат - бу мустақил алоқа фаолияти ёки шундай фаолиятки, унинг мақсади алоқа ўрнатиш, ўзаро тушуниш, билим, кўникмага, ижтимоий қадриятлар (эътиқодлар) тизимига, бошқа одамнинг хиссий ҳолатига таъсир ўтказишдир. Оғзаки мулоқотнинг ижтимоий-маданий соҳасида эркин суҳбат асосий, энг кенг тарқалган алоқа тури бўлиб хизмат қилади.

Шундай қилиб, мавжуд ўқитиш услубларининг афзалликлари қуйидагиларни ўз ичига олади:

1. Коммуникатив вазиятнинг тўртта омилини ишлаб чиқиш: а) алоқа амалга ошириладиган ҳақиқий (вазият) ҳолатлар (шу жумладан, бегоналарнинг

борлиги); б) коммуникаторлар ўртасидаги муносабатлар (субъектив равишда - суҳбатдошнинг шахсияти); в) нутқ мотивацияси; д) нутқ учун янги муҳитни яратадиган алоқа ўрнатиш.

2. Одатий коммуникатив вазиятни ривожлантириш, масалан: харидор ва сотувчи ўртасидаги суҳбат, ўқитувчи ўқувчи билан, олимлар ўртасидаги суҳбат, яқинлар учрашуви ва бошқалар.

3. Мулоқотнинг уч турини тақсимлаш: индивидуал, гуруҳлараро ва жамоавий.

4. Нутқий алоқа моделларини ишлаб чиқиш: а) расмий индивидуал алоқа; б) иш юзасидан суҳбат; в) эркин суҳбат; г) расмий гуруҳ суҳбати; д) гуруҳ суҳбатида монолог; е) жамоавий мулоқот.

5. Оғзаки мулоқотнинг саккизта соҳасини тақсимлаш: а) хизмат кўрсатиш соҳаси; б) оилавий соҳа; в) касбий ва меҳнат соҳаси; в) жамоат фаолияти соҳаси; г) маъмурий-ҳуқуқий соҳа; д) ўйинлар ва сеvimли машғулотлар соҳаси; е) оммавий кўнгилочар соҳа.

Замонавий ўқитиш методикасининг камчиликлари қаторига қуйидагилар киради.

а) фонетик нутқ кобилиятларини шакллантиришнинг ривожланмаганлиги; б) лексик нутқ кўникмаларини шакллантиришнинг такомиллашмаганлиги; в) ўқувчиларда индивидуал лексик ва семантик кўникмаларни ривожлантириш услублари ишлаб чиқилмаганлиги; г) монологик нутққа ўргатиш методикаси ишлаб чиқилмаганлиги.

Гапиришни ўрганишда асосий кийинчиликларга мотиватсион муаммолар киради, масалан:

- ўқувчилар чет тилларида гаплашишдан уялишади, хато қилишдан кўрқишади, танқид қилинади;

- ўқувчилар нутқ вазифасини тушунмайдилар;

- ўқувчиларда муаммони ҳал қилиш учун тил ва нутқ воситалари етарли эмас;

- ўқувчилар маъруза мавзусини у ёки бу сабабларга кўра жамоавий муҳокамага жалб қилинмайди;

- ўқувчилар чет тилида мулоқотлар давомийлигини керакли даражада сақламайдилар.

Чет тилида сўзлашишни ўргатишнинг мақсади ўқувчининг нутқдан ташқари нутқ амалиётида ўқувчилар томонидан умумий қабул қилинган кундалик мулоқот даражасида фойдаланишга имкон берадиган бундай нутқ кўникмаларини шакллантиришдир.

Ушбу мақсадни амалга ошириш ўқувчиларда қуйидаги мулоқот қобилиятларини шакллантириш билан боғлиқ:

а) маълум бир алоқа ҳолатига, нутқ вазифасига ва коммуникатив ниятига мувофиқ равишда чет тилидаги матн ва нутқларни тушуниш ва шакллантириш;

б) ўзларининг нутқий ва нутқий бўлмаган хатти-ҳаракатларини, алоқа қоидаларини ва тили ўрганилаётган мамлакатнинг миллий-маданий хусусиятларини ҳисобга олган ҳолда амалга ошириш;

в) чет тилини ўзлаштиришнинг оқилона усулларида фойдаланиш, унда ўз-ўзини ривожлантириш.

Чет тилида мулоқот қилиш қобилияти, шунингдек, ўқувчиларда тилларни маданиятлараро алоқа воситаси сифатида ўзлаштириш жараёнини энг самарали қиладиган баъзи бир фазилатларни шакллантиришни назарда тутди.

Ҳозирда ўқувчида қуйидагиларни тарбиялаш ҳақида гап кетмоқда:

- ўрганилаётган тилга, ушбу тилда сўзлашадиган одамларнинг маданиятига қизиқиш ва ижобий муносабат;

- ўзини маълум бир лингвистик ва маданий хамжамиятга, шунингдек, умуминсоний онга тегишли шахс сифатида тушуниш;

- чет тилини ўрганиш муҳимлигини англаш;

- ўз-ўзини тарбиялашга бўлган эҳтиёж.

Шунингдек, ўқувчиларнинг умумлисоний, интеллектуал, когнитив қобилиятларини, чет тилидаги мулоқотни ўзлаштириш асоси бўлган ақлий

жараёнларни, шунингдек, хиссиётларни, ўқувчиларнинг ҳис-туйғуларини, уларнинг мулоқотга тайёрлигини, турли ҳил жамоавий мулоқот маданиятининг ўзаро таъсирини ривожлантириш муҳимдир.

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МЕТОД ИГРОВОГО ПРОЕКТИРОВАНИЯ КАК КРЕАТИВНЫЙ ПОДХОД ТЕХНОЛОГИИ ЭДЬЮТЕЙНМЕНТА

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Аннотация. В статье рассматриваются вопросы эффективного использования инновационных методов в процессе обучения русскому языку в высших учебных заведениях. Дается характеристика инновационного высшего учебного заведения. Предлагается применение метода игрового проектирования как креативного подхода технологии эдьютейнмента.

Ключевые слова: инновации, процессы, технологии, модернизация, проектирование, эдьютейнмент, образование, творчество.

Внедрение инновационных методов обучения в процесс обучения русскому языку является необходимым условием творческого и интеллектуального развития студентов. В системе современного высшего учебного образования Узбекистана инновационные процессы осуществляются в следующих направлениях: создание обновленного содержания образования, разработка и внедрение новых педагогических технологий, формирование новых видов учебных заведений. Изучением подобного рода изменений в педагогической практике занимается педагогическая инноватика. Наиболее кратко и понятно определение термину "педагогическая инноватика" дано Юсуфбековой Н.Р. Она трактует её как учение о создании педагогических новшеств, их оценки и освоении педагогическим сообществом, внедрением и распространением. Педагогическая инноватика непосредственно связана с модернизацией и инновационной деятельностью образования. [1, с.51]

Модернизировать образование означает улучшать его, что-либо меняя, привнося новизну и отказываясь от каких-то отживших, малоэффективных технологий, то есть, по сути вводить инновации. Разработка программы инновационной деятельности, направленной на создание, освоение, закрепление и распространение инноваций является первоочередной задачей инновационного образовательного учреждения. Современные высшие учебные заведения Узбекистана становятся центрами формирования инновационного развития. Инновационное высшее учебное заведение имеет ряд своих аспектов: инновационный вуз является конкурентным, занимает лидирующие позиции в образовательном пространстве, ведет инновационную научную деятельность, развивается на основе актуальных научно-обоснованных идей, концепций, подходов.

Применение инновационных технологий облегчает изучение, запоминание и закрепление профессиональных знаний, умений и навыков у студентов, способствует развитию и повышению профессиональных качеств

будущего специалиста, способствует выработке новых, оригинальных подходов к профессиональным ситуациям и к будущей профессии.

Одним из эффективных технологий является технология эдьютейнмента. Эдьютейнмент-это технология, которая включает в себя креативные подходы в организации обучения студентов, которые имеют желание учиться, поскольку они могут видеть практические результаты своей деятельности. Одним из креативных подходов является метод игровых проектов. Метод игрового проектирования выступает как возможное средство решения актуальных проблем при обучении русскому языку студентов узбекских групп. С точки зрения обучающей деятельности игровое проектирование бывает развивающим; по характеру когнитивной деятельности – исследовательским; по методу исследования – творческим; по смысловому аспекту – обучающим; по использованию – научным или прикладным; по количеству участников – индивидуальным или групповым; по продолжительности – краткосрочным (охватывает одну тему) или долгосрочным (охватывает несколько тем). Игровое проектирование формирует у студентов языковые, культурологические, коммуникативные, творческие, проблеморешающие, общенаучные, информационные, познавательные, коммуникативные, ценностно-смысловые, социальные компетенции. Метод игровых проектов включает реализацию следующих задач: выработать у студентов самостоятельное, критическое мышление, умение работать с информацией; научить размышлять, опираясь на знание фактов, закономерностей науки, делать обоснованные выводы, работать в команде, выполняя разные социальные роли; принимать самостоятельные аргументированные решения. Метод игрового проектирования имеет *педагогические основания* – свободное воспитание, опору на индивидуальный опыт учащихся, поисковую, исследовательскую ориентацию и *психологические основания* – гуманистическую психологию, естественную потребность учащихся в познании и исследовании. В организации игровых проектов роль преподавателя имеет

важное значение. Мастерство преподавателя определяется в совершенствовании искусства преподавания, научной и исследовательской деятельности, в подготовке творческих личностей и высококвалифицированных специалистов. Метод игрового проектирования может применяться как в аудиторной, так и во внеаудиторной деятельности. Метод игровых проектов позволяет организовать совместную работу нескольких преподавателей, носит характер сотрудничества, партнерства, которое возможно при гибком сочетании самостоятельности и ответственности студентов с управлением со стороны преподавателя; формирует креативно-интеллектуальную активность, коммуникативные умения, широкое усвоение информационных технологий; создает условия для творческой самореализации личности, способствующей повышению самооценки; формирует социальный опыт, умение видеть, выделять и решать социальные и профессиональные проблемы; расширяет социальные контакты, в ходе которых развивается умение взаимодействовать с разными людьми при решении проблем; развивает исследовательские способности к творческому сотрудничеству и формирует необходимое для профессиональной деятельности умение анализировать производственные проблемы, находить творческие пути их решения, осознавать ответственность за результаты общего труда; воспитывает инициативность, активность и самостоятельность студентов на занятиях русского языка.

Задания по методу игрового проектирования стимулирует студентов самостоятельному изучению русского языка на основе 3 принципов: связывают теорию с практикой, являются последовательными и доступными.

Ярким примером использования метода игрового проектирования при обучении русскому языку являются такие задания, как:

Задание №1 - изучить деятельность выдающихся мастеров ораторского искусства. Подготовить выступление на тему «Я оратор».

Задание №2. - познакомиться с традициями и обычаями русского народа, подготовить выступление, рассказать о национальных русских блюдах и приготовить их, поиграть в русские национальные игры, собрать пословицы,

Задание №3. - организовать виртуальное путешествие по городам, входящим в Золотое кольцо России, подготовить выступление об архитектурных достопримечательностях, древним местам этих городов.

Задание №4. - написание сценариев и воспроизведение театральных сцен из произведений русских писателей.

Задание №5. - работа с фильмом. Просмотреть фильм и составить вопросы к каждому кадру; ответить на вопросы преподавателя при просмотре фильма; озвучить фильм на основе письменно составленных вопросов и ответов; составить вопросы, раскрывающие содержание фильма (количество вопросов определяется преподавателем).

Заключение. Подводя итог вышеизложенному необходимо отметить, что обеспечить качество высшего образования можно эффективным внедрением в образовательный процесс передовых педагогических инновационных, информационных, коммуникативных технологий, также воспитанием студентов в духе патриотизма, уважения национальных традиций и ценностей, формированием духовно развитого и физически здорового поколения. Использование метода игрового проектирования как креативного подхода технологии эдьютейнмент дает возможность подготовить специалиста, который владеет не только теоретическими знаниями, но и практическими умениями и навыками, конкурентоспособного на рынке труда, ориентированного на успешное и эффективное решение профессиональных задач.

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*Theory and practice of translation, literary problems***KETMA-KET TARJIMA JARAYONIDA
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Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada tarjimashunoslik sohasini rivojlantirishning muhim omillaridan biri bo‘lgan maxsus yozuv, ya’ni semantografiya haqida gap boradi. Kichik tadqiqotda mazkur yozuvning dastlabki ixtirochilari tomonidan ishlab chiqilgan yozuv mexanizmlariga munosabat bildiriladi. Ayniqsa, ketma-ket tarjima jarayonida ushbu maxsus yozuv turining afzalliklari tushuntiriladi.

Kalit so‘zlar: *mnemonik, nota, segment, semantik, konsentratsiya, fiksatsiya, kursiv, semantografiya, kognitiv*

Tarjima yozuvi bilan bog‘liq dastlabki qoidalarni Jenevadagi mashhur tarjimonlar maktabi vakili J. Erberning asarlarida topish mumkin. U ketma-ket tarjima texnikasidagi asosiy omilni qayd qilib borishga chaqiradi, bu esa o‘z-o‘zidan tarjimonning unutishga qarshi kafolati hisoblanadi. Bundan tashqari, J.Eerber ta’kidlaganidek, eslatmalar, qayd qilishlar, ya’ni yozuvlar nuqtasi tarjimonlarning xotirasini hali hanus rivojlantirishga xizmat qiladi [3, 44].

Sorbonna professori D. Seleskovich tarjima notasini majoziy ma’noda "xotira tugunlari" deb ataydi [6,16-18]. Boshqa tadqiqotchilar ham mnemonik funksiyasi haqida gapirishadi. Shunday qilib, S.A. Burlyayning fikricha, yozuv "nafaqat jumlar bilan, balki jumlar guruhlar bilan ham ishlaydi, ko‘pincha nutq segmentlari bir necha daqiqaga cho‘zilgan ketma-ket tarjimonning tezkor xotirasiga tushadigan ortiqcha yukni olib tashlashga yordam beradi".

Bizga E.N. Sladkovskaya tomonidan taklif qilingan izchil tarjimaning ta'rifi qiziq tuyuladi. Sladkovskaya, bu yerda tarjima yozuvi tarjima faoliyatining ushbu turini amalga oshirishning sharti sifatida qaraydi: "Izchil tarjima - bu og'zaki tarjima faoliyatining bir turi bo'lib, unda tarjimon maxsus yozuvdan foydalanib idrok etadi va o'rganadi" [5, 67-76].

Shunday qilib, turli tadqiqotchilar ta'kidlashlaricha, semantografik (tezkor) yozuvidan foydalanish matndagi ma'lumotlarning miqdori bilan belgilanadi va uning asosiy maqsadi xotiradagi yukni yengillashtirishdir.

Yozuvning birinchi batafsil ta'rifi R.K. Minyar-Beloruicheva tomonidan aytilib, unga ko'ra qog'ozdagi maxsus belgilar semantik qo'llab-quvvatlanadigan fikrlar majmuidir [4, 27].

Ushbu ta'rif yozuv mavzusini qat'iy cheklaydi: asl xabarning semantik qo'llab-quvvatlash nuqtalari; qayd etish maqsadi: bayonnomani takrorlash; ijro etish usuli: qog'ozga mustahkamlash; shuningdek, yozuv bilan birga keladigan ikkita jarayonni, ya'ni avvalgisi - tanlov, keyingisi – ijro muammosini aniqlashga yordam beradi. Keyinchalik muallif ta'riflash, ajratish va tuzatish jarayonlarini, yozuv tizimini yordamchi xotira vositasi sifatida taqdim etishni, shu qatorda tarjimon tomonidan ketma-ket tarjimada olingan ma'lumotlarni tanlash va qayd etish qoidalarini birlashtiradi.

Yozuv funksiyalarining ta'rifiga D. Seleskovich kengroq kiradi. Uning ta'kidlashicha, "eslatmalar ikki tomonlama maqsadga ega: ular tahlil paytida bayonotning barcha tafsilotlarini jamlashga yordam beradi va ifoda paytida xotirani qayta faollashtiradi". Faraz qilaylik, D. Seleskovich tarjimon yozuvlari haqida nafaqat xotiraning yordamchi vositasi sifatida qaraydi, balki, ehtimol "konsentratsiya" orqali u diqqatni jamlash, idrokni ham tushunadi, bu yozishni yanada murakkab psixologik rang berish jarayoni sifatida ifodalaydi. Buni E.N. Sladkovskayaga nazar tashlagan holda tasdiqlaymiz. Sladkovskaya qayd etganidek, yozuv "har bir tarjimonga xos bo'lgan fiksatsiyaning individual usullari bilan bir

qatorda, insonni idrok etish va nutqni tahlil qilishning umumiy naqshlarini aks ettiruvchi tizimdir".

Shuni ta'kidlash kerakki, tarjima notasi tushunchasida turli mualliflar tomonidan berilgan izohlar bir-biriga juda yaqin. Ularning barchasi tezkor xotirani yuklab olish va u bilan bog'liq psixologik mexanizmlarni bir joyga jamlash uchun tarjimon tomonidan uzoq vaqt davomida so'zlash holatida maxsus tashkil etilgan ma'lumotni qayd etishni anglatadi. Shu bilan birga, bir xil hodisani bildiradigan atamalarning aniq xilma-xilligi, bizning fikrimizcha, tushuntirishni talab qiladi, chunki ular har doim ham bir xil tartibdagi toifalarga tegishli emas. Shunday qilib, bizning fikrimizcha, ro'yxatga olish tizimi yozuvning o'zi emas, balki "kursiv" atamasi ushbu hodisaning texnik tomonini ochib beradi.

Yuqorida aytilganlar bilan bog'liq holda, biz yangi atamani - tarjima semantografiyasini, uning fikriga ko'ra, yozib olishning barcha ko'rib chiqilgan funktsiyalari va jihatlarini o'z ichiga olgan holda joriy etish mumkin deb hisobladik. Ta'kidlash kerakki, u mualliflik huquqi bilan himoyalangan va tarjima faoliyati uchun ilgari ishlatilmagan.

Ilk bor "semantografiya" atamasini (yunoncha semanto "belgi" va grafo - "xat" dan) Charlz Bliss u ixtiro qilgan universal ramzlar tizimiga murojaat qilgan. Ch. Bliss 1897 yilda Avstriyada 20 tilda so'zlashiladigan mamlakatda tug'ilgan. Keyinchalik Shanxayda yashaydi va u yerda xitoy qahramonlari bilan qiziqadi. U turli xil lahjalarda gapiradigan xitoylar bir-birini oson tushunishlaridan hayron bo'ladi.

Ikkinchi jahon urushidan keyin Ch. Bliss Avstraliyaga ko'chib o'tdi va avtomobil zavodida ishladi. Bo'sh vaqtida u alifbo tartibida bo'lmagan yangi yozuvlar tizimini ishlab chiqdi, keyinchalik u semantografiya deb nomlandi. Ch. Bliss tizimiga aloqador, ya'ni savdo, sanoat va fan sohalariga oid turli xil tushunchalarni olishga imkon beradigan 100 ta asosiy belgilar kiritgan.

1949 yilda Ch. Bliss ushbu tizim haqida hikoya qiluvchi kitob yozdi, ammo u faqat 1965 yilda nashr etishga muvaffaq bo'ldi. Unda aytilishicha, "300 yil oldin buyuk Leybnits bir kuni kimdir universal simvolizmni - barcha tillarda o'qilishi

mumkin bo'lgan ($1 + 2 = 3$ kabi) oddiy simvollar tizimini ixtiro qilishni orzu qilgan. Ushbu tizim oddiy mantiq va semantikani ham o'z ichiga oladi ($1 + 2 = 4$ ni hech kim tan ololmasligi singari) ". Ko'plab olimlarning e'tirofiga ko'ra, bu Ch. Blissning qo'lidan kelgan narsa edi.

Ch. Bliss tomonidan tarjima qilinadigan "semantografiya" atamasidan tarjima faoliyatiga nisbatan foydalangan holda, birinchi navbatda, uning ma'nosini aniqlashga jiddiy e'tibor qaratmoqchimiz. Shunday qilib, tarjima semantografiyasi deganda biz ketma-ket tarjima jarayonidagi ma'lumotlarni to'liq va batafsil tahlil qilishga qo'l keluvchi yozuv jarayonini tushunamiz.

Bundan tashqari, biz ushbu kontseptsiyani eng muhim zamonaviy tarjima jarayoni deb hisoblaymiz, shuningdek, fiksaj (mahkamlash) usullarini ketma-ket tarjima jarayonida tarjimon tomonidan qo'llaniladigan umumiy va individual usullar sifatida belgilaymiz [1, 35]. Ushbu usullar va kirish ma'lumotlarini tez va aniq yozma ravishda yozib olishga yo'naltirilganligi sababli, tezkor yozish va qisqa yozish tushunchalari bilan bog'laymiz. Demak, semantografik yozuv jarayoni tarjimonning kognitiv va individ faoliyati bilan bog'liq [2, 12].

Xullas, ushbu faoliyatning bilvosita mahsuloti matn (yozuv) ko'rinishidagi yozuv bo'lib, jarayon qabul qilinayotgan ma'lumotning batafsil ifodalanishiga xizmat qiladi.

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PROBLEMS OF TRANSLATING PHRASEOLOGICAL UNITS IN ENGLISH

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Abstract: This article focuses on the problems faced by phraseological units in English translation and how to translate them. How to interpret the differences between the translated language and the original language is the main problem of the article. Translation methods such as substitution, omission, and word addition are described in detail in the translation process.

Key words: *translation, phraseological units, phraseological phrases, analogues*

Translation is the process of converting original text in one language into identical text in another. L. S. Barkhudarov defines translation "...as the process of converting a speech work (text) in one language into a speech work in another language while maintaining an unchanged content plan" [1: 174]. However, translation goes beyond simply replacing the units of one language with the units of another. Different cultures, traditions, and customs interact in the translation process. Translation is a great source of information about the languages involved in the translation process and the cultures to which these languages belong. Many phraseological phrases remind of the events of bygone days. At the same time, the new text should be easily interpreted and comply with all the norms of the language into which it is translated. Thus, the translator plays an important role as a guide between cultures. According to A. D. Schweitzer: "Translation is not only the interaction of languages, but also the interaction of cultures..."

The translation process "crosses" not only the borders of languages, but also the borders of cultures." [2: 8] Knowledge of phraseology greatly facilitates the perception of both modern journalism and classical fiction. And the use of phraseological units in colloquial speech makes it more expressive. English phraseology is difficult to translate due to the lack of a standard method for translating phraseological units. The presence of a phraseological dictionary does not guarantee the complete reproduction of all shades of the meaning of the construction. Therefore, translators have to look for other methods for translation. One of the frequent mistakes of the translator is the inability to notice phraseological units and their literal translation. Thus, a phraseological unit is often taken as a free combination of words. This leads to gross errors and distortion of the meaning of the statement. "John set a great store by the town where he grew up" - John opened a huge store in the town where he grew up. (Instead, the city where John grew up was very important to him.) "After the resounding success she decided to hang up her ax" - After the resounding success, she decided to hang up her axe. (Instead-After a resounding success, she decided to retire).

The next difficulty is perceiving a phraseological unit. The translator must select the translation option depending on the context. This is a problem, since the expression can be used with a touch of irony, sarcasm, resentment, bitterness or irritation. The translator should also take into account that most of the English phraseological units have multiple meanings. For example, the expression "to take the floor" in the political sphere means "«ВЗЯТЬ СЛОВО», «ВЫСТУПИТЬ», and in colloquial speech «ПОЙТИ ПОТАНЦЕВАТЬ». Depending on the situation, "you can never tell" can be translated as «ПОЧЕМ ЗНАТЬ» и «ЧЕМ ЧЕРТ НЕ ШУТИТ». [3: 136]. Often phraseological units have false counterparts, i.e. phraseological units that coincide with them in form but completely diverge in content. For example, "wind in the head" – пустое воображение, зазнайство (not «ветер в голове»); "run smb. to earth" – разыскать, достать из-под земли (not «загнать, закопать кого-л. в землю»); "stew

in one's own juice" – страдать из-за собственной глупости, расхлебывать кашу, которую сам заварил (not «вариться в собственном соку»).

The English expression "to be born with a silver spoon in one's mouth" is close in meaning to the Russian phraseology "to be born in a shirt (shirt)", i.e. to be lucky. Often these expressions are given as correspondences. But the English version can't be used in the same situations as the Russian one, because it means "come from a rich family". From a translation point of view, English phraseological units can be divided into two groups: 1. Phraseological units that have equivalents and analogues in the Russian language. These are Russian expressions and proverbs that coincide with English ones in content, expressiveness, grammatical composition and stylistic coloring. Such phraseological units include stable comparisons ("like two peas in a pod" – как две горошины в стручке, russian equivalent – похожи, как две капли воды; "like a red rag for a bull" – как красная тряпка для быка; "as thick as thieves" – водой не разольешь), пословицы и поговорки ("revenge is sweet" – месть сладка; "a first time for everything" – все когда-то бывает в первый раз; "the road to hell is paved with good intentions" – благими намерениями ад вымощен), глагольные словосочетания ("to take the bull by the horns" – взять быка за рога; "bite one's tongue" – прикусить язык; "rest on one's laurels" – почить (почивать) на лаврах; "kill time" – убить время; "to be green with envy" – зеленеть от зависти). 2. Non-equivalent phraseological units. Many English expressions have no analogues in the Russian language.

Basically, these are realities that do not exist in our country. For example, "a hot potato" – a case that you want to get rid of as soon as possible, or a current topic; "to hear something straight from the horse's mouth" – to hear first – hand, from a reliable source; "to be the apple of someone's eye" – to be loved by someone. When translating non-equivalent phraseological units, you can use calculus or descriptive translation [3: 138]. Based on the above, it can be concluded that when translating, the translator must take into account the fact that phraseological units are polysemantic. The translator, understanding the meaning of the statement, can use

such translation techniques as interpretation and description, choosing the option depending on the context.

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DEVELOPMENT OF THE FIRST SIMULTANEOUS TRANSLATION METHODS IN WESTERN COUNTRIES

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Abstract: Every nation in the world, every single nation, other nations, unique masterpieces that enrich the spirituality created by nations, have not only benefited from the discoveries, but also contributed to the treasury of world culture. There are no languages, nations, countries that have developed in their shell without the influence of languages, nations, countries. The history of translation is as ancient as the history of language, the history of the nation, the history of the country.

Key words: *translation, literature, art, culture, science of different peoples, foreign language, speech activities, important skill*

Thanks to independence, the demand for learning and teaching foreign languages in our country is growing. For the further development and prosperity of our country, which today strives to take its rightful place among the developed countries of the world, for our people, who are building their great future together with our foreign partners, perfect knowledge of foreign languages is very important.

Our President Sh.M. Mirziyoyev also paved the way for the development of the Republic in the field of science. Scientific research is also underway. It is known that the law on education pays special attention to the development of new technologies of teaching foreign languages, the use of intensive methods. To enjoy the achievements of urban countries, it is impossible to supply world-class professionals. We see that the pillars of a number of new laws proposed by the head of our state are based on terms that are new to our lives.

Linguists and translators are well aware that behind any term there is a life after life. Their entry into the national language field, and the extent to which the range of fields they represent are mastered within the language, are the focus of attention of translators and semiotics. It is clear from these documents that today's Uzbek language is enriched with colorful terms.

Translation is a very big and important role in human development, in its cultural life. Translation introduces people from one country or continent to the life, culture, customs, history, literature and science of people from another country. Through translation, we learn other cultures, and others learn the great Uzbek culture. If we want to understand each other's national and cultural features faster and better, we will have to translate the works of other nations.

The meaning of the word translation is very wide. Poems, works of art, scientific and popular science books in various fields of science, diplomatic documents, working papers, people's conversations, etc. are translated from one language to another. Of course, translation is the key to all of this.

Translation as a spiritual activity of mankind dates back to ancient times. It (translation) has played and continues to play a very important role in the history of culture of some nations, as well as in the history of world culture. K. Musayev, G. Salomov, A.V.Fedorov, LSBarkhudarov, worked hard, and in the field of translation history A.V.Federov, G. Gafurova, J.Sharipov, N.Kamilov and others made a great contribution.

Its scientific significance in both translation theory and the history of translation is of great interest in translation, which is its object. Translation is a creative activity related to language and literature, and the two languages are intertwined, in which the original the text is represented by other language tools. A number of questions arise with the process of comparing and translating languages. These questions, in turn, encourage them to analyze them, to study the specifics of each.

The study of the history of translation in close connection with the history of society, culture, history of literature is also a requirement of the time. However, it would be wrong to study them separately. how many scientists have worked.The main goal, as noted above, is to use past experiences to more accurately define our present and future lifestyles and not to repeat the mistakes made along the way.

As mentioned above, translation is an activity that serves to bring together the literature, art, culture, science of different peoples. For a student learning a foreign language, translation is all kinds of speech activities - listening, speaking, reading and writing. skills are equally important.

The study of the history of translation opens the way to a deeper understanding of this field, to the development of the science of translation and translation studies today, because it is impossible to create the future without knowing the history. It is time to seriously study these rare manuscripts, which embody the centuries-old life experiences, religious, moral and scientific views of our ancestors.

So what is the purpose of studying the history of translation? Along with the study of the history of translation, firstly, to show the contribution of Uzbek

literature, scholars to the treasury of world literature, secondly, to show the role of Uzbek literature in world literature, thirdly, the role of translation in the development of world science and culture clearly visible.

These works explore the various schools of translation history from antiquity to the present day, their activities, prominent figures, and the role of translation history in the development of modern translation trends.

"Nevertheless, many major monuments in the history of translation, the work of talented translators have not been studied," said G. Ostonova.

Translation occupies a worthy place in all national literatures with a centuries-old literary tradition. Therefore, it is safe to say that without creating a history of translation, the laws of translation have developed in each period, the same national. It is impossible to give a full, complete account of the history of that national literature without defining what schools of translation were formed in the development of literature and what role these translations played in the development of world culture. In the second half of the XX century, there was a slow process of translation from Germany into France. Even English realism could not influence him, and the focus on translation was still not growing.

In the twentieth century, much attention was paid to translation. This century was a century of translation. By the end of this century, British scholars A. Duff, A. Malle, L. Newmark, Naido and others studied the history of translation. Of course, they could not pass without looking at the past. In their book, *Approaches to Translation*, P. Newmar writes about translation, noting that the translation of the past has shifted its influence to the translation of the present.

The profession of translator is a very difficult activity, which serves to establish communication between countries, their culture, literature, customs. Through this type, "A Thousand and One Nights", "Shohnoma", "Qobusnoma", "Hamlet", "Romeo and Julietta", "Layli and Majnun", "Farhod and Shirin" and countless other literary and scientific masterpieces became the property of the peoples of the world.

It is known from the history of science and culture that the exchange of ideas through translation goes back a long way. In the developed countries of the world there are large schools of translation, translation schools. In particular, R. Toldeysky's Western European school of Translation (XII century), Among them are the Russian Translation Society (XVIII century), the Baikal Wisdom (House of Knowledge) in Baghdad, the Al-Ma'mun school, the Arabic Translation school (XVII century), and the Khorezm Translation School (XIX century) (O. Muminov, translation date T.1999).

In Armenia, "Translation Day" has been celebrated every year since the 5th century. In his work, P.I. Kapanov. describes the translator as a universal and artistically harmonious representative of the peoples who serve to unite and unite people in world culture.

The word "translation" has long been used in the Eastern sense of description, narration and explanation. Literary translation means not just translating a text from one language to another, but "recreating" it. Therefore, translation is a creation, a translator. it is no exaggeration to say that he is creative.

G. Salomov, one of the prominent scholars of Uzbek translation, gives such evidence in his works (Gaybullah Assalom, p. 10).

During one of his trips to India, the scientist was asked in which language he would write. When he was told that he would write in Uzbek, he was told that only his compatriots could read. The scholar said that his work had been translated into Russian and other languages, and that the translation and translation work was very well organized.

After that, the Uzbek writer Hamid Olimjon, Samad Qurgun, Gafur Gulam, Berdi Kerboboyev, Oybek will explain how and in what languages the works of famous writers and poets have been translated.

The problem of making unique cultural, literary, and scientific monuments, which have been created for thousands of years, the property of the people, has always been a dream of creativity in all times, and it needs translation.

There are two goals. One is the interest in learning books written in the languages of other nations around the world; the second is to distribute books written in their own language among the peoples of the world. (G.Salomov). As human beings speak different languages, translation has always been and will always be important. That is why the history of translation has been of interest to scholars for many years, but a number of problems in the history of translation have not been solved.

The history of translation in the United Kingdom can be divided into 4 stages:

1. The period from ancient times to the XII century.
2. Covers the XIII-XVII centuries.
3. XVIII- XIX centuries.
4. XX-early XXI centuries.

The main feature of the 1st stage is related to the spread of Christianity, and during this period Latin became the main international language in the West.

When talking about the development of the history of translation in the West, the English expert is, of course, primarily interested in the history of British translation..

Speaking about this, O. Muminov divides the history of translation of the United Kingdom into 4 periods:

1. The period from antiquity to the XII century.
- 2.XIII-XVIII centuries.
3. XVIII- XIX centuries.
- 4.XX century.

In addition to this, we think that the history of translation in the new XXI century has entered a new fifth period, and its specific features should be studied. First of all, given that today the development of science and technology, new information technologies are entering various spheres of life, including foreign language education, especially translation, this period also has its own characteristics.

As in various western countries, the first stage of the history of translation in the United Kingdom is associated with the spread of Christianity and the translation of the Bible into different languages. This is the period when Latin gained the status of an international language.

From the II century onwards, the Bible was translated into various Western languages, including English. The translation of the Bible into the languages of the peoples of Europe played an important role in the development of these languages. One of the features of the translation of that period was the translation of Latin mantas under each word.

Such a word translation method, of course, had flaws, lexical, syntactic errors and misunderstandings. As a result, free translation was used.

The Bible, which has been translated into various Western languages, has been translated in different ways by different translators. Western translators have placed great emphasis on the study and translation of inscriptions, mainly in Greek and Latin.

Renaissance In Britain, Alfred, the king of West Saxony, translated rare Renaissance works from Latin into the English Wessex dialect. His translation career dates back to 886-893.

The translation of the artistic property of the great works of the East into European languages has a long history. Interest in Eastern culture in the West dates back to the beginning of the ninth century. The southern regions of Spain, which belonged to the Arab Caliphate, had favorable conditions for the introduction of Eastern culture to the West, because at that time Europe lagged behind the East in all areas of human development. During this period, many powerful translators were able to benefit Europeans with the culture, science, art, and customs of the East by translating universal studies into Arabic into Latin.

As a result of this influence of the East on the West, new philosophical currents and freedom of speech emerged.

There were two major styles of Renaissance translation: literal translation and free translation, and there was a constant struggle between them.

At that time, Britain was also interested in oriental culture and art, and for several centuries Central Asia attracted the attention of the British. Samarkand, located on the Great Silk Road, was one of the favorite topics of English writers and poets. Famous Central Asian scholars Al-Farabi, Ibn Sina, Ahmad-Al-Farghani translated great figures from Arabic into English at the time.

Later, in the 16th century, Shakespeare's mentor K. Marlo wrote *The Great Temurlane* (1587) in the spirit of the East, influenced by the East. During this period, both in the East and in the West, a number of legends and stories about Amir Temur were written. The book "King of the Scythians" was published in Latin in the XVI century. In addition, Timur's Statutes were translated into several foreign languages and became popular in the West. The book was translated into English in 1830, into Urdu in 1845, and into Russian in 1894. A copy of this century, written in Turkish, has been preserved in Yemen and translated into Uzbek in 1991.

British tourists and traders were in contact with the countries of the East through Russia. The ancient peoples of Movaraunnahr, Samarkand and Bukhara were the centers of relations. J. Jersey, A. Jeniksok came to Bukhara and Urgench through Moscow and tried to establish trade and diplomatic relations. As a result, a number of words moved from one language to another. In the middle of the seventeenth century, Oriental centers were opened at the universities of Cambridge and Oxford in the United Kingdom, where he was taught Arabic, Turkish and Persian. This major revolutionary period in world history, especially in the history of translation and the development of languages.

After reviewing the sources on the history of translation studies, it can be said that the history of translation, especially the history of Oriental translation, has been thoroughly studied.

The Uzbek scholar G.Salomov, who is engaged in the theory and practice of translation, speaks about this in his scientific works, mentions the names of a number

of Russian scientists, in particular, an in-depth analysis of MM Rojanskaya's "Medieval Eastern Mechanics". (G. Salomov. Fundamentals of translation theory. Tashkent "Teacher" -1983, pp. 14-15)

There is a feature associated with translation, that some scientific and artistic works are not only in the hands of one people, but also in many countries around the world, and translation plays a key role in their dissemination in the languages of other peoples. At the same time, translation sometimes serves directly and indirectly in the spread of scientific and artistic ideas, images, ideas, new views, and in the form of pictures. MM Rozhanskaya also emphasizes in her works that through translation peoples are united. - those who thought with each other, the writers who communicated with each other. The culture, science, literature and art he has created have always benefited from the translation of literary, scientific and political works.

"But it must be reiterated that if the translation only served the purpose of making a new book appear in another language, and ending with that, it would be like the birth of a lifeless child."

Turning to the history of translation, the author writes that there were two great schools of translation in the history of world culture. One was the Baghdad School of Translation, which translated the works of ancient Greek scholars into Arabic, and the other was the translation of rich Arabic literature into Western European languages. Both schools of translation have played an unprecedented role in the development of world science. In many cases, even when the originals of works created by scientists are lost in vain, they are still the same. The translations made by the representatives of the two translation centers have been preserved. In particular, the unique works of thinkers who wrote in the Near and Middle East, Central Asia in Arabic, Latin and Greek, and later other Western European peoples, thanks to the translators of the Toledo school. It has connected, enriched, and enriched the cultures of the East and the West. served as a golden bridge without l.

Under the influence of the East to the West, new philosophical currents emerged. Thus, the Renaissance was a period of influence in Western Europe in the history of scientific development, cultural riches, and human culture of the East.

In the history of this day translation, two great principles of translation have been followed; the first is literal translation; the second is free translation. This required a good knowledge of ancient Latin and Greek, and critical views on the quality of translation began to emerge. The result was a struggle between those who supported the theory and practice of word-for-word and free translation.

During this period, the translation of classical literature in England intensified. Renaissance, Protestantism and the new aristocracy created all the conditions for this. The study of Central Asian science through translation took a long time. According to the English scholar Sam Russell, Central Asia has attracted the attention of the British for centuries. Samarkand has become a favorite subject of many English writers and poets. As mentioned above, from the twelfth century onwards, many Englishmen also studied in the madrasas of Baghdad, Kufa, Cordova, Damascus, and Farabi in order to study the Arabic language in depth. His contemporaries Daniel, Marley, and Robert Chester also translated many works into their home countries after studying them in Bukhara, Baghdad, and Damascus. Thus, the representatives of the Eastern translation schools translated many works into European languages, as a result of which the achievements in science, technology, culture, literature were popularized in the West, strong ties between peoples were established and the East played a worthy role in world civilization. who have proved that.

In conclusion, it is clear from the sources on the history of translation that there is not enough research work to study the history of translation. The life experiences of our ancestors over the centuries, thousands of works on religious ethics, philosophy, medicine, mathematics, physics, chemistry, astronomy, architecture and agriculture have been translated into other languages and contributed to world science and culture. These rare works should be seriously studied and enjoyed by today's readers.

It is well known that in both the East and the West, most of the written sources are translated works. The traditions of translation and literary relations go back many centuries.

The translator has the task of translating the masterpieces of the peoples of the world into their native language and making them available to the people.

The study of translated works is also important for the study of the history of translation. Because the principles, methods and techniques of translation, which are a unique field of creativity, have been improved over time, traditions have been formed and developed, mutual benefit, influence and literary-artistic ties have increased. Therefore, it is important to study each period of the history of translation, each translation separately.

The study of the history of the world's translation schools shows that since ancient times, Eastern translators have been engaged in the translation of religious, scientific, technical, literary and artistic works published in the West and used modern principles and methods. Western scholars, in turn, introduced the teachings and scientific inventions of the great thinkers of the East to their peoples and took advantage of these achievements.

We will try to gain a deeper understanding of the history of translation by studying the relationship, history, principles and methods of the two great schools of East and West, the Toledo and Baghdad translation schools.

Both schools played an important role in the development of world science. The original works of the scholars have been lost, but the translations of these works have been preserved by the representatives of these translation schools. Many books by classical Greek scholars have been lost due to various historical changes, but their Arabic translations and commentaries have survived. A number of valuable works by Middle Eastern and Central Asian thinkers, written in Arabic, have been translated into Latin, Greek, and later into other Western European languages by translators from the Toledo School of Translation. The translation acted as an incomparable golden bridge between the West and the East and enriched and enriched their culture.

In the late eighth and early ninth centuries, a group of scholars, translators, and rewriters appeared in Baghdad.

The Khorezm School of Translation in Central Asia (early XX century) has its own tradition of translating many historical works written in poetic style into prose in Turkic languages.

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ADVANTAGES AND DIFFICULTIES OF SIMULTANEOUS TRANSLATION

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Abstract: This article highlights the advantages and difficulties of simultaneous translation. To work in the simultaneous translation mode, you need a certain endurance and appropriate training that can develop speech reactivity in the translator. Next, the description of the types of simultaneous translation is revealed, several of its varieties are presented, and advice is given to simultaneous interpreters. A detailed description of simultaneous interpretation from the point of view of psychology is also given. The problem of teaching interpretation, and in particular simultaneous translation, is one of the most interesting and less developed problems in Uzbekistan.

Keywords: *interpreting, simultaneous interpreting, training, teaching simultaneous interpreting, translation mode*

In the "global village", which has become synonymous with the current world, translation plays a very important and so far irreplaceable role. Representatives of one of the first professions of the ancient world – translators spoke in "a thousand languages" and began their career since the time of the Tower of Babel. This was shortly after the golden age, when there was one tongue and one dialect in all the earth (Genesis 11: 1). The leading Russian scholar in the field of translation theory, V. N. Komissarov, wrote: "A great need for translators and interpreters will be caused by the further expansion of international contacts, exchange in the field of culture, sports, tourism, holding various international forums, meetings and negotiations, not

to mention the representation of our country in numerous international organizations, governmental and non-governmental." There are several types of translation. First of all, of course, the translation can be oral and written. Interpretation is divided into simultaneous and consecutive interpretation. Simultaneous interpretation involves the transmission of the meaning of a statement by means of another language simultaneously with the speaker's speech. This type of translation is used at conferences, major symposia, and summits, which are attended by representatives of different countries that do not always speak international languages at the proper level. This is probably the most difficult type of translation, requiring the utmost concentration and speed of reaction. After all, a simultaneous interpreter does not have the time necessary to select the right words and build a sane statement. He has to deliver the translation at the same time as the speaker, who, by the way, can not always boast of oratory. It is surprising, however, to what extent the participants in international meetings and contacts themselves misunderstand or greatly underestimate the work of those who give them the opportunity not only to communicate and get to know each other, but also to develop and sign documents and contracts. "By the way? Here's our translator?" - this is usually the first thing that an American interpreter, i.e. a simultaneous interpreter, hears when he comes to a meeting of an international forum. Thus, it is not taken into account. That in English, "translator" means a translator, and "interpreter" means an interpreter, and the difference between the work of translators and interpreters is huge. An Interpreter is a specialist in his field, for example, a surgeon in medicine. How would a surgeon like to be called a therapist?!

Simultaneous interpreters are interpreters of an oral form of translation, called simultaneous translation. There is another type of interpretation activity – sequential translation, when a specialist recreates the speaker's statements in the translating language at the time of the speaker's pauses. It turns out that the translator first listens and analyzes, and then pronounces the translated and adapted text. And with simultaneous translation, the translator recreates the speaker's statement at the same

time. This type of translation is used when accompanying forums, conferences and other major events, if necessary, to ensure mutual understanding of hundreds of participants. For the first time, simultaneous translation was used in 45, at the beginning of the Nuremberg trials, which is why it is considered a relatively new type of translation. An Interpreter does not wait for a pause, but translates the speaker continuously, without intermissions. In a few seconds, it should convey not only the meaning of the words, but also the tone, nuances and intonation of the person standing on the podium. A simultaneous interpreter must learn to simultaneously focus on the speaker's speech and listen to their own translation. The translator turns on and off his own microphone, which allows him to consult or talk with a work colleague. However, the microphone in the booth should not amplify the interpreter's voice, otherwise the loud sound of his own voice may drown out the speaker's voice. With such a high voltage, the synchronizer needs such conditions for work that would contribute to its efficiency. The written translation is "a lifeline," writes the Russian translator P. Palazhchenko.

If the simultaneous interpreter has such a circle, he can think through complex terms and even whole sentences in advance. If he has little time, it is best for him to pay primary attention to proper names, numerals, abbreviations, technical vocabulary, and syntactic difficulties. Most of the time in such a hurry should be given to the beginning and end of the text, since the mistakes here are most remembered by the listeners. Perhaps the most difficult role falls to the An Interpreter, when he has to deal with the uncertain and ultra-fast sources of the translated language. In particular, we are talking about videos and comments on slides, which are increasingly used as visual aids at international conferences today. In the eyes of an uninformed observer, a simultaneous interpreter is probably like a person who regularly tries to do dozens of different things at the same time, and eventually finds himself in danger of becoming an agitated neurotic. In the ability to be always in shape, in an instant reaction to each translated phrase, in the simultaneous juggling of concepts and thoughts, just lies the essence of the work of An Interpreters. As one of the

professionals in this field wrote, "there is no place among translators for the slow-witted or for the"verbally stupid". Psychologically, the working conditions of an interpreter are very difficult. The translator is not visible, anonymous, and therefore, naturally, is considered as part of the conference equipment or service. In English, the expressions conference facilities, communication aids, and electronic communications most often mean conference services, which include not only premises and equipment, but also translators. Another psychological press exerts its influence on the translator because in the sphere of his activity, everyone is rewarded only for errors. A translator is noticed not when he works brilliantly, but when he works poorly. They say that to translate means, first, to understand. In addition, to understand and translate, one mind is not enough-you also need talent, knowledge, and special training. Therefore, simultaneous translation is largely possible thanks to what is called probabilistic forecasting, which is the basis of many types of human activity. In order for the degree of probability in simultaneous translation to be as high as possible, it is necessary first to have a good idea of the topic (subject) that is being discussed at this conference, seminar or "round table".

All other things being equal (approximately the same language proficiency, reaction, and practical experience), a person who is "savvy" in this field translates immeasurably better than an amateur. Therefore, the study of not only the terminology, but also the essence of the matter is a prerequisite for an Interpreter. Why did simultaneous interpretation replace consecutive interpretation at the most important international congresses and conferences? For only one reason. Because after the Second World War, the number of working languages in the meeting rooms of representatives of various countries increased several times. The Soviet Union, China, and Latin America came to the forefront of international life. If before the Second World War, international organizations in their work were limited to two languages (French and English), then after the victory of the Allies over the Fascists, both Russian, Chinese, and Spanish became working languages. It is clear that in such circumstances, consecutive interpretation would require five times more

time for meetings (five official working languages) than simultaneous interpretation. As for the quality of the translation, there is no doubt that if there are qualified translators, consecutive translation will give better results in terms of accuracy, completeness, expression of expression and normativity of the translation text. Many people have never seen a classic sequential translation with notes.

In French and English, the other name is "conference translator". Let us focus on one more advantage of simultaneous translation. For the simultaneous interpreter to work effectively, it was necessary to isolate him from the noise of the meeting room, and to make his speech accessible to every recipient (listener). The second difficulty of simultaneous translation is related to the translator's reaction, or rather, to his reactivity. The An Interpreter is forced to react instantly every second to words perceived, to the ear, or rather, phrases. That is why simultaneous translation deters slow people, although they have excellent command of a foreign language. A good knowledge of two or more languages is not a prerequisite for the success of a simultaneous interpreter. Such a condition, rather, is the presence of an indispensable stock of equivalent pairs of lexical units, connected with each other by a sign connection, allowing you to translate not through analysis and synthesis, but in terms of the "stimulus-response" model, i.e., not through thinking, but through conditioned reflexes. It is in this direction that the training of simultaneous interpreters should also take place, which we will discuss in more detail later. The listed difficulties of simultaneous translation are redeemed by its invisible advantage. To work as a simultaneous interpreter, it is not necessary to have an impeccable command of the usual set of conversational standards of a foreign language.

Namely, this side of the speech of a foreigner, together with the pronunciation, gives out its "foreignness" when communicating with native speakers. And if the pronunciation, if desired, can be worked out in the most boring phonetic exercises, then to remember and correctly use the gender of nouns, the conjugation of irregular verbs, and most importantly, the endless exceptions to the rules, for a person even with an outstanding memory in conditions of isolation from the corresponding

language environment, is a task of extreme difficulty. So, we sum up the results from the position of the generally accepted provisions on simultaneous translation. Simultaneous interpretation is indeed carried out simultaneously with the speaker's speech, which gives a significant gain in time and banishes from the conference rooms minutes and hours of endless longing that engulfed those present waiting for translations of a speech delivered in a language unknown to them. That is why simultaneous interpretation has become a mandatory attribute of major international conferences. To work in the simultaneous translation mode, you need a certain endurance and appropriate training that can develop speech reactivity in the translator. Simultaneous translation is easier and better when translating from your native language to a foreign language, and not vice versa, as many believe. Considering all this, it can be stated that the "choice" of a simultaneous interpreter consists only in the appropriate professional training, which, as is known, is necessary for any specialist.

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SPECIFICS OF LITERARY TEXT TRANSLATION

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Abstract: This article is devoted to specificity of literary texts translation and significance of idea of concept and influence of culture to the language.

Keywords: *translation of literary texts, concept, phraseological units*

The current stage of the linguistic development of society and the strengthening of the educational and cultural integration of states in the world community requires extensive knowledge in the field of translation of various types of texts, in particular from English. In this regard, a substantial, theoretical and practical analysis is made of translations of texts relating to all spheres of human activity, the main of which are economic, diplomatic, scientific, technical and socio-cultural. It is known that there are a large number of works (V. Komissarov, A.V. Kunin, L.S. Barkhudarov, etc.) written by practicing translators or researchers in the field of translation, concerning the main linguistic, functional-stylistic, pragma-communicative features of translation texts and discourse in these areas from English language and vice versa.

One of the most widely studied areas of such an analysis is the art of translation, in particular the translation of a literary text. The field of literary text is a specific medium, the interest in which is expressed by professional critics, readers and writers. Translation of texts reflects not only linguistic, but also ethnic, intercultural and communicative features of languages: in this case, English and Russian. In connection with this thought, attention should be paid to the linguoculturological aspects of translation. The theory of explication of the linguistic picture of the world is an extensive and general idea, which manifests itself in the psychological reproduction of the ongoing actions. So, an explication of the linguistic picture of the world can be called a specific action or even a word in the process of communication, because only communication induces actions, associative representations. The task of each translator is to correctly convey the content and not to miss a single concept, since the keywords are often repeated, designed to attract the attention of the reader.

The focus of modern anthropological-oriented linguistics is the problem of the interaction of man, language and culture. The question of the influence of language and culture, first formulated in the works of ancient philosophers, was developed in the works of V. von Humboldt, who believed that material and spiritual culture are

inextricably linked with language, embodied in it and determining the picture of the world of the people; in the studies of E. Sapir and B. Whorf, who formulated the theory of «linguistic relativity», it is stated that differences between national cultures are determined by differences in languages [1; p.39]. The explication theory of the linguistic picture of the world includes both universal general content, determined by the objectivity and reality of the world as an object of cognition, and national-specific content, based on the peculiarities of the cultural and historical development of people, which allows us to study the linguistic picture of the world in a linguistic aspect by establishing facts of the interlanguage similarities and differences and modeling of the semantic fields of the language, and in the cultural aspect in order to identify national-specific way of thinking of the nation, its attitude and perception of the world [2; p.29].

The scientist—linguist V. Maslova offers the following definition to this concept: «The theory of the explication of the linguistic picture of the world reflects the way of speech-thinking activity, characteristic of this or that era, with its spiritual, cultural and national values». Language — spontaneously arising in human society and developing a system of articulate sound signs, serving for the purpose of communication and capable of expressing the totality of knowledge and ideas of a person about the world. [3; p.28] The language of a certain people is an exact mirror of his life, mode of life, his environment. It is the main tool for the formation and manifestation of the worldview of the people, their views on the realities of life. «In the process of forming values, reality »presses« on the language, trying to capture its features in it...» [4; p.10]. Language, being an exact mirror of the culture and life of the people, undergoes changes or additions, if any, take place in the surrounding world of various people. At any stage in the development of national culture, the language of an ethnos reflects it fully and adequately. Thus, the theory of explication of the linguistic picture of the world is not a frozen static set of concepts and symbols, but a dynamic system in constant evolution. The explication theory of the linguistic picture of the world is reflected in the keywords — «concepts». The term

«concept» in linguistics is both old and new at the same time. In 1928, S.A. Askoldov published an article «Concept and word», where he defined «universal» (concept) as «a mental formation that replaces an indefinite number of objects of the same kind in our process of thought» [5; p.267]. But until the middle of the last century, the idea of «concept» was not perceived as a term.

Only in the 80s. XX century again the idea of «concept» arises as a term that serves to explain the units of the mental processes of human consciousness. The translation of concepts from one language to another is directly related to the cultural and social content of the translated concept, attached to it within the framework of a specific cultural environment. Depending on how a particular person, a native speaker of a language, understands the concept in question, its transmission in a given language depends. Thereby, the external formal transfer of a concept from one language to another should reflect the whole gamut of linguoculturological properties acquired by him due to a certain historical, cultural, psychological experience of a native speaker [6; p.25]. Translation, as a linguistic phenomenon, is a very ancient form of human activity. As soon as groups of people were formed in the history of mankind whose languages were different from each other, «bilinguals» appeared that helped communication between «multilingual» groups. With the advent of writing, such translators-interpreters were joined by written translators who translated various official, religious, and business texts. From the very beginning, translation performed an essential social function, making interlanguage communication possible. It should be noted that the concept is much more influential and significant, if richer the national, class professional, family and personal experience of a person who uses the explication of the linguistic picture of the world. The «conceptosphere» of the national language is the more colorful, the richer the whole culture of the nation — its literature, folklore, science, visual art (it also has a direct relationship to language and, therefore, to the national «conceptosphere»), it is also correlated with all the historical experience of the nation and religion in particular. It is known that when studying translation as a special type of verbal communication, the theory of

translation is not limited to the analysis of its linguistic abilities, because translation is not only the interaction of languages, but also the interaction of cultures, as was said earlier. «... the translation reflects the situation of generation of the source text and the situation of translation. It is hardly possible to adequately describe the translation process, not taking into account the fact that it is carried out not by an idealized construct, but by a person whose value and psychological orientation inevitably affects the final result...» [7; c.215]

It should be noted that a number of scientists have found that the translator equally (or almost equally) owns both the source and the translating cultures. But in our opinion, this is far from the case, and in most cases «... the translator very roughly estimates, and, therefore, translates certain elements or entire categories of the source text in a comparatively cultural sense»... [8; c.9] In the process of translation, it should be noted that the literary and artistic style, in a number of styles, occupies an independent, special place. It performs an aesthetic function, although it simultaneously directs the actions of people, the text educates, convinces, spiritualizes, inspires... the linguist scientist M. Lvov writes. [9; p.142] Literature reflects the world by means of not only logical, but mainly sensory cognition, in artistic images created and transmitted in the form of speech. Accordingly, the aesthetics of creative activity embraces the world of not only the beautiful, but also the ugly, not only the sublime, but also the base, evaluates it enthusiastically or ironically. Literature enriches the spiritual world of a person, helps to perceive the world in its infinite variety and complexity. The writer uses the wealth of language accumulated over the centuries, but he enriches it, for he lacks not only words—he is looking for new constructions of the literary text: this way was born Onegin stanza. The literary space of a major prose work, such as «War and Peace» by L.N. Tolstoy, requires different styles. In this novel, the folk-poetic style, and the French-Russian dialogues, and extensive scientific monologues, and texts of official documents, and the epistolary style, and aphorisms, and parodies, and soldier humor, and the colloquial-everyday style of various social levels coexist and interact.

Translation of literary texts is complicated by high semantic workload, and the translator often has to create a text in another language again, and not reproduce it from another language. It is well known that works of art are very rich in phraseological units. The transfer of phraseological units is a very difficult task. Due to its semantic richness, imagery, laconism and brightness, phraseology plays a very important role in language. It gives speech expressiveness and originality, and when translating phraseological units, the translator needs to convey his meaning and reflect his imagery, finding a similar expression in Russian and not losing sight of the stylistic function of phraseological units. In translating phraseological units, great importance is given to the context. Phraseologisms are a special type of combinations, the main feature of which is «partial or complete discrepancy between the content plan and the expression plan, which determines the specifics of the idiom» [10, p. 127] and, of course, will affect the choice of methods and ways of translation. The translator has to deal with the greatest difficulties when working with phraseological units based on modern realities. Only a few of them quickly become popular and penetrate international dictionaries, for example: «Ангелы ада» — «Hell's Angels», «Поле чудес»—«the Land of Wonders». In addition, historical expressions or catchphrases of various kinds should be mentioned. The difficulty lies in the fact that sometimes they have several correspondences, both in the original language and in the translation language. Consider the phrase, the authorship of which is attributed to the leader of the English Revolution, Oliver Cromwell. «Put your trust in God...and keep your powder dry!» If the military theme is traced in the context, then the expression can be translated literally: «Rely on God and keep the powder dry!» But historically, the expression has become very popular in English culture and is often used in everyday situations and does not cause any historical associations. To improve the education of each person, it is important to get acquainted with the masterpieces of world literature.

However, not everyone can learn the works in the original language. Only thanks to the translators-writers do the invaluable treasures of world literature

become available to us. A literary translation should be comprehensively understood from the point of view of the original, here you can't do only knowledge of a foreign language, you need a special flair, mastery — to be able to feel the language forms, play on words, and be able to convey the artistic image. For example, if, firstly, in the minds of the Russian people «душа» is opposed to the «тело» (soul and body), then in the English expression the «mind» and «body»—«mind and body» are contrasted (cf. also: камень с души свалился —it is a load off smb's mind); secondly, this word in Russian — unlike English — is a frequency one and is included in a number of expressions that are rarely translated into English with the word «soul»—the closest to the Russian word in semantic terms, but far from covering the whole variety its manifestations. Of the 34 Russian phraseological units with the word «soul» cited by S.G. Ter-Minasova, only 4 are translated using the word «soul» (mainly in the meaning of man —not a soul); «heart» is often used as «heart» (15 times): всей душой — with all one's heart, работать с душой — to put one's heart to one's work; there is also the word conscience «совесть»: кривить душой — to act against one's conscience « [11; p.162–170]. A number of linguistic scholars believe that the text is not a chaotic pile of units of different language levels, but an ordered system in which everything is interconnected and interdependent. The complete design of the units of the previous levels—words and sentences — does not contradict the possibility of their division into more elementary components. The same thing happens with the text. Its systematic and structured nature does not deny, but, on the contrary, suggests the possibility of its formal (architectonic) and substantial (compositional) division.

Therefore, works of large forms (books) are divided into parts, chapters, paragraphs that develop their own local topics and thus have a certain formal and substantial independence. It manifests itself, for example, in the possibility of publishing or stage performance of a single fragment from a novel, narrative, drama. But such a «text segment auto-semantics» has a relative character, for it requires mandatory support for the whole text. In other words, the category of separability

appears in indissoluble dialectical unity with the category of connectedness [12; p.71]. Hereby, the text is the linguistic fabric of the work, which reflected the human soul, his intellect, goals, aspirations. The text is a shot of linguistic creative process, presented in the form of a specific work. [9; p.163] Translation of literary texts is an art that has nothing to do with the craft and that means — the translator should be endowed with a gift of writing. The art of translation has its own characteristics, and yet, translators have much more in common with original writers than in differences. This is perfectly stated in the novel «Юнкер» by A.I. Kuprin: «... to translate from a foreign language, it is not enough to know, even perfectly, this language, but you also need to be able to penetrate the deep, vibrant, diverse meaning of each word and the mysterious the power of combining certain words.

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ITALYAN TILIDA PREDLOGLAR BILAN ISHLATILADIGAN AYRIM IBORALARNING TARJIMASI XUSUSIDA.

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Annotatsiya: Frazelogizm- ikki yoki undan ortiq soʻzdan tashkil topgan, maʼnoviy jihatdan oʻzaro bogʻliq suz birikmasi hisoblanadi. Ushbu maqolada italyan tilidagi predlogli frazeologizmlarning - iboralarning tahliliga eʼtibor qaratilgan. Maqolada berilgan nazariy maʼlumotlar misollar orqali asoslangan.

Kalit soʻzlar: *Ibora, tarjima, ekvivalent, asl tarjima.*

Yurtimizda yoshlarning xorijiy tillarni oʻrganishlari uchun barcha imkoniyatlar yaratilgan. Bugun yoshlarimiz ana shunday ulkan imkoniyatlardan samarali foydalanmoqdalar. Xususan, taʼlim tizimining barcha bosqichlarida amalga oshirilayotgan keng koʻlamli islohotlar natijasida koʻplab oʻgʻil-qizlarimiz muayyan mutaxassislik boʻyicha taʼlim olish bilan birga xorijiy tillarni puxta oʻrganmoqda.

Hozirgi kunda oʻzbek tilidagi iboralarni chet tillarida va aksincha chet tillardagi iboralarni rus tili orqali emas balki toʻgʻridan toʻgʻri asliyat tilidan oʻzbek tilidagi tarjimada aks ettirish alohida ahamiyatga ega. Tarjimada shakl va mazmun munosabatini bejirim talqin etish hamda tarjimaning badiiy nafosati va milliy xususiyatini yuzaga keltiruvchi barcha lisoniy-uslubiy vositalar vazifalarini ijodiy aks ettira oladigan muqobil til va nutq birliklari tanlash vazifasi qoʻyiladi. Chunonchi, muallif tomonidan foydalanilgan har bir bayon va tafsilot, har qanday soʻz va ibora

asosiy g'oyaning vujudga kelishida muhim ahamiyat kasb etadiki, asarning tarkibiy qismini tashkil etadigan bunday badiiy-tasviriy vositalarning to'la-to'kis idrok etilishi va tarjimada ijodiy qayta yaratilishigina muloqot maqsadiga erishish imkoniyatini yaratadi.

Iboralar tilshunoslikning alohida bir qismi bo'lib shakllanganiga hali ko'p vaqt bo'lmagan bo'lsa-da, uning kelib chiqish tarixi til taraqqiyotining ilk bosqichlariga borib taqaladi. Ilmiy tadqiqotlardan ma'lum bo'lishicha, iboraviy birliklar til bilan birga paydo bo'lib, til bilan birgalikda rivojlanib kelgan. Ammo jamiyatning turli davrlarida ularning o'рни va ahamiyati turlicha baholanadi. Iboralar tuzilishi, leksik-semantik, funktsional-uslubiy va sintaktik vazifalari, shuningdek, o'ziga xos shakllanish xususiyatlariga ega bo'lgan til birligidir.

Tildagi neytral so'zlar bilan qiyoslaganimizda iboralarning ajralib turadigan jihati – bu predmet va voqealarning mohiyatini hissiy ta'sirchanlik bilan ifodalash xususiyatidir. Ba'zan iboralar tarixiy voqea hodislar bilan bog'liq tushunchalarni ham ifodalab kelaganligi bilan e'tiborga molik. Hissiy ta'sirchanlikning ifodalovchilaridan biri bo'lgan iboralar hamisha tarjimashunoslik va tilshunoslikning diqqat markazida turadi, shu sababdan uslubshunoslikda iboralar va leksik uslubiy vositalar haqidagi bo'lim tarjima, tilshunoslik muammolarini o'rganishga bag'ishlangan boshqa bo'limlarni birlashtiruvchi bo'lim sifatida namoyon bo'ladi.

Iboralar lingvistik jihatdan juda chuqur o'rganilgan, buni inkor etish noto'g'ri, lekin tarjimashunoslik nuqtai nazaridan olib qaraydigan bo'lsak, asliyat tili matnida qo'llanilgan iborani qanday usullarda tarjima qilish, uning vazifasini tarjima tilida ham saqlab qola bilish doirasidagi ilmiy ishlar hali yetarli emas. Lekin bu sohada ishlar umuman olib borilmagan desak xatolikka yo'l qo'ygan bo'lamiz, chunki o'zbek tarjimashunosligi ustida ishlar olib brogan G'. Salomov, Q. Musayev, O. Mo'minovlar ancha muncha ishlarni amalga oshirganlar.

Har qanday barkamol tarjima ilmiy umumlashtirishga extiyoj sezgani holda, san'atkorning asliyatga aloqador barcha manbalarni to'la-to'kis ilmiy idrok etishini

xamda ularga asoslangan jami omillarni o'z tilida ongli ravishda bekami-ko'st aks ettirishini nazarda tutadi [2 – 3b.].

Bir tildagi iboralarni o'zga bir tilga o'girish ularni muqobili yoki o'xshash ekvivalentlarini topish qiyin. Chunki bular darrov kishining xayoliga kela qolmaydi. Xuddi shunday misollarni quyidagi italyan tilidagi predlogli iboralar orqali ifodalashga harakat qilamiz:

“A” predlogi bilan keladigan iboralar va ularning ma'nolarini quyidagi misollarda ko'rib chiqamiz:

A caro prezzo – Qimmat narxda

A dire il vero – Rostini gapirganda

A dirla schietta – Ochiq, oydin gapirganda

A due mani - Saxiy

A nessuno e nascosto... – Hech kimga sir emas (hammaga ma'lum...)

A noi! - Boshladik! (Bizning navbat!)

A norma di legge – Qonunga muvofiq

A notte alta (tarda) – Kech tunda

A occhiate – Tashqi ko'rinishidan, tashqaridan qaraganda

A parole – So'zda, tilda aytilganda (o'g'zaki)

A passi di formica – Kichik qadamlarda (juda sekin)

A passo saldo - Dadil qadam bilan

A passo svelto – Sergak, dadil qadam bilan

A bruciapelo - 1. Juda yaqindan; 2. To'satdan, tasodifan.

A malapena - Qiyinchilik bilan.

Alla buona - 1. Oddiy, 2. Shikoyatsiz

Bundan tashqari italyan tilida “di” predlogi bilan keladigan iboralar ham ko'p qo'llaniladi. Bu kabi iboralar va ularning ma'nolarini quyidagi misollarda ko'rib chiqamiz:

Di buon passo – Tez qadamlar bilan.

Di buona lega – Yaxshi sifatda (sifatli).

Di fatto - Aslida

Di sotto il naso – Burinning ostida

Di sua resta – O’z aqli bilan, mustaqil ravishda

Di tutto il cuore – Butun yuragi bilan

Di tutto l'anima – Bor qalbi bilan

Di buon’ora - Barvaqt;

Di gran lunga – Juda, juda ko’p;

Di punto in bianco – To’satdan, tasodifan;

Rimanere di sasso o di stucco – Hayratlangan, hayratlanib.

“In” predlogi bilan keladigan iboralar va ularning ma’nolarini quyidagi misollarda ko’rib chiqamiz:

Essere, trovarsi, navigare in cattive acque – Qiyin davrni/vaqtни boshidan o’tkazmoq.

In gamba = Oyoqqa turgan, o’zini eplagan.

In stato interessante = incinta – Homilador

“Per” va “con” predloglari bilan keladigan iboralar va ularning ma’nolarini quyidagi misollarda ko’rib chiqamiz:

Per filo e per segno - Batafsil;

Andare, procedere con i piedi di piombo = con molta prudenza – Juda ehtiyotkorlik bilan

Stare con le mani in mano – Qo’l qovushtirmoq.

“Su” predlogi bilan keladigan iboralar va ularning ma’nolarini quyidagi misollarda ko’rib chiqamiz:

Su due piedi - Darhol

Su per giù - Taxminan, chamasi

Stare sulle spine - Xavotirda

“Tra” predlogi bilan keladigan iboralar va ularning ma’nolarini quyidagi misollarda ko’rib chiqamiz:

Essere, stare tra due fuochi – Ikki o’t orasida bo’lmoq.

Ushbu misollardan kelib chiqib aytishimiz mumkinki tarjimaning asosiy vazifasi nafaqat bir tilda ifodalangan axborotni boshqa bir til foydalanuvchisiga yetkazib berish, balki u bir xalq madaniyatni va tarixini boshqa bir xalqqa tanishtirish hamdir. Ma'lum xalqning til xususiyatlarini bizga tanishtirishda muhim ahamiyat kasb etuvchi uslubiy vositalardan biri bu iboralar va ko'chma ma'noli so'zlardir. Tarjimani uslubiy vositalarni saqlagan holda amalga oshirish tili o'rganilayotgan mamlakatning madaniyati, tarixi va turmush-tarziga aloqador ko'pchilik real fakt voqea-hodisalarni ifodalaydi va unda til va madaniyat o'rtasidagi yaqinlik yaqqol namoyon bo'ladi.

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ПЕРЛ БАК ИЖОДИДА ШАРҚ МАВЗУСИ

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Аннотация: Мазкур мақола Ғарб ва Шарқ адабий алоқаларига бағишланган бўлиб, унда XX асрнинг биринчи ярмида Америка ва Хитойда яшаб ижод этган буюк ёзувчи Нобель мукофоти лауреати Перл Бак ижоди ўрганилган . Ёзувчининг Шарқ мавзусига бағишланган 1931 йили нашр этилган “Сахий ер” (“The Good Earth”) романи XX асрнинг энг оммавий романи эканлиги ва романнинг яратилиши натижасида Америка ва Осиё адабий алоқаларига ҳисса қўшилганлиги кенг ёритилган.

Калим сўзлар: *Ғарб ва Шарқ. адабий алоқалар, Хитой тарихи, бадиий услуб, хитойлик деҳқонлар, сахий замин, Ван Лун оиласи, инсон характери, конфуцийлик ғояси, умуминсоний қадриятлар.*

Америка адабиётининг таниқли намояндаси Перл Бак (1892-1973) ўзининг бутун ҳаётини Шарқ ва Ғарб ўртасидаги ўзаро муносабатларда “кўприк” ўрнатишга, Осиё ва Европа халқларининг бир-бирларини тўғри тушунишлари йўлига бағишлади. “Кўприк” тушунчаси унинг ҳаётий фалсафасида асосий мазмун бўлди. П.Бакнинг сўнгги романларидан бирида ўзига жуда яқин бўлган қадимги Хитой донишмандлигидан “Биз бир осмон остида яшаймиз”- деган ҳикматли фикрни келтиради³³. Бу ғоя адиба ҳаётининг мазмуни, тақдирига айланди. У Шарқ ва Ғарбга оламига бирдай мансуб шахс бўлиб қолди.

Перл Бакнинг адабий мероси жуда кенг миқёсли, бой ва бебаҳо ҳамда деярлик ўрганилмаган. Аммо шуниси аниқки, унинг адабиётга қўшган ҳиссаси энг аввало Хитой мавзуси билан боғлиқ. У ўзининг узоқ ҳаёти ва сермахсул ижодий фаолиятининг сўнгги даврларида бунга иқроқ бўлиб шундай ёзди: “Дунёнинг қайси бир қисми кўпроқ қадрли эканини айтиш мен учун мушкул ... Мен Осиёга худди ўз ватанимга каби содиқман”. У Хитойни ўзининг “иккинчи ватани” деб ҳисоблар эди.

Перл Бак 1892 йилнинг 26 июнида Ғарбий Виржиния штатининг Хилсборо шаҳрида туғилди. Бўлажак ёзувчи уч ойлигида Хитойга олиб кетилиб, ҳаётининг бир қисми, яъни қирқ йил ўша ерда яшади. Унинг ота-онаси Абсоллом ва Кэролайн Сайденстрикерлар ўзига тўқ, зиёли оила бўлиб, болаларининг тарбиясига катта эътибор беришган .

П.Бакнинг болалиги ўзгача тарзда ўтди. У тўрт ёшидан инглиз тилида қандай бўлса, хитой тилида ҳам худди шундай сўзлашар ва ёза олар эди. Болалигида П.Бакнинг энагаси хитойлик бўлиб, у халқ эртаклари ва ривоятларнинг билагони эди. Кейинчалик Перл Бак ана шулар унинг ижод чашмаси бўлганини хотирлайди. Лекин П.Бакни сеҳрли эртаклардан кўра,

³³ Buck, Pearl S. The Good Earth. Introduction. Pearl Buck and the Good Earth by Peter Conn. - N.Y., 1994, p.37.

қахрамонлари тирик одамлар иштирок этган тарихлар кўпроқ мафтун этар эди. Бу воқеаларни Перлнинг отаси ўзининг сафарларидан қайтиб келган пайтларида оила аъзоларига айтиб берган ҳикоялари орқали билиб олар эди. П.Бакда ёзувчи бўлишига сабаб бўлган, кўрган билганларини ифода этиш иштиёқи ёшлик чоғиданоқ пайдо бўлган. Шунини айтиш керакки, П.Бак Хитой оғзаки ҳикоя қилиш услуби, йўллари ва оҳангини аниқ эгаллаб олди, бу кейинчалик унинг ижодий услубининг моҳиятини белгилаб берди.

Хитойдаги ҳаётига сўзсиз унинг олган билими ўз таъсирини кўрсатди. У китобни жуда қаттиқ севар эди, лекин ёшлик чоғида ҳар доим ҳам замонавий муаллифлар асари билан таниша олмади. Унинг ўқиш доираси асосан инглиз тилидаги мумтоз асарлар билан чекланди: у севиб ўқийдиган муаллифлардан бири Ч.Диккенс бўлиб, уни ҳар йили ўқиб чиқишга ҳаракат қилар эди. Ўзининг устози жаноб Куннинг муруввати билан у хитой оғзаки ижоди, ҳамда конфуцийликнинг ³⁴ ноёб намуналари билан танишди. Шундай қилиб, у Хитойга оид билимларни жуда яхши, мукамал ўзлаштирди.

Ёзувчининг бутун жаҳонда севиб ўқиладиган ажойиб романлари, инсон тақдирини ҳикоя қилиш усулининг мумтоз намунасидир. Унинг мухлислари бутун жаҳон бўйлаб кенг тарқалган бўлиб, ўз ватани Америкадан ташқарида янада кўпроқ эди. Адибнинг китоблари дунёнинг кенг тарқалган ўн тилида чоп этилди ва шу сабабли ҳам унинг асарлари энг кўп севиб ўқиладиган Америка ёзувчиларидан бири бўлган Марк Твен асарлари билан бир қатордан жой олди.

30-йиллар П.Бак ижодининг энг сермахсул босқичи бўлди. У бу даврда Хитойга бағишланган машҳур роман ва публицистик асарларини ёзди.

1931 йили “Сахий ер” (“The Good Earth”) романи нашр этилган кундан бошлаб, XX асрнинг энг оммавий романи бўлиб келган. Унинг нашр нусхалари, тарқалиши ва совринлари жаҳон адабиётшунослигининг тарихий бойлиги,

³⁴ Конфуций (Кун-цзы) (тахминан эрамиздан олдинги 551– 479 йиллар), Хитой мутафаккири, конфуцизм асосчиси. Конфуцийнинг асосий қарашлари “Лунь юй” (“Сухбат ва муҳокамалар”) китобида ифодаланган. Эрамиздан аввалги II асрдан то 1911-1913 йилларгача Синьхай революциясигача конфуцизм расмий давлат мафкура (идеология)си бўлган.

мероси бўлиб қолди. Романнинг бир неча миллион нусхалари Америка ва дунёнинг олтмишдан ортиқ мамлакатлари бўйлаб тарқатилди.

“Сахий ер” романини П.Бак ўзининг Хитойдаги шахсий тажрибаси натижасида яратган. Сиёсий майдонда “Сахий ер” романининг таъсири унинг машҳурлигидан ҳам муҳимроқдир. П.Бак романлари ўтган асрнинг кейинги 30-йиллардан то 60-йилларгача Хитой билан муносабатлар ўрнатишда Америкалик бошқа ёзувчиларнинг ҳар қандай бошқа китобларига қараганда муҳим роль ўйнайди. “Сахий ер” романида Америка ва Хитой китобхонлари биринчи марта инсонларнинг ҳаётий муносабатларини, ҳақиқий оддий одамлардай ўйлайдиган хитой характерларини кўрдилар. Худди ана шу нарса П.Бак романининг асосий ютуғи ва унинг доимий машҳурлигининг сабабидир.

1931 йил “Сахий ер” китоби нашр этилгунча, Америкаликлар Хитой ҳақида ҳеч нарса билмас эдилар. Фақатгина бир гуруҳ савдогар, дипломат ва миссионерлар Хитой ва хитойликлар ҳақида билишар, лекин уларга барча Осиё мамлакатларининг халқлари каби муносабатда бўлиб, ҳар жиҳатдан ўзларидан паст ҳисоблар эдилар. Хитой ҳақида аниқ билимлари йўқлигини айрим америкаликлар нуқсонларга ботган жамият ҳақидаги одобсиз фикрлар айтиш билан алмаштирдилар.

“Сахий ер” романи XX аср бошида Хитой қишлоқларидаги ҳаёт ҳақида қимматли билим ва маълумотлар манбаи бўлиб хизмат қилади. Нанкин университети чет тиллар факультети декани, профессор Луи Хайпинг П.Бакнинг бу романи ва бошқа кўпгина Хитой ҳақидаги асарларини: “Хитой тарихининг эгаси йўқ хазинасидир”³⁵ - деб ҳисоблаган.

Америкага қилган сафари даврида Э.Хемингуэй, У.Фолкнер, С.Льюис ва айниқса, ўзи жуда севган Т.Драйзер каби замонавий америка муаллифларини қизиқиб пухта ўрганишга интилади. “Ҳеч бир америкалик ёзувчи, - деб ёзади у, - қилган ишларининг аҳамияти бўйича Т.Драйзер билан бир қаторда тура

³⁵ Haiping L. Interview with the present writer (Nanjing, May 25, 1993)

олмайди”³⁶. Бу фикр 1938 йили айтилган эди. Бир жиҳатдан П.Бак ижодини “Драйзер мактаби” га мансуб дейиш мумкин. Т.Драйзер учун ижодининг асосий мавзуси моддий бойликка, бахтлилик сифатида қарашни қоралаш эди. Кичик инсон характерини очиб бериш – Т.Драйзер учун ҳам умумий бўлган. Сўзсиз ҳақиқатга интилиш ўз шахсий услубининг яратилишига олиб келди. Т.Драйзер услубининг оғирлиги, сўзларининг мураккаблиги ҳақидаги танқидларни рад этиб, тасвир кучи ва маҳоратига путур етказмай, унинг ёрдамида ўз услубига эришди. Ана шу “оддий”, “халқдан чиққан” ва “эскирган услублар” унга дунёни аниқ кўришда ёрдам берди. Т.Драйзер услубини ўрганиш П.Бак учун ўз услубини яратиш имконини берди ва у жаҳон танқидчилари томонидан жуда юқори баҳоланди.

П.Бакнинг энг машҳур асарига айланган бу янги асари ҳақида ёзувчининг таржимаи ҳолини ўрганувчилардан бири шундай деб ёзади: “Инсон ва воқеа-ҳодисалар хотирасининг бир ерида чуқур беркиниб ётган туйғулари уйғониб, энди қандай ривожланиш, нима қилиш керак эканини билар эдилар. Булар Хитой деҳқонлари бўлиб, улар на ўқишни, ва на ёзишни билишар, шунинг учун ҳеч қандай ҳуқуқлари йўқ эди. Давлат ҳукмдорлари уларни фақатгина меҳнатлари ва солиқ тўлашлари учунгина эсга олар эдилар ... Лекин, П.Бак уларни “нодон эмасликлари, ёзиш, ўқишни билиш, ўқимишли олимларнинг мураккаб, илмий сўзларини ёзиш ва такрорлаш ҳеч ҳам донолик ва нозик ҳисга эга бўлиш деганини билдирмайди. Деҳқон ўқишни билмаслиги мумкин, лекин катта сўз бойлигига эга бўлиб, мураккаб тушунчалар ва муносабатлар дунёсида яшайди, амалий ҳаётда ақлли ва кундалик ҳаёт учун курашда фаросатли бўлган, ўз кадр-қимматини билувчи инсонлардир”³⁷.

“Сахий ер” романида ёлғиз ва ожиз инсон яшаб тургандан кўра яхшироқ ҳаётга эришиш учун курашади.

³⁶ Nora Stirling. Pearl S.Buck. A Woman in Conflict. – N.Y. Copyright 1983 by Nora Stirling. p.171.

³⁷ Beverly Rizzon. Pearl S.Buck. The Final Chapter Copyright 1989. Palm Springs. California. p.283.

Қуёш нуридан қизиган ер, пахсадан қурилган уй ва эртадан кечгача ҳолдан тойдирувчи меҳнат – булар ҳақида кўплаб китоблар ёзилган. Лекин бу асар бошқача хусусиятга эга. “Сахий ер” романининг ўзига хослиги фақатгина унинг бошқа этнографик материаллар асосида яратилганида эмас, балки П.Бакнинг материаллар устида ишлаш бўйича ўзига хос йўли борлигида.

П.Бак романида бошқа асарларда учрайдиган ҳаётни ҳаққоний кўрсатмайдиган персонажлар ва вазиятлар йўқ.

“Сахий ер” романидаги воқеа ва ҳодисалар Перл ва унинг турмуш ўртоғи Лоссинг Бак биргаликдаги турмушларининг биринчи йилларини ўтказган Аньхой вилоятининг Нансхгоу қишлоғида содир бўлади. Роман ўз мазмуни билан оддий, лекин воқеаларга бой. Унда деҳқон Ван Луннинг ҳаёти ҳикоя қилинади. Унинг уйланишидан то кексалик давригача бўлган ҳаёти тасвирланади. Роман бошланишида Ван Лун – зўрға кун кечираётган қашшоқ бир инсон бўлиб, охирида у бойиб кетади.

Ван Лун ташқи дунёдан узилган ва саводсиз жамоада ўсади, у ерда патриархал тақводорлик маънавий бойлик ҳисобланар ва ҳаёт тинимсиз оғир меҳнат қилиш билан боғлиқ бўлган. У ҳаётда ростгўй, ақлли ва кундалик турмушда фаросатли.

Ван Лун учун ер – яшашнинг мазмун ва мақсади эди. У ерсиз яшай олмайди. Доимо фикри ўйида, ер - сахий замин, мўл-кўлчилик манбаи, фаровон ҳаёти, қолаверса унинг келажаги. Унинг ери жуда камҳосил эди, лекин Ван Лун учун ер дунёдаги ягона яшаш манбаи бўлиб, у бошқа нарсани тасаввур қила олмас эди. У бир неча бор очлик, қирғин, қурғоқчилик, сув тошқини, чигирткалар ҳужумидан зарар кўрса ҳам, ер у билан бирга ўзи ва ўзига ўхшаганлар барҳам бера олишини билар эди. Ван Лун конфуцийлик ғояси руҳида тарбияланганлиги учун қурғоқчилик бўлганда ёки йил серёғин келиб ҳамма ёқни сув босганда, табиат инжиқликлари кўпайган чоғларда осмон худосидан мадад сўраб, ибодатхонага келиб оромбахш шамлар ёқади.

Ернинг серҳосил бўлиши табиат инъоми эканлигини тушунган Ван Лун ҳар куни эрталаб уйқудан уйғонганида энг аввал об-ҳавони билиш учун деразани очиб ташқарини кузатар эди.

П.Бак энг оддий сўзлар билан Хитой деҳқонининг ўй - кечинмаларини асар бошида қуйидагича ифодалайди: He went to the hole and tore the paper away. It is spring... The hole was barely large enough to admit his hand and he trust it out to feel of the air. A small soft wind blew gently from the east, a wind mild, murmurous, and full of rain. It was a good omen. The fields needed rain for fruition.

There would be no rain this day, but within a few days, if this wind continued, there would be water. It was good. Yesterday he had said to his father that if this brazen, glittering sunshine continued, the wheat could not fill the ear. Now it was as if Heaven had chosen this day to wish him well. Earth would bear fruit.

«У дрезага яқинлашди-да, унга ёпиштирилган қоғоздан йиртиб, тешикча очди. Баҳор келди... Кичкина очилган тешикчадан, ташқаридаги об-ҳавони билиш учун зўрға қўлини тикди. Ташқарида билинар-билинмас товуш чиқариб, осойишта намли шамол эсарди. Бу яхшилик аломати эди. Ҳосил яхши бўлиши учун ёмғир керак. Гарчи, кунлар иссиқ, ҳаво қуруқ бўлаётган бўлса ҳам, агар шамол тинмаса бир неча кундан кейин ёмғир бўлишини у сизди. Бу яхши. Кеча у отасига, агар бу қуруқ иссиқ ҳаво яна бир неча кун давом этса, буғдойлар дон битмаслигини айтган эди. Гўё она – табиат унинг додини эшитиб, атайин бугун қувонтираётгандай. Ер бу йил албатта яхши ҳосил беради». (Бу ва бундан кейин келтириладиган инглизча матнлар таржимаси бизники - С.А.)

Романнинг биринчи қисмидаёқ Ван Лун мувафакқият қозонади, унинг тўнғич фарзандлари ўғил бўлиб, Хитой жамиятида бахтлилик белгиси эди. Ҳар куни эрталабдан кечгача о - Лан (қайлиғи)нинг Ван Лун билан ёнма-ён меҳнат қилиши ва тежамкорлиги эвазига анчагина ерга эга бўлдилар. Уларнинг Хванлар оиласидан янги ерлар сотиб олиб, оиласи мавқеининг кўтарилиб бориши ҳикоя қилинади. Кўриб турибмизки, бир оила авлодлари тарихи, улуғ

халқ тақдири, Хитой халқи мумтоз романи ёқтирадиган мавзу бўлиб, бу америкалик ёзувчи ижодининг асосий манбаидир.

Ёзувчи П.Бак Хитой халқининг ерга бўлган муносабатини, роман якунида бош қаҳрамон Ван Луннинг, ерни сотмоқчи бўлган фарзандларига мурожаати эпизоди орқали ёрқин ифодалайди: “It is the end of a family – when they begin to sell the land, he said brokely. Out of the land we came and into it we must go – and if you will hold your land you can live – no one can rob you of land”. «Ерни сотсангиз, оила барбод бўлади. Ибтидомиз ер, интиҳомиз ҳам ер бўлмоғи даркор. Фақат ерга эгалик қилиб яшаш мумкин. Ерингизни ҳеч ким ўғирлаб кетолмайди» - деган чақириқ сўзлари билан ифодалаб, Ван Луннинг ҳолатини шундай тасвирлайди: «And his two sons held him, one on either side, each holding his arm, and he held tight in his hand the warm loose earth». «Уни ўғиллари қўлтиғидан суяб турган пайтда у қўлида илиқ, юмшоқ тупроқни маҳкам сиқиб ушлаб турарди».

“Сахий ер” романининг оининг (асар март ойида чоп этилган эди) энг яхши романи деб топилиши муаллиф учун кутилмаган ҳодиса эди. П.Бакни бу муваффақиятни қабул қилиш ва машҳурлик ҳаяжонлантирди ва унинг ўзига бўлган ишончини янада кучайтирди.

П.Бак ҳаётини ўзгартириб юборган асари унга ҳам янгилик, шу билан бирга таниш бўлиб кўринар эди. У мавзуси бўйича ўзига хос янгилик бўлиб, лекин ижро техникаси бўйича анъанавийлиги аниқ кўриниб турар эди. Унда Т.Драйзер, Ч.Диккенс каби тажрибали қаламкаш ёзувчиларнинг таълими сезилар эди. Шунини алоҳида таъкидлаб ўтиш керакки, ҳеч бир америкалик ва Ғарб ёзувчиси Хитойни П.Бак каби билмас эди ва албатта шунинг учун ҳам унинг романлари жаҳон адабиётида катта воқеа бўлди.

“Сахий ер” романи – сўзсиз ижодининг чўққиси бўлмаса ҳам, ҳар ҳолда фикр юритиш босқичининг якуни бўлди. Чунки ёзувчининг бу асарида ер ҳаётбахш, ҳар нарсадан кўра қудратлироқ ва янгиловчи куч сифатида ифодаланди. П.Бак бу фикрга шу романини устида ишлашдан олдин келган

десак тўғрироқ бўлади. Чунки, бу китобдаги ҳар бир воқелик, балки муаллиф ихтиёридан ташқари ернинг қудрати ҳақида гувоҳлик қилади ва ер фақатгина қачон унинг кучини инсон ўзига бўйсундира олгандагина ҳаётбахш бўлади. Асарнинг биринчи сатрларидан бошлаб китобхон бўлаётган ҳодисалар ҳақиқат эканига ишонади.

“Сахий ер” романининг ўзига хос хусусияти фақатгина унинг бошқа этнографик материаллардан яратилгани эмас, балки П.Бакнинг ўз материаллари устида ишлаш услубидадир.

Ғояни амалга ошириш услуби ҳақида гапириб ўтиш алоҳида эътиборга лойиқдир. Унинг мазмуни жисмлар ва ҳодисаларни аниқ акс эттиришга интилишдан иборатдир. Роман жуда тўғри тузилган – унинг сюжетлари тўла-тўқис фабулалар билан мос келади. Характерларни ривожлантириш аста-секин ва кетма-кетлик билан амалга оширилади. Текис ва вазминлик билан ҳикоя қилиш усули кутилмаган ҳодисалар ва фалокатлар тафсилоти билан алмашилиши муаллиф учун одатий ҳолдир.

Ҳикояларга изоҳ берилмайди. Муаллиф эслатмалари китобхон назаридан четда қолади. Романда хитоблар, кўп маъноли сукут, хаяжонлар йўқ.

Аниқлик муаллифнинг асосий баён қилиш мезони ҳисобланади. Ана шу аниқлик шундай моҳирона амалга оширилганки, китобда унга эришиш учун ортиқча уринишлардан асар ҳам йўқ.

Асар равон ва бир текис ўқилади, бирор ортиқча сўз ишлатилмайди, ҳеч нарса тушириб қолдирилмай, узун, жуда батафсил тўлиқ ҳаракатлар билан, шунчалик жиддийлик ила ёзилганки, ҳатто воқеалар кескинлиги сезилмай қолади. Жисмлар шундай тасвирлаб берилганки, ўқувчи худди уларни кўриб тургандек бўлади. Одамлар шундай тасвирланганки, уларнинг ҳар бир қадами бир-бирига боғлиқ бўлиб, китобхонга таъсирчан ҳиссиётни уйғотади, гўё кўз олдимизда аниқ ва яққол ҳаракатланаётгандек, уларга қўл билан тегиш мумкиндек туюлади. Бу маҳорат бошқа ёзувчилардан П.Бакни алоҳида ўринга қўяди.

Сюжетли бошқотирмалар, кутилмаган ўхшаш сўзлар, ҳаяжон билан уйғунлашган таъсирчан таърифлар, ажойиб, лекин тушуниб бўлмас характерлар, аниқ, бироқ кўринмайдиган манзаралар - булар ҳаммаси “Сахий ер” романидаги одамлар ва жисмларнинг ёрқин тафсилоти сифатида намоён бўлади.

Шуни айтиш керакки, роман ҳақида Хитойнинг ўзидаёқ бир хил фикр билдирилмади, бироқ П.Бак тарафдорлари Хитойда кўпчиликни ташкил этарди. Романдаги воқеа ва ҳодисаларни мушоҳада қилиб, америкалик ёзувчи П.Бакнинг “Сахий ер” асари машҳур Хитой файласуфи Ли Ютан айтганидек, “беками кўст, ишончли асар” эканлигини хис этиб, ёзувчи Шарқ кишиларининг ҳаёти, анъаналари, урф-одатлари ва қадриятларини мукамал билганлиги ҳамда ўз романида Ван Луннинг нақадар катта маҳорат, кучли эҳтирос билан ёритилганлигига ишонч ҳосил қиласан киши. Ли Ютаннынг жияни ёзувчига мурожаат қилиб, унинг романини таржима қилишга ижозат сўрайди. У ёзувчига шундай деб ёзади: “Мен сизнинг ажойиб муваффақиятингиздан ажабланарли қувондим. Мен Хитой адабиётчиси бўлиб оддий деҳқон ҳаётини ўрганганман, бироқ сизнинг асарингиз бизнинг деҳқонларимиз турмуш тарзини ўрганган номдор чет эллик профессорлар асарларига караганда кўпроқ ҳақиқатдан иборат”³⁸. Дарҳақиқат, П.Бак худди деҳқоннинг ўзи каби содда услубга ёзишга ҳаракат қилди. Агар романда Хитой аҳолисининг бешдан тўрт қисмини ташкил этувчи деҳқонлар ҳаёти маромига етказиб ёритилмаганида, китобхонлар учун ҳам, танқидчилар учун ҳам хитойлик деҳқон ҳаёти “номаълум ер” бўлиб қолар эди. Фақатгина соддалик ва табиийлик ҳаёт талаби билан ерда меҳнат қилаётган инсонлар манфаати ва ибратли анъаналарини тушунтириб бера олди.

Хитойни юз йилликлар билан ўлчангувчи, манзараларининг турли-туманлиги дунёнинг ҳеч бир жойида учрамайдиган, «абადийлик» ни хис этмай

³⁸ Images of Chinese women Pearl S.Buck's novels: A study of characterization in “East Wind, West Wind”, “Pavilion of woman”, “Peony”, “The Good Earth” and “The Mother” for the degree doctor of Philosophy by Xiongya Gao. Ball State University Muncie, Indiana, 1993, p.196, ch.Y, “The Good Earth”, pp.186-218.

бўлмайдиган мамлакат деб таърифлайдилар. Ана шу ифода моҳиятини «Сахий ер» романи мазмуни аниқ очиб беради.

“Сахий ер” романи узоқ вақт бестселлерлар рўйхатидан жой олиб турди. Бир неча йил ичида 1 млн. 800 минг нусхаси сотилди, 30 дан ортиқ тилларга таржима қилинди. Диққатга сазовор жойи шундаки, Хитойнинг ўзидагина етти, турли тилда таржима қилинди.

Роман сахналаштирилди ва Бродвейда кўйилди. Шунингдек, Голливудда роман экранлаштирилди, фильм суратга олинди.

П.Бак ижодга бутун умрини бағишлади. У 1973 йил 8 мартда Данбияда вафот этди.

Сўнги йиллардаги асарлари тортишувларга сабаб бўлишига қарамасдан, муаллиф сермахсул ижод қилди – у юздан ортиқ асар яратди, сон-саноксиз мақола, сценарий ва ҳикоялар ёзди, булар П.Бакнинг мустаҳкам адабий ва ижтимоий ютуқларини исбот қилади. Бу ютуқлар уни жаҳон миқёсида улуғ инсон даражасига кўтарди. П.Бак ҳаётлигида йирик адабиёт арбоби сифатида танилди. Танқидчилардан бири хатто уни “Америка адабиёти қироличаси” деб атади. “У яратган асарларининг ҳаммаси, - деб ёзади Перл Бак ҳақидаги биринчи китобида унинг кичик синглиси Корнелия Спенсер, - инсонлар ўртасида алоқалар ўрнатишга, ҳамма учун ҳақиқат ўрнатилишига хизмат қилади ... У шундай ёзар эдики, ҳар ким ҳам унинг китобхони бўла олар, чунки у халқ учун ёзишга интилган эди”.

Жаҳон адабиёти ривожига П.Бак ижодининг муҳим аҳамияти шундан иборатки, унинг бутун ҳаёти, ижоди ва ижтимоий фаолияти Шарқ ва Ғарб умуминсоний кадриятларини ва инсонпарварлик ғояларини тушунган ҳолда бирлашишлари, бу ғоялар ер юзидаги ҳамма инсонлар учун ягона эканлигини тушунтиришга қаратилган.

Худди ана шу инсонпарварлик мазмунида бўлган асарлари ҳақли равишда унинг Нобель мукофоти эгаси бўлишига сабаб бўлди.

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**ИХАРА САЙКАКУ НАСРИЙ МЕРОСИДА “ЧЁНИНМОНО” –
“ШАҲАРЛИКЛАР ТЎҒРИСИДАГИ КИТОБЛАР”**

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Аннотация: Мақола XVII аср япон адабиётининг атоқли насрнависи Ихара Сайкаку ижоди ва унинг қаламига мансуб “чёнинмоно” – “шаҳарликлар тўғрисидаги китоблар” туркумидаги асарлар бадияти масаласига бағишланган.

Калит сўзлар: Гэнроку даври, япон адабиёти, шаҳар адабиёти, Ихара Сайкаку, “чёнинмоно”, “Япониянинг боқий хазинаси”, “Дунёнинг ҳисоб-китоблари”

Японияда XVII аср мамлакатнинг тадрижий равишда ўрта асрлардан янги даврга ўтишни англатувчи мураккаб давр сифатида намоён бўлди. Мазкур даврда бошқа Узоқ Шарқ мамлакатлари каби япон ижтимоий ва маданий ҳаётида бир қатор янгиликлар, адабиётда муҳим силжишлар кузатилди. Хусусан, ички урушларда кичик ҳокимиятларга бўлиниб кетган Япония марказлашган давлат сифатида қарор топди, ўрнатилган тинчлик иқтисодий тараққиётни таъминлаб берди, йирик савдо шаҳарлари юзага келди, учинчи қатлам вакилларининг ижтимоий ҳаётда роли тобора ортиб борди. Шунингдек, барча қатлам вакиллари учун таълим олиш имконияти яратилди, аҳоли орасида саводхонлик ўсди, тижорат босмаҳоналари фаолияти йўлга қўйилди, натижада адабиёт тобора ўзининг элитарлик хусусиятини йўқотиб борди [1,13]. Буларнинг барчаси япон шаҳар маданияти ва адабиётининг шаклланишида асосий омиллар бўлиб хизмат қилди. Мазкур даврда нимаики янгилик яратилган бўлса, барчаси айнан ана шу учинчи қатламдан юзага келди. Улар яратган адабиёт япон адабиётида “чёнин бунгаку” яъни “шаҳарликлар

адабиёти” атамаси билан юритилади [2, 102]. Япон шаҳар адабиётининг ривожланиши “хайкай” шеърляти, “каназоши” ва “укиёзоши” насри ҳамда “кабуки” ва “нингё жёрури” каби театр турларини юзага келтирди. XVII асрнинг иккинчи ярмида, яъни насрнавис Сайкаку, шоир Башё, драматург Чикамацу, мутафаккир Хакусэки, рассомлар Моронобу ва Иччё каби етук ижодкорлар фаолияти билан япон маданияти тарихида Гэнроку (1688-1704) номи остида машхур бўлган даврда, Киото, Осака ва Эдо ҳудудларида айниқса ўзининг юқори чўққисига етди.

1642 йилда туғилган ва 1693 йилда вафот этган, келиб чиқишидан Осакалик савдогарлардан бўлган Ихара Сайкаку (асл исми Хираямо Того). китобхонларни Гэнроку даврининг шаҳарлари ва уларда истиқомат қилувчи шаҳарликлар ҳаёти билан яқиндан танишишга имкон берувчи мазкур давр япон адабиётининг новатор насрнависи ҳисобланади. Сайкаку ёшлик чоғлариданок шоир-бадиҳагўй сифатида адабий доираларда машхур бўлган [3, 112].

Сайкакунинг 1682 йилда нашр эттирилган илк насрий асари 「好色一代男」 (“Муҳаббатга мубтало эркак”) романи китобхонларда катта таассурот қолдирди ва унинг қолган бошқа асарлари ичида энг катта шухрат қозонган асарга айланди. Адиб япон адабиётига илк бора асосий қаҳрамони шахзода, зодагон ёки жангчи-феодал эмас, балки оддий шаҳарлик бўлган асарни олиб кирди. У яна бир қанча турли хил мавзу ва характердаги, хусусан, ишқий, сеҳрли-фантастик, ҳарбий руҳдаги, суд ишлари билан боғлиқ детектив новеллаларни нашр эттирди. Умрининг охирига келибгина адиб шаҳарликларга қаратилган ва “чёнинмоно”, яъни “шаҳарликлар тўғрисидаги китоблар” дея таржима қилинувчи янги мавзу ва жанрдаги тарбиявий новеллаларни яратди [4, 103]. 「日本永代蔵」 (“Япониянинг боқий хазинаси”, 1688), 「世間胸算用」 (“Дунёнинг ҳисоб-китоблари”, 1692) ва бошқалар Сайкакунинг ана шундай асарлар сирасига кирувчи новелла тўпламлари ҳисобланади. Бош қаҳрамонлари ҳам, мутолаа қилувчилари ҳам муаллифнинг замондошлари бўлган мазкур асарлар беқарор бу дунёда қандай қилиб фаровон ҳаёт кечириш мумкинлиги

билан боғлиқ ҳаёт донишмандликларини ўзида мужассамлаштирган қизиқарли ва дидактик новелла тўпламларидир. Шу боис, уларда икки хусусият – биринчиси худди ҳужжатлардагидек ажабланарли даражадаги аниқлик ва ишончлилик, иккинчиси эса панд-насихатга тўлалик ва ибратлилик мавжуддир.

Адибнинг мазкур туркумдаги новеллаларини қолган асарларидан ажратиб турадиган жиҳат, Гэнроку даври япон шаҳарлари маиший ҳаётининг ранг-баранг тавсилотлар билан тасвирланганлигидир. Уларда шаҳарликларнинг бутун ҳаёти ундаги ташвиши ва ўйин-кулгулари, иш ва байрам кунлари, эътиқоди ва иримлари билан биргаликда келтирилади. Сайкаку мамлакатнинг турли ҳудудларида истиқомат қилувчи аҳолининг урф-одатлари ва расм-русумлари ҳақида ҳикоя қилади, ўз даврининг реал одамлари ва ҳақиқатда содир бўлган воқеа-ҳодисларни таъкидлаб ўтади. Кўчалар, кийимлар, пул бирлиги, маиший турмушнинг ҳар қандан тафсилотлари – бу каби даврнинг моддий белгилари унинг новеллаларида тўқима ва ҳақиқат бир-биридан ажралмас бўлиб туюладиган фонни юзага келтиради. Адибнинг кўриш доираси ҳақиқатдан жуда ҳам кенг. У мувафакқиятга эришган савдогарнинг ҳашаматли ҳонадони билан бир қаторда, қашшоқ одамларнинг фақирона кулбасини ҳам кўра олади. Унинг новеллаларида ҳақиқий кундалиқ ҳаёт можаролари, зиддиятлари асосан киноя ва ҳазил орқали очиб берилади.

Ўттиз икки новелладан иборат “Япониянинг боқий хазинаси” тўпламида адиб топқирлик ва қаттиқ меҳнати туфайли бойиб кетган қамбағаллар, лоқайдлик ва пулни бўлар-бўлмасга совуриш сабаб қасодга учраганлар ҳақида ҳикоя қилса, “Дунёнинг ҳисоб-китоблари” тўпламининг новеллаларида йил сўнггида қарзларидан халос бўла олмай, умидсизликка тушган одамлар ҳолати ёрқин тасвирланган. Икки тўплам образлар тизимидан ташқари, яна кўп жиҳатдан муштарак. Уларни энг аввало умумий бир мавзу – шаҳарликлар ҳаёти, аниқроқ айтганда, учинчи қатлам ва унинг ижобий фазилатлари, ушбу фазилатларнинг фойдаси тўғрисидаги мавзу бирлаштириб туради. Адиб томонидан илгари сурилаётган меҳнат ва тежамкорлик ғояси ҳам бундан

мустасно эмас. Асосида пул ва моддий жиҳатдан фаровонликка эришишга интилаётган инсон ўртасидаги тўқнашув ётувчи новеллаларда ҳикоя қилинаётган воқеа-ҳодисалардан келиб чиққан ҳолда, мазкур ғоя ҳам ижобий, ҳам салбий мисоллар орқали ўз ифодасини топади. Ҳар бири бир неча саҳифадан ошмасида, шаҳарликлар тўғрисидаги новеллаларнинг композицион тузилиши жудда мураккаб ва кўп планлидир. Сюжет парчалари пейзаж тасвири ва муаллифнинг насиҳатомуз жумлалари билан навбатма-навбат келиб, улар билан ё ассоциациялар, ёки кескин контраст билан боғланади. Одатда, сюжет қисмидан олдин, узундан-узун панд-насиҳатлар билан бошланган новеллаларида Сайкаку шаҳарлик китобхонларини жамиятдаги ўз мавқеига мос равишда тутишга ўргатади, кунт билан ҳалол ишлаш, тиришқоқлик ва тежамкорликка чақиради.

Ишнинг кўзини биладиган, уддабурон, тadbиркор ва бойликни кўпайтириш ҳақида қайғурадиган одам муаллиф ўз образлари орқали гавдалантиришга интилган идеал шаҳарлик бўлиб, у адиб даврининг ёш савдогарлар табақаси қизиқишларига жавоб берар эди. Сайкаку ушбу типик образни шаҳарликлар ҳақида китобларида аниқ шакллантира олган. “Япониянинг боқий хазинаси” тўпламидаги 「世界の借屋大将」 (“Бутун дунёдаги ижарачиларнинг генерали”) новелласининг бош қаҳрамони – ўткир зеҳнли ва тежамкор савдогар Фужиичи бунинг ёрқин мисолидир. Бой бўлишига қарамай, зодагонларга тақлид қилмаган ҳолда кичик бир уйда яшайдиган Фужиичи, нафақат ишларини оқилона юритади, балки қизининг савдогар хонадонига муносиб рафиқа бўла оладиган одам қилиб тарбияланишига ҳам катта аҳамият беради [5,57]. Бошқа новеллаларда мазкур шаҳарлик – пахта савдоси билан шуғулланувчи Кускэ [5, 160-166], уддабурон балиқчи Гэннай [5, 71-75], савдогар кўлида иш ўрганувчи зеҳнли шогирд болакай ёки ҳаридорбop маҳсулотни олдиндан арзонга ҳарид қилиб, вақти келганда яхши нарҳга сотиб фойда кўраётган қария аёл [5, 352-358] сифатида гавдаланади.

Шаҳарликларнинг ана шундай идеал образлари ва уларга хос ижобий фазилатлар мисолида учинчи қатлам вақилларига тегишли муносиб хулқ-атвор тамойиллари муаллиф томонидан етарлича аниқ шакллантирилган ва батафсил асосланган эди. Шундай бўлсада, Сайкаку-санъаткор Сайкаку-насихатгўй устидан ғалаба қозонади. Унинг ҳаёт тўғрисидаги билимлари бахтли тақдир ҳақидаги шаҳарликлар табақасига хос тасаввурларнинг тор доираларига сиғмайди. Тежамкорлик тамойилларини тарғиб қилиш билан биргаликда Сайкаку бир вақтнинг ўзида ҳар бир танга учун қалтирайдиган зикна одамларнинг гротеск образларини ҳам яратади. Киноявий жумлалар билан тўлдирилган ушбу турдаги образларнинг барчаси жонли, реал ва китобхоннинг хотирасида узок сақланиб қолади.

Хулоса ўрнида таъкидлаш мумкинки, Ихара Сайкаку асарларида XVII аср япон анъаналари, урф-одатлари, турмуш тарзи, ўша давр одамларининг ҳаётий қадриятларини ҳаққоний ва ҳеч қандай бўрттиришларсиз муҳрлай олган истедодли ижодкор, япон адабиётининг классик ёзувчиси сифатида ном қолдирди. Сайкакуга хос ўткир кузатувчанлик, қизиқувчанлик, барча гўзал нарсаларга нисбатан муҳаббат ва уларни маҳорат билан қоғозга тушира олиш қобилияти унинг асарларини XVII асрдаги японлар ҳаётидан гувоҳ берувчи ҳаққоний ва ҳаётий материалларга айлантди. Шу боис, Сайкакунинг асарлари нафақат Япония адабий меросининг бир қисми, балки ўрта асрлар жамиятидан янги даврга ўтиш оралиғидаги давр тасвирларини ўзида мужассамлаштирган тарихий манба сифатида қимматга эга. Бундан ташқари, XVII аср японлар онгида юз берган муҳим ўзгаришларни акс эттирган адибнинг насрий мероси ҳам бадиий асар, ҳам тарихий манба сифатида ўрганилишда муҳим аҳамият касб этади.

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*Issues of social sciences***ORGANIZATIONAL AND LEGAL BASIS OF TEACHING ENGLISH TO
MANAGEMENT PERSONNEL IN CIVIL SERVICE**

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Abstract. *The article aims to analyze organization and legal aspects of teaching English to civil servants, including management personnel. The article studies the features of teaching English to civil servants in the Academy of Public Administration under the President of the Republic Uzbekistan. According to the results of the research, some of suggestions and recommendations have been developed.*

Key words: *civil service, civil servant, management personnel, English, Academy of Public Administration, Master's degree, “English in public administration”, negotiation, meeting, communication.*

The process of globalization and the development of information technology make it urgent to retrain management staff and teach them English in the process. In the process of communication and negotiations with representatives of foreign countries, management personnel are required to know foreign languages, in particular English. For this purpose, a system of teaching English to management staff has been formed in our country.

In our opinion, the training and formation of the reserve of management personnel is the most important aspect of the civil service. In Uzbekistan, the Institute for training management personnel is the Academy of Public Administration under the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, established in 1995 as the Academy of State and Public Construction and named after 2012 [1]. In addition to training

management personnel, the Academy of Public Administration also performs the functions of retraining and professional development of management personnel. Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan “On measures for the further development of an effective system of training, retraining and professional development of managerial personnel in the Academy of Public Administration under the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan” dated August 8, 2017 plays an important role in enhancing the activities of the Academy [2]. The main purpose of the Academy is to organize an effective system of training, retraining and advanced training of management staff, as well as to conduct fundamental and applied research in the field of public administration.

On September 19, 2017, the Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers No. 745 "On approval of regulatory legal acts on training, retraining and advanced training of management personnel" was adopted. According to him, the state educational standard of higher education in master's specialties and other normative legal acts in the field of management training have been approved. According to the state educational standard, curricula should provide for the mastery of the following subject blocks by students:

- ✓ general methodological sciences;
- ✓ specialty sciences;
- ✓ scientific activity.

The resolution included English in the block of general methodological sciences. It should provide for the acquisition of foreign language management in the field of management, the formation of the ability to negotiate in a foreign language and the public presentation of practical and research results. In addition, the graduate must understand the essence of analytical and research work in one of the foreign languages, have a basic knowledge of negotiation in a foreign language, be able to publicly present the results of practical and research activities in a foreign language.

[3]

According to the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated June 27, 2019 “On additional measures to improve the system of training, retraining and professional development of management personnel at the Academy of Public Administration under the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan”, in the Academy on the specialty “Public Administration” 1-year and 2-year Master’s programs, also 4-month and 10-month retraining courses are established on the basis of educational programs.

Of these, 1-year and 2-year master's degree and 4-month retraining listeners are taught the subject “English in public administration” [4].

“English in public administration” as a subject is among the general subjects. This subject differs from the subjects of the state higher educational institution in that it provides an opportunity not only to develop the communicative skills of the audience in a foreign language, but also to participate equally in the life of the society, work in a team, to make the right decisions in the performance of practical tasks. Therefore, the issuance of knowledge is carried out not only on the basis of teaching theoretical knowledge, but also on the basis of the development of the skills of four of the audience, including Reading, Writing, Listening and Speaking.

Science provides for the formation of communicative, scientific and professional skills in English language in the audience; formation of an understanding of the actual importance of English in public administration in the audience; development of a database of English words and phrases commonly used in such areas of State importance as social, economic and territorial management, management, finance, political science, entrepreneurship, international business.

Competitions formed as a result of mastering the subject “English in public administration”:

1. Formation of communication skills:

- Salutation, dating;
- Start, continue and end the conversation;
- Giving information about the profession and the profession itself;

2. Presentation:

- Important requirements of the presentation;
- Effective presentation skills;
- Phrases used in the presentation;

3. Negotiating:

- Negotiate with partners;
- Participation in discussions;
- Negotiating strategies;

4. Holding meetings:

- Organizing a meeting (words and phrases);
- Lead a meeting (words and phrases);
- Completion of the session (words and phrases) [5].

In order to learn subject “English in public administration”, it is important to use advanced and modern methods of teaching, to apply new information and pedagogical technologies. In the mastering of science, textbooks, teaching and methodological manuals, handouts and electronic materials are used. Also, key-stadiums made of English materials related to the field of organization and management are used. One of the types of modern information and pedagogical technologies is interactive teaching.

The fundamental essence of this method is that almost all listeners are involved in the learning process. The use of interactive methods facilitates the process of mastering new material, as well as developing critical thinking of the audience. To do this, the tutorials are organized individual, double-and group-group work, Role-Playing, work with different sources, mind attack, memory card, cluster, etc. [6].

In conclusion, teaching English to civil servants, including management personnel in Uzbekistan, has some distinctive features, in addition to including general aspects of language teaching. This difference is due to practical processes in the field of Civil Service and management, including negotiating with foreign partners, holding meetings with subordinated employees.

The following suggestions can be made for research.

First, it is necessary to introduce “English” in the entrance exams of the Academy. It is known that the entrance exams are based on “history of Uzbekistan”, “logic” and “general conversation”. The addition of English to the examination blocks will ensure that the Academy admits management personnel who know English at least fundamentally. This, in turn, contributes to the effective organization of the educational process and the training of better quality personnel.

It is advisable to include English in the recruitment process of civil service. The reason is that now every civil servant needs to know English. Because newly recruited personnel are also potential management personnel. The process of admission to the civil service for information is also carried out on the basis of a general interview with tests in the disciplines of “law”, “information technology”, “spirituality” and “economics”.

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ИЖТИМОЙ РЕКЛАМАЛАР ТАРИХИДАН

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Аннотация. Ушбу мақолада ижтимоий рекламаларнинг қисқача тарихи ҳақида гап боради. Шунингдек, ижтимоий рекламаларнинг мазмун мундарижаси аниқланади ва уларнинг босқичма-босқич ривожланиши манбалар асосида тушунтирилади.

Калит сўзлар: *реклама тарихи, литографик кўринишли босмаҳоналар, ёзма кўринишдаги рекламалар.*

Реклама тарихи жамият тарихи билан узвий боғлиқ бўлган ижтимоий ҳодисадир. Рекламанинг мақсади жамиятдаги муҳим ҳодиса ва жараённи тарғиб қилишга, айниқса, жамият иқтисодиётини ривожланишига, савдо-сотиқ ишларининг жадаллашувига хизмат қилиб келган. Ўзбекистон Республикаси Марказий Давлат архиви (МДА)да сақланётган ҳужжатлар шундан гувоҳлик берадики, мамлакатимизда ҳам реклама узок ўтмишга эга бўлиб, бизда ҳам реклама дастлаб оғзаки шаклда пайдо бўлган, кейинчалик унинг ёзма шакли вужудга келган. XIX асрда ўлкамизда литографик кўринишли босмаҳоналар, фотография ательелари ҳамда доимий равишда чоп этилган газета ва журналлар ижтимоий рекламанинг шаклланишига ва кенг тарқалишига сабаб бўлган. Кузатишларимиз натижасида XIX асрга тегишли газета ва журналларда, фото ва кино архивларида бир қанча реклама намуналари сақланиб қолинганлигини гувоҳи бўлдик.

XIX асрнинг охирига келиб мамлакатимиз ҳудудига Россия капитали ҳамда ишлаб чиқарилган тайёр маҳсулотларининг жалб этилиши натижасида мусулмонлар ҳаётида европача маданият пайдо бўлди. Оқибатда тадбиркорликнинг етакчи омили бўлган реклама санъати юзага келди. Бу жараён рекламанинг янги турларининг шаклланишиги ҳам асос бўлди. Натижада, реклама ижтимоий ҳаётнинг ажралмас бир қисмига айланди. Мамлакатда, ижтимоий, сиёсий ҳамда тижорат рекламаларининг ахамиятини ортиши жамият ўз-ўзидан рекламани янги бир авангард босқичига олиб чиқди.

1917 йил Октябрь инқилобидан сўнг рекламанинг таркиби ва вазифаси, аниқроғи, мақсади ўзгарди. Энди у давлат тасарруфи даражасида назорат қилинадиган бўлди. Энг ёмони, тадбиркорлар реклама эвазига ўз фаолиятларини кенгайтириш имкониятидан маҳрум бўлдилар, фақат ундан сиёсий мақсаддагина фойдаланишга имкон берилган. Ўша даврда чоп этилган газеталардаги рекламалар гўёки чақирик, даъват кўринишида бўлиб, оммани ўзига жалб этишга қаратилган оҳангда бўлган Жумладан: А.Виноградованинг “Хоразм Совет халқ Республикаси” газетасида чоп этилган мақоласида³⁹, “революционерлар олдинда бўлишлари керак, ҳамда Х.Саматовнинг “Хивада халқ революциясининг ғалабаси” номли мақоласида⁴⁰ “коммунистлар ҳамма вақт халқ оммасининг олдида бўлиши керак!” каби чақирик кўринишидаги рекламалар газеталарда чоп этилган. Демак, ушбу рекламаларнинг газетада чоп этилганлигининг ўзиёқ ёзма кўринишидаги рекламаларнинг пайдо бўлганлигига гувоҳлик беради.

1920 йиллардан Туркистонда тижорат ва ижтимоий рекламаларнинг мазмун моҳияти тубдан ўзгарди. Юртда ижтимоий рекламаларга бўлган талаб ва эътибор ҳам кучайди. Рекламалар стандарт: композицион ва ранг ечимида

³⁹ “Жизнь национальностей» 1923, Газета и №1. История советского государства и права Узбекистана Том 1 (1917-1924гг.) Издательство Академии Наук Узбекской ССР Ташкент- 1960.

⁴⁰ Вопросы истории КПСС, 1957, №3 История советского государства и права Узбекистана Том 1 (1917-1924гг.) Издательство Академии Наук Узбекской ССР Ташкент- 1960.

ишланди, уларда, асосан, меҳнат аҳли образи тасвирланди. Реклама плакатлари эса коммунистик мафкура рамзи бўлган қизил-алвон рангда эди. Шаҳар муҳитига мос ташқи безак сифатидаги маҳсулотларнинг етишмаслиги, рақобатнинг мавжуд эмаслиги, ўз-ўзидан, ижтимоий ҳаёт фаолиятида рекламага бўлган зарурятни йўққа чиқарди.

1936 йилдан бошлаб мамлакатимизда қурилиш ишлари фаоллашди, ҳукумат томонидан бу саъйи-ҳаракатга катта баҳо берилди ва бу борада қатор Қарорлар⁴¹ ҳам қабул қилинди. Ўша даврда чоп этилган газета ва журналлар ҳам ушбу масалани ёритишга ўзининг муҳим ҳиссасини қўшди. Газета ва журналларда “Лойиҳасиз шартнома тузилмасин ва имзоланмасин!” деган реклама рукуни асосида мақолалар ҳам чоп этилганган эди.⁴²

1940 йилга келиб мамлакат ҳаётида коммунистик партия томонидан олиб борилган тарғибот ва ташвиқот ишлари муҳим ўрин тутган, партия ўз навбатида ижтимоий ҳаётда ҳал этилиши керак бўлган масалаларнинг ечимини топишга ҳаракат қилинган, Ўшанда ҳал этилиши керак бўлган энг муҳим масалалардан бири - аёлларнинг жамиятдаги ўрни ва мавқеини ошириш ҳамда жамиятда уларга енгиллик яратишга қаратилганлигидир. 1940 йилда фаолиятда бўлган даврий рўзномалардан бири “Известия” газетасида чоп этилган мақоладан маълум бўлишича, завод ва фабрикада ишлаётган ишчиларнинг 40,7 фоизини аёллар ташкил этган, шундан: 16.000.000.таси ўзбек аёллари бўлган. Ўша даврда “Аёлларга енгиллик яратиш керак” рукуни остидаги рекламалар ифодалаган мақолалар тез-тез чоп этилган.⁴³

Маълумки, 1953-1958 йилларда мамлакатимизда уруш оқибатида вайрон бўлган жойларни қайта тиклаш билан бирга, ҳукумат халқ хўжалигини

⁴¹ История советского государства и права Узбекистана Т.3.Издательство»ФАН»Узбекской ССР Ташкент-1966. 58-59 стр.

⁴² Журнал “Арбитраж” 1940, №8, Журнал, “Финансовый и хозяйственный бюллетень, 1939, №27/28, стр 15.”История советского государства и права Узбекистана. Том-3. Издательство» ФАН»Узбекской ССР Ташкент-1966. 58-59 стр.

⁴³ “Правда”8 марта 1940г.

ривожлантиришга бутун эътиборини қаратган. Бу ўша вақтда чоп этилган журналларда ва ҳукумат томонидан қабул қилинган қарорларда ўз тасдиғини топган. “Янги иқтисодий сиёсатга ўтамиз” деган реклама рукуни остидаги шиор давр матбуотининг мақсадига айланиб бўлган эди.⁴⁴

XX асрнинг 60-70 йилларида айрим ҳудудларда махсус реклама ташкилотлари юзага кела бошлади. Ушбу ташкилотларга собиқ СССР савдо-сотиқ вазирлигининг “Союзторгреклама”, СССР Центросоюзи қошидаги “Главко-опторгреклама ” ташкилоти ва бошқа ишлаб чиқариш соҳасидаги тижорат-реклама ташкилотлари (бошқа вазирликлар қошидаги) кирган. Уларнинг асосий вазифаси бутун Совет иттифоқида реклама ишини ташкиллаштириш, назорат қилиш ва махсус ярмаркалар ўтказишни амалга оширишдан иборат эди.

Хулоса ўрнида таъкидлаш жоизки, юқорида келтирилган маълумотларнинг барчаси реклама жанри тарихда қандай кўринишларда мавжуд бўлганлиги, юртимизнинг сиёсий ва ижтимоий ҳаётида тутган ўрни, унинг жамият ҳаётида ҳам ғоявий, ҳам эстетик жиҳатдан муҳим аҳамият касб этганлигини яна бир бор исботлайди.

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ЮРИДИК ТАЪЛИМДА АНЪАНАВИЙ, МАСОФАВИЙ ВА АРАЛАШ (ГИБРИД) ЎҚИТИШДАГИ ИННОВАЦИОН ҚАРАШЛАР

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Бугунги шиддат билан ривожланиб бораётган бутун дунёга халқларни таҳликага солган коронавирус балоси кириб келди. Бундай балога ҳеч бир давлат ёки соҳа тайёр эмас эди. Коронавирус пандемияси биргина бутун дунёда таълим олиш жараёнини ўзгартириб юборди. Минглаб мактаб, коллеж, лицей ўқувчилари, талабалар ўқишга бормаи, уйдан туриб ўқишни давом эттиришига тўғри келди.

Ҳаттоки, қисқа фурсатда олий таълим муассасаларида хусусан, ҳуқуқшунослик университетларида ҳам анъанавий ўтилган дарсларнинг тўсатдан масофавий (онлайн) шаклга кўчгани таълим берувчи ўқитувчилар учун ҳам катта тажриба-синов мактаби бўлди.

Шу ўринда анъанавий, масофавий ва аралаш(гибрид) таълим тизимининг асосий тушунчаларини келтириб ўтишимиз жоиздир.

Анъанавий таълим – бу таълим олувчи ва таълим берувчи ўртасидаги ўзаро таълим жараёнига оид муносабатларнинг тўғридан-тўғри (билвосита) асосига қурилган алоқаси.

Масофавий таълим – бу ўқитувчи ва ўқувчи (талаба)нинг бир бири билан масофа ёки информацион технологиялардан фойдаланган ҳолда алоқа қилиш тури. Иккинчи таъриф, масофавий таълим – ўқув жараёнининг мақсади, мазмуни, услублари, ўқитиш воситалари ва интернет технологиялари ёрдамида тингловчи ҳамда ўқитувчиларнинг масофадан туриб, интерфаол мулоқот қилиш жараёни ҳисобланади⁴⁵.

Аралаш (гибрид) таълим – анъанавий таълим, масофавий таълим ва интерактив таълимнинг биргаликда олиб борилиши, ўқувчи (талаба)ларнинг ҳам ўқитувчи билан ҳам мустақил равишда таълим олиш шаклидир.

Бугунги кунда барча халқ таълим (асосан аралаш-гибрид) ва олий таълим муассасалари анъанавий ҳамда масофавий таълим шаклида фаолият олиб бормоқда. Масофавий таълим шакли пандемия сабабли таълимнинг юқори босқичига кўтарилди.

Пандемия сабабли, ҳуқуқшунос талабалар замонавий таълимнинг энг муҳим ва тобора оммавийлашиб бораётган масофавий таълим шаклидан кенг фойдаланиб келмоқда. Бунда ҳуқуқшунослар талабаларнинг мустақил фикрлаш, ҳолатни баҳолаш, хулоса қилиш, мустақил қарор қабул қилиш қобилиятларини ривожлантиради. Мустақил билим олишга, изланишга, фикрлашга ўргатади. Бунда талаба ўзига қулай вақтда, қулай жойда, қулай муҳитда билим олиши ва илмий тадқиқот олиб бориши мумкин. Шу туфайли ушбу тизим бугунги кунда дунёда кенг оммалашмоқда.

Хўш, анъанавий таълимнинг қандай афзалликлари мавжуд?

⁴⁵ С.Ниёзова ТДЮУ профессори в.б, ю.ф.д. (DSc), А.Алланова ўқитувчи <http://hudud24.uz/masofaviy-talimning-afzalligi-bu-tizimning-dunyoda-keng-> mmalashishiga-sabab-nima/

1. Қисқа вақт ичида ўқувчи (талаба) ларни фан асослари ва фаолият усуллари, мисоллари билан яъиндан таништиришга имкон беради⁴⁶.

2. Бевосита билимларни ўзлаштириш, амалий кўникма ва қобилиятларни тезда шакллантиришнинг мустаҳкамлигини таъминлайди.

3. Савол жавоблар жараёни бевосита тарзда амалга оширилади. Бу таълим жараёнида бўшлиқлар пайдо бўлишининг олдини олади.

4. Ассимиляциянинг коллектив хусусияти одатдаги хатолар ва уларни бартараф этиш учун йўналтиришларни аниқлашга имкон беради.

Бундан кўриниб турибдики, ҳуқуқшунослар фаолиятида ҳам анъанавий таълимнинг ўрни бекиёсдир. Чунки, ҳуқуқшунослик соҳасидаги баъзи фанлар анъанавий таълимда олиб борилиши орқали кўпроқ самара беради.

Масофавий таълимнинг афзалликлари нималардан иборат?

1. Ўқувчи (талаба)лар кўпроқ мустақил ишлашга, илмий ижод билан шуғулланишларига, китобларни мутолаа қилишларига имкониятига эга бўлади⁴⁷.

2. Хориж давлатлар томонидан ташкил қилинадиган онлайн видеоконференцияларда қатнашиб, касбий маҳоратларини ривожлантириб боради.

3. Саломатлиги анаъвий ўқишида чекланганлар, олис ҳудудларда яшовчи ўқувчи(талаба)лар ҳам таълим олиши мумкин.

4. Масофадан туриб ўқиганда бир неча курсларда бир вақтнинг ўзида таълим олиш имкони мавжуд.

Ўзбекистон Республикаси “Таълим тўғрисида”ги қонуннинг 15-моддасига биноан таълим олиш шакли сифатида масофавий таълим олиш

⁴⁶ <https://apriori-nauka.ru/uz/education/dostoinstva-i-nedostatki-tradicionnoi-istemy-obucheniya.html>.

⁴⁷ М.Ҳакимова Инновацион ривожланиш вазирлиги ҳузуридаги “Филология, психология ва педагогика” Илмий-техник кенгаши раиси, Тошкент давлат иқтисодиёт университети профессори, п.ф.д. <https://mininnovation.uz/uz/news/2054>

яратилган⁴⁸. Ушбу қонуннинг 16-моддасига биноан масофавий таълим ўқув режалари ва ўқув дастурларига мувофиқ таълим олувчилар томонидан зарур билим, малака ва кўникмаларни ахборот-коммуникация технологияларидан ҳамда Интернет жаҳон ахборот тармоғидан фойдаланган ҳолда масофадан туриб олишга қаратилганлиги белгиланган.

Шундан келиб чиқиб, бугунги кунда ТДЮУ да таълим олиш жараёни Ўзбекистон Республикаси Президентининг 2020 йил 29 апрелдаги “Ўзбекистон Республикасида юридик таълим ва фанни тубдан такомиллаштириш бўйича қўшимча чора-тадбирлар тўғрисида”ги ПФ-5987-сон фармони асосида олиб борилмоқда⁴⁹. Жумладан, масофавий ўқитиш шаклини босқичма-босқич жорий этиш бўйича чора-тадбирларни амалга оширилмоқда. “Электрон университет” (E-University) тизимини жорий этган ҳолда очик, шаффоф, субъективлик ва суиистеъмолчиликлардан холи бўлган таълим муҳитини яратиш; Замонавий технологиялар ва интерактив таълим услубларини (**E-Minbar** электрон платформаси), талабаларинг мустақил ўқув ва амалий фаолияти объектга йўналтирилган ва динамик таълим муҳити (**Moodle**) <http://distant.tsul.uz> масофавий таълим платформаси ишга туширилди. “Start-up” экотизимини яратиш мақсадида университетда Legal Tech лабораторияси жорий этилди. Ушбу лаборатория ёшлар томонидан стартап лойиҳаларни ахборот-техник жиҳатидан қўллаб қувватлашга қаратилган. Ҳозирги кунда лаборатория томонидан Huquiy Shahar электрон платформа ва мобил иловаси яратилди. Форсайт прогнозлаш платформаси устидан ишлар олиб борилмоқда.

Университетда ўқув жараёни distant.tsul.uz масофавий таълим платформаси ҳамда Zoom дастури орқали, адабиётлар ва манбалар эса

⁴⁸ Ўзбекистон Республикаси “Таълим тўғрисида”ги қонун.

⁴⁹ Ўзбекистон Республикаси Президентининг 2020 йил 29 апрелдаги “Ўзбекистон Республикасида юридик таълим ва фанни тубдан такомиллаштириш бўйича қўшимча чора-тадбирлар тўғрисида”ги ПФ-5987-сон фармони

library.tsul.uz электрон кутубхонасига жойлаштирилган. Юридик кадрларни халқаро стандартлар бўйича тайёрлаш марказида ҳам ўқув жараёни масофавий тарзда олиб борилмоқда.

Бундан ташқари, Олий ва ўрта махсус таълим вазирининг 2020 йил 27 мартда қабул қилинган “Олий таълим муассасаларида масофавий таълимни жорий этиш тўғрисида”ги буйруғига кўра республикамиздаги мавжуд ОТМлар масофавий ўқитиш технологияларини яратиш ва ишга тушириш юзасидан ишлар олиб борилган⁵⁰

Бугунги пандемия даврида олий таълимнинг сиртқи ва махсус сиртқи шаклларида дарслар масофадан туриб онлайн тарзда ўқитилши йўлга қўйилган.

Таълим шаклининг аралаш ўқитиш шаклига тўхталиб ўтадиганг бўлсак, ушбу шакл асосан халқ таълимида кенг қўлланилиб келинмоқда. “Blended Learning” деб аталадиган ушбу шаклда ўқув жараёнининг айрим элементлари электрон таълим муҳитида олиб борилади.

Анъанавий, масофавий ва аралаш(гибрид) таълим шакллари бўйича хориж тажрибасини келтириб ўтамиз.

Буюк Британиянинг университетида масофавий таълим фақат талабалар билан масофавий ишлашда фойдаланилади. Бунда талабаларнинг ҳар бири виртуал ўқитувчига бириктирилади. Маслаҳатлар ва якуний назоратларни топшириш учун худудий бўлимлар ташкил этилади. Бундай ўқув курсларида ўқитувчи ва талабаларга ўқув шаклини ва формасини танлашда катта имкониятлар ва эркинликлар берилади.

Англия ва Австралия университетларида масофавий ва кундузги таълим турларини интеграциялашувидан ҳосил бўлади. Талабалар ўқув курснинг бир қисмини кундузги, бошқа қисмини эса масофадан ўқийди. Шу билан бирга бу

⁵⁰ Олий ва ўрта махсус таълим вазирининг 2020 йил 27 мартда қабул қилинган “Олий таълим муассасаларида масофавий таълимни жорий этиш тўғрисида”ги буйруғи <https://xs.uz/uzkr/post/yangi-oquv-jilidan-boshlab-talabalar-masofadan-turib-oqitilishi-jolga-qojiladi>

таълим турига виртуал семинар, презентациялар ва маърузалар ўтказиш ҳам киради.

Юқоридагилардан келиб чиқиб, таклиф ва тавсияларимизни келтириб ўтишимиз жоиздир.

Биринчидан, масофавий таълимда **Эдвайзер** (фр. “avisen” – “ўйламок”, “advisor” – “ўйловчи”) битирув малакавий иши, курс лойиҳаларининг таълим олувчилар томонидан индивидуал, мустақил бажарилиши вақтида методик ёрдам берадиган маслаҳатчи, **Фасилитатор** (лот. “facilis”, ингл. “facilitator” – енгил, қулай) – масофавий таълим хизматидан фойдаланаётган гуруҳларнинг фаолиятини муаммонинг ечимини топишга йўналтирувчи, гуруҳларда юзага келадиган мулоқотни ривожлантирувчи, шунингдек, гуруҳлар фаолиятини холис, самарали баҳоловчи педагог, **Инвигилатор** – масофавий таълим асосида ташкил этиладиган ўқитиш натижаларини назорат қилувчи мутахассис-педагогларни кўпайтириш лозим.

Иккинчидан, масофавий таълим тизимида продуктив, репродуктив, муаммоли баён, эвристик ва илмий изланиш (тадқиқот) методлари кенг қўллаш лозим.

Учинчидан, оммавий очик онлайн курслар (МООС) – бу интернет орқали кўпчилик кириш имконияти мавжуд бўлган онлайн курсларни ташкил қилиш лозим.

Тўртинчидан, анъанавий таълим шаклида “Кластер”, “ФСМУ”, “SWOT”, “Инсерт” каби интерактив усулларни ва “Конференция”, “Чархпалак”, “Вазиятли масалалар” “Ақлий ҳужум” каби усулларни кенг қўллаш лозим.

Фикримиз сўнггида хулоса қилиб айтадиган бўлсак, бугунги ва келажакда ҳам анъанавий, масофавий ва аралаш(гибрид) таълим ўқитишда ҳам инновацион қарашлар ривожланиб бормоқда. Чунки, замон ривожланиб боргани сари таълим шакллари ҳам ўзгариб бормоқда. Бу эса ҳар бир таълим шакллариининг ўзига хослигини назарда тутди.

Фойдаланилган адабиётлар рўйхати:

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